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Mirza Popovac

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Preface

This Book of Abstracts compiles the submissions presented at the *20th OpenFOAM Workshop*. Abstracts appear as provided by the authors, with only minimal formatting and organizational editing.

As chairman of the *20th OpenFOAM Workshop*, I had the pleasure and honor of organizing the largest and longest-running OpenFOAM® conference, held in Vienna from June 30th to July 4th, 2025. This special anniversary edition marked two decades of a tradition that continues to bring together the global OpenFOAM® community. For the first time, the workshop took place in Austria—and fittingly, in its capital, Vienna—a city renowned for its cultural richness, creative energy, and its setting along the Danube, where history and innovation converge. Hosting the event here felt both timely and symbolic, highlighting Austria’s growing role in open-source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and the collaborative ethos that has shaped the OpenFOAM® community over the years.

The *Austrian Institute of Technology – AIT*, as host of the *20th OpenFOAM Workshop*, embodied this spirit remarkably well. As Austria’s largest non-university research organization, AIT’s mission blends scientific excellence with societal impact. By fostering open-source approach in research and technological development, AIT provided an ideal setting for a workshop dedicated to the world’s most widely adopted open-source CFD platform. Through this gathering, AIT proudly showcased not only its own advancements in simulation and modeling but also the breadth and vitality of Austrian research in fluid mechanics and its diverse applications.

This year’s program reflected that diversity: prominent professors from Austria’s top universities shared national expertise in multiphase, particulate, and laser-induced flow phenomena. Meanwhile, esteemed keynote speakers from institutions across Europe, America, and Asia enriched the global dialogue, offering perspectives on topics ranging from machine learning in fluid dynamics to the evolution of CFD in fields as varied as maritime engineering and biomedical flows. Collectively, these contributions underscored the field’s ongoing expansion—from fundamental physics to data-driven innovation.

The workshop welcomed over two hundred participants from academia and industry, promoting a truly international and interdisciplinary exchange of ideas. With technical sessions, poster presentations, and a dedicated high-performance computing session, the event highlighted how OpenFOAM® thrives at the intersection of community, computation, and creativity. Beyond the formal program, the workshop offered a valuable chance to reconnect in person, share experiences, and reflect on the remarkable progress of OpenFOAM® and the open-source movement through years of collaboration.

My sincere thanks go to all participants, contributors, sponsors, and volunteers who made this event possible. Organizing the *20th OpenFOAM Workshop* has been a privilege and a rewarding opportunity to celebrate not only technical progress but also the strength of an international community united by curiosity, transparency, and shared purpose. ***The 20th OpenFOAM Workshop was the perfect opportunity to connect, learn, and celebrate the spirit of innovation together: as the conference chairman, on behalf of the OpenFOAM Workshop Committee, I thank you all for your contribution to this exciting event!***

Mirza Popovac
Conference Chairman

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Multiphase, dispersed flows

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF HIGH-PRESSURE CAPILLARY VISCOMETER

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Keywords: High-pressure capillary viscometer, non-Newtonian fluids, Heat dissipation, OpenFOAM®

High-pressure capillary viscometers are essential tools for characterizing the rheological properties of non-Newtonian fluids under controlled pressure and temperature conditions. These devices are particularly useful for understanding the viscosity behavior of polymers, elastomers, and other complex materials under high shear rates. These non-Newtonian fluids exhibit viscosity changes based on shear rate and temperature variations. To describe this behavior accurately, established models such as Power Law, Cross, and Carreau with their temperature extensions are employed. Using numerical simulations in OpenFOAM®, it is possible to capture the effects of shear-rates, temperature dependence, and viscous heating, providing insights into the material characterization devices such as High-pressure capillary viscometers.

In this work, a new incompressible solver for OpenFOAM® v2006 is developed. Power-law Arrhenius, Carreau-Arrhenius, and Cross-Arrhenius viscosity models are integrated to effectively capture the shear-dependent and temperature-dependent behavior of shear-thinning non-Newtonian fluids [1]. The viscosity parameters are modularly defined within the transport properties dictionary, allowing adjustments to key parameters and viscosity limits for each model. These implementations enhance OpenFOAM®'s usability for engineering applications requiring precise rheological modeling. Additionally, viscous dissipation is incorporated to account for heat generation due to shear heating. The solver has been rigorously validated against analytical solutions and experimental data, ensuring its accuracy and robustness.

Figure 1a illustrates the computational geometry of high-pressure capillary viscometer setup consisting of piston section (upper part of the geometry) and outlet section (die); in a second geometry, the last 3/4 of the die section is considered for analytical validation. The die has a length of 20 mm and a diameter of 2 mm, giving a length-to-diameter (L/D) ratio of 10. The piston-cylinder section has a diameter of 15 mm. A fixed velocity corresponding to the piston speed is applied at the inlet, while the outlet is set to atmospheric pressure. The walls are maintained at a fixed temperature for consistency with measurements, and no-slip conditions are applied.

Computational geometry is prepared using OpenFOAM®'s blockMesh utility, which can be seen in Figure 1b. After a detailed mesh study, an optimally structured grid consisting of 44,400 cells provides a good balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

Figure 1: (a) Geometry and (b) generated mesh with side, top and bottom view of the die section

The power law Arrhenius model with $n = 0.139$, $k = 16526 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}^{0.139}$ and $E = 6023 \text{ J/mol}$ is used to model the non-Newtonian behavior of the elastomer for the simulations. These parameters are extracted from the same measurement series that are used for comparison. Additionally, dissipation effects are included to account for viscous heating, significantly improving the accuracy of simulations where temperature variations impact viscosity and flow characteristics.

To validate the solver, two separate validation cases at different shear rates were performed: (1) Analytical validation: The pressure drop in the last 3/4 of the die was compared against analytical predictions following equation 1 which describes a fluid that obeys power law behavior in a circular pipe [2]:

$$\Delta P = \frac{2kL}{r} \left[Q \cdot \frac{3+1/n}{\pi r^3} \right]^n \quad (1)$$

(2) Experimental validation: The full high-pressure capillary viscometer (HPCV) setup was simulated, and pressure drop results were compared with experimental data. Figure 2 presents a comparative analysis between experimental measurements, analytical predictions, and CFD results, demonstrating good agreement.

Figure 2: Simulation pressure drop results comparison with (a) Analytical and (b) Experimental data in 80 °C

Additionally, Figure 3 provides contour plots of pressure, viscosity, and temperature within the system, illustrating the impact of shear-thinning effects and viscous heating. The incorporation of viscous dissipation allows for the evaluation of temperature variations, which is particularly important in measuring output temperature or in applications where temperature changes significantly impact viscosity and flow behaviour. The implemented solver accurately captures pressure drop, viscosity variations, and heat dissipation, confirming the solver’s accuracy in predicting non-Newtonian flow behavior. This result confirms the robustness and reliability of the proposed implementations, making them valuable additions for the studies with high-pressure capillary viscometers and complex non-Newtonian fluid simulations.

Figure 3: Pressure, dynamic viscosity and temperature contours at 80 °C and 100 1/s

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Modeling High-Viscosity Spray Injection Using Volume-of-Fluid Method and Large Eddy Simulation

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Keywords: High-viscosity spray injection, Spray Atomization, Geometric Volume-of-Fluid Method, Large Eddy Simulation, Adaptive Mesh Refinement, Dynamic Load Balancing

Introduction

Despite the rise of renewables, fossil fuels—particularly heavy residues like heavy fuel oil (HFO) and vacuum residue oil (VRO)—remain essential as light crude supplies decrease. In entrained-flow gasifiers, these high-density, cost-effective feedstocks are converted into syngas via drying, pyrolysis, and char conversion, with efficiency governed by reaction kinetics and the interfacial surface area of liquid sprays. This study models the spray interface evolution of a VRO-like liquid to quantify its dynamics and enable a more environmentally friendly energy conversion.

Methods

The Volume-of-Fluid (VOF) approach is a simulation technique that models the interface between two immiscible fluids [1]. It is particularly effective at capturing the breakup of a liquid into ligaments and droplets as VOF tracks the liquid–vapor interface by computing the liquid volume fraction, α , in each computational cell. The *plic-RDF* algorithm reconstructs the interface accurately [2], and the *isoAdvector* algorithm geometrically advects and preserves interface sharpness [3].

The governing equations for Large Eddy Simulation (LES) for compressible flows, namely conservation of mass, momentum and energy, along with the advection equation for the liquid volume fraction, are given by:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_j) = -\frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \bar{\rho} g_i + \bar{f}_{\text{surf},i} + \bar{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}^R}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \bar{T})}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j \bar{T}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\alpha_T \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x_j} \right) - \left(\frac{\bar{\alpha}}{c_{v,l}} + \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}}{c_{v,g}} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\tilde{u}_j \bar{p}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_i}{2} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\tilde{u}_j \frac{\bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i \tilde{u}_i}{2} \right) \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\bar{\alpha} \bar{\rho}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\bar{\alpha} \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j) = 0 \quad (4)$$

where the $\tilde{\cdot}$ denotes Favre-filtered quantities, and the $\bar{\cdot}$ indicates filtered properties. t is time, u is velocity, x is the spatial variable, p is pressure, T is temperature, and g is gravitational acceleration. The specific heat capacity at constant volume is c_v , and α_T is thermal diffusivity. The subgrid-scale stress tensor, τ_{ij}^R , is closed using the wall-adapting local eddy-viscosity (WALE) model. μ and ρ are the weighted-average dynamic viscosity and density, respectively, calculated using the volume fraction. The surface tension force, f_{surf} , is represented via the continuum surface force (CSF) model [4]. In deriving the simplified energy equation (Equation 3), we neglect terms of minor magnitude, specifically pressure jump at the interface, viscous dissipation, and surface tension work.

The framework is derived from the solver of *compressibleInterIsoFoam* in OpenFOAM. To enhance robustness and efficiency over a wide range of Mach numbers [5], we modify the pressure equation to be Equation 5, by treating the gas density as temperature-dependent via the ideal-gas law and assuming the liquid phase to be incompressible.

$$(1 - \bar{\alpha}) \left(\frac{\psi_g}{\rho_g} \frac{D\bar{p}}{Dt} - \frac{1}{\bar{T}} \frac{D\bar{T}}{Dt} \right) + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_j}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (5)$$

where ρ_g is the gas density, and ψ_g is the gas compressibility in OpenFOAM.

Computational Setup and Results

Atomization is achieved using an air-blast atomizer. The liquid is injected axially at an average velocity of 0.096 m/s, while the gas enters the chamber through eight inclined side pipes, reaching a peak speed of 260 m/s. Along with the large velocity difference, the high viscosity and density differences also pose challenges for this multiphase flow simulation.

Using the *setAlphaField* utility in OpenFOAM, we initialize a pre-existing liquid column in the atomization zone with a velocity of 0.096 m/s to mitigate delays in spray formation caused by the low injection speed.

The computational grids for this study are generated using *blockMesh* and *snappyHexMesh* tools in OpenFOAM. Adaptive mesh refinement (AMR) is applied to capture interface dynamics with a minimum cell size of approximately 62.5 microns. To balance the uneven workload induced by AMR, dynamic load balancing redistributes cells across processors for optimal performance.

Figure 1 shows the spray evolution. High liquid viscosity produces elongated ligaments that subsequently fragment into droplets, and their lateral protrusion promotes a potential breakup into clusters of droplets.

Figure 1: Time evolution of the air-blast spray. Liquid is injected axially through the central tube, while gas enters via eight surrounding pipes. The liquid–gas interface is colored by velocity magnitude, and the gray surface shows the Mach number 0.2 isosurface in the gas phase.

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Interface-Resolved Modelling of Droplet Evaporation Using a Finite Volume Moving-Mesh Method

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Keywords: *droplet, evaporation, interface-resolved, moving-mesh, non-equilibrium*

Droplet evaporation is a ubiquitous physical process occurring in a wide range of environmental and industrial flows, with critical applications in areas such as fuel injection in internal combustion engines, spray cooling, inkjet printing, and pesticide dispersion. It also plays a significant role in natural phenomena like cloud formation and raindrop evaporation in the atmosphere. Broadly, the evaporation process consists of two key stages: the detachment of molecules from the droplet surface and the subsequent diffusion of vapor into the surrounding gas [1]. While the existing literature on mathematical modeling is extensive, most models emphasize the only diffusion phase. Moreover, they typically assume phase and thermal equilibrium at the droplet interface—an assumption that can be fundamentally flawed. Capturing the detachment dynamics accurately requires solving the Boltzmann equation or employing molecular dynamics simulations in the so-called kinetic region near the droplet surface. However, approximate treatments based on kinetic theory or irreversible thermodynamics can be used to derive interfacial jump conditions, thereby relaxing the oversimplified assumptions of equal temperature and vapor pressure at the interface.

In this research, a finite volume moving-mesh method [2] is employed to enable highly accurate predictions of droplet behavior during the evaporation process. The key advantage of this approach lies in its elegant treatment of boundary conditions on both the gas and liquid sides, maintaining a sharp interface without numerical smearing. The set of interfacial balance equations is nonlinear and requires tight coupling to ensure solution stability. When the equilibrium assumption is relaxed, additional equations accounting for pressure and temperature jumps across the interface must be incorporated. This method allows for precise calculation of temperature gradients and velocity fields in both the gas and liquid domains. As such, the primary objective is to assess the validity range of simpler models and to provide deeper insight into the fundamental physics of droplet evaporation—specifically, the effects of surface tension, internal circulation, and Marangoni flow in convective environments.

First, an equilibrium formulation for a stationary droplet is developed, implemented using the surface-tracking solver available in foam-extend. In the simulation, the droplet is initially at room temperature and placed in a quiescent hot gas. The results are compared with the classical equilibrium model from the literature [3], confirming the d^2 law for droplet diameter reduction following the initial transient heating phase. This approach is applicable in regimes of mild evaporation, where the assumption of local phase and thermal equilibrium at the interface holds reasonably well, such as in low-temperature combustion, aerosol dynamics, or atmospheric water droplet evaporation.

However, under more extreme conditions—such as those found in internal combustion engines, where steep temperature gradients are present—the non-equilibrium formulation exhibits significant deviations from its equilibrium counterpart. Similar behavior is observed in environments involving rarefied gases, where continuum assumptions begin to break down. In such cases, non-equilibrium effects become prominent, manifesting as an increased droplet lifetime and elevated interfacial temperatures compared to predictions from equilibrium models. To account for these effects, jump conditions at the interface must be introduced. For the mass and pressure fluxes, the Hertz-Knudsen relation is typically employed, which incorporates the mass accommodation coefficient—a key parameter controlling the rate at which vapor molecules condense or evaporate at the interface. For the temperature jump, no universally accepted expression exists; however, formulation used is derived from kinetic theory, typically involving the thermal accommodation coefficient, which characterizes the degree of energy exchange between gas molecules and the liquid surface. These coefficients play a critical role in accurately capturing the interfacial transport processes under non-equilibrium conditions.

Figure 1: Comparison with results from [3]

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HYBRID VOF TO LAGRANGIAN CFD MODEL FOR JET BREAKUP AND SPRAY TRANSPORT

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Keywords: Volume of Fluid (VOF), Lagrangian, multiphase flows, atomization, liquid jet in crossflow

For a complete CFD modelling of jet breakup processes as in atomization followed by spray propagation, a transition model from an interface tracking consideration with the volume of fluid method (VoF) to Lagrangian particles is presented. The model was integrated by the authors into the open-source CFD toolbox OpenFOAM, validated on various benchmarks, and finally used to clarify disintegration processes in molten metal atomization.

Modelling approach

To represent the interactions between dynamic, viscous and surface forces during the disintegration, the initial fluid dispersion is modelled using a volume-of-fluid approach. Here, adaptive meshes on the liquid-gas interface are used to geometrically resolve the lamellae and ligament structure. If the individual cell regions of disintegrated ligaments form separated and spherical structures, they are converted into Lagrangian particles. The transformation is required, because the many droplets produced during atomization are often too small for a further spray modelling using interface tracking methods. Typical criteria to identify VoF sections valid for a transition to Lagrangian particles are the sphericity, size and position of separated fluid cell regions. After the transformation the mesh is locally coarsened again and the interactions between the droplets and continuous flow are realized via Lagrangian source terms. In the following, the droplets can further disintegrate according to their respective Weber number in a secondary breakup model.

The model has been integrated into OpenFOAM as cloud-functions. Thus, it can be used with both incompressible and compressible solvers, with compressible solvers being particularly suitable for twin-fluid atomization at high gas velocities.

Validation

For validation the fuel jet in cross flow benchmark is set up [1] [2]. A LES model is used to represent the turbulence structure and an iso-advect interface tracking algorithm is applied [3]. The horizontally flowing air atomizes the liquid whereby the final drop sizes at a greater distance are dominated by the secondary break-up of the Lagrange droplets according to the Reitz-Diwakar model. Good agreement with experimental results is achieved for the resulting particle size in the control planes at different distances from the injection nozzle.

Figure 1: Fuel injection in cross flow – Experiment [1] [2] and simulation

Additional applications, such as pressure atomization from round nozzles, also yield accurate results for droplet sizes and velocities, see Figure 2. The comparison is made here with experimental data from the thesis of E. Deux [4]. The simulation in OpenFOAM is also carried out with an LES model. In contrast to the fuel injection benchmark, a single-component atomisation is used. For this reason, the secondary break-up (also modelled with the model according to Reitz-Diwakar) is of minor importance.

Figure 2: Atomisation from a hole nozzle - experimental droplet sizes and velocities [5] at a distance of 25mm from the exit in comparison to simulation

Molten metal atomisation

The model developed in this way is used to explain processes in the atomisation of metal melts during powder production [5]. In this process, a pressure swirl atomiser is first applied to the molten metal, which causes the lamella to primarily disintegrate. Subsequently, the droplets are atomised into small particles by gas jets at high speed, see Figure 3. Due to the transonic gas velocity, compressible modelling is used. With this model, significant effects on the breakup processes could be better understood. In particular, the interaction of the gas jets with the ligaments and effects on the particle size could be analysed.

Figure 3: Atomisation of molten metal in twin fluid configuration

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GAS-LIQUID MIXING AND SEPARATION IN CONTINUOUS TUBULAR REACTORS

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Keywords: gas-liquid mixing, bubble separation, static elements, Two-fluid model, interphase forces

In this work we present an application of the Euler-Euler Two-fluid model (TFM) to the simulation of an innovative continuous equipment based on the adoption of static elements for accomplishing gas-liquid reactions and separation in different sections of the same pipeline. The investigation is aimed at the improvement of mass transfer limited gas-liquid chemical reactors by Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) based methods. In this realm, reliable predictions of turbulent gas-liquid mixing and bubble breakage and coalescence are required, since the process efficiency is dominated from the capability to promote absorption of species from the gas to the liquid phase and to enhance mass transfer rates. An additional target is to enable the design of novel equipment by computational methods for achieving process intensification, adding a gas separation section to the reactor. Separation can be obtained exploiting the prevailing tangential motion obtained by helical-type static elements and the significant density difference between the gas and liquid phases [1]. For this reason, appropriate turbulence modelling is crucial and not straightforward, being highly swirling motions of the bubbles induced by the static elements particularly difficult to be predicted with classical two-equation turbulence models for Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equation closure. We put particular efforts in the evaluation of modelling challenges related to the complex two-phase fluid dynamics and uncertainties due to the numerical solution of the model equations in the complex geometry of the computational domain. Among the available multiphase flow models, we selected the TFM since it has proved effective in the simulation of a number of chemical engineering applications, including gas-liquid static mixers [2]. For the validation of the interphase momentum transfer terms required in the TFM and the turbulence models, we collected experimental bubble size distributions and gas volume fraction distributions in the same operating conditions adopted for the simulations.

The computational domain matches quite closely the geometry of the experimental system. It consists of a vertical pipe of diameter D equal to 0.022 m equipped with Kenics type static elements. Each static element consists of a twisted plate of diameter equal to D and length of $1.5 D$. Depending on the type and arrangement of the elements, either mixing or separation of the two phases is obtained. In the experiments, three elements are located consecutively in the pipe at $10 D$ from the gas inlet and $17 D$ from the liquid inlet. In the simulation, in order to reduce computational time, the length of the pipe upstream and downstream the Kenics is limited to $3 D$ and $7 D$. The mixing and the separation configurations are investigated separately, with the three elements located in the pipe as depicted in Figure 1. Water and air at ambient temperature are considered, flowing co-currently upwards in the pipeline with the volumetric gas flowrate equal to 5% of the volumetric mixture flowrate, and the Reynolds number based on the pipe diameter, the liquid physical properties and the mixture superficial velocity in the empty pipe equal to 1.6×10^4 .

Figure 1: Computational domain and static elements shape and relative position for mixing (a) and separation (b)

The simulations of the turbulent gas-liquid flow are based on the numerical solution of the Reynolds-averaged TFM equations, as implemented in OpenFOAM v11. The interphase momentum transfer is accounted for by the drag force, F_D , and the turbulent dispersion force, F_{TD} . Swarm and liquid free stream turbulent effects on the drag coefficient are not taken into account. Virtual mass, F_{VM} , and lift, F_L , forces are also included using their classical definitions. Monodisperse assumption on the bubble size is adopted in order to evaluate the effect of the different forces and their formulation, considering the experimental Sauter diameter downstream the static elements, that is equal to 2.3 mm in the mixing and 4.0 mm in the separation cases.

For the closure of the Reynolds-averaged TFM, based on the results obtained in single phase flow [3], the $k-\omega$ SST is selected for the liquid phase considering an additional term accounting for bubble induced turbulence [4], while the dispersed gas phase is assumed to be laminar [5]. Also, the $k-\omega$ turbulence model with the gas-liquid mixture properties is implemented and the results obtained with the two models are compared. As for the near-wall treatment, the formulation of Menter [6] is selected. The resulting set of equations is solved by the multiphaseEuler solver, adopting second order discretization scheme for the convective terms and the Local Time Stepping approach (LTS) for the temporal solution strategy using a first order scheme. The pressure-velocity coupling is based on the PIMPLE algorithm. The spatial discretization of the computational domain is selected considering the results obtained with three structured grids with a refinement ratio of 1.3 estimating the Grid Convergence Index of selected variables and the corresponding value obtained from the Richardson extrapolation. The results of different sub-models will be presented and critically discussed adopting the experimental gas distribution for comparison. By means of example, the gas volume fraction distribution predicted with a selected set of closure models is shown in Figure 2(a) and (b), respectively. Issues related to the numerical stability of the solution and possible model improvements will be highlighted.

Figure 2: Gas volume fraction distribution for mixing (a) and separation (b) compared with experimental results.

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ADVANCES IN LIQUID FILM SIMULATIONS USING GEOMETRIC VOLUME-OF-FLUID

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Keywords: *Volume-of-Fluid, isoAdvector PLIC-RDF, dynamic contact angle, partial slip, Navier slip*

In chemical engineering, liquid films are often encountered in many process equipments like structured packings or fixed beds of catalysts, either operated in ascendant flow or as trickle beds. The interaction between liquid films and gases is thus of the utmost relevance for many industrial processes, particularly regarding mass transfers between phases. To better understand these complex phenomena, this research uses Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), with a focus on the Volume-of-Fluid (VOF) method. The VOF method inherently captures the interface between the phases.

The geometric VOF method named isoAdvector developed by Roenby et al. [1] is employed to resolve the interface. The use of the Reconstructed Distance Function (RDF) was implemented by Scheufler and Roenby [2] to improve interface reconstruction and the computation of the interface curvature used for surface tension calculations. This method is reported to reduce spurious currents by orders of magnitude when compared to traditional algebraic interface compression methods [3].

A proper modelization of the moving contact line between the liquid, gas, and solid, is a well-known and challenging task in VOF methods. In this study, we evaluate different contact angle boundary conditions, applied to the volume fraction equation. Our current implementation of the Cox-Voinov dynamic contact angle model, based on [4, 5], correctly models the advancing and receding behavior of an inertia dominated flow. In conjunction, partial and Navier slip boundary conditions for the velocity are also assessed.

To validate this implementation for surface tension dominated flows, the case of a droplet spreading over a flat plate without initial velocity is simulated and the results compared with experimental [6] and numerical [7] data. The 2D axisymmetric computational domain is shown on the left of Figure 1. The domain is discretized with 96×96 cells. The time evolution of the non-dimensional droplet radius is shown on the r.h.s. of Figure 1. Stat1 and Stat2 curves are obtained with a constant contact angle, with respectively no slip or partial slip velocity boundary conditions. λ_N designs the slip length, taken as half the grid size in the Stat2 case. The Dyn2 and Dyn3 results are obtained with the Cox dynamic contact angle model. We use the same nomenclature as Legendre [7]. One can clearly see that a static contact angle model leads to too fast droplet dynamics. Using the Cox dynamic contact angle improves drastically the results. Unsurprisingly, when a partial slip boundary condition is used, the droplet dynamics is faster and the droplet reaches its equilibrium earlier. However, when the no-slip boundary condition is used together with the Cox model (Dyn2 green dashed curve), the droplet becomes unstable and periodically contracts. This unexpected behaviour is currently under investigation. It disappears when the slip length is reduced from $\Delta/2 = 0.015625$ to a low value like 10^{-8} : See the magenta curve on Figure 1, which is identical to Dyn2 green dashed curve before time $\tau = 150$.

In an attempt to further validate this dynamic contact angle model, a liquid film with side contact lines is simulated flowing down a vertical flat plate under the effect of gravity, leading to the formation of rivulets. The relation of the initial film width to the number of rivulets formed and the wavelength are compared with the numerical results from [8], obtained with the JADIM CFD code. As a stepping stone for future simulations of liquid films flowing over complex geometries, a confined thin liquid film flowing over an inclined flat plate is simulated. The resulting velocity profiles and thickness of the film are measured in post-processing and compared with the known theoretical Nusselt solution.

Future work includes simulating liquid films flowing down inclined plates with several different base plate geometries, incorporating of mass transfer models, and comparing the numerical results with analytical solutions and experimental data.

Acknowledgments

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Figure 1: Spreading droplet over a flat plate: (Left) Configuration of the 2D axisymmetric case. (Right) Non-dimensional droplet radius measured on the bottom plate. Comparison of Legendre results with isoAdvector PLIC-RDF simulations, with or without Navier-Slip boundary condition.

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BUBBLE FORMATION AND FLOW DYNAMICS INDUCED BY LIQUID SLOSHING

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Keywords: *Liquid Sloshing, Bubble Formation, VOF model, Discrete Bubble model*

The hydraulic oil tank of a construction machine experiences acceleration due to the machine's forward, backward, and rotational movements. Inside the tank, hydraulic oil sloshes, and bubbles are formed. These bubbles in the hydraulic oil induces cavitation in the hydraulic pump, which results in material damage. Therefore, numerical simulations of bubble formation caused by liquid sloshing are essential for optimizing tank shapes to mitigate bubble formation.

Liquid sloshing has been simulated using the volume of fluid (VOF) model to capture the gas-liquid interface. However, representing smaller-scale bubbles requires a large number of grids, even with the use of adaptive mesh refinement. In the present study, a hybrid model solver was developed based on atomizationFoam [1]. The solver utilizes a hybrid approach combining the VOF method and the discrete bubble model (DBM), where bubbles smaller than the grid cells are represented using a Lagrangian formulation with bubble translation motion taken into consideration. The solver was employed to simulate bubble formation induced by liquid sloshing, and its correlation with flow dynamics was analyzed.

A closed tank with dimensions $144 \times 144 \times 34$ mm, filled with liquid to a height of $h = 85$ mm, was driven by a sinusoidal oscillation at a frequency of $f = 2$ Hz and an amplitude of $A_x = 10$ mm. The liquid phase is water and the gas phase is air. Figure 1 shows time evolution of a gas-liquid interface and discrete bubbles. At $t = 840$ ms, a portion of the wavehead plunges into the interface. Then the gas phase follows and is entrained in the liquid, resulting in the formation of a discrete bubble at $t = 845$ ms. By $t = 920$ ms, VOF and discrete bubbles are formed near right sidewall because of the fragmentation of stretched gas phase. On the other hand, the downward interface flow near the left sidewall entrains the gas phase into the liquid phase, leading to bubble formation at $t = 975$ ms. In the presentation, simulation results will be compared with the corresponding experimental results for validation.

Figure 1: Time evolution of a gas-liquid interface represented by an isosurface with $\alpha_l = 0.5$ and discrete bubbles visualized as white particles (diameters doubled for clarity).

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A COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS MODEL FOR THE SIMULATION OF FLASH-BOILING FLOW INSIDE PRESSURIZED METERED DOSE INHALERS

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Keywords: *pMDI, flashing flow, phase change, numerical model, OpenFOAM*

Pressurized metered-dose inhalers (pMDI) are one of the most common medical devices for respiratory drug delivery. Despite their geometrical simplicity and ease of use, the operation of a pMDI involves many complex physical phenomena occurring at the same time, including depressurization, atomization and flash-boiling, a violent evaporation of the pressurized liquid propellant into a liquid/vapor mixture. Moreover, the characteristic length and time scales of these phenomena are such to make laboratory measurements inside the pMDI very difficult to perform even with modern experimental techniques [1].

Over the years, mathematical models based on first principles have been developed to predict the characteristics of the two-phase flow inside the pMDI as well as some of the properties of the flow through the device nozzle, such as the density and the mass flow rate of the liquid/vapor mixture [2], and of the spray emitted by the pMDI, such as the droplets size [3]. Such models have the advantage of being computationally inexpensive but they are based on a-priori assumptions on the flow regime inside the device and require a significant amount of model parameters to be calibrated.

In this work, we present a first attempt in developing a CFD model for the flashing flow inside the pMDI. The model, based on a mixture-type representation of the multiphase flow and on the cavitation model of Kunz et al. [4] for the modeling of the phase-change process associated with flash-boiling, is able to represent explicitly the device operation, from the decompression of the propellant stored in the metering valve to the choked-flow of the liquid/vapor mixture through the device nozzle. Moreover, compared to system models, the CFD model allows for the analysis of the effect of changes in the device internal geometry on the mixture flow inside the pMDI.

The CFD model is validated using several experimental datasets and mainly against the measurements carried out by Mason-Smith et al. [5] using X-ray phase contrast imaging and quantitative radiography. Very similar flow features compared to the X-ray images are found in the simulated metered discharge and a general good agreement is found with the with measured profiles of average mixture density and vapor and liquid flow rates at the nozzle-orifice. An extensive study of the sensitivity of numerical results to modeling parameters is also carried out to establish the potential and limitations of the present model.

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On the implementation of free-surface for a prolate spheroid submerged underwater

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Abstract

The author presents a study on the near-field implementation of the free surface for a submerged prolate spheroid to evaluate its advantages and limitations. This study focuses on the linearized methodology in contrast to the non-linear Volume of Fluid (VOF) approach. Both methodologies are supported within the OpenFOAM platform, which serves as the computational framework for this research. The linearized methodology uses the solver `potentialFreeSurfaceFoam` and the VOF methodology uses the solver `interFoam`. Thus far, literature indicates that the `potentialFreeSurfaceFoam` solver has remained under utilized. The reference by [1] shows the implementation of a numerical wave tank using this solver. However, validation of a submerged body under a linearized free surface solver using experimental data has not been performed. Therefore, this study proceeds to use the experimental domain size with a particular focus on replicating the conditions used in experiments documented in [2]. The comparative analysis aims to identify potential inaccuracies inherent in the linearized implementation and, if feasible, to quantify the degree of such inaccuracies. Such an analysis forces the understanding of low fidelity vs high fidelity methods of CFD being applicable at various occasions. While the study presented here is based on near field simulations, this comparison has a profound impact on far field applications including 2D and 3D+t simulations.

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REDUCING SPURIOUS CURRENTS BY IMPROVING GRAVITY DISCRETISATION IN THE INTERFACIAL FLOW SOLVERS OF OPENFOAM

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Keywords: Interfacial flows, interIsoFoam, isoAdvector, Volume-of-Fluid, spurious currents, gravity discretisation

The open-source CFD package, OpenFOAM, includes a family of interfacial flow solvers for two or more compressible or incompressible, immiscible fluids. These solvers are based on the one-fluid formulation within the finite volume framework, employing the Volume-of-Fluid (VoF) method to advect the fluid interface, and a collocated variant of the PISO algorithm for the pressure-velocity coupling. The abrupt jump in material properties at the fluid interface poses a challenge to the equation discretization leading to unphysical velocities near the fluid interface, especially for large jumps in fluid density across the interface. This is particularly pronounced for surface tension dominated flows, but the problem also occurs for gravity dominated flows such as simulation of ocean waves [1]. The original interFoam solver uses an algebraic VoF method (artificial interface compression with the MULES limiter) and holds no geometric information about the position of the interface within mesh cells. It therefore uses a crude estimate of this position in the discretization of the gravitational potential that enters as a source term in the momentum equation. The interIsoFoam solver was later introduced to use the geometric VoF method, isoAdvector, for advecting the interface. An unfortunate effect of the sharper fluid interface produced by isoAdvector was an increase in the spurious velocities [2].

Here, we show how these spurious velocities can be significantly reduced by exploiting the interface data available from the geometric interface reconstruction in the discretization of the gravity source term. An example is shown in Fig. 1, where a simple numerical standing wave experiment is conducted with interFoam, interIsoFoam, and interIsoFoam with the modified gravity formulation. While spurious air currents along the water surface are observed in all three cases, the modified gravity case (right panel) represents a clear improvement compared with the original formulation (center panel).

Figure 1: Spurious velocities at air-water interface for standing wave in a 1 m x 1 m domain. Time step, $dt = 0.01$ s, cell size $dx = 0.02$ m, densities 1 and 1000 kg/m³, gravity 9.81 m/s², no viscosity or surface tension.

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SIMULATION OF POOL SPREAD AND EVAPORATION OF CRYOGENIC LIQUID HYDROGEN ON SOLID SURFACES USING FILM MODEL

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Keywords: *Liquid Hydrogen, Cryogenics, Film Model, Hydrogen Safety.*

As the dependence on hydrogen as an energy storage medium increases, the amount of transported liquefied hydrogen (LH2) also increases. However, many safety concerns arise while utilizing LH2, such as its very low boiling point, which reaches 20.3K, and the high evaporation rates once the liquefied gas comes in contact with the solid ground at normal temperatures. Therefore, the need for a simulation tool that can predict the spread of the LH2 pool in case of accidental leakage and the resulting gaseous hydrogen cloud concentrations and movement becomes of great interest to safety researchers.

In this work, the film solver of OpenFOAM v11 was modified to include the thermodynamic process of evaporation and the resulting mass and energy source terms added to the continuityPredictor and the thermophysicalPredictor. Unlike the fvModels approach, the presented approach solves the evaporation process implicitly to ensure more stability and accuracy. The film solver was selected rather than the VoF approach because of the accuracy of the film model in simulating the spread of a thin layer of liquid on a solid surface while ignoring the motion in the direction normal to the solid wall. This provides more stability and lower computational efforts of the solution process.

To apply such a method in OpenFOAM v11, the thermodynamic properties of both liquid and gaseous hydrogen are re-defined using user-generated tables generated using the CoolProp [1] library and its Python wrapper pyFluids [2]. The original implementation of liquid properties in OpenFOAM v11 employs the thermo-physical model presented in Ref. [3] which is not suitable for the current application since the provided models implies the standard pressure and temperature conditions, i.e. $T = 298.15\text{K}$ and $p = 1$ bar, in calculating reference sensible enthalpy. This reference value results in a negative value while calculating the sensible enthalpy of the liquid at cryogenic temperatures, which results in instability in the solution of the energy equation.

Another important aspect of applying this approach in OpenFOAM is to model the heat transfer between the solid substrate and the liquid cryogen. The heat transfer at high-temperature differences is modeled by implementing the heat transfer model of the computer code LAuV [4] developed by Forschungszentrum Jülich. The LAuV heat transfer model is implemented as a boundary condition of the interface patch between liquid film and solid substrate to calculate the heat flux transferred from solid to the cryogenic liquid which can be calculated by [4]:

$$\dot{q} = \frac{\lambda \Delta T}{\rho_l \sqrt{\pi \alpha} \sqrt{t-t'}} \quad (1)$$

where \dot{q} – the evaporation mass flux; λ – thermal conductivity of the solid ground; ΔT – temperature difference between liquid and solid; ρ_l – is the liquid's density; α – thermal diffusivity; t' – time moment from which the solid surface element contacts the cryogenic liquid.

Preliminary simulations show numerical stability compared to using the liquid properties values from Ref [3] due to overcoming the aforementioned problems. However, these results need more verification and validation to ensure the reliability of this approach. Also, the accuracy of the LAuV model in calculating the heat flux between the liquid film and the solid wall should be compared with other heat transfer models under such high temperature differences. Additionally, more physical phenomena should be considered for addition to the solver, such as accounting for condensation and solidification of humidity, nitrogen, and oxygen from the surrounding atmosphere.

Figure 1: Preliminary test case with LH2 evaporation

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Enhanced interface force modelling in MPPICInterFOAM for three-phase flow simulations

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Keywords: Taylor flows, Microreactors, MPPIC, Volume of Fluid, Interfacial force

This work presents new developments in the MPPICInterFOAM solver to improve the simulation of three-phase Taylor flows with suspended nano- to micro-scale particles, such as Alumina (400–1000 nm), used in heat transfer applications and microreactors for materials synthesis [1]. Accurate prediction of particle confinement and transport near gas-liquid interfaces is critical for understanding multiphase behavior in capillary-scale systems. Traditional interface force models in OpenFOAM (as well as other software packages) often apply uniform coefficients and fail to localize interactions, leading to non-physical particle behavior in bulk regions. To address this, we implemented a physics-based capillary interaction model in OpenFOAM v2306 under:

`$FOAM_SRC/lagrangian/intermediate/submodels/Kinematic/ParticleForces/Interface`

The force is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{int}} = -C_{\text{int}} m_p \nabla \alpha \quad (1)$$

where C_{int} dynamically accounts for particle diameter, density, wettability, and fluid surface tension. Additionally, a gradient-conditioning algorithm restricts this force to regions with significant $\nabla \alpha$, eliminating spurious acceleration of particles in the liquid bulk. The complete theoretical background and solver framework are detailed in [2].

Simulations were conducted using a capillary tube geometry (1 mm diameter, 25 mm length) with four-way coupling and the VOF-MPPIC framework. A wide range of interface force coefficient values (10 to 1000) was tested to evaluate both physical and exaggerated behaviors. The results show that increasing the hydrophilicity of the particles (implied by C_{int}) enhances the repulsion of particles from the gas-liquid interface, promoting confinement within the near-wall film and increasing its thickness by up to 20%.

Validation was conducted based on the bubble coalescence scenario investigated in [3], where comparable interfacial dynamics in particulate slurries were observed. The effects of the proposed interface force modification are illustrated in Figure 1, which compares particle trajectories before and after applying the gradient-localized force. Two key improvements are evident: (1) artificial particle aggregation is effectively eliminated, and (2) particles are fully confined within the continuous liquid phase.

In the main Taylor flow case, Figures 2 and 3 demonstrate the influence of interface force strength on both film thickness and particle distribution across the tube cross-section, with particular emphasis on the behavior within the liquid film layer. These simulations were conducted at $Re = 100$, $\phi = 3 \times 10^{-4}$, and $d_p = 400$ nm. In Figure 2, the shaded region denotes the non-physical data range associated with $C_{\text{int}} > 273.4$, which corresponds to a negative particle contact angle. Beyond this threshold, the impact of C_{int} on the results diminishes, approaching a plateau.

These findings confirm that the enhanced interface force model not only improves numerical stability but also establishes a physical basis for simulating particle-interface interactions. As a result, the updated MPPICInterFOAM solver offers greater reliability for applications in particle transport, heat exchanger optimization, and reactive multiphase flow systems.

Figure 1: The effect of the modification of the interface force model used in the MPPICInterFOAM solver.

Figure 2: The effect of C_{int} on the film thickness (primary y-axis) and the percentage of particles in the film layer relative to the total particles in the Taylor flow field (secondary y-axis).

Figure 3: Flow field and particle distribution for different values of interfacial force coefficient C_{int} .

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Compressible flows

APPLICATION OF ADVANCED ACTUATOR LINE METHOD FOR COMPRESSIBLE PROPELLER SIMULATIONS IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: Propeller, Actuator Line Method, Aerodynamics, OpenFOAM, Installation Effects.

For propeller design, accurate predictions of blade forces are crucial for enhancing propeller performance and optimising structural design. Especially to capture complex effects related to propeller-airframe interaction and propellers operating outside normal design conditions CFD simulations are a valuable tool in the propeller design process. While fully resolved blade simulations offer high accuracy, their computational expense restricts their practical use to later design phases, necessitating less expensive methods for early-stage evaluations. The Actuator Line Method (ALM), originally developed by Sørensen and Shen [1], is such a lower fidelity approach where rotor blades are efficiently modelled by imposing body forces into the fluid at discrete actuator points along virtual lines representing the blade axis. The local body forces are determined by sampling local velocity vectors, calculating the local angle of attack and using tabulated airfoil polars. Initially employed for wind turbines in incompressible flows, ALM's proven capability in capturing rotor wakes and tip vortices has encouraged its application to other rotor types, such as helicopter rotors and propellers. Subsequent enhancements, notably the Advanced Actuator Line Method (AALM) by Churchfield et al. [2], have improved the accuracy of velocity sampling and force projection, refining predictions of tip vortices and near-wake phenomena.

In previous work [3], we have evaluated approaches of different modelling fidelity implemented in the publically available *Simulator for Offshore Wind Farm Applications* (SOWFA) OpenFOAM library for simulating incompressible flow around wind turbines, including the ALM approach. In this work, the AALM implementation of SOWFA was extended to compressible propeller flows. Density sampling was introduced into the body-force terms, which were originally derived from incompressibility assumptions. Secondly, these terms are consistently incorporated into both momentum and energy equations.

Validation is conducted using a proprietary test rotor geometry provided by Flying Whales alongside experimental benchmark data acquired at Aero Concept Engineering's wind-tunnel facility in Magny-Cours. The numerical approach employs unsteady RANS (URANS) simulations with the k-omega SST turbulence model. A customised version of the rhoPimpleFoam solver is used, featuring a consistent pressure-velocity coupling to avoid checkerboard pressure fields and increased numerical stability. The aerodynamic polars required as input for the AALM were generated with Upstream CFD's RANS-based 2D airfoil suite, where values for stall conditions were extrapolated using a flat plate assumption. The computational domain represents the wind tunnel test section with the nacelle geometry mounted on a cylindrical arm. Flow speeds of 0 m/s to 30 m/s and rotation speeds of 6038 rpm to 6078 rpm were simulated, leading to maximum Mach numbers of 0.63 at the propeller tips, thus necessitating a compressible approach. A comprehensive best practice study was conducted to determine efficient settings for solver, numerical schemes, grid resolution and time step size.

Table 1: Difference of time-averaged performance quantities to experimental benchmark data

U_∞ [m/s]	Rotor AoA [°]	Pitch [°]	RPM	ΔT [%]	ΔQ [%]	$\Delta \eta$ [%]
30	0	+15	6078	-2.2	+6.9	-8.5
30	20	+15	6078	+2.4	+6.5	-3.8
20	0	-10	6043	-6.0	-16.8	+13.0
20	20	-10	6038	-13.2	-18.4	+6.3

Validation simulations were conducted for varying inflow speeds, flow angles and blade pitch angles to simulate both forward and reverse thrust conditions. The exact operating conditions are listed in Table 1 together with the percentual differences of thrust T , torque Q and the aerodynamic efficiency η compared to the experimental benchmark data. Flow visualisations for two representative cases are shown in Figure 1. For forward thrust conditions, thrust predictions were within $\pm 3\%$ and torque values within 6% to 7% of the experimental benchmark, so that the resulting aerodynamic efficiency predicted by CFD was between 3% to 9% lower. Under more challenging reverse thrust conditions, the

difference between CFD and experiment increased to 6% to 13% for the aerodynamic efficiency. In general, reverse thrust conditions can lead to highly unsteady flow fields and are thus also a challenging application case for experimental test facilities. The developed AALM implementation showed strong numerical robustness for these cases and delivered results within the same magnitude of the experimental benchmark, which is highly encouraging for future studies given the level of modelling fidelity applied in the approach.

Future work will include further validation and direct comparison with fully resolved propeller simulations. The application of AALM in combination with scale-resolving methods such as σ -DDES is planned as well as the combination with the EBL turbulence model, which is better suited for flows with strong coherent vortices. Finally, productive use cases of the AALM with simulations involving multiple rotors, such as full-scale airships, drones/eVTOL or wind farms are targeted.

Figure 1: Flow visualisation of two representative validation cases. Iso-Q surfaces coloured with velocity magnitude + iso surface of force projection (left) and time-averaged velocity magnitude on z-slice through rotor centre (right).

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VALIDATION OF A PRESSURE-BASED COUPLED SOLVER FOR HIGHLY COMPRESSIBLE TURBOMACHINERY FLOWS

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Keywords: Turbomachinery, compressor, coupled solver, highly compressible flows.

The accurate and robust simulation of highly compressible flows in turbomachinery remains a critical challenge in the field of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). In high-speed axial compressors, where Mach numbers frequently exceed unity, numerical instability, convergence difficulties, and sensitivity to discretisation schemes are common issues that compromise both the reliability and predictive capability of CFD models. To address these challenges, coupled solvers are often preferred over segregated solvers due to their improved numerical stability and convergence properties in compressible regimes. Unlike segregated approaches, where pressure and velocity are solved sequentially, coupled solvers resolve all flow variables simultaneously, yielding a tighter and more consistent solution coupling that is particularly advantageous at high Mach numbers. Commercial solvers such as ANSYS CFX, ANSYS Fluent, and NUMECA Fine™/Turbo have set industry standards in this regard, offering robust algorithms and proprietary features that enhance solver stability and performance. These tools often outperform open-source alternatives like OpenFOAM, which, despite their flexibility and extensibility, still face difficulties when applied to high-speed turbomachinery flows due to limitations in solver design and numerical schemes.

This work focuses on the validation and application of the pressure-based coupled solver available within the HELYX CFD software [1], which has previously been validated for incompressible and mildly compressible flows. The objective of this study is to evaluate its performance and establish best practices for solving highly compressible turbomachinery problems. Particular emphasis is placed on solver stability, mesh and time step sensitivity, and accurate capturing of transonic flow features such as shock waves and tip-leakage vortices. By applying the solver without structural changes to its underlying numerical algorithms, the study investigates the extent to which an existing industrial-grade, open-source-based coupled solver can handle the stringent demands of high-speed axial compressors.

The validation campaign includes two well-established axial compressor benchmarks: the NASA Rotor 67 [2] and the TUDa GLR open stage [3]. These cases feature open-stage configurations with publicly available experimental data, allowing for a detailed and transparent validation process. The validation focuses on replicating key performance parameters such as total pressure ratio and isentropic efficiency across the operating range, while also comparing local flow quantities (e.g., total pressure and velocity profiles) at measurement stations. Results demonstrate that the improved solver maintains stable convergence across the full operating map and achieves good agreement with experimental data, with total pressure ratio and isentropic efficiency errors within 2%, confirming its predictive capability in complex, highly compressible environments as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Total pressure ratio results for the NASA Rotor 67 (left) and TUDa GLR open stage (right)

In conclusion, this work outlines a set of best-practices for achieving numerical robustness in pressure-based coupled solvers for turbomachinery applications and illustrates their effectiveness through rigorous validation. Future work will focus on expanding the validation suite to include additional compressors and multistage configurations, thereby further strengthening the generality and industrial relevance of the proposed solver framework.

Acknowledgments

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SIMULATING GAS DYNAMICS OF MULTI-SPECIES, HIGH-PRESSURE JETS USING blastFOAM: SENSITIVITY TO EQUATIONS OF STATE, GAS COMPOSITION, AND MODEL GEOMETRY

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Keywords: Hydrogen, Natural gas, Soave-Redlich Kwong, BlastFOAM, Turbulence models, Decompression wave speed

This study examines the sensitivity of gas composition, real gas equation of state, and modeling geometries on the solution accuracy of simulations of multi-species, high-pressure jets. This fundamental issue is garnering interest in several applications, including direct injection in propulsion systems [1] and high-pressure pipelines or gas storage safety [2]. It has been extensively investigated in the literature through both experimental [3] and numerical [4] methodologies. Here, blastFOAM [5], a solver developed by Synthetik Applied Technologies based on the OpenFOAM framework, is utilized to perform simulations based on the experiments of Botros et al. [3] in which natural gas containing (2-8%) hydrogen is released from a shock tube to determine the decompression wave speed propagation. blastFOAM offers fourth-order Runge-Kutta time integration and a wide variety of real gas equations of state (EoSs) with the capability to assign different equation for each gas in the same mixture; the Soave Redlich Kwong (SRK) EoS is not included in the published version of blastFOAM, and so was added as a part of this study.

The geometry and initial conditions of the problem are modeled similar to the shock tube experiments shown in Figure 1. A structured O-H grid with local refinement is used around the burst disk. Mesh independence study is performed by increasing the number of discrete segments along the perimeter and length. Decompression wave speed is employed to validate the simulations results against experimental data. The decompression wave speed is derived from linear fit of the arrival time of the decompression wave of a given pressure at the first 5 pressure transducer locations from the experiments and at the corresponding locations in the simulations. The geometry is modeled with 2D and 3D setups. Additionally, a symmetry boundary condition is implemented and compared to the full domain simulations in case of a 3D setup. Thermodynamic properties are calculated with various EoSs—ideal gas (IG), Van-der Waals (VW), Peng Robinson (PR), and Soave-Redlich Kwong (SRK). As turbulence may impact the gas mixing following the rupture of the shock tube, different turbulence models are compared— $k - \omega$, $k - \omega$ SST, $k - \epsilon$, Realized $k - \epsilon$ and Spalart-Allmaras. Different gas compositions are tested by comparing the exact experimental gas composition, as indicated in Figure 1, with pure methane then sequentially adding the other gases based on their respective mole fraction.

Figure 1: Numerical model with boundary and initial conditions

The experimental and a sample of the simulation results are plotted in figure 2. The results highlight that among the tested EoSs, the ideal gas EoS is not suitable owing to the high pressures in the shock tube (12.12 MPa). Both VW and PR EoSs provide similar trends, although SRK produced the best accuracy. Similar comparative studies of gas composition, model geometry effects, and turbulence model sensitivity were explored. The results of these cases (not shown) are discussed at length in the presentation to identify the most accurate method of simulating such multi-species, high-pressure jets. Both 2D and 3D simulations are performed using the same axial and radial discretization. However, simplifying the problem to 2D did

not present a significant variance between the two approaches. Also one quarter of the tube is modeled by employing symmetry boundary condition, but the full domain results achieve much better agreement to experiments than the quarter domain. The gas mixture in this validation case is composed of seven gases with different mole fractions but methane is dominant (89% mole fraction). Analyzing the decompression wave speed results shows a negligible deviation between the mixture of CH₄, H₂, CO₂ and the full composition. However, removing CO₂ from the modeled mixture leads to significant inaccuracy. This is likely due to carbon dioxide being a relatively heavier gas compared to the rest of mixture species. Finally, the current case physics seem to be dominated by highly compressible gas dynamics, with turbulent mixing playing a less dominant role in the experimental observations. Hence, different turbulence models do not affect the accuracy of decompression wave speeds predicted by the numerical simulations.

Figure 2: Comparing current results with previous research studies [6, 2]

In summary, this study demonstrates the capability of OpenFOAM-based tools in modeling complex gas release scenarios. Future research will aim to integrate high-fidelity numerical solvers with real-gas equations of state to study compressible, turbulent, high-pressure jet releases of gas mixtures.

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EVOLUTION OF AN UNDER-EXPANDED JET OF HYDROGEN-ENRICHED NATURAL GAS FOLLOWING ACCIDENTAL RELEASE FROM A PIPELINE

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Keywords: *Hydrogen, Natural gas, Under-expanded jets, Turbulence, LES, Flammability limits*

Integrating hydrogen gas into existing natural gas pipelines has been proposed as a promising short-term strategy for incorporating hydrogen into the current energy system [1]. However, injecting hydrogen into the natural gas grid requires careful consideration of several factors. Hydrogen can increase the explosion limit of the mixture, has a tendency to auto-ignite at high pressures, and decreases the volumetric energy density, leading to increased flow speed and pressure losses [2]. Therefore, understanding the gas dynamics, thermodynamics, and chemical processes of the mixture at different blending ratios is crucial for safety. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools are used as a cost-effective and safe method to study these fundamental physics in scenarios involving accidental gas dispersion.

The primary aim of this study is to configure the simulation setup within OpenFOAM to replicate the scenario of an accidental release of hydrogen-enriched natural gas from a high-pressure pipeline. The turbulent gas dynamics of the released jet develop moderately or highly under-expanded conditions depending on the pipeline pressure, which substantially impacts the dispersion and mixing evolution of the gas mixture following accidental release. As this study aims to estimate the safety envelope following release, a series of simulations are performed to calculate upper and lower flammability limits (UFL, LFL) of the mixture, investigate the effect of the gas flow rate inside the pipeline, and compare Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) to Large Eddy Simulations (LES) approaches. Moreover, we investigate the effect of different hydrogen blending ratios on the flammability limits and the structure of the gas jets. As the pipeline operating pressures are too low to cause hydrogen auto-ignition or detonation, chemical kinetics are not considered in this preliminary stage of the research. Instead, we focus on the gas dynamics, thermodynamics, and turbulent mixing of the gas mixture following release, which are pivotal steps towards improving the understanding of accidental hydrogen/methane releases.

blastFOAM—a variant of OpenFOAM-v9—was used for the simulations. The computational domain consists of a pipeline of diameter $D = 30$ in with a circular orifice of diameter $0.05D$ open to atmosphere. Two pipeline pressures are tested to represent transmission ($P = 4$ MPa) and distribution ($P = 0.4$ MPa) conditions. Natural gas with different hydrogen blending ratios (0, 5, 10, 20 vol%) is simulated. At first, the assumption of negligible internal flow in the pipeline is considered, then an additional simulation is performed with a pipeline mass flow rate of 14.78 kg/s to investigate the effect of the internal gas flow rate. To determine the gas mixture flammability limits, the Law of Le Chatelier [3] and correlations proposed by Miao et al. [4] are used to calculate the LFL and UFL regions throughout the release. The Le Chatelier relation conservatively estimates the UFL region, while no significant difference is observed between the two methods in calculating the LFL.

Initially, two simulations are performed at $P = 4$ MPa and 20 vol% H_2 . One simulation included gas flow inside the pipe, while the other applied a no-slip boundary condition on the pipe walls. The results indicated no significant differences in jet structure or flammability limits. Therefore, all subsequent simulations treated the pipeline as a long storage container with zero initial velocity.

Figure 1 illustrates the significant variance in the UFL dimensions depending on the pipeline pressure. It also shows that UFL axial distribution is not affected by hydrogen blending ratio in the mixture. On the contrary, there is noticeable variation in the radial distribution of UFL. However, the UFL radial dispersion variance can be neglected as it is less than one quarter of the axial dispersion. An abrupt change in the slope of UFL axial dispersion curve at lower pressure is observed in Figure 1. Initially, the jet velocity is similar for both pressure values during the first 0.005 ms then it gradually decreases as the jet begins to entrain ambient air.

The pressure conditions of distribution and transmission pipelines develop a nozzle pressure ratio (NPR) of 4 and 40 respectively. The resulting jets are categorized as moderately under-expanded jet for the low pressure and highly under-expanded jet for the high pressure. As seen from Figure 2, the two jet types exhibit different gas dynamics phenomena. Firstly, the maximum Mach number for the higher pressure ($M_{max} = 4.9$) is double that of the lower pressure ($M_{max} = 2.2$). Secondly, the moderately under-expanded jet undergoes a series of compressions and expansions, forming a diamond shock-cell pattern. On the other side, the highly under-expanded jets generate a Mach disc, similar to a normal shock, where the flow

becomes subsonic afterward.

In these RANS simulations, key flow features, including Mach disks, barrel shocks, and mixing layers, were captured, as shown in Figure 2. The influence of hydrogen content on jet penetration and entrainment was quantified and proved to be negligible in the range of (5 : 20) vol% H₂. Furthermore, LES simulations are performed and results are compared with RANS to assess the reliability of RANS simulations for transient investigations of the high-pressure turbulent gas dynamics of such multi-species jets. Ultimately, the result contributes to improving the understanding and safety of hydrogen-enriched natural gas.

Figure 1: Upper flammability limit length and width. Dashed line: P = 0.4 MPa, Solid line: P = 4 MPa

Figure 2: Numerical schlieren and Mach no contours at t = 4.5 ms with P = 4 MPa (left) and P = 0.4 MPa (right)

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rhoCubic4KFoam: A FOURTH-ORDER MULTI-SPECIES COMPRESSIBLE FLOW SOLVER ON UNSTRUCTURED GRIDS

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Keywords: *Compressible flows, Low-diffusion schemes, shock sensor, Richtmyer-Meshkov instability, ECN Spray G*

Many fluid flows of engineering importance include high-density ratios, shock waves, and numerous chemical species. In these cases, accurate predictions are dependent on the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) algorithm's capacity to ensure stable and robust time and spatial discretisation of the governing equations while efficiently minimising numerical diffusion.

The OpenFOAM community is actively addressing numerical diffusion concerns for incompressible and compressible flows. This paper presents a high-order solver for compressible, multi-species flows of ideal and real gases on unstructured grids, which can accurately simulate compressible, turbulent multi-species flows in industrial applications with minimal computing overhead. We integrated our solver into the open-source library OpenFOAM. The code features a newly developed discretization scheme that reaches fourth-order accuracy in space and, thanks to explicit Runge-Kutta integration, in time. The algorithm exploits the Kurganov and Tadmor diffusive fluxes and can handle discontinuities in the solution using a purposely developed sensor, which introduces artificial diffusion where necessary. Different from other sensors, it is based on the evaluation of the jump of all the functions at the interface, and its functional definition is such that it vanishes for continuous functions when the grid size tends to zero. The developed numerical methodology allows for more accurate simulations of various engineering interest problems than typical CFD codes, which demand a significant amount of resources to achieve equal accuracy.

To assess the solver's reliability, after having tested it with the classical 1D shock tube, we studied two different test cases. The first is the study of the Richtmyer-Meshkov instability induced by a shock-bubble interaction with real gases. Figure 1 shows the temporal evolution of the square bubble simulated. The second case analyzed deals with the flow in the internal ducts and in the near-nozzle region of a high-pressure fuel injector. We adopted a real-gas equation of state (EoS) and demonstrated the code's capability to accurately reproduce transcritical flows in complex geometries with significant density ratios. Figure 2 shows the pressure field computed using rhoCubic4KFoam and rhoCentral4kFoam [2], highlighting significant improvements in the reproduction of the flow dynamics.

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Figure 1: Comparison of the numerical prediction with the experiments in [1] at the same time instants (personal elaboration)

Figure 2: Pressure field computed using rhoCubic4kFoam and rhoCentral4kFoam.

Thermofluids, reacting flows, combustion

CFD MODELING OF BREAD BAKING PROCESS: INTERNAL TRANSPORT AND LOAF LARGE DEFORMATION

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Keywords: bread baking, large deformations, reactive flow

Bread has historically been among the first staple foods produced by humans and continues to rank among the most frequently produced baked products globally. Consequently, the knowledge of bread baking is worldwide known [1]. The baking process involves subjecting the dough in ovens to "appropriate temperatures" for a "appropriate time" [2]. This procedure triggers intricate chemical and physical changes, such as starch gelatinization, water vaporization and consequent condensation, carbon dioxide release, the development of crumb and crust, or the volume expansion paired with the formation of pores [3]. Additionally, the bread must meet established quality standards, which are primarily assessed based on attributes such as texture (with an emphasis on the crust percentage), moisture content, color (browning), structural integrity, and sensory analysis [4]. Consequently, accurate modeling of the baking process is multidimensional and complex, which results in continued reliance on the "cook and look" approach within the industry to determine the "appropriate time and temperatures" [3].

The ongoing progress in numerical mathematics and computing power is broadening the scope for applying computational fluid dynamics (CFD) across different disciplines. Our long-term goals include (i) developing a validated CFD model to simulate the baking of bread in industrial ovens, (ii) reducing the computational cost of the model using traditional model order reduction methods, and (iii) utilizing the model to minimize energy usage in the baking process.

In the previous work, we developed and validated the solver for the internal mass and heat transfer in the loaf of bread, see [5] and Figure 1.

Figure 1: a) Bread inside the oven with the streamlines colored by the velocity, b) contours of the water vapors content (ω_v) and temperature T after 4 minutes of the baking.

In the present contribution, we build on those results and extend the solver by the linear momentum balance (1) allowing to account for the bread deformation caused by the increased internal pressure generated by the formation of carbon dioxide via fermentation. Assuming the total Lagrangian framework, the linear momentum balance can be formulated as,

$$\nabla \cdot (J\mathbf{F}^{-1}\boldsymbol{\sigma}) + J\rho\mathbf{g} = \nabla \cdot (J\mathbf{F}^{-1}(p_g\mathbf{I})), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient with J as its determinant, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor, ρ is the mass density and \mathbf{g} gravitational acceleration. The right hand side of the equation (1), which comprises the internal pressure p_g , acts as the force source term causing the deformation. Note that in the model, the visco-elastic behavior of the bread dough is assumed, which is in agreement with [3].

The resulting bread shape and size are presented in Figure 2, where we compare our model with the surrogate model by Zhang et al. [3] and their experimental data. Observe quite a good prediction of the total volume expansion in comparison with the both surrogate model and also the experimental data. On the other hand, the shape of the bread seems to be more flat especially in later stages of baking.

Figure 2: Change of the bread size and shape in 1, 4, and 6 minutes of the baking. Original shape depicted in blue, the presented model in gray, and surrogate model by Zhang Et al. [3] in black. Experimental data from [3] in the second row.

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MULTI-REGION CFD SIMULATION OF THE THERMAL BEHAVIOUR IN AN AUGER PYROLYSIS REACTOR

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Keywords: multi-region CFD, pyrolysis, reaction kinetics, combustion

Biomass pyrolysis is a key process to produce biofuels, biochar and valuable by-products. Various types of equipment are used in industry to facilitate the thermal degradation of biomass [1]. Auger reactors are a promising technology for enabling the continuous output of pyrolysis products, like biochar, while enhancing the efficiency through the combustion of pyrolysis gases. However, optimizing reactor performance at industrial scales remains challenging. This is due to several interconnected phenomena within the device, including biomass degradation, pyrolysis gas combustion, and thermal heat transport in the reactor components [2]. This study presents a Multi-Region Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model of an auger reactor, highlighting flow patterns of multicomponent flows, combustion properties and temperature distributions within different components of the reactor. The results reveal the distribution of temperature and flow within the reactor, thus enabling a better understanding of the reactor behaviour and providing a foundation for reactor design improvements.

Figure 1: a) Current design of the auger reactor; b) Slice through reactor and reactor materials

The biomass pyrolysis reactor depicted in Figure 1 utilizes dual screw feeding for biomass transport along the reactor, where the biomass undergoes thermal degradation. Produced biochar can then be removed at the end of the screw conveyors. Pyrolysis gases, which are generated during the process in the feeding screw, are directed over a weir into the combustion zone, where a secondary air inlet initiates their combustion. The resulting combustion heat is then mixed with air via tertiary air inlets and distributed in the reactor volume via the tangential positioning of these inlets. This design effectively distributes combustion heat around the screw conveyors, promoting the pyrolysis of the biomass, while enhancing efficiency by the re-use of the pyrolysis gases.

To conduct this modeling approach in OpenFOAM 12, a multi-region mesh was established to represent the key reactor components. The outer jacket was defined using thermally insulating materials with an external heat flux boundary condition, while the inner components were modeled with high thermal conductivity to maximize heat transfer to the biomass within the screw conveyors. The gas phase was represented as a multi-species mixture based on representative pyrolysis gas compositions for wood [3]. The pyrolysis gas was introduced at the screw inlets using a fixed mass flow rate derived from available data. Importantly, the thermal degradation of biomass was not modelled, and no multiphase treatment was applied. Instead, only the pyrolysis gas, characterized by its composition and mass flow rate, was used to define the inlet conditions for the screw conveyors. Simulations employed the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model to resolve flow behavior. Radiative heat transfer in the combustion zone was implemented using the finite volume discrete ordinates

method (fvDOM), while combustion was modelled using the Partially Stirred Reactor (PaSR) approach, incorporating reaction kinetics from GRI-Mech V3.0 [4].

a) **Figure 2: a) Volumetric heat release in central part of reactor; b) Temperature distribution in central part of reactor**

Figure 2 reveals that the primary combustion zone is concentrated near the secondary air inlet, where the oxygen availability promotes intense combustion. In contrast, the tertiary air inlets predominantly serve to transport combustion gases from the high-temperature region to other sections of the reactor, rather than contributing significantly to the combustion process itself. The asymmetric placement of the tertiary inlets also leads to a slight displacement of the combustion zone off the reactor’s centerline, resulting in an uneven temperature distribution across the two screw conveyors.

a) **Figure 3: a) Temperature on outer wall of the screw conveyors; b) Plot of average wall temperature along screw conveyors**

This spatial imbalance in thermal exposure causes higher heat input in screw conveyor 1 compared to screw conveyor 2 (Figure 3). Consequently, the system efficiency may benefit from operational adjustments, such as varying screw rotation speeds or feed distribution for conveyor 1 to optimize biomass conversion yield and to enhance overall process flexibility and adaptability.

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ADAPTIVE AND MULTI-OBJECTIVE LOAD BALANCING FOR DETAILED CHEMISTRY SIMULATIONS IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *detailed chemistry, reactive flows, load balancing, parallel efficiency*

The accurate simulation of reactive flows with detailed chemical kinetics, involving hundreds of species and thousands of reactions, remains a major computational challenge in computational fluid dynamics (CFD). When operator-splitting approaches are adopted, the chemical integration step often accounts for more than 95% of the total computational cost. Moreover, the highly localized and non-linear nature of chemical activity leads to severe load imbalances across parallel processes: cells near flame fronts or ignition kernels demand significantly more CPU time than inert regions. Standard domain decomposition techniques in CFD solvers, including OpenFOAM, partition the computational domain based on geometric criteria and assume uniform computational load per cell. Consequently, they fail to address the heterogeneity introduced by detailed chemistry, resulting in processors finishing at different times, idle cores, and poor parallel efficiency. As the number of MPI processes increases and the number of cells per core decreases, this imbalance further amplifies, severely limiting scalability.

To mitigate this issue, several chemistry-specific dynamic load balancing (DLB) strategies have been developed. Notable efforts include DLBFoam [1], which dynamically redistributes chemistry tasks during runtime and applies reference mapping to exploit local thermochemical similarity; the chemistry load balancing library by Gärtner et al. [2], which optimizes task redistribution for both standard and TDAC chemistry models through efficient point-to-point MPI communications; and the method of Zirwes et al. [3], focusing on simple dynamic offloading of chemical computations between paired processors based on measured load. Recently, Van den Oord et al. [4] proposed a multi-level dynamic balancing approach targeting both chemical kinetics and real-fluid thermodynamics, achieving remarkable performance improvements through modular load redistribution stages. However, the existing techniques present certain limitations. Many rely on pairwise work exchange strategies that may become suboptimal at high core counts or suffer from increased communication overhead when scaling to massively parallel architectures. Furthermore, some approaches, while effective, are tightly coupled to specific solvers or require careful tuning of rebalancing parameters.

In this context, we implemented and systematically evaluated several dynamic load balancing algorithms within the OpenFOAM framework, specifically targeting the chemical integration step in reactive flow simulations involving detailed kinetic mechanisms. The tested strategies include task migration schemes inspired by previously published methods, such as sender/receiver pairing [3], cost-sorted redistribution [4], and an optimization-based scheduling algorithm using a 1.5-approximation scheme [5]. All techniques were adapted to the operator-splitting framework of OpenFOAM and assessed in terms of load balancing effectiveness, communication overhead, and overall simulation performance. The objective is to achieve a more uniform chemical workload distribution across MPI processes, reduce idle time, and improve parallel efficiency in simulations where chemistry dominates the computational cost.

Methodology

The proposed dynamic load balancing technique is specifically conceived to address the challenges arising in reactive flow simulations involving very large detailed kinetic mechanisms, where the number of species can easily exceed several hundreds. In such cases, the chemical integration cost becomes extremely high and tends to scale more than quadratically with the number of species, making it the dominant component of the total computational time.

The method builds upon the optimization-based scheduling strategy originally introduced by Wu et al. [5], and adapts it to the OpenFOAM framework, introducing key improvements to maximize performance and robustness under these specific conditions. Rather than attempting to rebalance the complete computational workload, the methodology focuses exclusively on the chemical step. Each computational cell is dynamically assigned a weight proportional to its estimated or measured chemical integration cost. The objective is to redistribute cells among MPI processes to minimize the maximum cumulative chemical load per process, thereby achieving near-uniform load balancing across the domain.

The cell redistribution is formulated as a scheduling optimization problem, where the goal is to assign tasks (cells) to processors in a way that approximates the optimal solution within a known performance bound. A parallel 1.5-approximation algorithm is used: heavy-weight cells are first allocated optimally to minimize peak load, while lightweight cells are assigned through a greedy procedure to fill remaining gaps.

Compared to previously proposed OpenFOAM-specific approaches, the methodology introduces two major innovations.

- 1) **Adaptive Rebalancing Frequency:** rather than performing rebalancing at fixed intervals, the method monitors the chemical load imbalance dynamically during the simulation. A rebalancing operation is triggered only when the

monitored imbalance exceeds a predefined threshold (e.g., a maximum load imbalance ratio η greater than 1.2). This adaptive strategy minimizes unnecessary data migration during quasi-steady-state phases, while responding rapidly to dynamic events such as flame propagation or ignition.

- 2) Multi-Objective Balancing Strategy: during the redistribution phase, the optimization does not only minimize the chemical load peak but also penalizes excessive data migration between processors. A simple multi-objective cost function is introduced, combining the chemical load with a migration penalty term, thus favouring partitioning solutions that achieve good load balance while containing communication costs. This ensures that the improvements in load balance do not come at the expense of excessive overhead, although in cases dominated by large chemistry the impact of communications remains secondary relative to the chemical integration cost.

The methodology is especially suitable for simulations characterized by a moderate number of computational cells and a limited-to-moderate number of MPI processes. Unlike classical load balancing strategies that target massively parallel simulations with millions of cells, the focus here is on maximizing efficiency for highly detailed chemistry cases, where the primary challenge is the enormous computational weight of the chemical step rather than the sheer size of the mesh. Key features of the implementation include: i) lightweight data structures for storing cell-specific chemical load estimates; ii) efficient construction of send/receive maps during rebalancing phases; iii) non-blocking MPI communications for migrating thermochemical state data. Importantly, the method preserves the existing mesh decomposition for solving transport equations, ensuring compatibility with mesh-based load balancing strategies, adaptive mesh refinement (AMR), and minimizing intrusive code modifications.

Results

The proposed dynamic load balancing methodology has been tested in two challenging reactive flow configurations characterized by the use of highly detailed kinetic mechanisms, pushing the computational load and scalability limits typical of operator-splitting approaches.

The first test case consists of a pulsating laminar coflow flame, where the fuel stream is periodically modulated to induce unsteady flame dynamics. The chemical kinetics are modelled using a detailed mechanism comprising ~ 160 species and $\sim 2,500$ reactions, including an extended NO_x formation sub-mechanism. The simulation was carried out using ~ 0.1 million cells distributed across 32 MPI processes. In the absence of dynamic load balancing, the chemical step exhibited a load imbalance ratio η exceeding 3, leading to substantial idle times among faster processes. By applying the proposed dynamic rebalancing strategy, the chemical load imbalance was reduced to below ~ 1.2 , resulting in a total chemistry step time reduction of approximately 50%. The overall simulation speed-up, accounting for both chemistry and transport steps, was over 40%. Importantly, the dynamic rebalancing was able to maintain stability and accuracy without introducing numerical artifacts.

The second test case involves the simulation of a 2D turbulent non-premixed flame in decaying isotropic turbulence [6]. The chemical mechanism includes detailed soot formation and growth modelling via a Discrete Sectional Method (DSM), involving ~ 320 species and more than $\sim 14,000$ reactions. The computational domain contained ~ 0.25 million cells, and simulations were performed on 128 MPI processes. Due to the highly localized nature of soot chemistry and the evolving turbulence structures, the chemical step load imbalance initially exceeded a ratio of 4. With the dynamic load balancing activated, the imbalance was reduced to ~ 1.15 . Consequently, the chemical integration wall time decreased by more than 50%, and the overall simulation efficiency improved by approximately 50%. The dynamic method effectively adapted to the evolving turbulent structures, consistently redistributing the chemical load as the flame and soot production regions evolved.

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CLOUD-BASED AUTOMATED CFD DESIGN TOOLS USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE HEAT TREATMENT OF TITANIUM COMPONENTS

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Keywords: CHT, Coupling, Multi-region, Workflow automation

While CFD methods for simpler flow conditions have already found their way into product and process development, complex problems such as multiphase or multiphysics applications often still require intensive model validation and, due to the usually long computing times, model optimisation. One way to provide the developer with a design tool for these more demanding CFD tasks is to create an automated CFD tool for a specific process that is validated and optimised for the application. This makes it particularly easy to use, especially in conjunction with cloud resources, as the frequently required high computing resources can be made available as needed. This means that HPC systems can be addressed in the background under Linux and the administration of hardware systems on site is no longer necessary.

Modelling approach

Using the example of modelling the cooling behaviour of titanium components during heat treatment, the creation and application of such a tool to reduce creep processes during cooling is demonstrated. Natural convection, heat conduction, radiation exchange and energy release due to microstructural transformation are taken into account in a transient conjugate heat transport analysis. The CFD model was created in OpenFOAM, validated by numerous experiments and optimised in terms of computing time.

Figure 1: CHT model in CFD analysis

Validation

Figure 2 shows the normalized temperature curve and the cooling rate of some comparison positions. In general, a good agreement between simulation and experiment is achieved. Various effects can be reproduced in the simulation, especially for the more important cooling rates in the right-hand picture: the cooling rates are characterized by an initial sharp drop due to the high energy dissipation to the environment. In the second step, there is a strong decrease in the cooling rates, since energy is released in the component due to the structural transformation. In the following, the cooling rate in the different positions depends strongly on the environmental conditions:

Figure 2: Temperature and cool ingrate vs. relative time for cooling in quiescent air in different positions of the component

At the outermost component position 8 of the thermocouple, cooling occurs faster than in the centre positions (e.g. position 5), because on the one hand there is less thermal mass here and on the other hand the radiation exchange with the grate is reduced due to the smaller cross-sectional area. The effects of the position-dependent cooling rates in the experiment are thus very well reproduced by the simulation. This is the crucial prerequisite for optimizing the cooling process, since the creep of the component is finally attributed to uneven cooling of the component.

In addition to cooling in quiescent air, cooling under forced convection in a rapid cooling chamber was also analysed [1]. For creep modeling, the time-dependent temperature field from the CHT analysis is transferred to the Abaqus structural solver, where the creep analysis is performed. Here, it has been shown that unidirectional coupling is sufficient.

Automation

The CFD workflow is fully automated. The geometry exported in STL format for grate, supports and component serves as input. With a parameter file for the individual boundary conditions, the case is automatically meshed via Python and shell scripting, provided with boundary conditions and finally calculated. For the meshing, the OpenFOAM-internal mesh generator snappyHexMesh is used, which generates a hexahedron-dominant polyhedral mesh. The meshing and simulation are carried out on a local server or in the cloud under Linux. A monitoring tool allows the simulation progress to be checked from a Windows desktop. Finally, the mapping of the temperature data to Abaqus is also done via the monitoring tool, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Automated workflow for the creation and calculation of the CFD model

Application

The tool is used by the end user to optimise the cooling conditions of titanium components in the preliminary design phase. In particular, it was shown that component distortion due to creep is minimised if the component is cooled as evenly as possible on the top and bottom surfaces. In this context, the grate on which the component lies is of particular importance, as a large amount of energy is stored here, which is exchanged with the component over a long period of time through radiation. As a result, the component cools down more slowly on the underside. Numerical simulations can be used to test various measures in advance in order to compensate for these effects and ensure uniform cooling of the component

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REDUCED CFD, NUMERICAL CONTINUATION FOR ROTATING DETONATION ENGINES

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Keywords: RDEs, Numerical Continuation, Reduced CFD

The steady wave mode in rotating detonation engines (RDEs) - the final number and direction of detonations after ignition - is known to impact performance. However, many questions remain concerning their connection to operating conditions. A useful framework for answering such questions comes from the field of dynamical systems. The various wave modes, as well as conventional, deflagration behavior, can be thought of as asymptotic attractors of the engine system. From a dynamical systems viewpoint, the goal is to construct a bifurcation diagram illustrating the different branches of attractors and how they vary with operating conditions, framed as bifurcation parameters. To more completely understand the phenomena governing these attractors, it is also necessary to understand the unsteady physics by which they precipitate. For these reasons, the goal of this work is to develop means to study both the asymptotic attractors and the unsteady physics that saturate to produce them, particularly how these depend on operating parameters of the system. Ultimately, this work seeks to aid in the design and operation of RDEs by establishing how they relate to device behavior.

Figure 1: 2D “unwrapped” RDE model with boundary conditions and dimensions

While real RDEs depend on fuels with complex chemistry and have a 3-dimensional flow-field, prior work has established that 2-dimensional, “unwrapped” models with simplified chemistry retain essential physics necessary to develop such an understanding [1]. Therefore, we opted to utilize such a model (shown in figure 1) in order to explore a broader design / operational space. The governing, non-dimensional equations of are model are as follows

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + R(Q) = S(Q), \quad (1)$$

$$R(Q) \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \begin{pmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ (E + p)u \\ \rho uZ \end{pmatrix} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \begin{pmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ (E + p)v \\ \rho vZ \end{pmatrix}, \quad S(Q) \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \omega q \\ \omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega \equiv Da\rho(1 - Z) \exp\left(-E_a \left[\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ign}}\right]\right) \quad (3)$$

These equations are given in terms of the conserved variables $Q \equiv (\rho, \rho u, \rho v, E, \rho Z)^T$. We adopt the same non-dimensionalization used by Koch et al, the reference values for which are discussed therein [2, 3]. Combustion is modeled

using single-step, Arrhenius-type combustion kinetics regulated by the combustion progress variable Z , following prior work [1]. Because the inlet supplies premixed, unburnt reactants, $Z = 0$ at the inlet. The fluid is treated as a calorically perfect gas with constant specific heat ratio γ and a (non-dimensional) ideal gas constant of 1. The remaining model constants - the activation energy E_a , heat release rate, C-J post-shock (von Neumann) temperature T_{ign} , and Damköhler number Da - are further discussed in our prior work [3]. Note that the flow time scale is $t_0 \equiv y_0/u_0$. This is the fixed convective time scale resulting from the velocity and length scales used for non-dimensionalization (near the sound speed and detonation height, respectively).

The time evolution of the system was computed by numerically solving the aforementioned system of equations. This was performed using a custom application based on blastFoam, an open-source solver based on OpenFOAM-9 and developed by Synthetik Applied Technologies [4]. This solver has been extensively validated for simulating highly compressible, reacting flows, particularly those with detonations. The variables were estimated at the cell faces using the quadratic MUSCL scheme in blastFoam, which uses the gradients and Hessians (that is, the 1st and 2nd spatial derivatives) to perform high order reconstruction. The convective fluxes are estimated using the HLLC scheme for shock capturing. Temporal integration was performed using the 4th order, strong-stability-preserving Runge-Kutta (RK4SSP) scheme. An adaptive time step was used to fix the CFL at 0.75.

To directly compute steady attractors and construct the aforementioned bifurcation diagram we developed the open-source software tool “LOCAFOAM.” This code combines the accessibility and widespread familiarity of OpenFOAM with the power of the numerical continuation package LOCA (“Library of Continuation Algorithms”), part of the scientific computing suite Trilinos developed by Sandia National Laboratories. Besides having a long and successful history of use for fluid mechanical problems, LOCA has the added advantage of a highly modular structure; all of its algorithms operate on a discretized dynamical system through abstract “model interfaces.” In other words, one can set up and discretize a system in OpenFOAM without ever interacting with LOCA or other Trilinos software. As OpenFOAM is exceedingly easy to use and widely popular among combustion researchers (and Trilinos far less so), this pairing is highly advantageous.

Once a system is discretized in OpenFOAM, it is manipulated by LOCA through Trilinos’ own linear algebra data structures within an abstract “model evaluator” in the Trilinos package Thyra. The user has the option of either hand-coding a Jacobian or using an approximate one estimated via finite differencing. The latter enables greater abstraction and ease of use but can be computationally expensive. To mitigate this downside, we employ a graph coloring approach that takes advantage of the structural orthogonality of the Jacobian to drastically reduce the number of function evaluations needed for its estimation. All aspects of the continuation problem are subsequently handled by LOCA, including the computation of solutions and the eigenvalue problem for stability and bifurcation analysis. Although we developed LOCAFOAM specifically for this study, we emphasize that it is quite general and can be used for any PDE continuation problem.

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TOWARD FIRE DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS OF THERMAL RUNAWAY PROPAGATION IN BATTERY ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

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Keywords: *Lithium-ion batteries, Thermal runaway, Fire dynamics*

Introduction

Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) are a prevalent and growing means of stabilizing power grids with high penetration of intermittent renewable energy sources [1]. BESS typically rely on lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) as their basic building block. LIBs are packed together in an enclosure to form a module. Multiple modules are assembled into a rack, and these racks are housed within a container to form one of many units in a BESS. LIBs pose a safety hazard if abused thermally, mechanically or electrically due to a failure mechanism known as thermal runaway (TR) [2]. TR is a localized breakdown of the LIB internal structure, causing exothermic chemical reactions that lead to a propagating reacting front within the LIB. It further results in the production of large quantities of flammable gas, which increase the LIB's internal pressure and lead to its rupture, releasing the flammable gas. This rapid self-heating thermally abuses neighboring LIBs within a module, driving them into TR, initiating a cell-to-cell cascade known as TR propagation (TRP). Since the LIBs are enclosed within a module, the large volume of vented gas produced by TRP is driven out of vents and openings on the module body [3], whereupon it mixes with ambient air and poses a fire and explosion hazard. Fire dynamics thus come into play at the module scale, due to the potential for flame heating of the module exterior by a vented gas-fueled fire. To this end, the present study will discuss recent model developments and their implementation in an OpenFOAM solver at the module scale, toward building a predictive capability for analyzing and predicting rack and unit-scale TRP events and associated fire dynamics.

Methodology

The developments we consider in this work utilize FireFOAM, an LES solver in the OpenFOAM family developed originally at FM [4] for simulation of fire dynamics and fire suppression. FireFOAM is capable of simulating complex fire scenarios, handling the coupled physics arising from gaseous flows and combustion, water sprays, films, radiation and solid-phase pyrolysis. FM maintains a branch of FireFOAM with specific capabilities for handling practical fire scenarios [5].

In this work, we implemented TRP as a region model derived from the base pyrolysis model within FireFOAM. In particular, our implementation targets recent module-scale [3] and rack-scale [6] TRP fire dynamics experiments conducted at FM using large pouch-format Li-NMC532 (nickel-manganese-cobalt oxide)-graphite cells. The mathematical formulation of the TRP model is based on our earlier work [7] and is only described at a high level here. The thermo-chemical behavior of each LIB is described by one-dimensional reaction-diffusion equations for mass, energy and species to consider multi-species reactions and mass loss due to venting. A one-dimensional treatment is reasonable due to the high in-plane thermal conductivity of pouch-format LIBs, and thermal and kinetic parameters are obtained via parameter optimization against single-cell experiments [7]. To analyze TRP, we apply an inter-cell thermal resistance as a boundary condition between LIBs, the value for which we infer from the module-scale experimental data [3], and assemble a stack of LIBs as a single object representing a module within the region model. We include treatments for the coupled boundary condition such that vented gas exits the module at physically realistic locations based on the module geometry. The experiments use a torch to ensure the vented gas burns to permit studying of the fire dynamics, and thus we likewise assume that all vented gas burns in the ambient air.

Results

Here we show a sample of the results to be presented at the Workshop. The geometry considered is based on two-module TRP tests conducted at FM [3] with twelve LIBs per module. Each module is a rectangular prism with dimensions

Figure 1: Left: Snapshot at a time $t_2 < t < t_3$, showing the stoichiometric isosurface; Center: Space-time evolution of temperature in Module 0, with white lines showing boundaries between LIBs; Right: Coupled boundary temperature over time.

0.85 m \times 0.45 m \times 0.11 m. The lower module, denoted Module 0, is located 1.1 m above the ground, and Module 1 is located 0.055 m above Module 0.

The simulation begins by heating the non-coupled boundary of Module 0 to TR, which induces TRP at $t = t_0$, where times are marked by vertical lines in the right subfigure. The left subfigure shows an instantaneous snapshot from the simulation, showing that the vented gas burns in two turbulent, buoyant plumes due to the presence of vent holes on either side of each module. The fire imposes a heat flux on the coupled boundary of both modules, increasing their temperature, as shown in the right subfigure. This initiates a second TRP front in Module 0 at t_1 and a third in Module 1 at t_2 . The bi-directional progression of TRP in Module 0 is shown in the center subfigure. TRP completes in Module 0 and Module 1 at t_3 and t_4 , respectively. The fire is thus largest for $t_2 < t < t_3$, when there are three TRP fronts propagating simultaneously; the snapshot shown in the left subfigure corresponds to this time period. These results are phenomenologically in agreement with the experimental results [3], and further analysis of the simulation results, along with comparisons to experimental data, will be provided during the Workshop presentation.

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FAST METHOD FOR PREDICTING RADIATIVE PROPERTIES OF PARTICIPATING MEDIA IN SOLID ROCKET MOTOR AND IMPLEMENTED IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: Radiative properties, Particle, Combustion gas, Solid rocket motor, Radiative heat transfer

Thermal radiation has a significant impact on the internal thermal environment and plume radiation characteristics of solid rocket motor (SRM) with metallized propellants. The two-phase flow coupling with the radiative transfer process of alumina particles and combustion gas molecules determines the thermal environment of SRMs^[1]. In order to achieve precise numerical predictions of the internal thermal environment and plume radiation characteristics of SRMs, it is crucial to establish an accurate and efficient prediction method for the radiative properties of alumina particles and multi-component gas.

In this study, an improved method for determining the spectral and effective gray radiative properties of alumina particles and multi-component gas at the microscale was proposed. It combines Mie theory and line-by-line calculation method to establish a comprehensive database of spectral and effective gray radiative properties^[2]. The code of implementing Mie theory and line-by-line calculation was verified by comparing with literature results^[1,2]. As shown in Figure 1, the database includes several important parameters such as absorption efficiency, scattering efficiency, scattering phase function of individual particle and absorption coefficient of individual gaseous species.

Based on this database, a fast prediction method for the radiative properties of combustion products in SRM at macroscale was developed. As shown in Figure 2, it utilizes the data interpolation method and Planck-mean absorption coefficient global model for fast calculation of the spectral and effective gray absorption coefficient, scattering coefficient and scattering phase function of mixture of particles cloud and multi-component gas. The computational time was reduced by two orders of magnitude compared to applying the Mie theory and line-by-line methods directly. It is especially suitable for simulating the radiative heat transfer within metallized SRM, where the radiative properties of particles and gases need to be calculated frequently.

Finally, using this fast prediction method, an OpenFOAM solver coupled the combustion gas flow (continuous phase), particle flow (discrete phase), and radiative heat transfer of participating media (radiation field) was developed. The calculation flowchart of the solver for one time step is summarized in Figure 3. As shown in Figure 3, the continuous phase and discrete phase were coupled by source terms, and the radiation field was coupled with the continuous phase and discrete phase by radiative source term. In the solution process of radiation field, the radiative properties of the continuous phase and discrete phase for constructing the radiative transfer equation were calculated using the fast prediction method, instead of directly taking constants as in previous solvers^[3]. By combining the fast and accurate prediction method of radiative properties of combustion products and multiphysics field solver, a higher simulation fidelity level could be provided for the internal thermal environment in solid rocket motor in the future.

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Figure 1: Radiative properties of individual alumina particle and species

Figure 2: Calculation flowchart for the fast method for predicting radiative properties

Figure 3: Calculation flowchart of the solver for one time step

A GENERALIZED DYNAMIC THICKENED FLAME FRAMEWORK FOR HYDROGEN COMBUSTION IN AERO-ENGINES WITH CSP DIAGNOSTICS

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Keywords: *Hydrogen combustion, Low-NOx Burner, aero-engines, DTFLES, Computational Singular Perturbation*

Hydrogen is becoming central to efforts aimed at decarbonizing aviation, particularly through its application in Sustainable Aviation Fuel (SAF) combustors. However, hydrogen-air combustion exhibits a set of physical challenges that make its accurate modeling highly nontrivial. The low molecular weight and Lewis number of hydrogen introduce strong differential diffusion effects, which significantly alter flame topology, flame stabilization mechanisms, and sensitivity to heat losses [1]. Additionally, the high laminar flame speed and wide flammability range of hydrogen lead to a narrow operability window in industrial burners, where turbulence effects play a pivotal role [2]. This results in an increased risk of flashback and unstable flame anchoring, especially under the lean conditions typical of next-generation aero-engines [3, 4].

Among the most considered configurations under development are swirled and dual-swirl coaxial injectors. Example of the latter is the low-emission, and cost-effective HYdrogen LOw NOx (HYLON) injector [5, 6] designed for gas turbines, in which the flame can stabilize either at the injector lip in a diffusion-dominated regime or as a lifted flame in a partially premixed mode. Capturing these transitions demands a numerical framework that is not only capable of resolving the turbulent flame dynamics but also of faithfully representing the underlying chemical kinetics and multicomponent transport phenomena.

In this work, we present a robust simulation pipeline structured on the OpenFOAM[®] framework designed to address these challenges with a focus on predictive, physically grounded modeling of hydrogen flames in complex industrial configurations. The framework is built around a dynamically thickened flame approach (DTFLES) [7, 8], enabling large eddy simulation (LES) of turbulent combustion without the need for excessive mesh refinement near the flame front. The thickening factor is locally adapted based on flow and flame gradients to maintain accuracy in both premixed and partially premixed regimes. Specifically, the artificial thickening is modulated by a flame sensor that activates only in regions where combustion is occurring, ensuring that thickening is applied selectively. A hyperbolic tangent function is used to smoothly blend the thickening factor across flame and non-flame regions, preserving physical accuracy in the transition zones. The chemical problem is solved through direct integration of the ordinary differential equations governing finite-rate kinetics. The use of GPU acceleration [9, 10, 11] significantly reduces the computational cost associated with mildly-detailed reaction mechanisms, including NO_x dissociation pathways [12, 13]. Transport properties are evaluated with a mixture-averaged formulation including non-unity Lewis numbers, using Hirschfelder-Curtis approximation for diffusivity and Wilke's method for viscosity and conductivity. To capture the impact of wall heat losses, the workflow can include a multi-region coupling strategy that enables solid-fluid thermal interaction at the injector walls. This bidirectional heat exchange is essential for accurately predicting ignition behavior and flame anchoring, particularly in confined geometries.

The entire framework is validated against experimental OH-PLIF and PIV datasets for the patented HYLON injector [14, 15], demonstrating good agreement in capturing flame topology, stabilization location, and velocity fields.

To complement the purely fluid-dynamic and thermal modeling, we also integrate high-level post-processing using Computational Singular Perturbation (CSP) analysis [16], to extract physically meaningful chemical information from the simulations [17], including identification of explosive modes, reaction path dominance, and sensitivity to radical production [18]. In particular, CSP-based diagnostics provide insights into flame stability by pinpointing the regions where fast chemical timescale modes dominate, revealing where ignition, quenching, or transition between regimes may occur [19, 20]. Such layer of analysis is critical in understanding the complex flame behaviors observed in industrial burners.

By merging high-fidelity CFD, GPU-accelerated chemistry, and rigorous CSP-based diagnostics, this work offers a predictive and physically interpretable approach for hydrogen flame simulations. The methodology is generalizable to other hydrogen-based SAF burner geometries and paves the way for further investigations into plasma-assisted ignition and detonation-supported flame regimes.

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Numerical Investigation of Heat Transfer in Nanoparticle-Enhanced Taylor Flow Using `thermalMPPICInterIsoFOAM`

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Keywords: Taylor flows, Heat Transfer Enhancement, Microreactors, MPPIC, Volume of Fluid, Interfacial force, Iso advection

This study presents a numerical investigation of heat transfer in three-phase Taylor flows containing nanoparticles within millimetric channels, using a newly developed OpenFOAM solver, `thermalMPPICInterIsoFOAM`. This solver extends `MPPICInterFOAM` by introducing a thermal energy equation and enabling dynamic coupling of fluid, bubble, and solid phases under laminar flow. Modifications include: (1) full incorporation of temperature-dependent thermophysical properties; (2) additional thermophoretic and Brownian force models acting on the Lagrangian phase; (3) replacement of the MULES interface capturing method with the geometrically conservative `isoAdvection` scheme [1] to suppress unphysical currents at phase boundaries; and (4) correction of the interface force submodel to eliminate spurious particle behavior near the gas-liquid interface. The improved force formulation is confined to the interfacial region using a gradient threshold filter on $\nabla\alpha$, and the interface force coefficient is dynamically scaled with particle properties, as detailed in [2]. The accuracy and stability of the `thermalMPPICInterIsoFOAM` solver were validated by comparing results with prior studies on nanoparticle-based fluid flows [3] and interface dynamics benchmarks [4]. This framework offers a scalable and extensible tool for studying nanoparticle-enhanced cooling strategies in microreactors, electronics, and biomedical systems [5, 6]

Simulations were performed at $Re = 200$ in a capillary channel using two configurations: (1) two-phase Taylor flow (water and air), and (2) three-phase flow with suspended 100 nm Al_2O_3 nanoparticles at a volume fraction of $\phi = 1 \times 10^{-4}$. The solver computes the thermal field, particle transport, and interface evolution using a coupled VOF–MPPIC framework with iterative property updates at each time step. Heat transfer was analyzed using local and average Nusselt numbers across the unit cell.

Figure 1: Temperature distribution (isotherms) along the axial direction of the channel for two configurations at Reynolds number $Re = 200$: (Upper) Two-phase Taylor flow without nanoparticles; (Lower) Multiphase flow with suspended nanoparticles (volume fraction $\phi = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, particle diameter $d_p = 100$ nm).

Results show that nanoparticles increase the liquid film thickness between the bubble and the channel wall (Figure 1), reducing wall shear and accelerating bubble movement. This change results from the altered bubble cross-section and lower

flow resistance due to particle-induced film thickening. As the film becomes thicker, it buffers sharp thermal gradients typically observed near the wall, enhancing thermal stability.

This effect is reflected in the Nusselt number distributions (Figure 2). In the two-phase case (without nanoparticles), the local Nusselt number shows a steep variation near the wall at the transition from the bubble to the liquid slug: a sudden drop followed by a sharp rise. This behavior is attributed to the very thin liquid film that forms in the two-phase case, allowing heat to transfer inefficiently from the wall to the low-conductivity gas phase. Once the flow transitions into the liquid slug, heat is transferred into the water, resulting in a rapid increase in the Nusselt number.

In contrast, in the nanoparticle-enhanced case, the thicker liquid film reduces direct wall-to-gas heat transfer and moderates the thermal transition into the slug, resulting in a smoother and more gradual Nusselt number profile. Although particle accumulation near the wall may slightly reduce local peaks due to increased viscosity and wall friction, the overall heat transfer performance improves. The smoothed and extended heat transfer profile enhances the average Nusselt number by approximately 6% at $Re = 200$ and $\phi = 1 \times 10^{-4}$, without disrupting the beneficial internal recirculations.

Figure 2: Local Nusselt number distribution as a function of normalized axial position X/L_c , where X is the channel length and L_c represents the unit cell length (slug + bubble).

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Aeroacoustics

An accurate near-field aeroacoustic model for low Mach number flows

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Keywords: *Aeroacoustics, CAA, PCWE, CFD*

Aeroacoustic modelling plays a vital role in modern engineering, increasingly driven by the demand for quieter and more sustainable technologies. This need extends far beyond the traditional aerospace and automotive sectors, affecting electric vehicles, renewable energy systems like wind turbines, railway infrastructure, fans, HVAC systems, turbomachinery, consumer electronics, and even marine propulsion.

Regulatory frameworks such as ISO 3744, ISO 9613, IEC 61400-11 for wind turbines, ISO 5136 for ducted fans, EN ISO 3095 for railways, and ICAO Annex 16 for aviation, as well as RTCA DO-160 and EU Directive 2000/14/EC, increasingly require predictive noise control at the design stage. The growing regulatory and environmental pressure to reduce noise emissions across industries has placed Computational Aeroacoustics (CAA) at the heart of modern product development. As noise limits tighten and sustainability goals become more ambitious, accurate and efficient predictive tools are essential. CAA enables high-fidelity simulations of noise generation and propagation in complex engineering systems, providing a deep understanding of flow-induced acoustic phenomena without the need for extensive and expensive experimental campaigns. This accelerates the design process, reduces development costs, and supports early-stage decision-making. Crucially, CAA allows engineers to isolate dominant noise sources, explore mitigation strategies, and ensure compliance with evolving standards, all within a virtual, controllable environment.

In this work, the Perturbed Convective Wave Equation (PCWE) is implemented in HELYX [1] to study low Mach number flows. CAA model based on PCWE has many advantages over more traditional CAA methods such as acoustic analogies (e.g. Ffowcs Williams and Hawkings) or Direct Noise Computations.

The Perturbed Convective Wave Equation (PCWE) offers an efficient and versatile approach to aeroacoustic modelling. It directly computes the acoustic pressure field using a simple, easy-to-evaluate scalar source term, which reduces computational cost and memory requirements. Acoustic wave reflection and refraction can be analysed. The scalar source term is easily visualisable and can be derived directly from any incompressible unsteady flow simulation, relying only on the incompressible pressure and mean velocity fields, making it broadly applicable and easy to integrate into existing CFD frameworks [2].

The work also explores the pivotal role of advanced numerical methods in aeroacoustic simulations, with a particular focus on higher-order time integration schemes and sub-cycling strategies that enhance both accuracy and efficiency. It demonstrates how the modular USF (Unified Solver Framework) technology of HELYX enables seamless coupling between flow and acoustic fields, including the integration of synthetic noise generation. Additionally, the study presents validation and verification (V&V) efforts that support the reliability and robustness of the approach.

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HYBRID COMPUTATIONAL AEROACOUSTIC SIMULATIONS OF UAV PROPELLER NOISE

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Keywords: *Computational aeroacoustics (CAA), CFD, Propeller noise, Propeller interaction, OpenFOAM*

Noise prediction for small unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) is a critical factor in the design and optimization of modern aerial systems. The increasing prevalence of UAVs in both civil and military applications has highlighted the need for accurate, efficient noise prediction methods. Hybrid methods in computational aeroacoustics (CAA), which decouple the sound generation and sound propagation mechanisms, have emerged as an effective strategy for reducing the computational cost and complexity of noise analysis.

Hybrid CAA methods are based on modeling acoustic source terms using results from computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations. In this work, a hybrid computational framework is presented for predicting noise generated by a pair of interacting UAV propellers. Theoretical foundations of hybrid aeroacoustic modelling, including the assumptions and approximations involved, are first outlined. The aerodynamic fields used to model the acoustic sources were obtained through transient CFD simulations, with particular attention given to the aerodynamic and acoustic interactions between two rotating propellers.

Prior to conducting transient CFD simulations, steady-state simulations using the Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) approach were carried out to provide initial conditions for the unsteady calculations. All simulations were performed using the open-source CFD toolkit `foam-extend`, a fork of the OpenFOAM environment. The results demonstrate the capability of the presented framework to capture complex propeller interactions and provide detailed input for subsequent acoustic analysis.

The developed methodology offers a robust and flexible tool for propeller noise prediction in UAV applications, supporting further research into noise reduction strategies and aerodynamic design optimization.

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IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACOUSTIC RADIATION FORCE IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *acoustic radiation force, acoustic streaming, Lagrangian-Eulerian coupling, microfluidics*

Introduction

Microfluidic devices (MFDs) are used in chemical technology to intensify processes. MFDs are characterized by a large area-to-volume ratio, and usually their characteristic dimension is less than 1 mm. These properties allow for superior process control through enhanced heat transport, and diffusion-dominated mass transport. Chemical and transport phenomena can be further intensified inside MFDs by sonication. By applying ultrasound, depending on its frequency and the setup's physical properties, we can induce diverse acoustofluidic phenomena, such as: acoustic cavitation, acoustic streaming (AS), and acoustophoresis. If a standing acoustic wave is applied to a rectangular channel, Rayleigh streaming, a form of AS, arises within the channel. Additionally, if there are objects suspended within the said channel, e.g., solid particles, or dispersed droplets or bubbles, and their acoustic contrast is non-zero, they experience the acoustic radiation force (ARF), as they enter the acoustic field. If ARF's magnitude is great enough to influence objects' motion, as they travel through the channel, we call this phenomenon acoustophoresis. Thus, acoustophoresis can be leveraged to control the flow of suspended media through MFDs. In this work we present our implementation of ARF into OpenFOAM. We use a modified pisoFoam solver, with added kinematic cloud with colliding parcels. PisoFoam additionally simulates AS, and ARF is applied to the kinematic cloud *via* a particle force.

Model

AS is the time-averaged velocity field that arises through the sonication of a fluid medium. At the immediate scale sound waves spread, as the name would suggest, with the speed of sound, but the absorption of acoustic energy leads to non-ideal sound propagation, which leads to apparent streaming profiles, whose magnitude is much smaller than that of the speed of sound. Therefore in order to model AS, one can perform a direct simulation of the immediate scale with a compressible Navier-Stokes solver, and time-average the results. This approach is very compute-intensive, so instead one can apply the perturbation theory, and decompose the compressible Navier-Stokes equation to two scales, where the output of the immediate-scale is a source term for the time-averaged scale [1, 2]. When modelling ARF [3], one can leverage the previously computed source term to calculate the force exerted on a spherical particle by the acoustic field, as the two quantities are proportional. To model ARF and AS, we have modified the pisoFoam solver [4] by adding the source term to the velocity computation, and a kinematic cloud, which experiences the ARF, for which we have added a new particle force to the *lagrangian* library. The Lagrangian-Eulerian coupling was greatly inspired by the protocols presented in [5]. To model mixtures of colliding particles with different properties, we have modified the colliding cloud class to include parcels with different material properties (density and speed of sound in the material). Additionally, we have included a random injection model which randomly, according to prescribed weights, assigns said material properties to a newly injected parcel.

Verification

To verify our implementation of the ARF in OpenFOAM we performed a test run where we simulate AS and particles focusing in a 2D channel slab. The setup is inspired by [3]: rectangular duct (width \times height = $400 \times 175 \mu\text{m}^2$), fluid medium is water (density = 998 kg m^{-3} , speed of sound = 1480 m s^{-1}), 1.85 MHz actuation frequency. The latter suffices to create a standing half-wave, with the node positioned at half the channel width, and antinodes at channel walls. First we solve the first and second order Navier-Stokes equations to get the acoustic streaming profile, and the ARF field. Then we start a run where Lagrangian particles are injected into the domain, 2000 particles per second for 4 seconds - totaling 8000 particles, with uniformly distributed sizes between 0.25 and $1 \mu\text{m}$. Particles are randomly assigned either a positive (density = 1050 kg m^{-3} , speed of sound = 1550 m s^{-1}) or a negative (density = 950 kg m^{-3} , speed of sound = 1500 m s^{-1}) acoustic contrast factor with a 3-to-2 probability. The total simulated time is 10 seconds. The expected behavior

is for denser particles to be displaced to the wave's node – the middle of the channel, and for less dense particles to be pushed to the channel walls where the antinodes are. As the ARF scales with the third power of the particle diameter, and the particle drag force only scales linearly with the particle diameter [3], ARF should have a bigger effect on larger particles.

Results

Fig. 1 is displaying verification results. These suggest that denser particles are pushed to the middle of the channel, and the less dense particles to channel walls. Furthermore, smaller particles are less likely to be separated from the bulk flow than bigger particles. Particles, that are pushed to the middle of the channel, experience better separation even at smaller diameters.

Figure 1: Simulation snapshots after 1 s (left), 4 s (middle), and 10 s (right). The compound images include rendered flow field representations with overlaid particle positions (top), and spectra of particle size distribution against the x-coordinate, overlaid with histograms of particles' distribution for different material densities (bottom).

Discussion and conclusion

Results confirm the expected behavior of the verification run. The discrepancy between the separation quality of negative contrast factor and positive contrast factor particles, where the size exclusion was less sensitive for the latter, may be explained by the magnitude of these contrast factors, and different magnitudes of AS at those locations. Looking at density differences between the fluid medium and each of the particle groups, the difference is slightly greater for the positive contrast factor particles – the ones made of a denser material. Additionally, inspecting the histogram of the negative contrast factor particles' distribution, one can observe that there is a small peak in the middle of the channel, suggesting that they are collected at the node, rather at the antinodes. This may be explained with these particles being trapped by the surrounding denser particles, and is thus likely a phenomenon reserved 2D simulations or perhaps for dense suspensions. It should be noted, however, that we have presently only implemented the primary ARF, and in dense suspensions the secondary ARF may dominate. The secondary ARF can be seen as a particle-particle interaction [6], and we plan to add it to our solver in the future. Overall, our implementation of ARF in OpenFOAM gives expected simulation results, and will be used and developed further in our research.

Acknowledgments

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Naval hydrodynamics

Semi-resolved DEM-FV simulations for ocean engineering applications

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Keywords: *Finite-Volume Method, Discrete Element Method, DPMFoam, Sliding mesh interfaces*

In this presentation, we share our experiences using DPMFoam to model large particles on relatively fine grids. We combine the strengths of the Discrete Element Method (DEM) to describe particle-particle and particle-wall interactions and the Finite-Volume Method (FV) to model unsteady flows in complex and rotating geometries [1]. The flow around particles is semi-resolved, offering less detail than methods that resolve the particle-fluid interfaces such as the Immersed Boundary Method (IBM) or the overset grid method, but is sufficient for our intended application domain. Cheaper continuum based computational methods, such as Euler-Euler or Drift-Flux, would presumably miss the dynamics of cluster formation near walls as constitutive relations based on rheology and kinetic theory assume local equilibrium of the particle-particle and particle-wall contact statistics. This assumption is not valid in dispersed multiphase flows with high spatial and temporal variability.

Stability issues appear when particles displace fluid from computational cells that are of the same size as the particle or smaller. It is also essential to define an appropriate representative local fluid velocity for the drag force computation. For this, we investigated the effectiveness of the kernel and diffusion methods [2], [3]. We observe several advantages of the kernel method, but the implementation of the kernel method near sliding mesh and processor interfaces is not trivial. Continuity errors are relatively large compared to grids without a sliding mesh, but fortunately they are still negligible for our intended application. We have validated our approach by accurately reproducing particle settling velocities at both low (see Figure 1) and high concentrations, effectively capturing the hindered settling effect [4]. Additionally, particle-wall collisions in viscous fluids are well represented.

In the presentation, we provide two examples of applications in ocean engineering: rock spillage in cutter suction dredging

Figure 1: Effective flow field around a single particle using the kernel method to redistribute the solid phase concentration and the drag force on the computational mesh of the fluid region.

and rock installation for the protection of subsea infrastructures. We can accurately describe cutter spillage. This is very helpful in identifying the locations and mechanisms of cutter spillage. In rock installations with inclined pipes, we observe the formation of particle clusters along the bottom wall of a pipe while a constant particle feed is provided at the inlet, see Figure

2. We found qualitative agreement with experimental observations. A better understanding of this processes is crucial to gain more control of the particle feed at the sea bed and hence allow for an effective protection layer of seabed infrastructures.

Figure 2: Cluster formation and development of return flow in inclined fall pipe. Colors of particles indicate the magnitude of their velocities and the colors in the fluid region indicate the vertical velocity component of the fluid.

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SUBMARINE COLLAPSE AND WAVE GENERATION DURING THE 2011–2012 TAGORO ERUPTION: INSIGHTS FROM 3D OPENFOAM MODELING

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Keywords: Submarine landslide, tsunami generation, multiphase flow modeling

Submarine volcanic eruptions are capable of triggering flank failures that redistribute large volumes of material downslope and may generate hazardous tsunamis. The Tagoro submarine volcano (Canary Islands), formed during the 2011–2012 eruption near El Hierro, is a recent example to study such events. Over a six-month eruptive period, 13 multibeam bathymetric surveys documented the birth and evolution of the volcanic cone, including at least three collapse episodes. These high-resolution bathymetric datasets allowed us to reconstruct the cone's construction and failure phases and quantify the volume and geometry of the largest collapse event.

We numerically simulate this collapse using a three-dimensional two-phase flow model implemented in `interMixingFoam`, in which the volcanic material is modeled as a viscoplastic Coulomb granular fluid following a similar implementation as in [1]. The rheology is based on the approach of Domnik and Pudasaini [2], in which the granular shear stress tensor is given by:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = 2\rho\nu^s\mathbf{S} \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the bulk density, ν^s the effective viscosity, and \mathbf{S} the strain-rate tensor. The viscosity is modeled as:

$$\nu^s = \nu_{\min} + \frac{\mu_s(p - p_{\text{hyd}})}{\|\mathbf{S}\|} \left(1 - e^{-m_y\|\mathbf{S}\|}\right) \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: a) Perturbation of the free surface caused by the the granular collapse obtained with the numerical model. Circles show the shape of the experimental granular deposit. Comparison between experimental and numerical free surface elevation time series measured at wave gauge WG2 (b) and WG4 (c) for the 2D submerged case of [3].

Before applying the model to Tagoro, we validated it against 2D laboratory experiments by Grilli et al. [3], which involved submerged granular slides generating surface waves. The model reproduces both the final deposit shape and the free surface elevation at multiple gauge positions with good accuracy (see figure 1), confirming its ability to capture slide–wave interactions.

Using time-lapse bathymetric data collected by the Spanish Institute of Oceanography, we reconstructed the second major collapse of the eruption [4], which mobilized approximately $30 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ of volcanic material. The simulation successfully reproduces the observed final morphology: the summit deepened from 90 m to 130 m and a lobe-shaped deposit extending 800 m downslope, consistent with post-eruption multibeam surveys [5]. These waves propagate radially but attenuate rapidly with distance.

Figure 2: Simulation of the collapse and subsequent tsunami wave generation that occurred at some point between October 31st and November 12th.

This case study demonstrates that moderate submarine collapses associated with volcanic cone growth can generate localized tsunamis. Our results support the use of multiphase viscoplastic modeling with bathymetric reconstruction to assess near-field hazards. The OpenFOAM framework validated here can be applied to other volcanic island settings, including larger hypothetical flank failures, to improve tsunami hazard assessment.

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Implementation of a Physics-Based Cavitation Model in OpenFOAM for Marine Propeller Simulations

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Keywords: Physics-based cavitation model, IAPWS-IF97, Marine Propeller

The calculation of cavitation in marine propellers (Figure 1) is crucial for minimizing cavitation erosion and reducing underwater noise during the propeller design stage. Among various cavitation models, many researchers have used the Schnerr–Sauer model [1], which includes user-defined, problem-dependent parameters such as C_v , C_c , and bubble number density. However, these parameters often require case-by-case tuning, making the model less convenient and more empirical in practice. Recently, Kim et al. [2] developed a physics-based cavitation model that accounts for both bubble inertia-controlled growth and heat transfer-controlled growth simultaneously. In addition, this model provides empirical relations for the bubble number density during evaporation and condensation separately, while eliminating the need for C_v and C_c . In the present work, the first objective is to implement this model in OpenFOAM. Since the model requires accurate saturation properties during implementation, the IAPWS Industrial Formulation 1997 (IAPWS-IF97,[3]) was also integrated. The developed model is then carefully evaluated through benchmark numerical simulations. Finally, the model will be applied to a marine propeller case to verify its predictive capability without the need for tuning C_v and C_c .

Figure 1: Results of cavitation simulation

The physics-based cavitation model expressed as follows:

$$\dot{m}_{vp} = 3 \left(\frac{4\pi(1-\alpha_v)}{3\alpha_v} \frac{B}{3R_{min}^3} \right)^{1/3} \frac{\rho_l \rho_v \alpha_v (1-\alpha_v)}{\rho} \min \left(\left| \dot{R}_i \right|, \left| \dot{R}_t \right| \right) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{m}_{cd} = -3 \left(\frac{4\pi(1-\alpha_v)\eta_{cd}}{3\alpha_v} \right)^{1/3} \frac{\rho_l \rho_v \alpha_v (1-\alpha_v)}{\rho} \min \left(\left| \dot{R}_i \right|, \left| \dot{R}_t \right| \right) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\dot{R}_i = \text{sign}(p_{sat} - p) \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \frac{|p_{sat} - p|}{\rho_l}} \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{R}_t = \text{sign}(p_{sat} - p) \cdot 2 \sqrt{\frac{4f(|Ja|)}{\pi} \frac{D_l}{t_{ch}} |Ja|} \quad (4)$$

with

$$Ja = \frac{\rho_l c_{pl} (T_l - T_{sat})}{\rho_v L}, \quad f(Ja) = \frac{\pi}{8Ja} + \frac{1}{16} \left(\left(\frac{6\pi^2}{Ja^2} \right)^{1/3} + \frac{3}{4} \right), \quad t_{ch} = \frac{L_{ref}}{V_{ref}}, \quad T_l = \min \left(\frac{T - \alpha_v T_{sat}}{1 - \alpha_v}, T_\infty \right) \quad (5)$$

$$R_{min} = \frac{2\sigma}{p_{sat} - p}, \quad B = 1.495 \times 10^9 \exp(-15.86\Delta T^*), \quad \eta_{cd} = 1.144 \times 10^9 \exp(2.912\Delta T^*), \quad \Delta T^* = \frac{\rho_v L}{\rho_l c_p} \quad (6)$$

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Numerical methods

DEVELOPMENT OF A VOLUME-AVERAGED DIRECT SURFACE DESCRIPTION METHOD FOR MODELING WAVE INTERACTION WITH POROUS STRUCTURES

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Keywords: Porous medium, Turbulence, Free Surface Modeling, Floating Wind Turbines, Nature-Inclusive Design

Modeling the interactions between surface waves and marine structures with porous components is essential for predicting hydrodynamic behavior, structural loads, and energy dissipation across a wide range of coastal and offshore engineering applications. Porous materials are increasingly used to enhance the performance and environmental integration of marine systems, from breakwaters and scour protection layers to innovative nature-inclusive designs for floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs)[1].

This study develops and implements a robust numerical framework that extends the Direct Surface Description (DSD) method [2] by incorporating the volume-averaging technique[3] to accurately simulate wave–porous media interactions. The new volume-averaged DSD solver integrates sharp-interface free-surface tracking with macroscale averaged momentum equations that account for porosity, permeability, and resistance effects, while efficiently solving only the water-phase flow.

The volume-averaged DSD framework is validated through benchmark comparisons with existing OpenFOAM methods (interFoam, interIsoFoam) and demonstrated in two-dimensional and three-dimensional showcase cases featuring more complex and realistic scenarios. The focus of this study is on the development, validation, and performance assessment of the volume-averaged DSD model, which provides an advanced simulation tool for a broad range of marine engineering problems involving structures with porous components and wave interactions.

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IMMERSED BOUNDARY METHOD FOR SIMULATION OF FLOW AND HEAT TRANSFER IN MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS

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Keywords: *immersed boundary method, heat transfer, mechanical metamaterials*

Metamaterial is an artificial material whose internal structure is designed to meet the demands of a specific application. In the case of a mechanical metamaterial, its internal structure is usually designed to give the material unique physical and mechanical properties. In our work, we focus on mechanical metamaterials designed to withstand extreme thermal loading present in, for example, metal casting or the energy industry. Such mechanical metamaterials are mostly 3D-printed from a metallic alloy, and the metamaterial design has to consider multiple scales: (i) the microscale, determined by the choice of the alloy and printing technique; (ii) the macroscale, determined by the topology of the printed structure; and (iii) the device scale, determined by the choice of post-processing techniques.

In this contribution, the focus is on the macroscale, i.e., the topology of the printed structure. To design the topology, a mathematical model capable of simulating flow and heat transfer inside the structure is required. We have prepared such a model using an immersed boundary method (IBM). The reason for using an IBM was to later enable an easier inclusion of the model into a topology optimization framework, where the IBM will allow us to use one mesh for any structure topology and thus save a substantial amount of time on remeshing. In the following text, we present the model itself, its behavior in an initial test case, and comparison of results with a standard mesh-conforming approach.

Immersed boundary method For the model construction, we use our custom variant of an immersed boundary method, the hybrid fictitious domain-immersed boundary method (openHFDIB) [1]. In openHFDIB, the presence of a solid body within a computational domain is indicated by a scalar indicator field λ . In a cell Ω_P , the λ_P is defined as

$$\lambda_P = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \Omega_P \subset \Omega_f \\ 1 & \text{if } \Omega_P \subset \Omega_s \\ \tilde{\lambda} \in (0, 1) & \text{if } \Omega_P \subset \Omega_{fs} \end{cases}, \quad \tilde{\lambda} = 0.5 \left[1 - \tanh \left(\frac{\sigma}{V_P^{\frac{1}{3}}} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where Ω_f contains cells that are in fluid, Ω_s contains cells in solid and Ω_{fs} contains cells that are intersected by the fluid-solid interface. Next, V_P is the cell volume and σ is the signed perpendicular distance from the cell center P to the surface of the solid.

The flow and heat transfer in Ω is described by the following equations

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{u}) \equiv \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) - \nabla \cdot [\nu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] &= -\nabla \tilde{p} + \mathbf{f}_{ib}, & \mathbf{f}_{ib} &= \text{ceil}(\lambda) [\mathcal{M}(\mathbf{u}_{ib}) + \nabla \tilde{p}] \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}(T) \equiv \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{u} T) - \nabla \cdot (\alpha \nabla T) = Q_{ib}, \quad Q_{ib} = \text{ceil}(\lambda) \mathcal{L}(T_{ib})$$

where \mathbf{u} is the velocity, \tilde{p} is the kinematic pressure, ν the kinematic viscosity, T the temperature and α the thermal diffusivity. The source terms \mathbf{f}_{ib} and Q_{ib} are present to simulate the effect of the solid phase on the flow and enforce boundary conditions at the immersed boundary. These source terms are active only in cells where $\lambda_P > 0$ and are calculated from values \mathbf{u}_{ib} and T_{ib} that are preset and enforced by the iterative solution of the equations. The preset values are obtained by polynomial interpolation in the direction normal to the surface. The polynomials are constructed based on values in the free stream and a given boundary condition.

Figure 1: Comparison of θ fields from simulations of metamaterial cooling. (a) Computational domain for a mesh-conforming simulation. (b) Domain and λ for simulation with IBM. (c) Results from a mesh-conforming simulation for $\text{Re} = \{0.5, 1, 5\}$ ordered from left to right. (d) Results from simulations with IBM for the same Re values as in (c).

Initial results and future steps An initial test case was created to compare IBM with a standard mesh-conforming simulation. Specifically, a 2D simulation of coolant flow through hot metamaterial was considered. The computational domain has two inlets where the coolant with temperature T_c and velocity \mathbf{u}_{in} enters the domain. Inside the domain, the coolant meets the metamaterial with temperature T_h that is enforced by a Dirichlet boundary condition. The computational domain used for the mesh-conforming simulation is depicted in Figure 1a. The domain used for IBM where the metamaterial structure is represented by λ field is given in Figure 1b.

With both domains, the simulation was run three times with different \mathbf{u}_{in} that correspond to Reynolds numbers of $\text{Re} = \{0.5, 1.0, 5.0\}$. The resulting fields of dimensionless temperature $\theta = (T - T_c) / (T_h - T_c)$ are given in Figure 1c and 1d. The agreement between a mesh-conforming simulation and IBM seems satisfactory, but it is not perfect. The difference in outlet temperatures is about 4.5% on average. To improve this, in future work we will focus on, for example, a problem with spurious currents that we discussed in [2] and that may lead to unwanted convection flux across the immersed boundary.

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VERIFICATION OF A FINITE VOLUME SOLVER FOR ACTIVE AND PASSIVE CARDIAC MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR

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Keywords: *Finite volume method, solids4foam, Cardiac mechanics, Hyperelasticity*

solids4foam [1] is an open-source computational toolbox for solving solid mechanics and fluid-solid interaction simulations in OpenFOAM. The study focuses on verifying solids4foam for active and passive cardiac material behaviour based on the benchmarks presented by Land et al. [2] and Aróstica et al. [4].

The current work uses a newly developed Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov, cell-centred finite volume solid solver implemented in solids4foam [5]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first application of a finite volume solver to these benchmarks; in contrast, all results presented by Land et al. [2] and Aróstica et al. [4] came from finite element methods.

The benchmark problems (problems 2 and 3 from Land et al. [2]) consist of an idealised ellipsoidal ventricle geometry (Figure 1) loaded with a combination of internal pressure and active material contraction. The material behaviour is defined by the Guccione anisotropic hyperelastic material law [3]. A utility was developed to initialise the fibre distribution for the active contraction case (Figure 2, left). The displacement magnitude for the passive inflation case (problem 2 of Land et al. [2]) is shown in Figure 1 (right), while predictions for four different mesh refinements for this case are shown in Figure 2 (right) and coincide with the predictions from other groups presented in the benchmark paper. In addition, benchmark problems from Aróstica et al. [4] are explored, specifically, cases A and B, which use different geometry, material, pressure and activation models compared to Land et al. [2].

The `setFibreField` utility, activation function as well as the problems described in Land et al. [2] and Aróstica et al. [4] can be found at <http://github.com/solids4foam/cardiacFoam>, where the `feature-petsc-snes` branch of solids4foam has been used.

Figure 1: Left: Idealised ventricle: undeformed geometry (103 680 cells); Right: Idealised ventricle: deformed geometry

Figure 2: Left: Idealised ventricle: fibre field distribution; Right: Idealised ventricle: predictions for the four meshes from the present work overlaid on the round-robin predictions from Land et al. [2]

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A TEMPORALLY SECOND-ORDER ACCURATE FINITE VOLUME DISCRETIZATION OF ONE-FIELD NAVIER-STOKES EQUATIONS WITH HIGH DENSITY RATIOS

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Abstract

We derive conditions for consistent volume, mass, and momentum conservation in the one-field formulation of Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible two-phase flows without phase change. The derived consistency conditions are independent of the interface tracking method or the equation discretization scheme. Aiming at two-phase flows in geometrically complex engineering systems, we discretize the model equations and the consistency conditions using the unstructured Finite Volume method and verify and validate our approach for two very different interface capturing methods, namely the Level Set / Front Tracking method and the flux-based Volume-of-Fluid method. Verification and validation demonstrate stability when simulating challenging two-phase flows with density ratios up to 10^6 and viscosity ratios up to 10^5 . We finally discuss the requirements for consistent mass-flux approximation with second-order temporal accuracy in the context of the Crank-Nicolson temporal discretization scheme.

Introduction

Incompressible two-phase flows that involve fluids with very different densities (high density ratios) are ubiquitous in natural and technical processes, and the one-field formulation of Navier-Stokes Equations (one-field NSE) is widely used to model such flows. The one-fluid, integral form of the two-phase NSE enforces consistency between volume, mass, and momentum conservation, which, when not ensured in the discretization, leads to instabilities. The phase indicator function further uniquely defines the mass flux, which must be consistently used in the mass conservation and momentum conservation equation. These exact consistency requirements, derived from the integral form of the one-field NSE, are independent of the method used to model the fluid interface. Research into two-phase flow simulation methods for handling high density ratios is highly active; however, focusing primarily on the discrete level. In this work, we derive exact consistency requirements at the level of the mathematical model. These conditions must be tailored to the PDE discretization and fluid interface tracking methods, but they must be upheld. Since we develop numerical methods for simulating geometrically complex engineering multiphase flow systems, we discretize the one-field NSE with the consistency requirements using the unstructured Finite Volume method and validate and verify them for the unstructured Level Set / Front Tracking [1] method and plicRDF-isoAdvector, a flux-based geometrical Volume-of-Fluid method [2].

Method

The solution domain Ω is split into two sub-domains filled by incompressible fluids of constant densities ρ^\pm , $\Omega := \Omega^+(t) \cup \Omega^-(t) \setminus \Sigma(t)$, separated by the sharp fluid interface $\Sigma(t) := \partial\Omega^-(t)$ (cf. Fig. 1). The phase indicator identifies $\Omega^\pm(t)$ as $\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 1$, if $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega^-(t)$, and $\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) = 0$, if $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega^+(t)$, resulting in the one-field density $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t) = (\rho^- - \rho^+)\chi(\mathbf{x}, t) + \rho^+$, with constant phase-specific densities ρ^\pm . Integrating $\rho(\mathbf{x}, t)$ over a fixed control volume Ω_c (cf. Fig. 1), and defining the volume fraction $\alpha_c(t) := \frac{1}{|\Omega_c|} \int_{\Omega_c} \chi(\mathbf{x}, t) dV$, results exactly in $\rho_c(t) = (\rho^- - \rho^+)\alpha_c(t) + \rho^+$, if the integral $\int_{\Omega_c} \chi(\mathbf{x}, t) dV$ is exactly evaluated. This density update is used by all methods that discretize one-field NS, even those that do not actually solve a transport equation for the volume fraction or the phase indicator and, instead, replace $\alpha_c(t)$ by an approximate “marker field” modeled by the fluid interface $\Sigma(t)$, e.g., from the Level Set function or the Front in Front Tracking methods. The relation $\rho_c(t) = (\rho^- - \rho^+)\alpha_c(t) + \rho^+$, although exact, hides the following additional exact consistency requirement between the mass and volume *transport*, namely, with shorthand notation $\phi_c^n := \phi_c(t^n)$,

$$\int_{t^n}^{t^{n+1}} \int_{\Omega_c} \partial_t \rho dV = \rho_c^{n+1} - \rho_c^n = -\frac{(\rho^- - \rho^+)}{|\Omega_c|} \int_{t^n}^{t^{n+1}} \int_{\partial\Omega_c} \chi \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS dt - \frac{\rho^+}{|\Omega_c|} \int_{t^n}^{t^{n+1}} \int_{\partial\Omega_c} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS dt, \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Two-phase flow domain.

with $\int_{\partial\Omega_c} \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS = \int_{\Omega_c} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) dV = 0$ for incompressible two-phase flows. In other words, the control-volume density average is updated by a phase-specific volumetric flux $\chi \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{n}$, scaled with the density difference $(\rho^- - \rho^+)$. If the method used to track the fluid interface $\Sigma(t)$ does not use a phase-specific volumetric flux to track $\Sigma(t)$, the equivalence between $\rho_c(t) = (\rho^- - \rho^+) \alpha_c(t) + \rho^+$, when $\alpha_c(t)$ is a “marker field,” and equation (1) is not ensured, and this inconsistency leads to artificial acceleration and deceleration, i.e., parasitic currents, which are catastrophic in some cases. The solution for methods that do not rely on volume fractions (phase indicator) transport is to solve an auxiliary density equation to ensure equivalence defined by (1) when solving one-field NSE.

Solving the auxiliary density equation has been done for a variety of methods in the literature on the discrete level; we introduce the mass conservation equation on the level of the mathematical model. Methods that do not transport the phase indicator function require an exact reconstruction of the mass flux $\rho \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) = (\rho^- - \rho^+) \chi \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \rho^+ \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, by reconstructing exactly $\chi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from $\Sigma(t)$. Discretely, we approximate $\tilde{\chi}(\mathbf{x}, t) \approx \chi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from the approximation of $\Sigma(t)$. For the unstructured Level Set / Front Tracking method [1], we approximate $\tilde{\chi}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ from signed distances. For the plicRDF-isoAdvector flux-based geometrical Volume-of-Fluid method [2] we demonstrate the equivalence of solving an auxiliary mass conservation equation and discretizing the one-field NSE with the Euler and upwind schemes when $(\rho^- - \rho^+) \chi \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ in the mass flux $\rho \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is approximated by scaling the phase-specific fluxed volume. We analyze and apply the consistency requirements in the context of the Crank-Nicolson second-order temporal discretization scheme. Finally, on the discrete level, once a consistent mass flux has been approximated, the same mass flux must be re-used when discretizing the momentum equation.

Results and Discussion

Challenging verification and validation test cases involving droplets and jets with density ratios up to 10^6 and viscosity ratios up to 10^5 confirm our analysis. Verification involving droplets translated with constant velocity results in solutions that are accurate up to the linear-solver tolerance and maintain sphericity (Fig. 2), while droplets transported in ambient fluid remain stable. An exceptionally challenging mixing layer case in an inviscid setting remains stable. Finally, a coarsely resolved jet in crossflow remains stable, and its trajectory is successfully validated with experimental data. In all cases, when our suggested combination of consistent schemes, or, equivalently, an auxiliary mass conservation equation, is not used, errors increase significantly in the best case, and simulations catastrophically fail in the worst-case scenario.

Conclusion

We demonstrate how to ensure the consistency of volume, mass, and momentum conservation prescribed by the one-field formulation of Navier-Stokes Equations for incompressible two-phase flows, for methods that do not transport a phase indicator function, and how to avoid hidden sources of inconsistency in Volume-of-Fluid methods.

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Figure 2: Top left and top right images show catastrophic failures of inconsistent methods for a translating droplet. Lower left image shows artificial deformation of the droplet caused by inconsistent discretization. Lower right image shows a more accurate droplet motion given by the consistent method.

A Second-Order Accurate Topology Preserving Remap for ALE Methods

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Keywords: Data Transfer, Field Mapping, Topology-Preserving Remap, Arbitrary-Lagrangian-Eulerian

We present a second-order accurate data transfer technique between two arbitrary polyhedral meshes with same topology. Data transfer, is a key element in Arbitrary-Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) simulation methods. The term *ALE method* does not refer to a unique simulation procedure. In this work, we offer an advective data transfer technique suitable for topology-preserving *discrete rezoning* ALE procedures, in which the solution is obtained in a time-marching manner following the steps shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Discrete rezoning ALE

After rezone+remap, the Lagrangian solution on the target mesh is obtained again. This loop is iterated until the end time is reached, see Figure 1.

Method and Results: In this work, we introduce a second-order accurate *advective* remap procedure, the details of which follows. First, we move the source mesh points towards obtaining the target mesh, then derive and solve the equation that governs the transport of fields in such a motion. By mesh *motion*, we mean corresponding every mesh configuration with a real number, which we call *fictitious* time, denoted by τ . The fictitious-time-rate of an example scalar field T reads $\frac{d}{d\tau} \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho T dV = \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho \frac{dT}{d\tau} dV + \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho T n_i (v_{bi} - v_i) dS$, where \mathcal{V} is an *arbitrary* region, as the mesh does not stick to the material in this motion. Considering the fact that T is not a function of τ , and not so is u_i , $\frac{dT}{d\tau} = 0$ and $v_i = \frac{du_i}{d\tau} = 0$, and the transport equation reduces to $\frac{d}{d\tau} \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho T dV = \int_{\mathcal{V}} \rho T n_i v_{bi} dS$, where $v_{bi} = \frac{dx_{bi}}{d\tau}$, and x_{bi} stands for the position of the region boundary. Assuming a spatially uniform density, the Finite Volume (FV) discretised approximation of the equation is $\frac{(TV)^N - (TV)^O}{\Delta\tau} = \sum_f T S_i u_{bi}$, where O and N stand for ‘old’ and ‘new’ fictitious times, and the summation is done over all faces of the cell under consideration. When the T at the RHS is T^N , the equation for all cells forms a system of linear algebraic equations with T^N for all cells being the unknown vector. By solving the system, T field over the new mesh is obtained.

The algorithm is summarized in Figure 3. According to the flowchart, we input to the remap algorithm the source mesh, e.g.,

Figure 2a, and the desired target mesh, e.g., Figure 2c. Having the two meshes, we obtain the displacement field that produces the target mesh from the source mesh, which is simply obtained by subtracting the coordinates of the corresponding points of the two meshes. Then at each time step, we move the source mesh only by a fraction of the displacement field obtained in the previous step, so that the *mesh Courant number* remains less than or equal to a user-specified value. Finally we solve the system of the fictitious transport equations to obtain the field over the new mesh, i.e., the remapped field. In OpenFOAM syntax, this reads `fvm::ddt(T) == fvm::div(mesh.phi(), T)`. The loop iterates until the end time.

We examine our remap method by mapping an arbitrary scalar field ρ , used in a similar work [3], $\rho(x, y) = 1 + \sin(2\pi x)\sin(2\pi y)$. Field contours on the source and the target meshes shown in Figures 2b and 2d show good agreement. Figure 4 is the plot of the mapping error versus the mesh size for two methods, i.e., the current method and an inverse distance interpolative map, available in OpenFOAM `meshToMesh` class. Comparison shows that the current method produces lower error magnitudes, and also it is second-order accurate, while the interpolative map is only first-order accurate.

(a) Distorted source mesh (b) A field over the source mesh (c) Smooth target mesh (d) Target field

Figure 2: Source and target meshes and fields

Figure 3: Advective remap algorithm

Figure 4: The order of the error

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MULTI-VARIATE NON-NEWTONIAN VISCOSITY MODEL IN CFD

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Polymers play a crucial role in various industries, making it essential to understand their rheological properties to accurately model their behaviour. These materials exhibit shear-thinning, non-Newtonian viscosity, which depends on shear rate, temperature, and, to a lesser extent, pressure at moderate conditions (below a few hundred bars) [2]. To characterize their viscosity, models typically consist of two interconnected components: one describing shear dependence and another accounting for temperature effects [1].

The Power Law, Cross, and Carreau models are widely used to capture shear-dependent behaviour. The Power Law model, though simple and easy to implement, cannot describe the viscosity behaviour of polymer melts over the full range of shear rates and the model approaches infinity as the shear rate becomes very small. The Carreau model tries to overcome these cons by accounting for plateaus at both low and high shear rates, ensuring smooth transitions [2].

For temperature dependence, empirical models such as Arrhenius and Williams-Landel-Ferry (WLF) are commonly applied. The Arrhenius equation, while effective for moderate temperatures, fails near the polymer's glass transition, where the more advanced WLF model provides a better fit [3]. To comprehensively describe viscosity under varying conditions, shear and temperature models are often combined multiplicatively. For instance, Arrhenius can be paired with Power Law or Carreau, leading to four formulations that integrate both effects (table 1).

Table 1: Classical shear rate and temperature dependent viscosity models

	Arrhenius	WLF
Carreau	$\eta_0 \cdot e^{\frac{E}{R \cdot T}} \cdot (1 + (\lambda \cdot \dot{\gamma})^2)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}$	$\eta_0 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{c_1 \cdot (T - T_g)}{c_2 + (T - T_g)}\right)} \cdot (1 + (\lambda \cdot \dot{\gamma})^2)^{\frac{n-1}{2}}$
Power Law	$\eta_0 \cdot e^{\frac{E}{R \cdot T}} \cdot \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$	$\eta_0 \cdot e^{\left(\frac{c_1 \cdot (T - T_g)}{c_2 + (T - T_g)}\right)} \cdot \dot{\gamma}^{n-1}$

As shown in Table 1, the provided viscosity models are explicit, meaning that shear ($\dot{\gamma}$) and temperature (T) effects were derived separately and later combined. However, these formulations involve multiple fitting parameters and complex mathematical operations (e.g., power, logarithm, and exponential functions), making them computationally demanding when applied to Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations. Since viscosity must be computed at every time step for millions of computational cells, non-algebraic operations significantly increase computational cost.

To overcome this challenge, machine learning, specifically symbolic regression, was employed to derive a simplified, implicit viscosity model that incorporates both shear and temperature effects in a single equation. Unlike conventional regression, symbolic regression identifies both the structure and parameters of an equation without predefined assumptions, typically using Genetic Programming or advanced optimization techniques [4]. This data-driven approach enables the discovery of compact, interpretable models with only algebraic operations (addition and multiplication), significantly reducing computational effort while maintaining accuracy.

Using symbolic regression and a dataset encompassing shear- and temperature-dependent viscosity measurements, the following equation was derived to implicitly represent viscosity behaviour:

$$\eta(\dot{\gamma}, T) = \frac{(c_1 - T) \cdot c_2}{c_3 + (\dot{\gamma}^2 \cdot (\dot{\gamma} + c_4)^{c_5})} \quad (1)$$

The new formulation (η in Pa.s, $\dot{\gamma}$ in s^{-1} and T in K) consists of only five fitting constants (C_1 [K], C_2 [Pa/(K.s^{1+C₅)], C_3 [1/s^{2+C₅)], C_4 [1/s] and C_5 [-]) and relies solely on algebraic operations, making it significantly faster and easier to fit while also improving computational efficiency in applications such as CFD. This approach eliminates the need for computationally expensive functions, ensuring higher performance without compromising accuracy.}}

To validate its effectiveness, the derived model was tested on three independent, unseen datasets and compared to the Carreau-Arrhenius model (fitting performed using the lmfit library in Python). As shown in Table 2, the new model

requires up to one-fifth of the fitting effort while achieving comparable accuracy, demonstrating its potential for practical implementation in CFD simulations.

Table 2: Needed iterations for fitting models and the fit quality

Compound	Polymer 1		Polymer 2		Polymer 3	
	Carreau-Arrhenius	New Model	Carreau-Arrhenius	New Model	Carreau-Arrhenius	New Model
R-Square	0.9918	0.9771	0.9835	0.9904	0.9897	0.9573
Fitting iterations	367	43	155	74	341	55

Both viscosity models (the Carreau-Arrhenius model and the new implicit viscosity model) were implemented in OpenFOAM® v2006 and a high capillary viscometer simulation was conducted under identical conditions. Over a 20-second simulation period, both models produced nearly identical viscosity predictions, as shown in Figure 1. However, the new model required 87.92s of computational time, compared to 88.96s for the Carreau-Arrhenius model, demonstrating its efficiency.

Figure 1: Viscosity (left) and velocity (right) contour plots for both Carreau-Arrhenius and the new viscosity model

These results confirm that the new multi-variate implicit viscosity model, derived using machine learning, achieves the same accuracy as the classical Carreau-Arrhenius model while being computationally much more efficient. The improved efficiency is evident both in fitting the model to experimental data and in numerical simulations, as it relies solely on algebraic operations, reducing computational cost without sacrificing predictive capability.

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IMPLEMENTING A JACOBIAN-FREE NEWTON-KRYLOV METHOD IN OPENFOAM BASED ON PETSC: APPLICATIONS TO SOLIDS, FLUIDS AND FLUID-SOLID INTERACTION

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Keywords: *Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov, Finite volume method, GMRES, solids4foam, OpenFOAM*

Traditional Newton-based approaches require explicit Jacobian matrix formation and storage, which can be computationally expensive and memory-intensive. In contrast, Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov methods [1] approximate the Jacobian's action using finite differences, combined with Krylov subspace solvers such as the generalised minimal residual method (GMRES), potentially offering seamless integration into existing segregated finite-volume frameworks like OpenFOAM without major code refactoring. This study proposes and benchmarks the performance of a compact-stencil Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov method against a conventional segregated approach on a suite of test cases for different physics.

To facilitate a Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov algorithm, the governing are expressed in the *residual* form:

$$\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{R} represents the *residual* (imbalance) of the equation, which is a function of the primary unknown field \mathbf{u} . A Newton method is then applied in terms of an iteration over a sequence of linear systems:

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{u}_k)\delta\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u}_k), \quad \mathbf{u}_{k+1} = \mathbf{u}_k + s\delta\mathbf{u}, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{J} \equiv \mathbf{R}' \equiv \partial\mathbf{R}/\partial\mathbf{u}$ is the Jacobian matrix. Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov methods circumvent the need for the Jacobian matrix by combining the Newton-Raphson method with Krylov subspace iterative linear solvers and noticing that such Krylov solvers do not explicitly require the Jacobian matrix. The key step in Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov methods is the approximation of products between the Jacobian matrix and a vector using the finite difference method; that is

$$\mathbf{J}\mathbf{v} \approx \frac{\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u} + \epsilon\mathbf{v}) - \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{u})}{\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{v} is a vector (e.g., from a Krylov subspace), and ϵ is a small scalar perturbation.

The proposed Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov approach has initially been applied to linear and nonlinear solid mechanics, encompassing varying geometric dimensions, nonlinearities, dynamic responses, and material behaviours. Figure 1 demonstrates the analysis of the stress distribution around a spherical cavity in an infinite linear elastic body subjected to uniaxial stress using a polyhedral mesh, for which an analytical solution exists.

Subsequently, the generalisation of the proposed Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov approach to a laminar incompressible Navier-Stokes solver is shown, as well as a monolithic fluid-solid interaction solver, where the primary unknowns (fluid velocity, fluid pressure, fluid mesh motion, solid displacement) are concurrently solved in the same block-coupled matrix. Results show that the proposed Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov method exhibits greater speed and robustness for solid mechanics cases than existing segregated approaches and promising performance in the initial fluid and fluid-solid interaction investigations.

The findings demonstrate that the Jacobian-free Newton-Krylov method is a promising avenue for developing robust and efficient strongly coupled multiphysics solvers in OpenFOAM without major library refactoring. Further details on the formulation can be found in Ref. [2]. The described implementations are available in the solids4foam toolbox for OpenFOAM, inviting the community to explore, extend, and compare these procedures.

Figure 1: A spherical cavity in an infinite linear elastic body subjected to uniaxial stress

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TOWARDS EFFICIENT CHEBYSHEV POLYNOMIAL SMOOTHING FOR MULTIGRID SOLVERS

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Keywords: *Finite volume method, OpenFOAM, Polynomial smoothing, Chebyshev polynomials, Highly parallel algorithms*

The efficient solution of large sparse linear systems is essential in computational fluid dynamics (CFD) applications, where it serves as the foundation for computing numerical solutions of partial differential equations (PDEs). These numerical solutions are required for simulating fluid flows, heat transfer, and combustion in real-world scenarios. In CFD applications, the accurate modeling of physical phenomena relies on the discretization of continuous PDEs into algebraic systems, typically resulting in large sparse linear systems. The size of these systems is determined by the spatial discretization, where the number of finite volumes corresponds to the dimension of the coefficient matrix. As computational domains become more refined, the resulting sparsity patterns of the linear systems can significantly impact the efficiency of iterative linear solvers [1]. The algebraic multigrid (AMG) method [2] has proven to be an efficient and scalable parallel solver [3], but modern high-performance computing platforms introduce new challenges for its parallel performance.

This study presents an algorithm that utilizes polynomial smoothing as a simple and effective way to enhance the efficiency and scalability of the AMG solver. As suggested in the literature, there is no universally “best” polynomial; the optimal choice depends on the eigenvalue distribution, which is rarely known a priori [4]. In particular, we demonstrate that the Chebyshev polynomial is attractive for parallel architectures due to its avoidance of memory-intensive inner product calculations [5]. The newly developed algorithm will be tested for single-phase, incompressible, laminar, and turbulent flows. The expected outcome of the proposed algorithm is a faster solution phase. We anticipate that the findings of this study will help address the challenges associated with using recent high-performance computers and that the proposed approach can serve as an effective solution procedure for solving large sparse linear systems in CFD applications.

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VALIDATION OF A FINITE VOLUME SIMO-REISSNER BEAM METHOD FOR MOORED FLOATING SOLAR PLATFORMS

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Keywords: *Fluid-structure interaction, Mooring cables, Simo-Reissner beam model, Finite volume method*

This work validates the use of a finite volume beam solver for the mooring lines of a semi-submersible floating photovoltaic platform to simulate the motion of the platform in a wave basin. Bali et al [1] developed a finite volume solver for geometrically exact Simo-Reissner beams. Taran et al [2] built on [1] coupling this beam solver with `sixDoFRigidBodyMotion` library and a multiphase flow solver to solve the fluid dynamics of a moored rigid floating platform. This work builds on [2], expanding on the applicability of the developed coupled solver.

Mooring line analysis is often performed using finite element-based approaches. However, finite element approaches can be affected by “shear-locking”, a phenomenon that makes the elements appear stiffer than they are [1]. Shear locking does not affect finite volume approaches [1]. The finite volume-based solver in use in this work is based on the first finite volume formulation for beams subjected to finite displacements and rotations [1]. This advancement makes the solver particularly valuable for simulating extreme sea conditions which requires effective handling of fluid structure interaction and significant geometric nonlinearities in 3D [2].

A previous validation for this solver focussed on a moored box with fixed anchor points and four catenary mooring chains [2]. This work expands the applicability of the developed finite volume solver by considering a system with two taut mooring lines with springs at the anchor points. The Young’s modulus of the mooring line is used to find a spring constant for the mooring line. Considering the mooring line to be a spring in series with the anchor spring allows for an equivalent spring constant for the entire mooring system to be calculated. This equivalent spring constant is then converted to an equivalent Young’s modulus for the mooring system. It is this equivalent Young’s modulus that is used for modelling the beams.

The model is being validated against experimental data for a semi-submersible floating photovoltaic platform under regular wave conditions featuring different wave amplitudes and frequencies [3].

Figure 1: Moored Semi-Submersible Photovoltaic Floating Platform (FPV)

Figure 2: OpenFOAM Simulation of Moored FPV

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ASYNCHRONOUS MODIFIED CONJUGATE GRADIENT METHOD

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Keywords: HPC, One-sided communication, Conjugate gradient method, Asynchronous

Linear solvers are undoubtedly one of the key building blocks of numerical software. Their performance is a limiting factor in reducing time-to-solution and energy-to-solution of many applications. Current linear solver technology is often limited at scale by the communication cost. The ratio between the cost of reading two floats from memory and adding them is of several orders of magnitude. It is therefore paramount to reduce the need for communication as much as possible, even at the expense of extra computations. This work puts forward a concept for a novel asynchronous linear solver technology which requires neither global sums nor synchronised pairwise communication.

The algorithm developed operates asynchronously from start to finish, removing all synchronisation barriers. This approach enhances the efficiency of computer systems and supports the use of energy-efficient features available in next-generation hardware. This is a crucial step towards future exascale supercomputers’ cost-effective and environmentally friendly use. For instance, it will have a significant impact on computational fluid dynamics, a key field for advancing energy-efficient technologies and exploring new methods of energy production.

The key idea behind the asynchronous Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient algorithm (aPCG) is to use 1 Krylov-space per MPI rank so that each rank continues to work individually. This method is applied for a symmetric matrix structure and adopts the Polak/Ribiere/Polyak [1] search direction. The algorithm asynchronously calculates the global residual by monitoring boundary updates and comparing the local residual to its previous value. The global residual update happens only when significant changes occur towards termination.

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show the execution time line of a simplified classical PCG and aPCG algorithm. PCG uses a traditional MPI-based two-sided communication model. The key observation is the presence of idle periods (highlighted in red), which occur due to the synchronisation imposed by two-sided, non-blocking MPI communication (MPI_Isend and MPI_Irecv). These idle periods hinder performance as it takes more time to complete data exchanges. In contrast to the PCG, aPCG utilizes one-sided communication (MPI_Put and MPI_Get). The small black squares in the graph indicate operations where the MPI window is being filled, meaning data is placed in memory locations accessible to other processes. Using this approach, aPCG significantly reduces idle time, as communication happens in the background while computations continue. This results in a more continuous workflow with fewer delays. Additionally, since processes do not have to wait for message exchanges to complete before proceeding with computations, the algorithm achieves better load balancing and improved parallel scalability.

In this presentation, the performance of aPCG algorithm tested on the pressure solver for a DLR combustor [2] (variable density, transient, LES) (DLRCJH) with 3 and 24 million cells originating from the exaFoam project will be presented.

Figure 1: The schematic execution timeline of a simplified algorithm using two-sided MPI communication (PCG).

Figure 2: The schematic execution timeline of a simplified algorithm using one-sided MPI communication (aPCG).

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ON DEVELOPMENT OF FINITE VOLUME METHOD IMPLEMENTATION OF MINDLIN THICK PLATES IN SOLIDS4FOAM

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Keywords: Mindlin Plate Theory, solids4foam, Finite Volume Method

1 Introduction

`solids4foam` [1] is an open-source computational toolbox for solving solid mechanics and fluid-solid interaction simulations in OpenFOAM. Currently, a non-rotational Kirchhoff thin plate solver is available in the toolbox `solids4foam`, which can be applied to thin plates with aspect ratio $l/h > 10$ (l is the length and h is the thickness of the plate). Mindlin [2] derived the thick plate theory ($l/h > 5$) governing equations by including transverse shear angle deformation and rotational inertia to Kirchhoff plate theory. This work extends the library of `solids4foam` plates by adding the Mindlin thick plate theory. In recent years, the Mindlin governing equations have been implemented using the finite-volume (FV) approach, first by Demirdzić [3], later by Fallah [4], and more recently in Torlak's thesis [5]. Additionally, OpenFOAM also has the solver `acousticFoam` [6] to simulate the propagation of acoustic pressure waves. The integral form of the Mindlin plate (Fig. 1) equations is given by,

$$\int_l (Q_x n_x + Q_y n_y) dl + \int_{S_z} q dS = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\int_l [M_{xx} n_x + M_{xy} n_y - (x - x_P)(Q_x n_x + Q_y n_y)] dl - \int_{S_z} (x - x_P) q dS = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\int_l [M_{xy} n_x + M_{yy} n_y - (y - y_P)(Q_x n_x + Q_y n_y)] dl - \int_{S_z} (y - y_P) q dS = 0 \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Balance of forces and moments on a plate of thickness h

where, q is the external pressure acting on the plate. The shear forces acting on the plate are,

$$Q_x = Gh \left(\theta_x - \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right), Q_y = Gh \left(\theta_y - \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)$$

where, G is the torsional stiffness. The primary variables are the normal displacement w in z -direction and the rotations θ_x and θ_y about x and y . The moments M_{ij} is moment due to stress σ_{ij} acting on the plane with normal vector n_i . The bending moments are related to primary variables as,

$$M_{xx} = D \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial x} + \nu \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial y} \right), \quad M_{yy} = D \left(\nu \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial y} \right), \quad M_{xy} = \frac{D(1-\nu)}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial x} \right)$$

The bending stiffness $D = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\nu^2)}$ where E is Young's modulus, and ν is Poisson's ratio.

2 Preliminary Results

A test case of a squarePlate of 10 x 10 m with 1 m thickness with a distributed load of 1000 Pa is used for simulation. The material properties of steel with $E = 2 \times 10^{11}$ Pa and a Poisson's ratio of $\nu = 0.3$ are chosen. Figures 2 show the variation of displacement w in z - direction and the rotations θ_x and θ_y of a fully clamped plate. The preliminary results are verified against results from commercial software ABAQUS.

Figure 2: The variation of w , θ_x and θ_y across a fully clamped square plate

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MODELLING OF FOAM DRAINAGE AND FLOW IN STOKES REGIME

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Keywords: foam drainage, capillary pressure, slip velocity, drift flux

Foams are dispersions of gas bubbles in a liquid matrix, exhibiting complex flow and drainage behaviors depending on their liquid content. Wet foams, with gas volume fractions of 75% to 95%, exhibit unique behavior: bubbles are in direct contact due to high gas content, leading to strong capillary effects, whilst the relatively high liquid fraction allows for easy interphase slip and flow of the mixture as a whole. These foams behave as complex non-Newtonian fluids, where liquid drainage, surface tension, and viscous forces are of equal importance.

From the numerical point of view, the main challenge stems from the subtle balance between gravity, pressure, and capillary forces. Capturing these interactions requires a robust numerical framework capable of resolving both macroscopic transport and microscopic interfacial effects. In this study, we modify the **driftFluxFoam** solver to incorporate capillary pressure effects whilst ensuring numerical stability. The model is as follows.

Velocities of the phases can be represented via the slip and volumetric velocities as

$$\mathbf{u}_g = \mathbf{U} + \alpha_w \mathbf{u}_r, \quad \mathbf{u}_w = \mathbf{U} - \alpha_g \mathbf{u}_r. \quad (1)$$

The governing equations include momentum balance and incompressibility condition of the mixture

$$0 = -\nabla P - \alpha_w \nabla P_c + \nabla \cdot 2\mu_m \left(\nabla \mathbf{U} + (\nabla \mathbf{U})^t \right) + (\rho_m - \rho_0) \mathbf{g}, \quad \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0, \quad (2)$$

slip velocity [1]

$$\mathbf{u}_r = \frac{k}{\mu_w} \left((\rho_g - \rho_w) \mathbf{g} + \nabla P_c \right), \quad (3)$$

and the transport equation for water content:

$$\partial_t \alpha_w + \nabla \cdot \alpha_w \left(\mathbf{U} - \frac{\alpha_g k}{\mu_w} \nabla \underbrace{\left((\rho_g - \rho_w) \mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{x} + P_c \right)}_{\Phi} \right) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The closure relations for the model, namely, mixture viscosity μ_m [2], permeability k [3, 4] and capillary pressure P_c [5] are implemented as classes in **driftFluxFoam** solver. Hereafter we summarise the adopted models.

Viscosity of the foam was modelled using the Herschel–Bulkley model, adapted for foam rheology. The viscous and yield components are treated following the recommendations of [2]. Regularisation is applied in the Papanastasiou manner, using the capillary number—not the shear stress—as the regularisation parameter.

The permeability model [3, 4] is based on the measurements conducted for bubble assemblies with both mobile and nonmobile interfaces over a wide porosity range, revealing that surface mobility significantly affects flow behavior. For nonmobile interfaces, which is the focus of the present research, the Carman–Kozeny law effectively captures permeability trends. The model accurately describes experimental data without adjustable parameters, suggesting a strong analogy between foams and solid porous media.

The capillary pressure model presented in [5] covers a wide range of volume fractions, from very dry to wet foams. In the dry regime, most of the liquid is contained in the Plateau borders. Their curvature dominates the capillary pressure and can be obtained from geometric considerations. In wet foams, interactions between bubbles can be described in terms of an empirically determined, nonlinear potential.

Note that the slip velocity in Eq.(4) is proportional to $\nabla\Phi(\alpha_w)$. It is well known that, on a co-located grid, such a term requires Rhie–Chow dissipation to prevent the checkerboard effect. In the present work, we adopted a more “staggered” approach: instead of modelling the slip velocity $\frac{\alpha_w k}{\mu_w} \nabla\Phi$ directly, its normal component at the cell face

$$f_n = \frac{\alpha_w k}{\mu_w} \partial_n \Phi \quad (5)$$

was implemented in Eq.(4). The normal derivative ∂_n is obtained using the OpenFOAM function `snGrad()`.

Figure 1: 1D foam in a steady state: the red line is the analytical solution $P_c = (\rho_w - \rho_g)gz$.

It follows from Eq.(2) that, for the foam to be in equilibrium, capillary and gravity forces must counterbalance each other. Note that ∇P_c enters the momentum equation as a source term, while α_w —and, consequently, P_c —are updated via Eq.(4). To verify that the balance of fluxes in Eq.(4) ensures the corresponding balance of forces in Eq.(2), we modelled one-dimensional foam drainage in a 1.0m column. The results are shown in Fig.1. In such a tall column, both the water volume fraction and the capillary pressure vary by four orders of magnitude, yet the system remains numerically stable.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF CELL VOLUME RATIO ON THE DISCRETISATION OF THE PRESSURE EQUATION IN FINITE VOLUME CFD

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Keywords: *Mesh Generation, Mesh Quality, Finite Volume Method, Pressure Equation*

Introduction

This abstract analyses the influence of the cell volume ratio on the stability and accuracy of the CFD simulations using the Finite Volume Method (FVM). The goal of the study is to show the importance of the cell volume ratio on the stability and accuracy of the pressure equation. It is a topic discussed often, see [1, 2], and the goal of this work is to provide theoretical insight into the problems occurring when the cell-volume ratio largely deviates from unity.

Discussion

The pressure equation is derived from the continuity equation and the semi-discretised form of the momentum equation [3], to calculate the pressure field. The semi discretised form of the momentum equation can be written:

$$a_P \vec{U}_P = \sum_{nb} a_{nb} \vec{U}_{nb} - \nabla p V_P \quad (1)$$

by inserting the velocity from the equation above into the continuity equation:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{U} = 0, \quad (2)$$

a pressure equation is obtained:

$$\nabla \cdot \frac{V_P}{a_P} \nabla p = \nabla \cdot \frac{\sum_{nb} a_{nb} \vec{U}_{nb}}{a_P}. \quad (3)$$

The equation 3 shows that the coefficient in front the pressure gradient term is dependent on the size of the cell. The cell volume ratio at a face is defined as:

$$V_r = \frac{V_N}{V_P} \quad (4)$$

where V_N and V_P are magnitudes of volumes of the neighbour cells adjacent to a face as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Two control volumes sharing a common face

By applying the FVM discretisation in the spirit of Rhie-Chow procedure [4], the discretised form of the pressure equation can be written:

$$\sum_f \left((1 - f_x) \frac{V_N}{a_N} + f_x \frac{V_P}{a_P} \right) (\nabla p \cdot S)_f = \sum_f \left((1 - f_x) \frac{(\sum_{nb} a_{nb} \vec{U}_{nb})_N}{a_N} + f_x \frac{(\sum_{nb} a_{nb} \vec{U}_{nb})_P}{a_P} \right) \cdot \vec{S}_f, \quad (5)$$

where f_x is the interpolation factor dependent of the chosen interpolation practice. By substituting V_N in Equation 5 with $V_N = V_r V_P$, according to Equation 4, results in a form:

$$\sum_f (V_P((1 - f_x)\frac{V_r}{a_N} + f_x\frac{1}{a_P}))(\nabla p \cdot S)_f = \sum_f ((1 - f_x)\frac{(\sum_{nb} a_{nb}\vec{U}_{nb})_N}{a_N} + f_x\frac{(\sum_{nb} a_{nb}\vec{U}_{nb})_P}{a_P}) \cdot \vec{S}_f. \quad (6)$$

[5] presents an analysis of the discretisation errors occurring in the discretisation procedure, depending of the interpolation practice of the $\frac{V_P}{a_P}$ term and the approximation of the surface-normal gradient $(\nabla p \cdot S)_f$ at a face. The error also depends on the cell type [6] indicated by the sum of faces. Equation 6 shows the influence of cell-volume ratio on the discretisation practice and, therefore, some interesting conclusions can be drawn:

- If V_r at a face tends to zero, occurring when the current cell is much larger than the neighbour cell, the interpolation results in $f_x\frac{V_P}{a_P}$. Please note that the linear interpolation factor f_x is closely linked to the cell-volume ratio and it also tends to be small in this case, making the coefficient coupling the cells attached to the face negligible when comparing to other faces. This results in cells being decoupled from each other. Hence, the small neighbour does not influence the results in the larger cell.
- When V_r at a face tends to infinity, occurring when the neighbour cell is much larger than the current cell, the interpolation tends to $V_P(1 - f_x)\frac{\infty}{a_N}$. This is not desirable because the coefficient at this face may become much larger than the coefficients at other faces of a cell, thus the pressure in the current cell is dominated by the large cell, and other neighbours have a little influence on the current cell.
- V_r largely differing from unity makes the interpolation error at a face larger and has a negative impact on the interpolation accuracy.
- The influence of the problems above is more pronounced for cell types with small number of faces. Convergence problems most often occur when a small tetrahedron is found next to a large polyhedron with many faces.

Conclusions and future work

This abstract presents the influence of cell-volume ratio on the stability and accuracy of the discretised pressure equation occurring in most fluid-flow simulations. It is shown that the cell-volume ratio largely differing from unity has detrimental effect on the stability and accuracy of the solution. Unlike other mesh quality problems, such as skewness, non-orthogonality, etc. the cell-volume ratio cannot be rectified by altering the discretisation practice, and it has to be kept under control while generating the mesh.

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Tuning OpenFOAM’s GAMG settings using Bayesian optimization

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Keywords: *GAMG, Bayesian optimization, SmartSim, Ax*

In computational fluid dynamics (CFD), multigrid methods are frequently employed to accelerate the solution of the discretized pressure Poisson equation. The performance of such multigrid solvers depends on a variety of hyperparameters, which are usually chosen based on experience or numerical experiments. A suboptimal choice of these hyperparameters mitigates the performance benefits or even affects the simulation’s stability. Choosing optimal settings is far from trivial and mainly depends on the coefficient matrix, parallelization, and hardware. Since the coefficient matrix resulting from the discretized pressure Poisson equation varies throughout a simulation and between different simulation setups, the optimal multigrid settings are likely to change as well.

The *Geometric-Algebraic Multi-Grid* solver (GAMG) [1] available in *OpenFOAM* provides more than 15 tunable parameters. These parameters can be categorical, natural numbers, or floating point numbers, e.g., the type of smoother, the number of sweeps, or the stopping tolerance, respectively. Due to the simulation’s computational cost, conventional search techniques such as random or grid search become infeasible when considering multiple parameters in combination. Bayesian optimization (BO) [2] offers a more effective navigation of the search space that relies on i) a few random initial sample evaluations of the objective function, ii) a probabilistic surrogate model of the objective function, and iii) a search policy that suggests new parameter combinations based on the surrogate model. The surrogate model is then updated iteratively based on the new sample points and queried for the next parameter sets to evaluate.

Our contribution shows the benefits of employing BO to tune the GAMG setting for optimal performance without sacrificing accuracy or stability. The objective function is based on the elapsed time for computing a small number of representative time steps, which can be extracted from the solver’s log output or the *timeInfo* function object. Residual control for the pressure-velocity-coupling with a low, fixed tolerance and a check for successful completion of the selected time steps minimize the impact of the changed settings on accuracy and stability. A user-defined configuration file specifies the search space, possible default settings to start from, HPC resource management, and BO parameters (e.g., the number of trials and the acquisition function). We employ the *Ax* library [3, 4] for BO and the *SmartSim* infrastructure library [5, 6] for batch execution of parametrized OpenFOAM simulations on HPC resources. Thanks to these powerful libraries, a small driver script is sufficient to apply the workflow to generic OpenFOAM simulations. The complete workflow is available on GitHub [7].

For extensive initial testing, we conducted numerical experiments on the two-dimensional laminar flow past a cylinder [8] modifying a subset of the available settings (*nPostSweeps*, *nPreSweeps*, *smoother*, *nFinestSweeps*, and *interpolateCorrection*). The course of the transient simulation may be categorized into three distinct stages. Starting from a potential flow solution, boundary layers develop in the first couple of time steps due to viscosity. High initial residuals and iteration counts characterize this stage, the most critical stage regarding stability. In the second stage, the flow remains nearly steady and symmetric for some time before periodic vortex shedding starts in the third stage. These stages are also reflected in the elapsed time per time step, which suggests that multigrid settings may be optimized for each stage rather than the entire simulation or every single time step. Indeed, our initial tests show that the optimal multigrid settings remain relatively constant throughout the characteristic stages when employing BO to different time step sequences within each stage.

Figure 1 presents the BO trials and a slice through the approximated objective function landscape. The mean suggests that no pre-sweeps and 3-5 post-sweeps should be performed for the investigated case. In contrast to a simple grid search, the surrogate model provides additional information on the sensitivity of an optimum with respect to the parameters. For example, the marginalized standard deviation in figure 1 shows that the optimal number of sweeps varies very little across the remaining search space dimensions (the other investigated settings).

In the full workshop contribution, we will present additional results for test cases with more complex physical modeling and the impact on parallel scalability. In addition to the obvious benefits of reduced computational cost and runtime, we hope our framework can inform future multigrid solver developments.

Figure 1: Marginalized mean (left) and standard deviation (right) of the Gaussian process model for the elapsed runtime. The yellow markers indicate the BO trials. The search space included $nPostSweeps$, $nPreSweeps$, $smoother$, $nFinestSweeps$, and $interpolateCorrection$. Light and dark colors indicate low and high execution times, respectively.

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A FRAMEWORK FOR INITIAL TRANSIENT DETECTION AS STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF CONVERGENCE IN CFD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *time series, confidence intervals, autocorrelated data, initial transient detection, fractional filtering, reversal mean standard error*

In the context of CFD, the simulations are often run longer than necessary to ensure statistical reliability, incurring significant computational costs; e.g., DES calculations can exceed 20 hours per case, with each additional hour consuming substantial energy end resources. To address this, we propose a method to terminate simulations exactly when sufficient data have been acquired, balancing accuracy with cost efficiency. By quantifying the convergence, monitoring various quantities of interest, and computing their statistical moments (e.g., mean and standard deviation), within a defined tolerance and confidence level, our approach avoids premature termination (yielding unreliable results) and excessive runtime (wasting computational cost).

CFD data often contain an initial transient phase before settling into physically meaningful oscillations. This must be identified and excluded from the computation of statistical moments. In order to detect this transient, a novel method is proposed that uses the reversal mean standard error (RMSE) as a metric to assess data stability, enhanced by a fractional filtering technique to reduce noise and highlight dynamical features. Local minima in RMSE identify candidate endpoints for the transient period, refined via interquartile range (IQR) filtering to remove statistical outliers. The remaining values are averaged to estimate the end of the transient region.

Furthermore, due to equation relaxation in steady-state solvers or the presence of time derivatives in unsteady solvers, the data typically exhibit strong autocorrelation. It leads to an underestimation of the standard deviation. To address this, an effective sample size correction combined with an autoregressive (AR) model is used to compute the true standard deviation.

The effectiveness of the proposed approach is demonstrated through extensive experiments on both synthetic and real-world time series datasets. The results show that the method accurately identifies the end of the initial transient and provides meaningful insights into the dynamics of the data. The resulting confidence intervals serve as a reliable measure of convergence that directly reduces computational costs in CFD simulations.

Figure 1: DDES simulation of the DrivAer car geometry

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Fluids and solids

Integration of an Explicit Godunov-Type Riemann Solver for Solid Dynamics in Solids4foam

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Keywords: *Riemann Solver, Fluid-Solid Interaction (FSI), solids4foam, Dual-Time Stepping*

The most effective numerical methods for solving hyperbolic conservation laws rely on Riemann solvers, which have been widely used for solving fluid dynamics problems due to their accuracy and computational efficiency [1]. This work presents the integration of an explicit Godunov-type Riemann solver for solid dynamics into the solids4foam toolbox [2]. By employing a first-order momentum-deformation-based formulation, this approach enhances computational efficiency and accuracy, addressing limitations associated with conventional solvers.

The first-order momentum-deformation-based formulation offers several advantages over traditional displacement-based approaches [3]. This formulation aligns with well-established computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solvers, facilitating the application of advanced numerical techniques such as Riemann solvers (e.g., Roe, HLLC) for flux evaluation and acceleration techniques like multi-grid methods. By leveraging these tools, solid dynamics simulations can achieve greater numerical stability and accuracy.

Adopting this hyperbolic conservation formulation reduces the conceptual and computational gap between fluid and solid frameworks, allowing for a unified computational approach. It eliminates inconsistencies arising from using separate numerical treatments of fluid and solid domains and allows for a consistent discretization strategy across both.

The explicit solver is derived from explicitSolidDynamics toolkit [4] and implemented as a new solid model subclass within solids4foam, named `explicitGodunvCC` [5]. To address the restrictive time-step limitations typically associated with explicit schemes, the new model incorporates a dual-time stepping approach. Additionally, it introduces a numerical flux model, offering flexibility in selecting different flux evaluation schemes.

The proposed framework is validated for fluid-solid interaction cases using a fluid-driven perpendicular flap benchmark problem [6, 7]. The validation results demonstrate the solver’s capability to accurately capture the dynamic response of solid materials. Figure 1 represents the benchmark geometry where the fluid flows through a two-dimensional rectangular channel with a solid, elastic flap fixed at the center of the channel’s bottom wall. At the left boundary, a constant inflow velocity of 10 m/s is prescribed in the x -direction. At the right boundary, an outflow condition is applied. The top and bottom boundaries and the surface of the flap are no-slip boundaries.

Figure 1: Perpendicular flap geometry

Figure 2: Perpendicular flap geometry

The flap oscillates due to the fluid pressure exerted on its surface. Figure 2 compares the time history of the flap top displacement between different frameworks. The reference solutions are extracted from the preCICE repository [7], where preCICE has been used to couple OpenFOAM incompressible flow solver `pimpleFoam` [8] with two Finite Elements solvers, deal.II [9] and Calculix [10]. Additionally, the solution from the displacement-based solids4foam solid model `linearGeometryTotalDisplacement` is also included in the same figure.

By introducing this new formulation, solids4foam is extended with a flexible solid dynamics modeling. This contribution enhances the OpenFOAM community’s capabilities in coupled fluid-solid simulations and opens the way for further research into high-fidelity FSI modeling using explicit hyperbolic formulations.

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A unified framework for coupled fluid-mooring modelling in OpenFOAM

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Keywords: Fluid-solid interaction, mooring line, Simo-Reissner beam theory

This paper introduces a unified framework for coupled fluid–mooring modelling. It builds on the earlier study of Taran et al. [1], which coupled a geometrically exact beam solver with OpenFOAM’s `sixDoFRigidBodyMotion` library and a multiphase flow solver to capture the hydrodynamics of a moored rigid floating platform. The new framework extends that coupling by capturing the effect of mooring-line dynamics on the surrounding fluid and the fluid’s effect on the lines. The mooring lines are represented with a finite-volume discretisation of the Simo–Reissner beam theory [4, 5], capturing bending, axial, and torsional responses within the same framework. By resolving the mutual interaction between a rigid floating body and its mooring lines, it provides a viable alternative to conventional lumped-mass spring models [2] and finite-element approaches [3]. Whereas most CFD mooring couplings merely swap platform positions and anchor-line forces at fairlead nodes, leaving the line itself invisible to the flow, the present work couples the beam and flow fields bidirectionally, sampling fluid loads on the line directly from the local velocity and pressure fields. Accounting for this active flow improves the prediction of drag and added-mass forces in both structural and fluid solvers. The entire formulation is embedded within a consistent finite-volume framework and implemented in the OpenFOAM environment, making it especially suited to the simulation of severe sea states, where the still-water assumption is untenable. To validate the coupled model, a test case involving wave-induced motion and force distribution along a flexible vertical stem is considered (see Figure 1). This setup captures key fluid–structure interaction mechanisms relevant to marine vegetation, mooring systems, and slender offshore elements. It provides a controlled environment for assessing the accuracy and robustness of the fluid–structure coupling.

Figure 1 - Instantaneous velocity streamlines coloured by velocity magnitude, illustrating wave-induced flow around a flexible vertical stem in a confined channel.

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THE HIGHER-ORDER FINITE VOLUME METHOD FOR SOLID MECHANICS IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *high-order discretisation, computational solid mechanics, HoPyFOAM, solids4foam*

Introduction

The development of finite-volume solid mechanics has relied on second-order discretisation, with the majority of solvers adopting semi-implicit segregated solution procedures similar to those used in fluid dynamics [1, 2]. These solvers have proven their robustness and efficiency; however, multiphysics applications, such as electro-mechanical coupling, might benefit from solvers capable of exceeding second-order accuracy. Demirdžić’s research [3] on fourth-order finite volume discretisation highlighted its potential to eliminate shear locking, but the discretisation was not easily generalised to unstructured grids and the segregated solution procedure was shown to be inefficient. Demirdžić suggested that a least squares procedure might provide a more practical approach for implementing high-order discretization. Building on this, Castrilo [4] utilised concepts from high-order (> 2) fluid solvers [5] to develop implicit high-order structural solvers based on a cell-centred grid arrangement. Both authors used in-house codes (which are not publicly available), which has led to a lack of comparative studies on the efficiency and accuracy of high-order discretisations versus second-order ones. This research seeks to fill this gap by implementing a cell-centred high-order discretisation within the OpenFOAM framework and an open Python framework, and evaluating its performance against a second-order discretisation. Given the challenges of larger computational stencils, denser matrices, and greater memory requirements associated with high-order discretisation, this study aims to assess its viability and effectiveness for solid mechanics applications.

Numerical Methodology

For brevity, the high-order discretisation procedure is demonstrated by discretising the diffusion term for scalar quantity ϕ . The surface integral is approximated by the sum of the values of the integrand function on the cell faces, and the integrand function is calculated using Gaussian integration:

$$\int_V \nabla \cdot [\Gamma \nabla \phi] dV = \oint_S \Gamma \nabla \phi \cdot \mathbf{n} dS \approx \sum_{f=1}^{f=N_f} \left[\sum_{g=1}^{g=N_g} \alpha_g [\Gamma_{f,g} \nabla \phi(\mathbf{x})_{f,g} \mathbf{n}_f] \right] S_f = 0, \quad (1)$$

where N_f represents the number of faces f of the control volume, N_g the number of quadrature points, α_g is the quadrature weight of the integration point g , Γ is the diffusion coefficient, and \mathbf{n}_f is the unit normal vector of face f . The value of the gradient of the dependent variable at the Gaussian integration point is determined by the values from the centres of the neighbouring cells:

$$\nabla \phi(\mathbf{x})_{f,g} = \left[\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} \right]_{f,g} = \left[\sum_{n=1}^{n=N_n} c_{x,n}(\mathbf{x})_{f,g} \phi_n, \sum_{n=1}^{n=N_n} c_{y,n}(\mathbf{x})_{f,g} \phi_n, \sum_{n=1}^{n=N_n} c_{z,n}(\mathbf{x})_{f,g} \phi_n \right], \quad (2)$$

where N_n represents the total number of cells in the computational molecule and ϕ_n is value of dependent variable at neighbouring cell centre. $c_{x,n}$, $c_{y,n}$, and $c_{z,n}$ are interpolation coefficients vectors located at Gauss points $(\mathbf{x})_{f,g}$. Interpolation coefficients are calculated using the method of local regression, by minimising the weighted sum of squares:

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{n=N_n} w(\mathbf{x}_n - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) [\bar{\phi}(\mathbf{x}_n) - \phi_n]^2 \quad (3)$$

where w is radially symmetric exponential weight function and $\bar{\phi}$ is the truncated Taylor expansion of the interpolation function, expanded around point $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$. The number of terms in the Taylor expansion determines the desired order of accuracy of the method. More details on calculating the interpolation coefficients can be found in [4].

Example Case

To test the numerical procedure, prototyping and initial testing have been carried out using a Python package named HoPyFOAM (High-Order Python FOAM). This package, inspired by the coding style and structure of the OpenFOAM library, is built on the `numpy` and `petsc4py` libraries. HoPyFOAM is available for download at www.github.com/iBatistic/HoPyFoam. Efforts are currently underway to integrate this implementation into the `solids4foam` library. This integration will enable both coupled solvers and solvers that rely on the Jacobian-free Newton–Krylov method [6].

Figure 1 illustrates the results for a 2-D case of a Hookean (linear elastic) solid with zero displacement imposed at the boundary and a variable body force within the interior. The body force is calculated using the method of manufactured solutions to achieve the targeted displacement field. From Figure 1, one can observe that 4th and 2nd order convergence is achieved when using cubic and linear distributions of the variable, respectively, while parabolic distribution of the variable tends to produce 2nd order convergence, which is consistent with observation from literature [4].

Figure 1: Two-dimensional manufactured solution case: displacement field on the finest mesh (left) and displacement magnitude discretisation errors (right).

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General CFD, HPC, GPU

BENCHMARKS IN THE TENDERING PROCESS FOR HPC CLUSTERS

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The Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute (BAW) is performing consultancy work for the German Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure and the executing bodies of the ministry. For this purpose, high-performance computing (HPC) systems have been used for several decades, starting in the 1990s with Cray multi-processor systems and have continually advanced since that time. As a public entity, the BAW must comply with strict rules in the tendering process. The following provides an overview on the benchmarks used in the past tendering processes and the lessons learned from it. Particular emphasis is placed on the role of OpenFOAM[®] in this process. The BAW uses HPC resources mainly for computational fluid dynamics simulations of various kinds. These range from large-scale geophysical models that cover the North Sea with the estuaries of northern Germany to small-scales such as gap flows measuring just a few centimetres. As a consequence, different numerical codes are used on the same computer systems. In the following, only the small-scale CFD models will be regarded.

In the BAW, several CFD codes with a connection to the work of Professor Gosman’s group at Imperial College London have played and continue to play an important role. This started with “Comet” in 1999, developed by Professor Peric, which was later superseded by StarCCM+ in 2005. After a short intermezzo with the university code NaSt3DGPF, which is based on cartesian grids, the first trials with OpenFOAM[®] began in 2009. OpenFOAM[®] was slowly introduced into the production work in the following years, after substantial effort was put into making it suitable for waterway consultancy. A major effort was the implementation of a suitable set of boundary conditions for hydraulic structures engineering. These were recently published [1] and are now available to the OpenFOAM[®] community.

The available computing resources at BAW (Karlsruhe) have continuously increased over the past three decades, doubling the number of CPU cores roughly every 2.5 years (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Installed HPC CPU cores in BAW (Karlsruhe branch)

This evolution has been accompanied by architectural changes: starting with vector processors in 1995, evolving into large shared memory machines, and, since 2007, into distributed memory cluster systems. As hardware advanced, application software progressed in parallel. Consequently, the software used for benchmarking in the tender process had to be adapted. Over the years, a mix between synthetic benchmarks and application benchmarks has always been used. As a long-standing standard LINPACK [2] was used. While not matching the application's performance, the LINPACK performance has the significant advantage to deliver consistent and comparable results over decades. Later file system tests and more recently HPCG were introduced into the benchmark suite. On the application side, OpenFOAM[®] was introduced into the mix in 2010 - at first only as a compatibility test, but since 2012 also as a benchmarking test for the

tendering process. The usage of OpenFOAM® in the benchmarks has revealed some difficulties in the last decade. The benchmarking is based on the interFoam solver, as this is the primary solver used at BAW. Due to required changes of the versions used - triggered by the close link between the OpenFOAM® version and the version of the compiler toolchain - results are barely comparable. We started with interFoam in version 1.6.1, which used a “p” formulation, changed than to 2.3.1, which used a “p_rgh” formulation, and later versions saw further changes in the algorithm. Thus, the benchmark results lost their direct comparability.

In the benchmarks for OpenFOAM®, the tendering vendors were always requested to perform tests on both the throughput as well as scalability of the jobs. Additionally, BAW performs extended in-house tests after the commissioning of the systems. These tests are not targeted on finding the peak performance, but at identifying the highest throughput. To this end, parallel efficiency is used as a measure. Over the last 15 years, we have observed a significant drop in the number of cells per MPI partition that results in the optimal efficiency. Starting with approximately 200,000 cells/partition in 2010, we now see the optimum at around 20,000 cells/partition (depending on the topology of the problem). It is notable that the scaling performance depends significantly on the preconditioner used (AMG, DIC) and on the linear solver (PBiCGStab, AMG). Our tests have shown that the apparent scaling (in terms of speedup) is better for the DIC-preconditioned PBiCGStab, resulting in the highest peak performance. However, the performance of the AMG-preconditioned PBiCGStab is only slightly worse at high core counts, while it performs better at lower core counts. Thus, AMG is the preconditioner of choice at BAW.

Apart from the CPU performance, the input/output (I/O) performance is also relevant for simulations. Here, we observe several trends. Firstly, ever-growing simulation sizes. Secondly, a shift from RANS-based simulations, which require little output, to DES or LES-based simulations, which require the output of much more data. Together with the increasing computing power available and the uncollated writing format, this results in a spectacular increase in the number of files written in a typical simulation. Unfortunately, the performance of the used file systems has not increased in the same way as CPU performance. We observed an increase in LINPACK performance by a factor of 100 over the last 15 years. For the same machines, I/O throughput has increased by a factor of only around 3-4 - significantly less. Even worse is the situation for OpenFOAM®: Here we additionally observe an increase in the number of written files, as the optimal number of cells per MPI partition is decreasing, as mentioned above. Thus, even for the same jobs, the number of written files has increased by a factor of 10 in the last 15 years. This increase must then be multiplied with the increase in the computing performance (which is not precisely known for OpenFOAM®, but is approximately 100 for LINPACK) and set in relation to the increase in the metadata performance of the file system. For the latter, we observed an increase by a factor of approximately 3 - several orders of magnitude lower than the increase in output generated by the CFD simulations. This effectively makes the file system metadata throughput a significant bottleneck for the use of OpenFOAM®.

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BEST MESHING PRACTICES FOR HIGH-QUALITY CFD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: *Meshing, geometry preparation, automatic refinement, boundary layers, mesh quality*

The generation of high-quality computational meshes remains a fundamental prerequisite for achieving accurate CFD simulations. Deficiencies in geometry preparation, inadequate refinement strategies, and poorly constructed boundary layers frequently introduce significant uncertainties. Consequently, the adoption of systematic meshing practices is essential for establishing robust and reliable CFD workflows.

This work addresses the critical stages of mesh generation, beginning with geometry preparation. A thorough methodology is outlined, encompassing surface cleanup, removal of non-essential geometrical features, smoothing of sharp edges, and elimination of unnecessary feature edges that do not contribute to the flow. Although meshing ideally starts from well-prepared CAD models, in practice, CFD engineers frequently work with imperfect triangulated geometries that require additional processing to ensure meshability and quality.

To achieve an optimal balance between computational cost and mesh fidelity, refinement regions are carefully defined using a combination of manual and automatic refinement algorithms. The study details automatic refinement strategies based on curvature, proximity, distinct features, ray casting, and edge length criteria, each selected according to the local geometrical complexity. Workflow controls are utilized to pause the meshing process after template generation, providing an opportunity to verify refinement adequacy and ensuring that small but critical features are accurately captured. This strategy enables the retention of flow-relevant details without unnecessary increase in mesh size or generation time.

Special emphasis is placed on the setup of boundary layers, given their critical role in resolving near-wall gradients and accurately predicting wall shear stresses [3]. Well-resolved boundary layers enhance overall accuracy, whereas poorly constructed layers can introduce numerical instabilities and degrade solution quality. Techniques for configuring inner and outer layers are discussed, with a focus on maintaining smoothness near complex surfaces.

Finally, mesh quality is assessed through key metrics such as volume ratio, non-orthogonality, and skewness, which are especially important in regions where the solution exhibits strong gradients [2]. An overview of mesh cell types is provided, discussing the advantages and limitations of polyhedral, tetrahedral, and hexahedral-dominant meshes [1]. Understanding the interplay between cell topology, mesh quality, and physical modeling is essential for achieving reliable, efficient, and accurate CFD simulations.

By following best practices in geometry preparation, refinement strategies, boundary layer construction, and mesh quality assessment, it is possible to generate computational meshes that significantly enhance the reliability and accuracy of CFD simulations. A systematic and informed approach to meshing not only improves robustness but also ensures that simulations accurately represent the underlying physical phenomena.

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EXPRESSION TEMPLATES IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: C++, expression templates, GPU

This abstract describes implementing expression templates in OpenFOAM. OpenFOAM is implemented to allow finite-volume modelling using an expression-like syntax. This comes with an overhead in terms of memory management. Especially in modern computer architectures there is a large mismatch between the processing speed of the computation unit and the memory access speed, especially with regards to latency. This can be mitigated by increasing the memory speed through e.g. fast-memory caching or by making the bottom level implementation more memory-access aware. In this work we demonstrate a near-transparent implementation of the latter using modern C++.

EXPRESSION TEMPLATES

In expression templates any expression becomes an instantiation of a templated class. Each class implements the indexing operator ‘[]’. Only when ‘evaluating’ the expression is this actual ‘[]’ operator used. Consider a typical OpenFOAM expression

```
scalarField A = B * C - D;
```

This will allocate a temporary for the result of multiplying B and C, subtract D from it and assign the contents to A. Using expression templating instead a class hierarchy is built up mirroring the expression:

```
class subtract<multiply<scalar, scalar>, scalar>
```

where its indexing operator ‘[]’ does the actual work: $b[i]*c[i]-d[i]$. In this implementation of expression templates the main OpenFOAM containers have been extended with a function to ‘wrap’ the contents in an expression form. Above expression can hence be written as

```
scalarField A = B.expr() * C.expr() - D.expr();
```

This same syntax can also be used for GeometricFields (field plus boundary conditions) and the most often used containers. There are two categories: can they be wrapped into expressions and can they be assigned to using an expression (as in above expression)

Table 1: Container expression template support

Class	Expression	Assignment
List	.expr()	yes
Field	.expr()	yes
GeometricField (e.g. volScalarField, surfaceVectorField)	.expr()	yes
tmp<Field>	.expr()	no
tmp<GeometricField>	.expr()	no
DimensionedType (for constant Field)	.expr(<size>)	no
DimensionedType (for constant GeometricField)	.expr(<GeoField>)	no
fvMatrix	.expr()	yes

Above framework supports most field functions (e.g. min, sqrt). The exception is the fvMatrix expression class which only supports linear operations.

TYPICAL APPLICATION

A typical use of above expression template would be in complex modelling. As a test the kOmegaSST turbulence model has been fitted with above expressions. As an example one of the base functions ‘F1’ becomes a templated function

```
auto arg1 = min
```

```

(
  min
  (
    max
    (
      (one/betaStar)*sqrt(k_.expr()/(omega_.expr()*y_.expr())),
      fiveHundred
      *(this->mu().expr()/this->rho_.expr())
      /(sqr(y_.expr()*omega_.expr()))
    ),
    fourAlpha0mega2*k_.expr()/(CDk0megaPlus*sqr(y_.expr()))
  ),
  ten
);
return tanh(pow4(arg1));

```

where all the constants (one, betaStar etc) are pre-declared as a DimensionedField(..).expr().

FUTURE WORK

There are still some missing operations - e.g. ones that change the return type. The expression template framework has been extended to use parallel execution through the C++17 'execution policy' construct. This requires changing a single loop only (in the expression template evaluation for the basic 'List' container) since all the work is done through the indexing operator[] and iterators. This will benefit vectorisation and/or GPU offloading. The other ongoing effort is to move the expression templates further up into the code into the actual discretisation:

Table 2: Discretisation support

Function	Returns
Interpolation	expression template
uncorrected Gauss Laplacian	fvMatrix

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TOWARDS A COMPETITIVE OPEN-SOURCE GPU SOLVER FOR OPENFOAM

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Keywords: GPU computing, High-Performance Computing, OpenFOAM Benchmarking, EXASIM.

Over the past decade, progress in High-Performance Computing (HPC) has shifted the state-of-the-art in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) decisively towards GPU-accelerated solvers. Commercial GPU-enabled codes already deliver game-changing performance improvements in simulation time, cost, and energy efficiency [1]. To safeguard the immense strategic value of OpenFOAM as an industrially applicable open-source solution, it must match or exceed the capabilities of commercial software. A high-performance GPU derivative of OpenFOAM is therefore urgently required.

The EXASIM project systematically evaluated the performance of OpenFOAM against modern GPU solvers using clearly defined key performance indicators (KPIs) such as the equivalent number of CPU cores giving the same performance as one GPU (“cores per GPU”, CpG), time-to-solution factor (TTSF) and cost-to-solution factor (CTSF). An automated HPC benchmark suite, based on the OpenFOAM Benchmark Runner (OBR), a derivative of the signac framework, was developed to support reproducible, scalable performance tests across diverse hardware platforms. This suite draws on recent best-practice work in benchmarking and software testing strategies, as outlined by Gärtner et al. [2]. Figure 1 shows an excerpt of the analysis of one of the microbenchmarks, where the time spend in different parts of the solution process was investigated. It becomes clear that offloading only the pressure solver to the GPU as done in hybrid approaches like OGL (described in the following) is not sufficient, as for this type of simulation most of the time is spent in the velocity matrix assembly.

a) Visualisation of Windsor Body microbenchmark in weak-scaling study mode

b) Share of wall-clock time per timestep used by different stages of the linear solution process, comparing OpenFOAM running on CPU only and with the pressure equation solved on GPU using OGL. MA: matrix assembly, U: velocity, P: pressure, OH: overhead (additional solver steps e.g. turbulence equations)

Figure 1: Excerpt of performance analysis for the Windsor Body, which should be representative for automotive external aerodynamics simulations.

Several initiatives to develop GPU-ready OpenFOAM derivatives were reviewed:

- OGL (OpenFOAM-Ginkgo-Layer): a hybrid approach offloading linear solvers to GPUs, developed within EXASIM [3][4]
- OpenFOAM-UM (and its predecessor prototype zeptoFOAM): simulations run entirely on GPU via a minimal-invasive porting approach, emphasizing quick feature extension and portability [5]
- NeoN: a new, generally applicable CFD backend, designed from the ground up for GPU-first architectures and full C++20 compliance [6], linked to OpenFOAM via an interface called FoamAdapter

Benchmarking data for Delayed Detached-Eddy Simulations (DDES) of automotive aerodynamics are summarised in Table 1 (missing data will be assessed in time for the workshop). A clear benefit of executing the entire simulation on GPU (zeptoFOAM) vs. offloading only the linear solver to GPU (OGL) is seen, as expected. Initial data published for OpenFOAM-UM [5] states a CpG value of around 220, indicating an appreciable performance improvement over zeptoFOAM. However, analysis of performance reported for a comparable commercial solver suggests there is much

more potential (approx. 3x), which is currently untapped by OpenFOAM implementations. To achieve this, it is believed that the core numerical methods must be structured from the ground up to fully exploit GPU architectures. This is the objective of the NeoN initiative, which targets the game-changing levels of performance demonstrated by the commercial reference code. As such, each OpenFOAM initiative represents a different balance between risk and reward: from the practical benefits of minimal-invasive porting to the performance targeted by revolutionary redesign.

Table 1: Key performance indicators for different GPU solver approaches using NVIDIA A100 GPUs for automotive aerodynamics DDES. Higher numbers are better for all KPIs.

Solver	CpG CPU cores required to give the same performance as 1 GPU	TTSF Time-to-solution reduction factor	CTSF Cost-to-solution reduction factor
OGL	15.9-19.5	0.15-1.03	0.42-0.51
zeptoFOAM	105-140	0.55-1.13	1.22-1.64
OpenFOAM-UM	to be evaluated	to be evaluated	to be evaluated
NeoN	to be evaluated	to be evaluated	to be evaluated
Commercial ref.	680	18	6.3

This contribution will summarize the EXASIM findings, highlight the OBR benchmark framework's capabilities, and compare the different GPU initiatives currently shaping the future of OpenFOAM.

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USING EXPRESSION TEMPLATES FOR MEMORY LOCALITY

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Keywords: Performance, Memory Locality, Expression Templates, Bandwidth

In this work we present further development of the expression templates technique for memory locality optimization in OpenFOAM-based CFD codes.

This work consists of two parts, a general purpose expression templates library ET and its adaptation for OpenFOAM called FVE.

ET library follows general design of the Boost.YAP expression templates library. The idea is to split working with expression templates into separate phases of expression construction, transformation, and evaluation. An expression is a simple struct that does not know anything about how it is about to be used.

```
template <typename Op, typename... Args>
struct expr;
```

Here, Op is an operation (a function object to be applied to the arguments), and Args... are arguments, which can be expressions themselves or terminals (leaf nodes, values or references to values, such as scalars or fields). Therefore all kinds of expressions are instantiations of the same template with different template arguments. This is in contrast with alternative designs where each operator has its own type. The advantage is that there is much less duplication of code, and much easier to handle all kinds of operators in uniform way.

For example, expression

```
auto e1 = et::make_terminal(3) + 5;
```

has type

```
expr<std::plus<>, int, int>
```

Note that at this point the expression is purely syntactic, similar to an AST (abstract syntax tree) used in compilers. Currently, ET library supports all C++ operators (+, -, *, /, %, unary -, &&, ||, !, &, |^, , ==, !=, <, <=, >, >=) plus identity function and select (analog of ?: operator in C++).

Once an expression is constructed, we can manipulate it in various ways. For this, ET library provides utility functions

```
et::transform_matching(expr, transform)
```

that call a function object transform on the nodes of the graph that match the signature of the transform. The transform would typically return a transformed copy of the expression. (Expressions themselves are expected to be lightweight and passed by value). Another utility function

```
et::transform_terminal(expr, transform)
```

applies a transform to all terminals.

Note that matching and manipulating trees of expression is similar to how compilers (such as GCC or Clang) operate. This is also similar to how the AI frameworks (such as TensorFlow, Torch, etc.) operate.

Finally, we can evaluate an expression using evaluate(expr) function, that just applies each node's operation Op to its arguments.

Additional utilities provided by ET include pretty-printing expressions, drawing them as graphs in graphviz format, using std::placeholders, and computing derivatives.

FVE uses facilities provided by ET to manipulate expressions found in OpenFOAM-based codes. First, it defines a number of new expression operations, associated with OpenFOAM's elementwise functions and with fvc:: functions. It also associates a location (either cells or faces) with every expression. Additionally, it allows getting

Figure 1: Graph of the viscous flux expression before and after interpolation lowering transform. Background shading indicates subexpressions with different locations.

dimensions of an expression and its mesh. All this does not require any changes to the expr struct due to ET’s design.

Next, we define transforms that substitute each field terminal with its internal field, boundary field, and a get_elem transform that substitutes each terminal with a value at index i. This allows to compute complex elementwise expressions without creating intermediate field, which saves memory, and also time by reducing memory bandwidth requirements and improving cache locality.

Next, we come to stencil expressions. To compute these, we first lower stencil-based fvc:: functions to elementary operations. More specifically, we want to reduce variety of stencil-based operations because they require special handling. Vast majority of OpenFOAM’s functions can be expressed in terms of own_nei operation (which takes values in owner and neighbour cells and return them as a pair defined on the face) or surface_reduce operation (which reduces face values around a cell using a specified reduction operation). These operations serve as transitions between cell-based and face-based subexpressions and vice-versa. (Exceptions being extended-stencil gradients, such as pointCellLeastSquares).

This infrastructure allows us to experiment with various computation strategies, such as:

- Evaluate the expression as is, operating on OpenFOAM fields as a whole, which is equivalent to the existing OpenFOAM’s strategy.
- Evaluate expressions within one location domain (either cell-based or face-based) using fused loops, but use temporary fields when crossing locations.
- Split the internal field into batches of cells/faces, and compute batch-by-batch. This requires using hierarchy of levels of batches, such that face batch i on level $\ell + 1$ includes all the faces needed to compute all the cells in batch i on level ℓ .

As an example, we consider viscous flux expression. In standard OpenFOAM, it reads:

```
surfaceVectorField Fv = ( fvc::interpolate(mu)
    * fvc::dev( fvc::twoSymm( fvc::interpolate( fvc::grad(U) ) ) ) ) & mesh.Sf();
```

To make an expression out of it, we wrap fields in et::make_terminal and replace "fvc" with "fve":

```
auto expr = ( fve::interpolate(et::make_terminal(mu))
    * fve::dev( fve::twoSymm( fve::interpolate( fve::grad( et::make_terminal(U) ) ) ) ) )
    & mesh.Sf();
```

Note that this approach does not require any modification of existing OpenFOAM classes, everything is done externally. With the first strategy, we can compute the expression with

```
surfaceVectorField F_visc = et::evaluate(expr);
```

or we can transform it first, for example replacing "grad" operation with its Gauss lowering:

```
auto expr1 = fve::apply_gauss_grad(expr);
```

which produces new expression "expr1", which we can evaluate or transform further.

OPENFOAM-UM: A MINIMALLY INVASIVE PORTING OF OPENFOAM TO GPU

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Keywords: HPC, GPU, C++, CUDA, HIP, AmgX, DrivAer

With the advent of general-purpose GPU computing, and due to this technology’s relevance to the current surge in AI applications, most modern HPC clusters employ a hybrid CPU-GPU architecture^[1]. Scientific computing software written for traditional CPU-based platforms, such as OpenFOAM^[2], cannot exploit the considerable performance increases offered by GPUs, unless they are adapted, or *ported*, to the new architecture. Several attempts have been made over the years to port OpenFOAM to GPU: some targeting specific compute-intensive parts of the code, such as the linear algebra solvers^{[3][4]}, others extending to the entirety of the solution process, matrix assembly included^{[5][6]}. The former are limited in the amount of performance gain that they allow, while the latter did not find widespread acceptance in the OpenFOAM community, remaining as standalone forks of the code.

Cineca started working on the GPU porting of OpenFOAM in the context of the EU-funded exaFOAM project, with the realization of a proof-of-concept reduced version of the code able to run natively on Nvidia GPUs using the CUDA API^[7]. This experiment proved that the algorithms and data structures of OpenFOAM are amenable to GPU architectures, and substantial performance gains can be obtained without requiring a significant refactoring. The amount of low-level GPU-optimized kernels written for this small proof-of-concept, however, was substantial. To allow the extension of this work to the entirety of OpenFOAM, a strategy inspired by the porting of the NEKO code^[8] was developed: a small number of parallel algorithm categories was identified, such that all parallelizable portions of the code would fall into one of them. By wrapping these portions of code into lambda functions, the hardware-specific backend for the relevant category can be called, leaving the remainder of the code hardware-agnostic.

This strategy allowed for the realization of OpenFOAM-UM^{[9][10]}, a production-ready version of OpenFOAM optimized for GPUs. By leveraging the high memory bandwidth and computational power of GPUs, OpenFOAM-UM enables larger and more complex simulations with less hardware compared to traditional CPU-based approaches. This GPU-optimized version allows for high-fidelity simulations that were previously impractical due to the limitations of CPU scalability.

Figure 1: Strong scaling results for the 235M cells DrivAer^{[12][13]} test case: speedups are reported relative to the 200 cores CPU run; OpenFOAM-UM uses the AmgX^[11] library as a linear solver for the pressure equation.

As shown in Table 1 and Figure 1, the potential for time and cost reductions is substantial. GPUs provide faster computation and lower energy costs per floating-point operation, while the smaller number of domain partitions aids the parallel scalability of the code. This makes OpenFOAM-UM an attractive option for industries requiring rapid and efficient CFD simulations, such as automotive and aerospace, and opens new opportunities for small and medium enterprises to incorporate advanced simulations into their workflows.

Table 1: Execution times for the 22M cells DrivAer^{[12][13]} test case between T=10 and T=110, with 3 different memory pools (implemented in OpenFOAM-UM) and without a memory pool (OpenFOAM-v2412)

Case	noPool (OpenFOAM v2412)	dummyPool	fixedSizePool	umpirePool
200k CPU cores	154.43 s	145.18 s	144.64 s	154.37 s
400k CPU cores	64.29 s	62.40 s	61.25 s	63.97 s
1 GPU	-	822.68 s	141.40 s	140.63 s
2 GPU	-	431.81 s	77.14 s	77.55 s

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Addressing the Over- and Undersubscription Challenge of GPU Based Linear Solver

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Keywords: *Linear solver, high performance computing, GPGPUs, parallel preconditioner*

Modern general-purpose GPUs have become an integral part of most HPC clusters. However, to this date, despite multiple efforts, no official OpenFOAM version has been released that provides general GPU support. Currently, two orthogonal approaches are pursued in the wider community: 1. a general refactoring or implementation of the OpenFOAM code base: NeoFOAM [1], OpenFOAM_HMM [2], zeptoFOAM and 2. plugin-based approaches, for example OGL [3] and petsc4FOAM [4], see [3] for a more comprehensive overview of GPU projects. The re-implementation/refactoring approach promises larger performance benefits because matrix assembly can also be performed on the GPU here, thus reducing the inherent communication overhead between the host and device present in the plugin approach. However, the refactoring approach comes at much larger development costs. Compared to the refactoring approach, the plugin approach has two main drawbacks. First, only the linear solver part can be offloaded, which limits performance benefits to cases where a matrix assembly contributes only a small share of the total computational costs. Second, if distributed computations are performed with matrix assembly remaining on the CPU and only the linear solver is executed on the GPU, finding an optimal partitioning of the computational domain, such that matrix assembly and linear solver costs are well balanced, is challenging. The authors of [5] refer to this as the over- and under-subscription challenge. In the case of an OpenFOAM simulation with a GPU solver plugin, this can be illustrated as follows. Consider a typical HPC node with two CPU sockets with 16 to 64 cores per socket and four accelerators. Common decomposition strategies are to decompose the case into i: n_{CPU} or ii: n_{GPU} subdomains. Case i. will ensure optimal performance for the matrix assembly portion of the computational cost, which generally benefits from more parallelism. However, with a naive implementation, case i. will also cause oversubscription of the GPUs with n_{CPU}/n_{GPU} ranks per GPU. Especially, OpenMPI is very sensitive to oversubscribing GPUs [6], which can cause serious performance degradation. Additionally, an overhead is introduced from the additional communication required between ranks on the same device. Case ii. avoids oversubscription of the GPUs by partitioning into n_{GPU} subdomains, which additionally reduces the unnecessary communication between inter-device ranks by reducing the number of cells at processor boundaries on the same GPU. The drawback, however, is that matrix assembly, which is performed on the CPU, can only utilize n_{GPU} CPU cores, leading to an under-subscription of the CPU. While an optimal partitioning can be found based on a computational costs model considering costs of the matrix assembly, the linear solve, and the expected speed-up when employing more parallelism, it is a substantial change from the typical 'use all available cores' workflow. In this work, we investigate a repartitioning approach to mitigate the drawbacks of the case i. utilizing as many CPU cores as possible.

The Repartitioning Approach

In the following, we will use the term repartitioning for the process of mapping from a CPU partition of the distributed linear system based on the decomposition of the simulation case to a separate GPU partition to solve the linear system. Here, the number of parts in the individual partitions is $n_{parts,CPU} < n_{parts,GPU}$. The general procedure can be described as:

1. Extract the sparsity pattern from OpenFOAM's LDU matrix, including all matrix interfaces.
2. Send local and non-local sparsity patterns to 'owning' ranks.
3. On the 'owning' ranks, all local sparsity patterns are fused into a single large matrix. All matrix interfaces are either fused into the new local sparsity pattern or remain non-local interfaces based on the communication pattern.
4. Step 3 yields a mapping between the LDU ordering on the source rank and the COO ordering on the destination rank. This mapping is used to update the matrix coefficients.
5. To update the matrix coefficients, each non-owning rank sends its matrix coefficients to the owner GPU rank into a continuous array. The owning rank then orders the data according to the computed mapping.

Figure 1: Performance data for the lidDrivenCavity3D case for grids sizes of 210^3 , 420^3 , and 630^3 conducted on up to 16 compute nodes.

Performance Evaluation

For the performance evaluation, the GPU-based linear solvers of the Ginkgo library are employed using OGL [3]. As a reference case lidDrivenCavity3D case [4] is taken. The numerical experiments were conducted on the HoreKa HPC cluster, which is equipped with two Intel Xeon Platinum 8368 CPUs and four NVIDIA A100-40 GPUs. Furthermore, CUDA 12.2 and OpenMPI 5.0.1 in combination with ucx v1.18.0 were used. Figure 1 (left) shows the performance achieved $P = n_{Cells}/t_{TimeStep}$ in MfvOps of the icoFoam solver on three different grid sizes for the default OpenFOAM version with (GPU*) and without GPU acceleration (CPU). The accelerated cases are divided into the repartitioned case, where 16 CPU ranks are repartitioned to a single GPU (GPUOSRR16), and the unrepartitioned, undersubscribed case using only 4 ranks per node and a single rank per GPU (GPUURR1). Based on the performance data, the speed-up $S = P/P_{CPU}$ with respect to the unaccelerated CPU case has been calculated and is shown in Fig. 1 (right). It can be seen that the performance of the repartitioned cases for the smaller grid sizes of 210^3 and 420^3 is at least comparable to that of the unrepartitioned cases, with a clear benefit for cases carried out on a smaller number of nodes (<6). For the largest tested case of 630^3 cells, repartitioning is generally favourable with a speed-up of approximately a factor of two compared to the unrepartitioned case and a speed-up of up to a factor of eight compared to the unaccelerated CPU case.

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OPENFOAM OPTIMIZATION FOR NEXT-GEN ARM CPUS

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Keywords: ARM v9, SVE, SME, HBM, vectorization, mixed precision

Next generation ARM based CPUs introduce key hardware features such as variable vector length extensions (SVE2) and Scalable Matrix Extension (SME2). These Instruction Set Architecture (ISA) extensions introduced in ARM v9 [1] significantly increase vector and matrix processing power through the Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) paradigm, especially when utilizing outer-product operations. Along with CPU architecture advances, major steps are taken to advance memory utilization such as DDR5 and high bandwidth memory (HBM). These hardware advances can directly address OpenFOAM performance bottlenecks. I.e. HBM can alleviate memory-bandwidth bottlenecks, and SVE/SME can address compute-bound kernels. Previous work on large-scale distributed computing collective communication showcased the value of utilizing ARM SIMD extensions in optimizing memory copies and reduction operations [2].

In our work, we explore and present several OpenFOAM compute kernel optimizations performed with clang compiler-based vectorization, and compared to manual vectorization directed to ARM SVE2. It is also shown that vectorization benefits from memory alignment. In addition, the use of HBM allocated arrays shows performance gains for medium grid sizes in case of multiple workers (see Figure 1). A new solver is tested in OpenFOAM to demonstrate the selective use of HBM. It shows that memory-bandwidth sensitive kernels benefit from local variable allocation on this scarce resource. Our work on a mixed precision defect correction (MxP) solver [3], presented last year, is extended to a native OpenFOAM solver to further leverage memory bandwidth. It demonstrates speedup while preserving double precision accuracy for the industrial DrivAer benchmark case. A new type of asynchronous communication solver is introduced into OpenFOAM, to showcase higher scalability for massively parallel tasks. In addition, the basic Sparse matrix–vector multiplication (SpMV) operations are introduced with ARM-specific SME instructions for further speedup. Finally, the concept of HBM-based memory pool is explored as part of an effort to load more OpenFOAM critical buffers within the limited HBM capacity.

Figure 1: Effect of vectorization and HBM locality on PCG extracted kernel

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POLYHEDRAL CELL DECOMPOSITION ON STRUCTURED CARTESIAN GRIDS FOR FLUID DYNAMICS

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Keywords: *Cartesian Grids Methods, Sharp Cut-Cell, Polyhedral Cell Decomposition.*

Body fitted grid generation is a critical aspect of CFD simulations, as it demands considerable user expertise and time [1]. Moreover, variations in grid design can significantly influence simulation results. To address these challenges, recent research has increasingly adopted Cartesian grid methods for handling complex geometries [2]. Applied examples methods include embedded boundary methods [3], immersed boundary methods (IBMs) [4, 5, 6], overset grids, snapping approaches, and adaptive mesh refinement (AMR). These methods are inherently well-suited for automation. However, the automation process requires careful attention, particularly when working with object-defining surfaces, which often present challenges such as detached faces, non-manifold edges, open baffles, interpenetrations, surface voids, silver triangles, and other morphological inconsistencies [7]. Efficient cell-cutting methods based on Cartesian grids can mitigate these challenges by generating cut cells without requiring a full reconstruction of the mesh topology, thereby reducing both computational time and cost. One of the earliest algorithms capable of handling multifaceted intersections uses a bitwise clipping routine based on the Sutherland–Hodgman algorithm [8]. Building on this foundation, the Aftosmis framework incorporates AMR to support multiple cell cuts, adapt cell sizes to local geometric complexity, and employ a ray-casting algorithm to identify distinct regions of interest [9].

Figure 1: Steps of the polyhedral cell decomposition algorithm: a) the surface intersects a hexahedral block; b) the portion of the surface within the hexahedral block is identified; c) the faces of the hexahedral block are subdivided by the surface; d) new polyhedral cells are generated; e) relevant polyhedral cells are selected.

This research introduces a hexahedral decomposition methodology for structured Cartesian grids, aimed at partitioning grid cells into polyhedra using a triangulated surface. The use of triangular surface faces ensures both face planarity and convexity. The primary objective is to accurately reshape cut mesh, thereby resolving geometric degeneracies and enabling the computation of polyhedral integrals required for implementing a sharp IBM. The proposed process includes grid cell selection, surface clipping, face and cell reconstruction, and the identification of fluid-region cells (Fig. 1). A modified version of the Sutherland–Hodgman clipping algorithm [8, 9] is introduced, incorporating these tolerance regions to reduce the creation of small geometric features, improve point-to-face association, and merge nearby points. The algorithm defines tolerance regions around points and cells to improve robustness in geometric processing. A point mapping strategy, combined with these tolerance zones, enhances indexing and point association. Face reconstruction is performed by defining edge chains and tracing boundary paths to identify surfaces with minimal area. When multiple nodes are present, the algorithm selects the path with the smallest turning angle to ensure geometric consistency. An incorrect path selection may result in failing to preserve the delimiting boundary. Cell reconstruction then assembles polyhedral elements from the clipped and modified mesh faces, using edge association to merge faces and form closed cell boundaries. Finally, a painting algorithm is applied

to identify and retain fluid-region cells while discarding external ones, thereby completing the boundary-conforming mesh generation. This suite of algorithms facilitates the handling of complex geometries and enables the generation of robust, high-quality meshes. The resulting mesh is well-suited for use in body-fitted mesh generation, with particular applicability to sharp Immersed Boundary Method (IBM) simulations.

Algorithmic developments has been validated on a series of sample surfaces with increasing geometric complexity (Fig. 2). Results include a discussion about the performance metrics.

Figure 2: Examples of applications of the polyhedral cell decomposition involving intersections with irregular surfaces.

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Aerodynamics

Verification and Validation of OpenFOAM for High-Speed Aerodynamics

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Abstract

Accurate prediction of sonic booms is essential for advancing the design of future supersonic aircraft with minimized boom impact. This study focuses on validating the performance of OpenFOAM in predicting near-field pressure signatures for the test cases from the Second AIAA Sonic Boom Prediction Workshop. The test cases included an axisymmetric equivalent area body, a JAXA wing-body configuration, and a NASA low-boom supersonic configuration with flow-through nacelles. All simulations were conducted at a free-stream Mach number of 1.6, zero degrees angle of attack, and a Reynolds number of 5.7 million per meter. The simulations were performed using viscous-mixed grids provided by the workshop committee. A comparison of the results demonstrates excellent agreement between the solutions obtained with OpenFOAM and Ansys, as well as with the results from other participants. The locations of shocks and expansions were found to be consistent across all test cases.

Keywords: *Applied Aerodynamics, Compressible Flows, Supersonic Flows, Sonic Boom, HiSA*

1 Introduction

The era of commercial supersonic civil aviation effectively ended with the final flight of the Concorde in 2003. In many countries, including under regulations such as FAR 91.817, enacted in the 1960s, the operation of civil supersonic aircraft over land is prohibited unless it can be assured that the sonic boom will not reach the ground [1]. Recently, there has been a global surge in research focused on the next generation of supersonic aircraft, with particular attention given to sonic boom regulations. Accurate prediction and mitigation of sonic boom signatures are crucial for the development of supersonic transport aircraft and the possibility of unrestricted overland supersonic flight [2]. Research has demonstrated a notable market potential for supersonic transport aircraft [3, 4]; however, the time savings provided by high-boom airliners on a significant number of routes are not substantial enough to compensate for the decreased efficiency caused by the increased drag during supersonic cruise. A low-boom airliner would enable additional flight routes and create new market opportunities, but the reduction of sonic booms must be achieved to a level deemed acceptable by the general public [5]. Recent advancements in numerical methods have significantly enhanced the design of low-boom supersonic transport aircraft and the prediction of their sonic boom signatures, making it a focal point of ongoing research [6]. In the present study, the High Speed Aerodynamic (HiSA) solver [7], was used to compute flow fields for test cases presented in the Second AIAA Sonic Boom Prediction Workshop (SBPW2). The objective was to evaluate OpenFOAM-based software's effectiveness as a tool for predicting near-field pressure signatures on industry-relevant geometries and to identify areas for further development to improve the accuracy of sonic boom predictions. Simulations were performed with both HiSA and Ansys Fluent v2024R2, and the results were compared to those from other participants of SBPW2. The structure of this paper is as follows. Section 2 provides a description of the SBPW2 test cases and the simulation setup. Section 3 presents the results. Finally, Section 4 offers some concluding remarks and outlook.

2 Test Cases

The Figure 1 shows the three test cases analyzed in the present study, which consist of an axisymmetric equivalent area body (AXIE), a JAXA Wing Body (JWB), and a NASA low-boom supersonic configuration with a flow-through nacelle (C25F).

The AXIE body was designed using Cart3D to match the near-field pressure signature of the inviscid NASA Concept 25D with a flow-through nacelle at 3 body lengths on the centerline, as referenced in [8]. JAXA provided the second test configuration [9], JWB, based on an inverse design to recover the C25F equivalent area. The JWB model has a length of 38.7 m, a reference area of 65.6 m², and a design angle of attack of 2.3°. The third configuration, the NASA C25F with a

flow-through nacelle, is a low-boom conceptual vehicle designed at NASA Langley [10]. It includes a 3.37° nose rotation to achieve the design angle of attack, with a length of 38.7 m and a reference area of 37.16 m^2 . All test cases were conducted at Mach 1.6 and an altitude of 15,760 m.

Figure 1: Geometries of the second AIAA Sonic Boom Prediction Workshop

CFD Solver Settings and Numerical Approach

The details of the numerical approach and the computational grids used to compute the flow field for the SBPW2 test cases are presented. The simulations were performed using SBPW2 viscous-mixed grids, scaled to full-scale meters, designed for a free-stream Mach number of 1.6 and an angle of attack of zero degrees.

The CFD simulations were carried out using Ansys Fluent, version 2024R2. A cell-centered finite volume solver was employed, utilizing the fully implicit density-based solution method with the Roe-FDS flux vector splitting scheme for convective fluxes. The Green-Gauss node-based method was used to compute secondary diffusion terms, velocity derivatives, and scalars at the cell faces. Additionally, second-order upwind spatial discretization schemes were applied to the flow equations (pressure, momentum, and energy). Finally, settings were configured to enable High-Speed Numerics (HSN) to stabilize and accelerate solution convergence.

The HiSA flow solver, implemented in OpenFOAM [7], was used for the simulations. This solver employs the AUSM+up upwind scheme for calculating face fluxes [11], allowing for the simulation of unsteady flows with significantly higher Courant numbers compared to explicit solvers. Additionally, it has been reported that implicit solvers are more efficient and accurate than explicit solvers at high Mach numbers [12]. The governing equations were solved using the Generalized Minimal Residual (GMRES) algorithm [11], with Lower-Upper Symmetric Gauss-Seidel (LUSGS) preconditioning [13].

The implementation of characteristic boundary conditions for non-reflective farfield and reflective walls and dual time stepping method in the HiSA solver plays a critical role in accurately simulating and predicting sonic booms. In sonic boom simulations, non-reflective farfield boundary conditions ensure that shock waves generated by supersonic flight exit the computational domain without reflecting back. This is crucial for accurate predictions, as reflected waves could distort the simulation, especially in the farfield where the sonic boom is perceived. Reflective wall boundary conditions are used when simulating scenarios like wind tunnel tests or low-altitude flights, where shock waves interact with the ground or other surfaces. These conditions allow the solver to model the reflection of shock waves from the ground, a key factor in determining the sonic boom's characteristics. Properly handling these reflective interactions ensures accurate predictions, particularly for ground-level boom impacts.

Dual time stepping is a method used to enhance the accuracy and efficiency of simulations, especially for transient phenomena such as shock waves in sonic boom predictions. It involves two key components: *physical time stepping*, which advances the solution in real-world time intervals, and *pseudo time stepping*, which introduces an artificial time parameter to iteratively update the solution within each physical timestep, speeding up convergence. Additionally, *local time stepping* is used to adapt the timestep size across different regions of the computational domain. Smaller timesteps are applied to regions with rapid changes (e.g., shock waves), while larger timesteps are used for less dynamic areas, improving computational efficiency. In general, *dual time stepping* accelerates solution convergence by iterating in pseudo-time while advancing in physical time. Pseudo time stepping stabilizes the solution and refines shock interactions. Local time stepping optimizes timestep usage, ensuring critical regions are resolved with high accuracy. Together, these methods ensure efficient and accurate simulations, particularly for capturing transient effects like sonic booms.

Finally, for both solvers, the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model was selected, as it has been shown to provide more accurate results in similar simulations when compared to the $k-\epsilon$, $k-\epsilon$ realizable, and Reynolds Stress models [14].

3 Preliminary Results

The simulation outcomes for the SBPW2 test cases are presented and discussed in this section. For each configuration, near-field pressure signatures were extracted at a distance of 1 body length from the surface and at off-track angles, ϕ , of 0° .

3.1 AXIE

Figure 2 illustrates the refined AXIE grid, consisting of 15 million cells, generated in Pointwise and employed for the simulations.

Figure 2: Grid of the AXIE configuration provided by the SBPW2 workshop

Figure 3 presents the AXIE symmetry plane, colored by the contours of $\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}$. The comparison between the predictions from Ansys and OpenFOAM appears visually consistent. Figure 4 illustrates the symmetry plane colored by the spatial derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$, while Figure 5 shows the symmetry plane colored using the numerical schlieren. Lines of constant density gradient extend toward the far boundary, and the shock and expansion regions of the flow field gradually dissipate. These observations provide qualitative evidence that the HiSA solver, applied to the given grids, effectively captures the sonic boom signature extending to the far-field boundary. Figure 6 presents a comparison of the near-field pressure signatures, extracted at a distance of one body length, between the Ansys, OpenFOAM, and workshop mean near-field pressure signatures. The OpenFOAM results show excellent agreement with both Ansys and the reference data [15].

Figure 3: Contour of $\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 4: Contour of $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 5: Numerical Schlieren visualization: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 6: Nearfield Normalized Pressure Signatures at $H/L = 1$. Reference data by [15].

3.2 JWB

JAXA provided the surface definition for the second workshop test case configuration, the JAXA Wing Body. Figure 7 illustrates the refined AXIE grid, consisting of 28 million cells, generated in Pointwise and utilized for the simulations.

Figure 7: Grid of the JWB configuration provided by the SBPW2 workshop

Figure 8 displays the symmetry plane, colored by the overpressure contours. The comparison between the predictions from Ansys and OpenFOAM shows good visual agreement. Figure 9 presents the symmetry plane, colored by the spatial derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$, while Figure 10 illustrates the symmetry plane colored using the numerical schlieren. Constant $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$ lines extend toward the far boundary, with the shock and expansion regions of the flow field gradually diminishing. These qualitative observations suggest that the HiSA solver, applied to the given grids, effectively captures the sonic boom signature up to the far-field boundary. A minor discrepancy is observed between the numerical solutions obtained from Ansys and OpenFOAM. Figure 11 presents a comparison of the near-field pressure signatures, extracted at a distance of one body length, between the Ansys, OpenFOAM, and workshop mean near-field pressure signatures. Slight differences are observed between the OpenFOAM and Ansys results compared to the reference data [15].

Figure 8: Contour of $\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 9: Contour of $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 10: Numerical Schlieren visualization: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 11: Nearfield Normalized Pressure Signatures at $H/L = 0.85$. Reference data by [15].

3.3 C25F

The C25F low-boom model represents the most complex case in this study. As illustrated in Figure 1, it features a nearly complete aircraft configuration, incorporating a fuselage, wings, and empennage, with a distinctively shaped bulb on the vertical tail. To simplify the aerodynamic analysis and eliminate the complexity introduced by powered boundary conditions, the model employs a flow-through nacelle. Figure 12 depicts the C25F grid, consisting of 45 million cells, generated using Pointwise and employed in the simulations.

Figure 12: Grid of the C25F configuration provided by the SBPW2 workshop

Figure 13 displays the symmetry plane of the C25F model, where the contours of $\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}$ visually depict the pressure distribution. A comparison of results obtained from Ansys and OpenFOAM demonstrates strong visual agreement, highlighting the consistency of the numerical predictions across different computational solvers. Figure 14 depicts the symmetry plane, where the spatial derivative $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty} \right)$ is used for visualization, while Figure 15 presents the symmetry plane rendered with the numerical Schlieren. These results qualitatively demonstrate the capability of the OpenFOAM solver to accurately capture the propagation of the sonic boom signature toward the far-field boundary. Figure 16 compares the near-field pressure signatures extracted at a distance of one body length, as predicted by Ansys, OpenFOAM, and the workshop-averaged near-field pressure data. A slight discrepancy is observed between the OpenFOAM results and both the Ansys predictions and the reference data [15].

Figure 13: Contour of $\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 14: Contour of $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\Delta p}{p_\infty}\right)$: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 15: Numerical Schlieren visualization: ANSYS (left), OpenFOAM (right)

Figure 16: Nearfield Normalized Pressure Signatures at $H/L = 1$. Reference data by [15].

4 Conclusions

This study presents the near-field sonic boom signatures for three benchmark test cases: an axisymmetric equivalent area body, a JAXA Wing Body, and a NASA low-boom supersonic configuration with flow-through nacelles. Simulations for all three cases were conducted using the grids provided for the SBPW2. For all cases, OpenFOAM performs well in predicting near-field sonic boom pressure signatures for the benchmark test cases considered. Minor discrepancies are observed in the aft part of the signatures that can be attributed to the complex flow region at the aft part of the C25F configuration.

This study lays the foundation for applying the HiSA solver to more complex configurations and challenging test cases, such as transonic conditions and delta wings, including examples like the simple delta wing VFE-2 [16, 17]. Future work could explore multiple wing configurations and other intricate geometries to further understand aerodynamic phenomena, including shock formation, leading-edge vortices, and related flow dynamics [18, 19].

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Tesla Cybertruck Aerodynamics - A fully automated reverse engineering methodology using 3D Scanning and OpenFOAM

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Abstract. Analyzing and understanding the aerodynamics of existing cars is key to improving the shape and efficiency of new cars. 3D scanning is commonly applied to obtain 3D models of cars, but these models pose significant challenges for CFD (computational fluid dynamics) methods - these typically require simplified and watertight models. This paper presents key aspects of a fully automated and validated workflow to analyze the aerodynamics of 3D scans without any manual efforts. The workflow has been validated against wind tunnel test data and has been endorsed by OEMs.

1 Problem Statement

Aerodynamics are key when it comes to reducing fuel consumption of ICE (Internal Combustion Engine) cars or extending the range of BEV (Battery Electric Vehicles). With many automotive players working on similarly shaped vehicles, it is common for manufacturers to reverse engineer competitor vehicles.

In terms of aerodynamics, CFD (computational fluid dynamics) simulations performed on accurate 3D scans of vehicles can provide a fast and reliable alternative or complement to time-consuming and costly wind tunnel testing. Such 3D scan files, however, pose an enormous challenge for CFD simulations, as they are typically composed of a large number of non-watertight and/or non-manifold volumes featuring irregular surfaces.

Manually repairing these CAD models can require weeks of work, which requires a lot of time and resources. With time to market being crucial to the success of OEMs and with Research and Development budgets under constant pressure in the highly competitive automotive market, this can become a strong challenge.

In this paper, a number of key elements and learnings are highlighted concerning a fully automated and proven workflow to run CFD simulations on such models. This approach uses AirShaper [1], an online CFD platform based on OpenFOAM, and the 3D scan used as an example was provided by A2MAC1 [2].

Figure 1: Visualization of the STL file of the Cybertruck

2 3D model

2.1 Mesh visualization

For this paper, a 3D scan of the Tesla Cybertruck was provided by A2MAC1. A2MAC1 offers various 3D scan files:

- The exterior scan of the car, which is made before disassembly. This scan features a relatively low number of components. Figure 1 illustrates the surface mesh of this STL file.
- The full 3D scan of the car, for which the car is completely disassembled. Each individual component is then scanned separately and digitally put back together (as shown in Figure 2). This can result in models with around 2.000 individual components.

2.2 Challenges for CFD simulations

Both methods offer highly precise data, but these 3D models come with a number of challenges for CFD simulations:

- File size: the resulting 3D files (usually in STL or OBJ format) are often very large - 2GB and more. This slows down or even prohibits loading such 3D files on machines with limited memory capacity.
- Number of components: some of these scans can have thousands of individual components. This requires the boundary conditions for the CFD simulations to be defined for each individual patch. Doing this manually would be very time consuming. Also, meshing each of these components separately can pose memory problems if this process is not properly dealt with.
- Surface quality: 3D scan data is based on spatial measurements of points on a surface. This means the resulting surfaces are never perfectly flat or smooth. When working with scans of a quality level below that of the Cybertruck example, this can pose strong challenges for the meshing algorithm to obtain a smooth surface mesh.
- Non-watertight and non-manifold geometry: when a 3D surface is not perfectly closed (imagine a sphere with a hole in the surface), then it is considered non-watertight. The edges of such a hole do not have a face on each side, and are considered non-manifold. Conventional meshing methods will not work on such models, as it is not possible to define the boundary beyond which certain volumes are not supposed to be meshed. Figure 3 highlights the large number of non-manifold edges of the example 3D scan file.

Figure 2: 3D scan file of the Tesla Cybertruck in STL file format

- Overlapping geometry: various parts of the mesh, especially when reconstructed based on individual scans, can overlap. Such overlapping geometry can again cause meshing problems, as different surface meshes cross into each other.
- Geometry variations: each car is different and thus has a unique aerodynamic flow pattern. For optimal results, a unique mesh needs to be generated for each geometry, taking not only the geometry variations but also the specific flow pattern into account.
- Rotating elements: 3D scanned data, by default, does not contain any intelligence as to which components belong to a rotating wheel assembly, where the axis of rotation is located, what the tire radius is, and so on. Setting this up manually can be a very time consuming and error-prone process.

2.3 Traditional solutions

Traditionally, these problems can be solved as follows:

- Manual CAD repair: manually repairing the CAD geometry by stitching 3D surfaces together, closing holes, etc. This can be very time consuming, which increases the time to market.
- automated CAD repair: techniques such as shrink wrapping (the digital equivalent of a vacuum bag) can be used to close holes. But these techniques are arbitrary, closing holes which should not be closed and vice versa. This also leads to larger, more monolithic 3D models. With less insights into the forces per component, this also reduces the value of a CFD simulation.

In the following section, a number of key aspects of the fully automated AirShaper workflow are highlighted.

3 Solution

The cloud-based AirShaper platform is built on top of OpenFOAM and Paraview. OpenFOAM is the most widely used open source CFD environment and paraview is the most widely used open source scientific 3D data visualization software. Both allow for a large degree of automation and customization. The AirShaper workflow is proprietary and confidential. Nevertheless, through this paper, some of the key elements and learnings are presented on how a fully automated CFD workflow compatible with any given 3D model was built using a.o. the tools mentioned above.

Figure 3: Visualization of the non-manifold edges of the STL file

3.1 3D visualization

Loading 3D models in a CFD software environment can be very demanding in terms of memory. 3D files of 2GB and larger can sometimes take 15 minutes or more to load, or not load at all if the computer of the user does not have sufficient memory.

In the presented workflow, 3D models are decimated in the back end, on the AirShaper servers, to reduce their file size. This decimation involves the reduction of vertices and faces of the 3D models until a certain maximum number of faces is reached.

The challenge in this process is to maintain an equal surface quality across the different components of the 3D scan files without merging them into one large 3D file, losing the component structure.

Therefore, the workflow features methods to apply the decimation across the entire model while still grouping the resulting decimated faces per component. The compressed 3D models are then further compressed for online viewing using the Draco compression, again preserving the component structure. The result is a compressed model which, to the user, doesn't look significantly different from the original model. This allows them to set up the simulation on a simple laptop with little memory, or even on a mobile phone. Once a simulation is launched, the uncompressed model will be used on the AirShaper servers for the actual CFD simulation.

3.2 Large number of components

Having thousands of individual components requires an automated approach to naming these components, so that afterwards, the forces for each component can be calculated. This requires separate surface meshes for each component. This can lead to very large memory requirements, especially when the meshing process is executed in parallel across different processors. To avoid loading the full geometry on each processor, the automated processes use the distributedTriSurface functionality to reduce the memory overall memory load.

3.3 Component splitting

Very often, 3D files are stored in STP or OBJ file format - these remember the component hierarchy, which can then be copied by AirShaper. But many 3D scanning softwares export files in STL format. Very often, individual parts or components are not stored separately, but merged into one large mesh in this file format. However, to properly define elements such as rotating wheels or radiators, it's essential to maintain some sort of component definition.

To this end, AirShaper has implemented a component splitting algorithm. This method will automatically loop across the faces (triangles) of an STL file to identify isolated components. Via this

Figure 4: Result of the component splitting algorithm - top view

method, it is often possible to regain some of the component structure that was lost during the export to STL (or other) formats. This, in turn, allows for a more precise setup of the simulation. Figures 4 and 5 illustrate the result of this process applied to the 3D STL file of the Cybertruck. As can be seen, this results in a large number of isolated components, with the wheels being separate ones. This is crucial, as this now allows for the definition of rotating wheels.

3.4 Non-watertight geometries

To avoid losing assembly intelligence and errors in closing gaps and holes, AirShaper opted to not fix 3D models at all. Instead, the entire workflow has been modified in such a way that it is compatible with non-watertight 3D models. This has large impacts on pre-processing, solving and post-processing.

3.4.1 Pre-processing During the meshing process, mesh will leak to the inside of non-watertight geometries. Take the example of a car, where there is a small panel gap between the door and the A-pillar, without any rubber seal to virtually seal this gap. If the mesh is fine enough, it will connect the outside air to the inside air inside the car via this small gap. This has a number of implications:

- Mesh inside the car: the inside of the car will also get meshed. This costs more in terms of meshing, but it is especially expensive when it comes to solving the simulation. The result is a static pocket of air, inside the car, being solved but not contributing to the actual aerodynamics of the car (assuming the gap is very small).
- Thin surfaces: the scan usually represents a surface, and not a solid body. That means a surface will have flow on both sides - so patches need to be defined on both sides (inside and outside), each with their own wall treatment.
- Surface edges: it's important to accurately capture the mesh around these open (non-manifold) edges. That means extracting them as sharp edges to be used in `surfaceFeatureExtract` for local refinement. Also, extra loops in the `snappyHexMesh` to snap to such sharp features can be added to improve this.

3.4.2 Solving

- Stability: if the gap inside mesh is connected to the external airflow via a gap in an area which is subject to large pressure variations, then this leads to large variations of pressure inside the car as

Figure 5: Result of the component splitting algorithm - bottom view

well as high flow velocities through the gap. Extra care needs to be taken to stabilize the solution in such regions by, for example, changing the relaxation factors or schemes.

- Adaptive mesh refinement: the adaptive mesh refinement by AirShaper will automatically refine the mesh after a first CFD run. This is done based on the gradient of pressure and the vorticity, both of which are typically low inside a static pocket of air. Therefore, the rest of the mesh (especially the external mesh) will get refined while the inside mesh remains relatively coarse. This limits the extra computational effort associated with the inside mesh. See also AirShaper's open source library for adaptive mesh refinement [3].
- Convergence monitoring and averaging: the internal flow can, as mentioned above, pose extra oscillations in the pressure and forces. Therefore, it is important to monitor the overall forces on the car and only declare a simulation converged once the forces have entered a stable pattern. From there on, it's equally important to average the forces over a window long enough to cancel out the effect of any oscillations (whether caused by external or internal flow aspects). To this end, AirShaper has developed mathematical methods to detect convergence and dynamically change the length of the averaging window based on the specific force pattern of each simulation. This library has also been made open source [4].

3.4.3 Post-processing Once the simulation has finished, these surfaces of non-watertight parts of the model will have pressure data on both sides. This has implications in a number of ways as well:

- Force integration: the force integration across the patches needs to be performed along the correct normal.
- Visualization: when visualizing surface quantities (like surface pressure and surface friction), programs like Paraview or other will suffer from visual glitches caused by a phenomenon called Z-fighting. This is caused when 2 surfaces overlap and have the same distance towards the camera (the Z-direction). The render engine doesn't know which surface is closest to the camera and the result will be a semi-random checkered pattern showing the inside pressure in some areas of the patch and the outside pressure in other areas. To solve this, techniques such as face culling are applied, which take the orientation of the normal into account to know which side of a patch is pointing towards the camera and which is pointing away from the camera. Not every software supports face culling, however, especially when it comes to more realistic renders of subjects (including lighting, materials, ...). In such cases, other techniques such as surface displacement can be used to offset both surfaces from each other to solve the Z-fighting. But this technique

Figure 6: Z-fighting for surface visualizations without (left) and with (right) face culling

comes with its own challenges, as these offsets can create new collisions or overlaps with other surfaces. Figure 6 illustrates this effect as well as the effect of turning on face culling (see further).

3.5 Self-intersections

Different parts of the geometry can intersect with each other, especially in case of multiple scans being combined into one large assembly. To accurately capture these intersections in the mesh, the self-intersect option can be enabled in the surfaceFeatureExtract dictionary. However, this needs to be used with caution, as this functionality can result in a significant increase in memory usage when assemblies with thousands of components and many intersections are used.

3.6 Adaptive mesh refinement

Each car is different and each 3D scan is different. This means that both in real life and in simulation, the aerodynamics are also different. When it comes to meshing, a number of rules of thumb can be applied to construct a reasonable initial mesh:

- Domain size: the AirShaper algorithm aims for a blockage factor below 1 percent. That means the width and height of the virtual wind tunnel need to be sized accordingly. In terms of the length, the tunnel extends around 2 times the vehicle length upstream of the vehicle (to allow for a proper flow development around the car) and 5-7 times downstream (to properly resolve the wake behind the car).
- Refinements: the mesh can already be refined gradually as you get closer to the surface of the car. Also, as more complex flow is expected around sharp edges, these can be additionally refined.

Although this is a great starting point, such a mesh does not account for the specific flow patterns around the specific car. Therefore, AirShaper has developed and implemented its own adaptive mesh refinement technique for OpenFOAM. After a first CFD run on the initial mesh, this method will automatically refine the mesh based on the gradient of pressure and the vorticity in the flow across a number of refinement loops. This adaptively refined mesh will feature more precision in the wake (due to the vorticity-based refinement) and around aerodynamic elements, stagnation and separation areas (due to the pressure-based refinement). Then, the results of the first CFD run are mapped onto this newly refined mesh and the CFD simulation continues. This method ensures each mesh is uniquely tailored to the geometry at hand, resulting in a far higher precision. Equally important is the consistency and comparability that results from such a standardized approach; despite geometries being different, scans from different cars are analyzed in the exact same way, vastly improving the comparability between different CFD simulations.

Figure 7: Setup of the simulation of the Tesla Cybertruck on AirShaper

4 Aerodynamic analysis

4.1 Input parameters

The fully automated approach was applied to the Tesla Cybertruck 3D scan as follows:

- Velocity: 30 m/s
- Ride height: set to low for highway speeds
- Cell count: 76 million
- Solver type: steady-state RANS using k-omega SST
- Floor: moving
- Wheels: rotating (tangential wall velocity)
- Simulation time: around 6 hours on HPC (high performance computing) infrastructure

Figure 7 illustrates the online simulation setup based on the compressed 3D model for online viewing.

4.2 Mesh

The mesh was generated as described above - an initial mesh with refinements around the car and geometric features and a final mesh with adaptive mesh refinement based on the gradient of pressure and the vorticity of the flow.

Figure 8 illustrates the refinement of the mesh in the wake of the car. None of this refinement was present in the initial mesh and so this was entirely based on the gradient of pressure. Figure 9 offers a close-up of the inside mesh. This 3D model was not watertight and so mesh leaked to the inside. However, it can be seen that some of the mesh inside is just as coarse as the free stream mesh outside of the car. The mesh penalty is therefore limited.

Figure 10 shows the surface mesh of the car, with figure 11 offering a close-up view. These illustrate how the mesh was refined along sharp edges, and how certain areas feature a difference in resolution due to the refinement based on the gradient of pressure. Large flat areas on the front wind screen, the roof and top rear side flanks feature a coarser mesh for example, as the pressure gradient is low there. Areas such as the air deflectors, sharp edges and tires, on the other hand, feature strong variations in pressure and therefore have a smaller cell size.

Figure 8: CFD Mesh - Slice through the center

Figure 9: CFD Mesh - Slice through the center - inside mesh

Figure 10: CFD Mesh - surface mesh

Figure 11: CFD Mesh - surface mesh - zoomed in

Figure 12: Convergence and averaging of the total force on the Tesla Cybertruck

4.3 Solution

Figure 12 shows the total force curve on the Tesla Cybertruck. The simulation was determined to be converged after 400 iterations. From there on, the algorithm continued for another 450 iterations to obtain a reliable averaged value.

Please note that this curve only illustrates the second CFD run, after the mesh had been refined based on the results of the first CFD run. The data of the first CFD run was mapped onto the refined mesh, explaining the very short oscillation in the beginning.

4.4 Drag coefficient

Car manufacturers often state or claim the drag coefficient of their cars. But it's hard to know precisely what the error bounds are around such values:

- Velocity: usually, the velocity at which the Cd value was obtained is not stated. As the Cd can vary with velocity (and thus Reynolds number) this adds uncertainty.
- Ride height: although we can reasonably assume the most favorable ride height is used, we can't know this for sure. Also, we don't know if the car had a representative load (passengers, cargo, ...) which can alter the ride height.
- Wheels and tires: here too, we can reasonably assume the cars are equipped with the most favorable wheels and tires. In this case, the 3D model didn't include the aero covers which are typically installed on a Tesla Cybertruck.
- Wind tunnel: wind tunnel testing is a very complex undertaking and also comes with its own errors. We don't always know what the blockage factor was, at which temperature the tests were performed, if there was a moving floor, ... Testing the same car at 2 different wind tunnel facilities without a doubt leads to differences in Cd value.

Similarly, CFD simulations also feature errors and uncertainties:

- Geometry: in this case, the geometry is extremely precise. Still, no technique is perfect and also scanners have a certain resolution, which translates into small deviations from reality.
- Meshing: despite best efforts like adaptive mesh refinement, a mesh never has an infinite resolution. So this always introduces errors into a simulation.

- Solving: There are hundreds of not thousands of possible combinations to solve a certain flow problem. Steady-state versus transient, RANS versus LES or DES or Lattice Boltzman, wall functions or prism layers, .. Each of these have a direct impact on the results.

So when comparing a drag coefficient, it should be noted that for both a wind tunnel test and a CFD simulation, such a value is the result of a stack of errors and uncertainties. Nevertheless, the drag coefficient obtained from the simulation is 0.344 differs by just 2.7% from the officially claimed Cd of 0.335. This certainly goes to show the values are very close. Even more so, it can reasonably be assumed that the official wind tunnel test was performed with aero covers. As these have been shown to reduce the drag on other cars, this gap is expected to be reduced even further.

4.5 Flow structures

In addition to evaluating performance parameters like the drag coefficient, it's important to also look at the flow structures of the simulation. Figure 13 illustrates the iso-surface for the total pressure coefficient for a value of 0. These clouds are very useful to understand the flow structure, as they indicate where energy is being lost. This visually corresponds fairly well with wake and flow separation areas:

- Front air deflectors: the front air deflectors help to push air away around the front tires. This reduces the pressure on and flow separation around the front tires which feature a very coarse thread pattern.
- Front hood: the sharp edge between the vertical nose of the car and the bonnet is a large source of flow separation. After some distance, however, the flow reattaches to the surface, as the surrounding air presses the flow against the bonnet & front wind shield.
- Wheels: the front wheels feature a large wake, due to the fact that they are fairly exposed (because of the ride height, which is still fairly high) and their rough thread. The rear wheels feature a smaller wake, as they are partially in the wake of the front wheels and do not face the incoming air directly.
- A-pillar: the very long A-pillars feature a sharp edge towards the side of the car, causing a very long and strong A-pillar vortex. As this vortex travels upstream along the side windows, it crosses over onto the roof & rear window of the car. This again results in a vortex, but one which rotates in the opposite direction.
- Roof edge: the transition between the front wind screen and the roof of the car is again a sharp edge. The flow struggles a bit but on average remains fairly well attached to the roof. This is key, as the base shape of the Cybertruck, with its long downward slope at the rear, allows for beneficial pressure recovery - but only if the flow stays attached across the roof.
- Mirrors: the mirrors are quite large and as a consequence feature a local wake.
- The underfloor has been optimized quite a lot to be as smooth and flat as possible. There are even covers on the suspension, so that they would form part of the larger flat underfloor and keep the flow attached all the way to the rear of the car. This accelerated airflow helps to reduce the size of the wake behind the car.

For a more in-depth analysis of the aerodynamics of the Tesla Cybertruck, please refer to the detailed AirShaper video [5].

4.6 Component forces

Figure 14 illustrates how each separate component of the 3D model was meshed

5 Validation

The method described in this paper has been applied to thousands of cases and has proven to be highly robust across different disciplines [6]. Specifically in the field of automotive simulations:

- Tesla Model Y: A2MAC1 took the Tesla Model Y to the wind tunnel. The delta between the simulated and measured Cd value was less than 6% for a mesh of just 10 million cells [7].

Figure 13: Iso-surface of the total pressure coefficient at value 0 - 3D view

Figure 14: Analysis of the forces & moments per individual component

- Rivian R1T: a reverse engineering analysis of the Rivian R1T was carried out at a resolution similar to the Tesla Cybertruck and published in a video [8]. This video was endorsed by Rivian themselves: *"It's also great to see what we do being validated by an independent 3rd party. Wouter Remmerie & his AirShaper team correctly identify many of the subtle aerodynamic mechanisms throughout R1T that make it so efficient! Nice work."* [9] - Andrew McAllister, senior manager fluid dynamics at Rivian.
- Other well known car manufacturers have been using AirShaper's automated approach for years [10] - for example:
 - NIO [11]: *"We have been using AirShaper at NIO (ONVO) Design to get quicker aerodynamic simulations that are faster than the traditional ones with very similar results. Also, AirShaper's Design Advice [12] provides us a red and blue map of areas for potential improvements on Cd values giving Design Flexibility to play with to achieve Cd targets"* - Roy Morlet, Studio Engineering, NIO (ONVO)
 - Morgan Motor Company [13]: *"We utilized AirShaper on XP1, our electric prototype. We reduced the Cd from 0.65 to 0.42, impacting range significantly. You'll see the effect on our future cars!"* - Matt Hole, managing director.
 - Aptera [14]: *"AirShaper helped us keep expenses low while still getting amazing CFD work done fast"* - Chris Anthony, Co-CEO.
- Vecto Trucks: the exact same automated workflow has also been applied to the European Union regulations on Heavy Duty Vehicle emissions. These regulations include reference 3D models to validate CFD methods. The AirShaper CFD results all are within the allowed error bands [15].
- the automated AirShaper workflow also includes the option to automatically morph geometries using the adjoint shape optimization technique on non-watertight 3D models:
 - Porsche Taycan: an A2MAC1 3D scan model of the Porsche Taycan was used to demonstrate the shape morphing tools of AirShaper on non-watertight 3D models [16].
 - Volkswagen ID3: here too, an A2MAC1 3D scan of the Volkswagen ID3 was used to optimize the rear roof spoiler geometry. The aerodynamic drag of the car was reduced by more than 5% [17].

6 Further work

The method is fully functional, but further work still needs to be done to further cut the time to market and increase the efficiency and accuracy for customers. Some of this work includes:

- Prism layers: currently, the default is to run simulations without prism layers and use wall functions. There already is a free-of-charge option available to work with wall functions, but further beta testing is required before releasing this as the default setting.
- Transient simulations: these are already available but not via the automated process. The computational cost of transient simulations is roughly 10 times higher (this can vary a lot though) compared to a steady state simulation and therefore economically less interesting. Especially because steady-state simulations provide most of the accuracy and insights required for drag reduction, the main goal of most OEMs.
- Artificial Intelligence integration: there is a lot of potential to integrate artificial intelligence into the automated workflow. Current research and software tools still require hundreds of simulations to train a model within a narrow band of geometries. But fast progress is being made in this field.
- Wheel rotation: currently, a tangential wall velocity is used for the wheel rotation. In some cases, however, it's more realistic to use a MRF (moving reference frame) technique for the rims.
- More features: the automated workflow also includes the option to add radiators. Other upcoming features include the option to add inlets and outlets so that air intakes and exhaust outlets can also be included in the simulation.

7 Conclusion

Having a fully automated workflow for CFD (computational fluid dynamics) is key to reduce the time to market and to increase the consistency and comparability between simulations. Traditional CFD softwares put strict requirements on CAD models, however, increasing the time required for CAD preparation. Especially when analyzing 3D scan files of cars, CAD repair can be highly time consuming, making the process extremely slow and costly.

In this paper, a fully functional and validated automated workflow has been presented. The result is a workflow which requires just 5 minutes of set up time and yet provides accurate simulation results, even and especially on highly detailed and accurate 3D scans of cars. This allows for a thorough competitor analysis, as well as the application to in-house developed 3D models, as both can be tackled using the same automated CFD approach.

The paper has highlighted the complex challenges and solutions to cope with the effects of a high number of components, non-watertight and non-manifold 3D models, geometry variations in terms of meshing and variations in force convergence behavior. Techniques such as automated component splitting, adaptive mesh refinement and automated convergence detection have been highlighted as just some of many to make this automated workflow possible.

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DESIGN OF LOW REYNOLDS NUMBER AIRFOILS CONSIDERING MANUFACTURABILITY

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Introduction

In recent years, the application of multi-rotor unmanned aerial vehicles(UAVs) has expanded significantly across both civilian and military sectors, including logistics, surveillance, and reconnaissance missions. These UAVs typically operate in low Reynolds number regimes, where achieving high aerodynamic efficiency often requires complex airfoil geometries or numerous design parameters [1, 2]. However, due to structural constraints such as short propeller diameters and thin blade sections, implementing such complex airfoil designs demands extremely high manufacturing precision. Previous studies have primarily focused on evaluating the aerodynamic performance of airfoils and enhancing performance through the exploration of various design parameters. However, this approach leads to a rapid increase in the number of configurations to be analyzed, resulting in substantial computational resource demands. Furthermore, relatively little attention has been given to practical considerations such as manufacturability and repeatability in mass production. To address these limitations, the present study proposes a set of simplified design variables that simultaneously consider both aerodynamic performance and manufacturability.

Design Parameters

In this study, an airfoil design approach was proposed based on geometric parameters with constant thickness and curvature, while incorporating angular definitions at the leading and trailing edges, in consideration of manufacturability. Based on prior research[3], which identified shape parameters significantly affecting aerodynamic performance, four primary design variables were selected: maximum camber, camber location, thickness, and leading edge angle, as illustrated in Fig. 1. In addition, the trailing edge angle was included as a design variable, as it is considered to influence aerodynamic characteristics such as flow separation, wake structure, and vortex generation. Accordingly, airfoil analysis was conducted based on these five design variables under the conditions presented in Table 1. The shape definition was carried out by constructing the camber line using a B-spline method based on maximum camber and camber location, while the airfoil outer geometry was generated using thickness, leading edge angle, and trailing edge angle.

Figure 1: Airfoil design parameters

Table 1: Geometric parameter ranges and constraints

Re	Mach	θ_{leading}	θ_{trailing}	Camber location	Max camber	Thickness
1×10^4	0.1	20°–80°	20°–180°	30 %–70 %	2 %–10 %	4 %–7 %

Validation of Numerical Approach and Results

The computational grid was generated using Pointwise with an O-grid topology. The initial grid height was set to 1.69×10^{-4} to ensure that $y^+ < 1$ was satisfied on all surfaces of the airfoil. To account for laminar-to-turbulent transition effects, the Langtry–Menter k- ω Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model[4] was employed. For the validation of the numerical approach, simulations were conducted on the NACA 0012 airfoil, for which experimental data under a Reynolds number of 4×10^4 are available[3]. The results are presented in Fig. 2.

This study analyzed the effects of five design parameters used in airfoil development on aerodynamic performance. The results showed that a thinner airfoil profile led to a reduction in form drag, thereby improving overall aerodynamic efficiency. In cases where the leading edge was sharp, a tendency for drag reduction was observed at low AoA. However, at high AoA, performance degradation due to early flow separation was identified. Additionally, when the camber location was located closer to the leading edge, flow attachment was better maintained, which resulted in improved $L^{1.5}/D$ performance. Notably, the highest efficiency was achieved under the condition of 6% maximum

camber. Regarding the trailing edge angle, the 180° configuration helped suppress severe flow separation and strong vortex formation as the flow passed over the trailing edge. This phenomenon is interpreted as the result of a trailing edge stagnation point being formed to satisfy the Kutta condition. Based on these findings, the airfoil configuration with 4% thickness, 50° leading edge angle, 180° trailing edge angle, 30% camber location, and 6% maximum camber demonstrated superior $L^{1.5}/D$ performance across most angles of attack. As shown in Fig. 3, the proposed airfoil improved performance over the conventional 6% cambered airfoil (with 1% thickness) across a wide range of angles. In particular, it exhibited peak performance at $\alpha = 4^\circ$, showing a more efficient lift-to-drag ratio under the same test conditions. These results suggest that the proposed airfoil provides enhanced aerodynamic characteristics in low Reynolds number regimes, owing to its optimized curvature and geometric configuration—even with increased thickness.

Figure 2: Numerical validation with NACA 0012 (a) C_l comparison, (b) C_d comparison

Figure 3: $L^{1.5}/D$ comparison of proposed and 6% cambered^[3]

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Towards a generalized open-source turbulence model for external aerodynamics

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Keywords: Turbulence Modeling, GEKO, Optimization, External Aerodynamics

The present work aims to modify the widely used k - ω Shear Stress Transport (SST) [1], drawing inspiration from the Generalized k - ω (GEKO) two-equation turbulence model [2] as implemented in ANSYS Fluent [3]. The overarching objectives are twofold: to simplify and generalize turbulence modeling.

The GEKO model is characterized by several tunable parameters, making it adaptable to a range of flow scenarios. A critical innovation is the blending function, designed to distinguish between free-shear and wall-bounded flows: it identifies wall proximity and constructs a near-wall layer, enabling a smooth transition between the wall and the free-stream regions.

The first step of the methodology involves modifying the baseline k - ω SST model within OpenFOAM by incorporating the GEKO-inspired blending function, denoted F_{GEKO} . Subsequently, a preliminary optimization of the blending function parameters is carried out. Model parameters are jointly optimized to enable multi-case calibration, thereby enhancing model robustness and accuracy. A second training phase follows, during which the complete set of model coefficients is optimized to improve further the model's predictive capability across selected benchmark cases.

For calibration and training, a suite of four two-dimensional wall-bounded flows from the NASA Turbulence Modeling Resource (<https://turbmodels.larc.nasa.gov>) is employed and, additional validations will be performed on two-dimensional airfoil flows and three-dimensional configurations.

The final trained two-equation k - ω turbulence model implemented in OpenFOAM is governed by the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_j k)}{\partial x_j} = P_k - \beta^* \rho \omega k + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \sigma_k \mu_t) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right], \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \omega)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u_j \omega)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\gamma}{\nu_t} P_k - \beta \rho \omega^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[(\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_t) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + 2(1 - F_{\text{GEKO}}) \frac{\rho \sigma_\omega 2}{\omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j}, \quad (2)$$

The optimization of model's coefficients is sought both with a gradient-free and a gradient-based method. For the gradient-free approach, the particle swarm optimization (PSO) [4, 5, 6] is chosen; for gradient-based optimization, it is first performed an explorative Design of Experiment (DOE) [7] and then an optimization algorithm, based on the gradient optimization of the parameters. The objective function consists of the minimization of the squared error of different quantities of interests QOI :

$$J = \sum_k^M J_k = \sum_k^M \sum_i^N (\phi_{sim_{i,k}} - \phi_{exp_{i,k}})^2 \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_{sim_{i,k}}$ is the QOI in the i -th location, for the k -th case, as the aim of this contribution is to find robust coefficients for a range of conditions and $\phi_{exp_{i,k}}$ is the experimental counterpart.

The calculation of the gradients is taken into account using the finite-difference method, which represents a very versatile option since it does not require any knowledge about how the function is evaluated; the drawbacks of this approach consist in a lower accuracy and efficiency [8]. The optimization algorithm is based on the open source framework which allows to wrap all the optimization steps in an easy to use python environment, e.g. OpenMDAO [9].

In this contribution, the authors provide a framework for tuning the GEKO model through two different optimization strategies, comparing the results with those obtained for an external aerodynamic case and the corresponding coefficients.

Preliminary Results

Preliminary results demonstrate the effectiveness of the newly implemented blending function, F_{GEKO} , and the trained coefficients, C_{FbLam} and C_{FbTurb} . Figure 1 presents the distribution of F_{GEKO} for the benchmark cases, including the flat plate, channel flow, and wall-mounted hump configurations. In each case, the blending function successfully differentiates between the near-wall region and the free-stream, enabling a smooth and physically consistent transition. The training of C_{FbLam} and C_{FbTurb} via PSO yields values that enhance the responsiveness of F_{GEKO} to different flow topologies. The optimized constants provide a sharp yet continuous blending, crucial for maintaining model stability and improving accuracy across diverse flow regimes.

Quantitative evaluations show improvements in the prediction of wall shear stress, separation and reattachment points, and velocity profiles compared to the baseline SST model. These encouraging results suggest that the trained blending function not only retains the robustness of the original SST formulation but also offers greater flexibility and improved generalization across wall-bounded and free-shear flow cases.

Figure 1: Visualization of the F_{GEKO} blending function across selected cases: (a) channel flow, (b) flat plate, and (c) wall-mounted hump. The blending function correctly identifies wall proximity and smoothly transitions to the free-stream region.

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ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE DEGRADATION ON HIGH-ALTITUDE LONG- ENDURANCE UAV DUE TO ICING

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Keywords: *Fuselage Icing, Propeller Icing, High-Altitude Long-Endurance UAV, Performance Degradation Analysis*

Introduction

HALE (High-Altitude Long-Endurance) unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) operate in the stratosphere at altitudes above 15 km by utilizing long wingspans, low-speed flight, lightweight structures, and efficient propeller operations. However, during the ascent to their mission altitude, UAVs are exposed to the risk of icing, leading to decreased aerodynamic performance and increased weight due to ice accretion, which poses a significant threat to flight safety.

Research investigating the effects of icing on HALE UAVs has been conducted over the past decades [1-3]. Vogel [1] confirmed that icing leads to a reduction in the rate of climb, thereby affecting operational safety. Son and Yee [3] investigated mission-capable conditions in icing environments and highlighted that reduced battery performance was a critical factor in mission failure.

Previous studies have primarily focused on icing effects on the fuselage, with the impact on propellers largely neglected. Although propellers cover a smaller area than the fuselage wings, their high rotational speed results in significantly increased airflow velocity, making them more susceptible to severe icing and aerodynamic efficiency loss. Therefore, it is essential to consider propeller icing when analyzing performance degradation.

This study aims to investigate the causes of performance degradation due to icing during HALE UAV operations, with a particular focus on propeller effects. An icing analysis was performed using OpenFOAM-based CFD simulations to predict ice accretion shapes, and the iced propeller and fuselage performances were comparatively analyzed.

Methods

The ICEPAC [4] (Ice Contour Estimation and Performance Analysis Code) simulation module, comprising an icing simulation stage and a performance analysis stage, was used for the icing analysis. Due to the relative motion between the fuselage and propeller, separate simulations were conducted. The propeller analysis employed a Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) approach to account for rotational effects, including Coriolis and centrifugal forces in the momentum conservation equations [5].

The EAV-4 HALE UAV [6] was used as the target aircraft for the simulation. This UAV, developed by KARI (Korea Aerospace Research Institute), is a HALE solar-powered UAV designed as a lightweight airframe capable of sustained flight in the stratosphere.

Icing environmental conditions were established based on Federal Aviation Regulations (FAR) 14 CFR Part 25 [7] and classified into nine cases according to LWC (Liquid Water Content), MVD (Mean Volume Diameter), and ambient temperature.

The icing exposure time was estimated using standard atmospheric profiles of temperature and density in stratus clouds, with icing assumed to begin at the altitude where ambient temperature falls below 0°C. Accordingly, the minimum and maximum icing altitudes were set at 2.3 km and 6.7 km, respectively, corresponding to the freezing level and the expected maximum cloud top altitude for HALE UAV operation. However, given that the average altitude of stratus clouds is approximately 1.6 km [8] and considering a climb rate of 0.6 m/s [6], the final icing exposure time was calculated to be 0.74 hours.

Results

Ice accretion was most severe under high LWC and relatively warm ambient temperatures. As shown in Fig. 1, the propeller exhibited more concentrated and extensive icing than the fuselage, highlighting its greater vulnerability. Figure 2 presents the resulting performance degradation, which was greatest when LWC exceeded 0.4. Propeller icing led to substantially greater performance loss than fuselage icing, underscoring its critical role in overall aerodynamic degradation.

Figure 1: Icing simulation results for fuselage and propeller surfaces at LWC > 0.4

Figure 2: Performance degradation of EAV-4 due to icing

Conclusion

This study demonstrated the applicability of the OpenFOAM solver for simulating ice accretion and the resulting aerodynamic degradation in HALE UAVs. The results indicate that OpenFOAM is a suitable tool for future icing research, including complex scenarios and operational analysis.

Simulations confirmed that high LWC and relatively warm temperatures increase both icing risk and performance loss. Propeller icing caused significantly greater degradation than fuselage icing, highlighting the need for particular attention to propeller icing in high-LWC and high-MVD conditions to ensure safe HALE UAV operation.

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Data driven simulations, machine learning, AI

COMPARISON OF HODMD MODES OBTAINED FROM NUMERICS AND EXPERIMENT ON THE EXAMPLE OF CYLINDER IN CROSSFLOW AT $Re \approx 5000$

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Keywords: CFD, Coherent structures, Dynamic mode decomposition, Higher-order dynamic mode decomposition.

In many industrial applications, the dynamical behavior of the flow field is of great importance, as it determines the excitations acting on any solid bodies submerged in the liquid, the noise generated by the flow field, etc. As the computing power of modern computers increases, fully dynamical simulations are making their way to engineering practice, generating the need for new advanced validation methods tailored specifically for such simulations. Since fully dynamical simulations generate vast amounts of data, data decomposition methods must be employed. There exists a broad spectrum of data decomposition methods applicable to fluid flow problems; see, e.g., [1] and [2]. The use of Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) for the validation of global dynamics has been proposed in [3]. This contribution aims to expand this idea by using Higher-Order Dynamic Mode Decomposition (hoDMD). HoDMD is one of the cutting-edge frequency-based methods, first proposed around 2016 by [4]. One of the advantages of all DMD-based methods is that they extract single-frequency modes, allowing a frequency-specific search to be employed. This in turn enables focusing the validation on the frequency band of interest, e.g. around eigenfrequencies of solid structures. HoDMD has been proved to be robust and reliable when accurate extraction of important data from a highly nonlinear underlying system is needed [5, 6].

In the case presented in this contribution, the simulation data is obtained from a digital twin of the $25 \times 25 \times 300$ cm experimental test section. A circular cylinder, which spans the entire test section, is placed at the beginning of the test section perpendicular to the flow; see Figure 1. The inlet velocity is $u_{in} = 5$ m/s, which results in a Reynolds number of $Re = 4815$.

Figure 1: Sketch of the computational domain with boundary conditions and part of the wind tunnel. Discrepancy between the domain and wind tunnel (virtual walls) in dark blue, cylinder in light blue, plane of interest in yellow. Image inspired by [3].

The numerical solution is based on the finite-volume method and is computed using OpenFOAM. The mesh was prepared in such a manner that most of the region of interest is simulated with a resolution close to direct numerical simulation (DNS). The rest of the region of interest is well inside the large eddy simulation (LES) region. The use of DES approach allows us to set well-defined boundary conditions on the test section boundaries. The boundary conditions used are mostly standard; see Figure 1. For an exact case description, as well as any additional reference and case setup, the reader is referred to [3]. The experimental data used were measured in the plane of interest using time-resolved particle image velocimetry (TR-PIV) and are the same as in [3]. The numerical and experimental datasets contain 4000 snapshots of the flow field sampled at $f_s = 2$ kHz and were pre-processed using the inherent symmetry of the case as in [3].

The main results are shown in Figure 2. The results compare the main antisymmetric modes computed from the experimental data and the OpenFOAM results. Figure 2 shows great qualitative agreement between experiment and computation, as expected, hinting at the possibility of using the hoDMD decomposition as a validation tool, provided it is combined with suitable validation metrics. Good agreement can also be seen between POD, hoDMD, and the theoretical vortex shedding frequency of $f_{St} = 69.4$ Hz. The POD frequencies were taken as the location of the highest peak in the power spectrum of the respective mode.

Figure 2: Streamwise components of first hoDMD mode from (a) Experimental data and (b) OpenFOAM calculation

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OPENFOAMGPT: AN AI ENGINEER

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Keywords: OpenFOAMGPT, LLM, agent

We developed a Large Language Model (LLM)-based agent to advance Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) workflows^{1,2}. CFD simulations often involve intricate configurations, including solver selection, initial- and boundary condition setup, and iterative adjustments, which require substantial expertise and manual effort. The proposed LLM-CFD framework integrates natural language processing capabilities with CFD tools, such as OpenFOAM, to assist users in navigating these complexities more efficiently. The LLM agent employs retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) on domain-specific datasets to provide accurate, context-aware guidance. Key functionalities include interactive solver configuration, and error diagnostics, allowing users to focus on analysis and decision-making. Reliability is a central focus of this work, addressing challenges such as potential hallucinations and uncertainty in LLM-generated outputs. The framework incorporates validations and benchmarks to ensure dependable performance.

The integration of LLM technology into CFD workflows has the potential to enhance productivity by automating routine tasks, reducing human error, and improving accessibility for non-specialists. It also provides opportunities for interdisciplinary collaboration by bridging the gap between domain experts and computational tools. The presentation will highlight use cases demonstrating the agent's capabilities, discuss methods to mitigate reliability risks, and outline future directions for applying LLMs in CFD research and industry.

This work aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on LLM applications in CFD, fostering innovation in simulation-based engineering and expanding the scope of fluid dynamics research.

Figure 1: Structure of the OpenFOAMGPT

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AI-POWERED SURROGATE MODEL FOR TRUCK CABIN AIRFLOW

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Keywords: *Computational Fluid Dynamics, OpenFoam, Neural Networks, GNN, U-Net*

The use of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is highly valuable for investigating airflow in electric vehicles to achieve efficient thermal management by numerically solving the relevant governing equations in real-world scenarios. However, depending on the complexity of the problem, CFD simulations can lead to significantly high computational costs [1]. To address this challenge, Machine Learning (ML) is increasingly being integrated with CFD, aiming to reduce the need for computationally demanding simulations when studying multiple scenarios.

To optimize the thermal management system and improve energy efficiency in electric vehicles (EVs), this study employs a data-driven surrogate modeling approach. High-fidelity cabin airflow simulations are first generated using the open-source CFD software OpenFOAM [2]. These simulation results serve as the training data for a neural network developed in PyTorch [3], enabling rapid and accurate prediction of cabin airflow patterns. The resulting model supports the efficient operation of the HVAC system, ultimately contributing to improved thermal comfort, reduced energy consumption, and extended driving range. The neural network is based on the U-Net architecture, which uses skip connections to enhance both accuracy and efficiency. U-Net is well-suited for fluid flow prediction due to its ability to capture detailed flow features with low computational cost [4]. A comparison is made between the CFD model and the ML-based surrogate model, with boundary conditions for velocity and temperature used as input parameters. An automated script generated 132 simulation cases for analysis.

The surrogate model dramatically reduces computational costs, achieving near real-time inference speeds (2.1 seconds), while maintaining a prediction accuracy exceeding 95% in most regions of the cabin. Despite minor limitations in resolving complex turbulent structures with high velocity gradients, the model demonstrates high accuracy in capturing key thermal comfort metrics, with less than 4% deviation for temperature predictions. These findings emphasize the surrogate model's potential for integration into EV thermal management systems, supporting both design optimization and real-time control strategies.

Figure 1: Temperature prediction using CFD and a surrogate model (top), with accuracy and Z-score (bottom), shown on the horizontal midplane

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Generative AI for Extreme Ocean Waves for Ship CFD

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Keywords: Generative AI, extreme waves, transient maneuvering

The next-generation ocean-going vessels will rely increasingly on alternative energy sources for propulsion, and high-fidelity simulation is essential to design platforms that can operate efficiently and safely. Traditional methods—model tests, nonlinear potential-flow simulations [1], or idealized *design-wave* studies[2] can only partially capture the most complex wind-wave-ship interaction. Although CFD has advanced steadily over the past several decades [3], it is still too expensive to use for Monte-Carlo type simulation of long-time exposure in the ocean.

To address this, we introduce GenWave [4], a generative-AI approach that *learns* from random JONSWAP seas and then synthesizes focused wave fields likely to produce extreme responses. Trained in a 30-minute Colab session on TPUs, GenWave generates unlimited unique seaways whose peak elevations exceed four times the standard deviation.

We apply GenWave to the ONR Tumblehome in sea state 6 ($H_s = 7$ m, $T_p = 15$ s), using HELYX-Marine with adaptive mesh refinement on the air-water interface (3.9M cells, five prism layers, 0.625 mm propeller resolution) and a sliding-grid propeller model. GenWave is used to bootstrap a sequence of language models, and 10 unique focused wave cases, alongside a calm-water baseline, are simulated at model scale 1-to-32. The unique wave environments are used to assess the stopping maneuver in following seas. The time history of the ten wave fields is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Ten unique design wave time histories at the location of encounter with the ship.

An image of the ship during backing after the large wave passes is shown in Fig. 2. The ship is already backing, and the ventilated propeller is shown pushing air-water mixture towards the bow.

Figure 2: Ship as large wave passes stern and causes propeller ventilation

Results show that while calm-water thrust peaks more rapidly, wave-induced torque can be 15 times higher (6,440 kN·m vs. 419 kN·m) with a 609 kN·m standard deviation. Trajectory scatter reveals complex propeller–wave interactions, including intermittent emergence and ventilation (Fig. 3). This demonstrates GenWave’s potential to uncover extreme loads that traditional methods may miss.

Figure 3: Visualization of the propeller in crashback shown by a contour of the Q criterion

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ONLINE MACHINE LEARNING FOR MESH DEFORMATION

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Keywords: mesh deformation, machine learning, online learning/inference

The mesh deformation problem (MDP) occurs often in Computational Fluid Dynamics, e.g., in fluid-solid interaction (FSI), shape optimization (SO), or two-phase flows. The MDP is sketched in Figure 1: a boundary-value problem that requires mapping of the deformation (e.g., displacements) \mathbf{d}_k from a part of the domain boundary $\Gamma_k \subset \partial\Omega$ into the interior of the solution domain Ω . Two subsets of the domain boundary $\Gamma_{j,k}$ with different displacements $\mathbf{d}_j \neq \mathbf{d}_k$ generate a non-uniform displacement field \mathbf{d} inside the domain Ω . Mesh deformation follows boundary deformations $\{\mathbf{d}_k\}_{k \in K}$ at all boundaries $\{\Gamma_k\}_{k \in K}$ as closely as possible and maps the boundary deformation into the domain's interior as smoothly as possible, to maintain high mesh quality.

Figure 1: Mesh deformation problem.

The MDP has traditionally been modelled in CFD as a diffusion process or an interpolation problem.

The diffusion process

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot (\lambda \nabla \mathbf{d}) &= 0 \\ \mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{d}_k(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \{\Gamma_k\}_{k \in K} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

is solved numerically for geometrically complex domain boundaries (cf. e.g., [1]). It is very often the case that a part of the domain boundary Γ_k experiences the largest non-linear deformation \mathbf{d}_k which diminishes from Γ_k . For example, for shape optimization, a deforming solid in FSI, or a rising bubble in quiescent fluid, Γ_k is the deforming boundary, while \mathbf{d}_j at Γ_j is zero. In this case, higher derivatives of $\mathbf{d}(\mathbf{x})$ are largest at Γ_k , and they determine the discretization errors for the Laplace equation in equal magnitude as mesh quality factors, i.e., discretization coefficients in the error estimates of the Laplace operator [2], [3]. Making the diffusion coefficient λ proportional to the inverse distance from the deformed boundary Γ_k ensures somewhat that the interior mesh near the deformed boundary follows the boundary deformation as closely as possible; however, even with a large diffusion coefficient, higher derivatives are still largest near Γ_k , so the errors remain largest near Γ_k .

Modelling MDP as an interpolation problem gives

$$\tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{d}_k(\mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x} \in \{\Gamma_k\}_{k \in K}, \quad (2)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta})$ is the interpolant parameterized linearly with $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, requiring the solution of equation (2) for $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. In large-scale engineering problems, equation (2) must be solvable and computationally efficient for large-scale unstructured data. Radial Basis Function (RBF) interpolation has been successfully applied [4], as it can be made strictly positive definite (solvable) for arbitrary unstructured sets of non-overlapping points, and it can generate a sparse linear equation

system from (2) using RBFs with compact support [5]. While sparsity through compact support reduces the computational complexity of the RBF interpolation, it still requires an iterative solution of a large sparse linear system requiring load balancing, because the RBF domain decomposition does not match the decomposition of the CFD simulation domain – many MPI ranks in a large-scale CFD simulation do not contain $\{\Gamma_k\}_{k \in K}$.

We propose solving the MDP as an online machine-learning problem where regression models are trained and inferred online using boundary data from a CFD simulation every time the boundary mesh $\{\Gamma_k\}_{k \in K}$ deforms. Therefore, we only solve equation (2) in a least-squares sense for the boundary deformation; we use the CFD training data at the boundary, as it defines the boundary deformation exactly. To facilitate the ease of implementation of practically arbitrary ML models, we rely on our OpenFOAM-SmartSim computational framework [6], [7]. We can quickly implement different ML models in this framework, whose characteristics are especially favourable for an MDP, w.r.t. displacement smoothness, accuracy, and execution speed. Computational efficiency is ensured by transferring θ from the previous training round and easily utilizing heterogeneous hardware in the OpenFOAM-SmartSim framework [6], [7]. We demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of ML for mesh deformation using benchmark cases, comparing it with the widely used Laplace mesh deformation.

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The authors thank all those involved in the organization of this OpenFOAM Workshop and all the contributors who will enrich this event.

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ON ADAPTIVE MACHINE-LEARNING-ASSISTED RANS MODELLING

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Keywords: *data-driven RANS modeling, Bayesian learning, clustering, model blending*

We present an adaptive data-driven turbulence modeling framework designed to enhance Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) simulations. The proposed method aims to address the limitations of standard RANS closures, such as the k – ω SST model available in OpenFOAM v2306 [1], by incorporating corrections learned from high-fidelity data. These corrections target the Reynolds-stress tensor, specifically enhancing its ability to represent complex, nonlinear turbulent processes like flow separation or strong anisotropy, which are not accurately captured by conventional Boussinesq approximations alone.

The Reynolds stress tensor is expressed as:

$$\tau_{ij} = 2k(b_{ij} + \frac{1}{3}\delta_{ij}), \quad b_{ij} = -\frac{\nu_t}{k} S_{ij} + b_{ij}^\Delta,$$

where the term b_{ij}^Δ represents a nonlinear, flow-adaptive correction, designed to complement rather than replace the original eddy viscosity model. To maintain consistency with the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) equation, an additional source term $R_k = b_{ij}^R \partial_j U_i$ is introduced. Crucially, the baseline turbulence model’s eddy viscosity (ν_t) and associated wall-treatment parameters remain unchanged, ensuring the retention of the original model calibration and numerical stability.

Both tensor corrections, b_{ij}^Δ and b_{ij}^R , are expanded as sparse linear combinations of Pope’s minimal tensor basis [2], formulated as:

$$b_{ij}^\Delta = \sum_{n=1}^3 \alpha_n^\Delta(I_1, I_2) T_{ij}^{(n)}, \quad b_{ij}^R = \sum_{n=1}^3 \alpha_n^R(I_1, I_2) T_{ij}^{(n)},$$

where the basis tensors $T_{ij}^{(n)}$ depend solely on the non-dimensional strain and rotation-rate tensors, $S^* = S/\omega$ and $\Omega^* = \Omega/\omega$, characterized by invariants $I_1 = \text{tr}(S^{*2})$ and $I_2 = \text{tr}(\Omega^{*2})$. The scalar coefficient functions $\alpha_n^{(\cdot)}(I_1, I_2)$ are determined via Sparse Bayesian Learning (SBL-SpaRTA) [3], an algorithm used to identify concise, interpretable polynomial forms of the correction terms from data.

Given that turbulence corrections derived from specific flow scenarios can lack generality across diverse flow regimes, internal model blending can be considered. This approach combines multiple pre-trained correction models, referred to as “experts”, by computing spatially varying weights $w^{(m)}(\phi) \in [0, 1]$ that depend on local non-dimensional flow features, listed comprehensively in Table 1. We explore two methodologies for generating these blending weights: an *a posteriori* strategy [4], where a random-forest regressor directly maps local flow characteristics to appropriate Gaussian weights, and an *a priori* strategy based on Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) clustering, where soft cluster memberships are interpreted as spatial blending weights.

The final blended model combines these experts according to:

$$b_{ij}^* = \sum_{m=1}^M w^{(m)} b_{ij}^{*,(m)}, \quad * \in \{\Delta, R\}, \quad \sum_m w^{(m)} = 1,$$

thereby dynamically adapting to local flow conditions by activating the most suitable correction in each region. The presented methodology is fully implemented as a runtime library within OpenFOAM v2306, enabling seamless integration into standard CFD workflows. The resulting framework demonstrates improved predictive performance, enhanced generalizability, and robustness across a range of non-trivial turbulent flows.

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Figure 1: Results of the blending strategy [4] on the test case, wall mounted hump. The figure shows skin friction coefficient and horizontal velocity at various streamwise stations of the flow domain. L is the the bump "chord" and the legend denotes the following: (.....) experimental data [5] and [6, 7], (---) jet flow expert [3], (---) baseline k- ω SST model, (---) Separation flows expert [3], (-.-.-) blended model RFR [4].

Table 1: Non-dimensional flow features used for blending weights learning/predicition

Feature	Formula	Feature	Formula
η_1 : Normalized Q -criterion	$\frac{\ \Omega\ ^2 - \ S\ ^2}{\ \Omega\ ^2 + \ S\ ^2}$	η_6 : Viscosity ratio	$\frac{\nu_T}{100\nu + \nu_T}$
η_2 : Turbulence intensity	$\frac{k}{0.5U_iU_i + k}$	η_7 : Non-orthogonality marker between velocity and its gradient	$\frac{U_kU_l \frac{\partial U_k}{\partial x_l}}{\sqrt{U_nU_n U_i \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} U_m \frac{\partial U_m}{\partial x_j} + U_iU_j \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} }}$
η_3 : Turbulent Reynolds number	$\min\left(\frac{\sqrt{k}\lambda}{50\nu}, 2\right)$	η_8 : Ratio of convection to production of k	$\frac{U_i \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_i}}{ U_l \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_l} + u'_j u'_l S_{jl} }$
η_4 : Ratio of turbulent time scale to mean strain time scale	$\frac{\ S\ k}{\ S\ k + \varepsilon}$	η_9 : Ratio of total Reynolds stresses to normal Reynolds stresses	$\frac{\ u'_i u'_j\ }{\ u'_i u'_j\ + k}$
η_5 : Decay/equilibrium turbulence indicator	$\frac{P_k}{ P_k + \varepsilon}$	η_{10} : Ratio of turbulent time scale to mean rotation time scale	$\frac{\ \Omega\ k}{\ \Omega\ k + \varepsilon}$
η_{11} : First nondimensionalized Pope invariant	$\text{tr}\left(\frac{S^2}{\omega^2}\right)$	η_{12} : Second nondimensionalized Pope invariant	$\text{tr}\left(\frac{\Omega^2}{\omega^2}\right)$

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Offshore, wind, energy

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF SCOUR AROUND OFFSHORE STRUCTURES

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Keywords: Floating offshore wind farm, Scour, Sediment transport, Finite area method

Floating offshore wind farms are increasingly recognised as a promising solution to harness renewable energy in deep-water locations. However, the stability and longevity of these structures are threatened by various geotechnical challenges, particularly liquefaction and scour processes. Liquefaction, caused by the sudden loss of soil strength due to dynamic loading, poses significant risks to the foundation integrity of floating wind turbines. Similarly, scour, the erosion of sediment, soil, or bed material from the vicinity of a structure due to hydrodynamic forces, can compromise the structural stability and overall safety of these systems. Numerical modelling of these phenomena is addressed within the EU project INF⁴INITY^a.

This presentation focuses on the numerical modelling of scour. Scour, the erosion of sediment around offshore structures due to hydrodynamic forces, poses a significant threat to the stability and longevity of marine foundations, such as those used for offshore wind turbines, bridges, and oil platforms. This happens since the flow accelerates around these structures, vortices are generated near the seabed, creating pressure gradients that lift and transport sediment. Over time, this erosion can lead to the formation of scour holes, weakening the foundation and increasing the risk of failure. Understanding the mechanisms behind scour is crucial for designing resilient structures that can withstand these erosive forces, especially as offshore installations are subjected to increasingly dynamic and unpredictable environmental conditions. Larsen [1] developed a numerical model based on solutions to Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations, coupled with additional bed and suspended load descriptions forming the basis for sea bed morphology. The model uses a mass-conserving technique developed by Jacobsen [2], incorporating scalar contributions to the bed evolution equation (Exner equation), introducing a sand sliding routine, and evaluating the accuracy and conservation properties of various interpolation approaches. The bed evolution is modelled using the finite area method from the OpenFOAM framework. The model has been validated for a scour around a vertical cylinder by Baykal et al [3] and also for backfilling processes around a circular pile by Baykal et al [4].

In this contribution, the results of the model will be presented by validating against benchmark scour cases. Also, the preliminary results with the structural configurations developed under the INF⁴INITY project will be discussed. Additionally, the parallel computational efficiency of the model will be evaluated, and potential improvements in both numerical modelling and performance will be addressed.

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a. The abbreviation stands for INtegrated designs for Future Floating oFFshore wIND farm Technology. INF⁴INITY is funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101136087. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Website: <https://inf4inity.com/>

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APPLICATION OF THE CUSTOM DRIFT-FLUX SOLVER FOR ANNULAR FLOW OF FLUID WITH PARTICLES

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Keywords: *particle-laden flow, drift flux, annular flow with rotation*

Deep well drilling requires precise planning and real-time monitoring. Among the many systems involved, the drilling relies on continuous circulation of drilling fluid to remove cuttings. The drilling fluid is pumped from the surface into the drill string, then flows through the drill string nozzles and returns to the surface through the annular space between drill string and the borehole walls. Typically, the drill string rotates, and the drilling fluid has a non-Newtonian rheology. Under certain conditions, the suspended cutting deposit and result in formation of cuttings beds, which are unpleasant for operations. The physical models consider cuttings transport in the annular flow, in particular bed formation. The present model is built on the drift-flux approach proposed in [1]. The numerical solution is implemented in [OpenFOAM-10](#). The development started from [settlingFOAM](#) after [2] and resulted in solver [slurryFOAM](#).

The model for drilling fluid with cuttings uses Euler-Euler approach. The drilling fluid (subscript c) and particles (subscript d) are two continua. The relative velocity of particles comes from the reduced momentum equation for particles. The reduction takes place as we put known forces exerted to a particle into the momentum equation for particle phase and neglecting several terms following [1]. The momentum equation for particles turns into relaxation equation for particles relative velocity with equilibrium relative velocity \mathbf{u}_{r0} . To find mass velocity of the mixture \mathbf{u} , relative particle velocity \mathbf{u}_r , pressure p and particles volume fraction α , the model states the mixture continuity equation, the particles continuity equation, and the mixture momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_d \alpha)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left(\rho_d \alpha \mathbf{u} + \frac{\rho_c \rho_d \alpha (1 - \alpha)}{\rho} \mathbf{u}_r \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{dt} = -\nabla p + \rho \mathbf{g} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{T}_\mu + \mathbf{T}_t) - \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_c \rho_d}{\rho} (1 - \alpha) \alpha \mathbf{u}_r \mathbf{u}_r \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho = \alpha \rho_d + (1 - \alpha) \rho_c \quad (4)$$

After [1] we assume that slip velocity relaxes to an equilibrium value with relaxation time τ_{p*} :

$$\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}_r}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}_r) = \frac{\rho}{\tau_{p*}} (\mathbf{u}_{r0} - \mathbf{u}_r) \quad (5)$$

The particles continuum assumes spherical cuttings of equal size. The equilibrium slip velocity results from relaxation time τ_p and balance of forces exerted to the particle, more details in [1]:

$$\mathbf{u}_{r0} = \frac{\tau_p}{\rho_d} \left[\Delta \rho \left(\mathbf{g} - \frac{d\mathbf{u}}{dt} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} \right) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \nabla \cdot (\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{pc} + \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sbm}) - \frac{1}{\alpha} (\mathbf{F}_L + \mathbf{F}_t) \right] \quad (6)$$

The model combines the drift-flux approach with well-established submodels to cover a variety of phenomena during drilling. Among them are Herschel-Bulkley model for fluid rheology, Cheng-Law correction for mixture viscosity, permanent contact friction model for dense suspensions $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{cp}$ specified after [3], isotropic suspension balance model $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{sbm}$ after [4], turbulent flux of concentration expressed as force F_t , lift force F_L for a single particle after [5].

Figure 1: a) Geometry and boundary conditions for annular flow estimate; b) Simulated particles fraction, initial and final

The model shows good agreement with the particles concentration profiles in pipes measured in flow loops at University of Kentucky [4], [6]. Though our primary application relates to the annular flow with the rotating inner pipe. For annular flows the measurements typically comprise total cuttings volume and visual bed estimates [7], [8]. Figure 1 shows the domain to reproduce the experiments. The length of the segment may play a role, if the flow is unsteady, but as a first step we start with 2D simulations. Here we assume a uniform pressure derivative along the pipe calculated by class `fvConstraint::meanVelocityForce` with respect to the specified mixture flow rate. The cyclic boundary condition binds the inlet and the output. The initial flow properties are uniform. The solution estimates the cuttings transport along the wellbore, once the time average flow parameters have reduced with time significantly.

Figure 2 considers cuttings transport in Carbopol fluid, in the annulus of dimensions 5x1.9 inch, for different pipe inclinations and flow rates, the source is [7]. Figure 2 compares the measurements with three simulated sets: the mechanistic model of Clark-Bickham [9], slurryFOAM, and HydraulicsEngine. The latter is 1D real-time in-house simulator for wellbore flow, for more details see [10]. Clark and Bickham estimated cuttings bed in a pipe from the balance of forces exerted to a single particle located at the bed top. As the model (1)-(6) considers interaction between particles, its predictions adjust the mechanistic model. Thus, slurryFOAM contributes to drilling planning.

Figure 2: a) Measured and simulated scaled bed heights after the experiments of Tomren *et al* 1986, for different flow rates and inclinations (see [7], Carbopol, rotation 50 rpm, eccentricity 0.5) b) Flow loop run at University of Tulsa, reproduction of Figure 20 from [8]

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CFD ANALYSIS OF TRIPLY PERIODIC MINIMAL SURFACE AIR-AIR HEAT EXCHANGERS: INFLUENCE OF GEOMETRY AND CELL SIZE ON PERFORMANCE

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Keywords: *Air-air heat exchanger, Computational Fluid Dynamics, Triply Periodic Minimal Surface, OpenFOAM*

Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures have gained attention in heat exchanger design due to their high surface area, and therefore potential for enhancing thermal performance. [1] extensively investigates the Fischer-Koch-S (FKS) structure's flow characteristics and heat transfer performance. They estimate an approximate 35% increase of heat transfer coefficient compared to conventional plate heat exchangers. Another study [2] investigates gyroid heat exchangers with different geometric variations using CFD simulations and an experimental setup as well. In their experimental results, the thermal performance of gyroid structured heat exchangers is better than a “shell and tube” type heat exchanger.

The study presents a CFD investigation using OpenFOAM [3] comparing multiple TPMS-based air-air heat exchanger geometries, including FKS and gyroid structures. The research examines how different TPMS geometries perform in terms of heat transfer efficiency, pressure drop, and temperature distribution. Additionally, the study explores the effects of varying cell sizes on these performance metrics to identify optimal configurations for improved thermal management. The simulations provide detailed insights into the trade-offs between heat transfer enhancement and flow resistance, offering valuable guidance for engineers and researchers in the development of next-generation heat exchangers. This work highlights the potential of TPMS structures for advanced thermal applications and underscores the effectiveness of CFD in optimizing their design.

Figure 1: Example of FKS structured heat exchanger produced with additive manufacturing

Figure 2: Temperature distribution inside heat exchanger – CFD simulation

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SWENSE-Based CFD: A faster approach to wave structure simulations

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Keywords: Lab wave reproduction, wave structure interaction, SWENSE, Functional decomposition

CFD-based numerical wave tanks (NWTs) have become essential tools for reproducing experimental applications in coastal and offshore engineering. Long-term simulations often suffer from numerical dissipation, particularly when the grid resolution is insufficient, resulting in the loss of high-frequency components of wave motion. Therefore, highly accurate computational grids are required to precisely capture wave generation, absorption, nonlinear interactions, and damping effects. However, this increases computational costs, presenting a significant challenge for practical applications. Recent advancements have focused on hybrid coupling models that integrate near- and far-field approaches to address these challenges. These coupling strategies can be classified into domain decomposition and functional decomposition methods. In the domain decomposition approach, the computational domain is split into a viscous inner sub-domain and a potential outer sub-domain. In contrast, the functional decomposition method separates the total wave field into the incident part (wave-only flow) and the complementary part, which accounts for wave-structure interactions using a viscous solver as shown in the Figure 1.

This study investigates and compares the performance of decomposition techniques by using a Higher Order Spectral (HOS-NWT) solver for far-field wave modeling and a finite volume-based OpenFOAM solver for near-field wave-structure interactions, with the results validated against experimental data. The comparison focuses on their ability to simulate short and long-term wave propagation and their interaction with a cylinder with a heave plate. Key metrics such as computational efficiency, accuracy in wave generation and absorption, and accuracy in structural load predictions will be presented, providing insights into their suitability for offshore applications.

Figure 1: SWENSE representation illustrates the total solution's functional decomposition into incident and complementary components

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Forced-motion simulations of vortex-induced vibrations of wind turbine blades coupling open-source CFD tool with advanced RBF mesh morphing

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Vortex-induced vibrations (VIV) on wind turbine blades represent a complex physical phenomenon that cannot be accurately predicted using standard engineering models. As a result, high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methods are required. The presented study investigates the forced-motion (FM) approach on an isolated wind turbine blade where structural motion is imposed on the blade's CFD surface adopting the modal shape assumption rather than a fully coupled two-way fluid–structure interaction.

The loading condition analyzed features a wind speed of 18 m/s, a pitch angle of 100° and an inclination of 30°. This scenario was simulated by means of the open-source CFD solver HELYX performing an unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) calculation in which a pressure-velocity coupled solver and the k – ω turbulence model were adopted.

The motion of the blade is defined by its first structural mode which was applied using a Radial Basis Functions (RBF) mathematical technique to reshape the blade and interpolate structural displacements within the volume mesh of the CFD case. The blade's motion is amplified sinusoidally and a frequency of 0.67 Hz, employing a bi-harmonic kernel function $\phi(r) = r$ for the RBF volume interpolation.

The aerodynamic power, defined as positive when injecting power into the structural system and negative when damping the structural response, is monitored to assess structural stability. The CFD open-source solver coupled with the RBF-based framework is showcased to provide the user with a robust and effective numerical means for evaluating VIV in complex wind turbine loading scenarios.

OPENFOAM CFD SIMULATION OF STEAM AXIAL TURBINE STAGE ON GPU

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Keywords: HPC, GPU, turbomachinery

Turbomachinery CFD simulations often involve several complexities, such as the interaction between rotating and stationary components, compressible flows, and intricate turbulent flow characteristics. An example geometry is presented in figure 1. While OpenFOAM [1] provides many of the core functionalities necessary for these simulations, such as solvers for compressible flows, dynamic mesh handling, and support for rotating frames and multi-region coupling, certain features tailored to turbomachinery are usually provided in community-developed extensions. Examples could be mixing-plane interfaces, overlapping interfaces, steam thermophysical models, and real-gas formulations in general.

Figure 1: Typical one stage turbine geometry, courtesy of De Pretto Industries s.r.l

Recently, CINECA has undertaken efforts to adapt OpenFOAM to execute on Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), which resulted in the development of the OpenFOAM-UM framework [1]. This adaptation leverages the enhanced memory throughput and parallel computing capabilities of GPUs to enable more demanding and high-fidelity simulations with reduced hardware requirements compared to conventional CPU implementation. Notably, GPU tendency to work efficiently at higher cell count per GPU can decrease the domain decomposition burden in large-scale unsteady turbomachinery analyses, allowing cases that previously required hundreds of CPU cores to be executed on a single GPU with non-negligible speedup. This shift allows for more accessible and economically viable computational fluid dynamics (CFD) workflows for industrial users.

OpenFOAM-UM [2][3] has already shown noticeable speedup for incompressible RANS simulation on static meshes, namely the driver geometry present in the OpenFOAM HPC committee repository [4]. The primary contribution of this work is the extension of OpenFOAM-UM to handle key physical aspects of turbomachinery simulation: compressibility, interface modeling, and rotational dynamics. The implementation is

validated on a representative industrial steam turbine stage, offering performance benchmarks and a detailed evaluation of the benefits associated with execution on GPU hardware.

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Optimization methods

On the Use of Model Order Reduction Techniques for Thermal Topology Optimization

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Keywords: Model order reduction, topology optimization, heat equation

Topology optimization is a powerful mathematical method used to determine optimal designs under specific objectives and constraints. In thermal applications, the optimization process relies heavily on large-scale simulations of the heat equation, which often forms the computational bottleneck of the optimization. Therefore, reducing the computational cost associated with these simulations is needed for speeding up the entire design workflow [1, 2].

This paper investigates the use of Model Order Reduction (MOR) concepts to reduce the computational complexity of thermal topology optimization simulations. The proposed Subspace Acceleration consists of a projection of the high-dimensional governing equations onto a significantly lower-dimensional space, thereby accelerating the iterative linear solver. We propose constructing projection bases dynamically using information collected during the optimization process to ensure that the reduced model is able to continuously adapt to the ongoing optimization process.

Proposed Workflow

Figure 1a illustrates the standard workflow for topology optimization, where we highlight that solving the large-scale simulations (marked as **Solve FOM**) represents the primary computational bottleneck. Based on prior work [3, 4], we propose an alternative workflow (Figure 1b) that integrates two separate reduced models: one for the forward equation and one for the adjoint equation. In our proposed method, the step labeled **update MOR** incrementally updates the reduced basis using the most recent full-order model (FOM) solutions through a Gram–Schmidt orthogonalization procedure. The step **solve MOR** involves solving a reduced-dimensional linear system, significantly reducing computational costs. Lastly, the step **assess MOR** evaluates whether the reduced-order approximation is sufficiently accurate to replace the expensive **Solve FOM** step.

Figure 1: Comparison between standard and proposed MOR-integrated workflows.

Implementation

In this work, all numerical results and implementations are performed using OpenFOAM-v2306. The discretization of the large-scale equations is carried out using standard OpenFOAM classes, such as the `fvMatrix`. To solve the resulting linear systems, we employ standard OpenFOAM preconditioners, specifically the Faster Diagonal-based Incomplete Cholesky (FDIC) and the Geometric Agglomerated Algebraic Multigrid (GAMG). However, we have developed a custom implementation of the conjugate gradient solver for a better stop criterion. In addition, we have implemented new OpenFOAM classes to implement the subspace acceleration, and integrated into the specialized solver. These classes include linear operations such as sparse matrix-full matrix multiplication and overall management of reduced bases such as orthogonalization procedures. This allows incorporation of MOR procedures directly within the OpenFOAM framework.

Results

We first demonstrate that carefully choosing an appropriate assessment criterion significantly impacts the accuracy and performance of the reduced models. Specifically, we use the following criterion:

$$\|r_{\text{MOR}}\| \leq \tilde{\tau}(\|b\| + \|A\| \|x\|), \quad (1)$$

where A is the system matrix, b the right-hand side vector, x the solution approximation, $\|r_{\text{MOR}}\|$ is the reduced residual, and $\tilde{\tau}$ a predefined threshold. Our results suggest that criterion (1) is particularly suitable in the context of topology optimization due to significant discrepancies between the magnitudes of $\|A\| \|x\|$ and $\|b\|$.

Secondly, we demonstrate that integrating MOR significantly reduces the overall computational cost of the topology optimization process. To illustrate the flexibility and effectiveness of our workflow, we evaluate performance with different FOM solver strategies:

- Incomplete Cholesky-preconditioned conjugate gradient (ICCG) solver until convergence.
- Multigrid-preconditioned conjugate gradient (MGCG) solver until convergence [1].
- ICCG solver with a fixed number of iterations (inexact solver).
- One-shot method as proposed in [5].

In the first two cases, expensive and accurate FOM solves are executed until convergence, differing only in their preconditioners. The last two methods use less accurate, faster approximations to test whether the reduced model can still be reliably constructed from these inexact solutions.

Our results demonstrate that the proposed workflow is able to speed up the optimization process while achieving the similar designs and objectives values.

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STUDY OF OPTIMIZED SOLUTION FOR TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION BASED ON THE BUOYANTBOUSSINESQSIMPLEFOAM WITH THE CONTINUOUS ADJOINT METHOD

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Keywords: Topology optimization, Natural convection, Continuous adjoint

In this study, a topology optimization solver based on the continuous adjoint method is developed from the *buoyantBoussinesqSimpleFoam* solver, which mimics the buoyant force assuming the linear variation of density with temperature. For the steady-state laminar flow, the primal governing equations (Eqs. (2) – (4)) are solved. Considering the objective function (Eq. (1)), which minimizes the difference between the temperature distribution and the desired temperature in the domain as considered in the previous study [1], the definitions of adjoint equations (Eqs. (5) – (7)) and sensitivity (Eq. (9)) are derived. Also, the volume constraints (Eq. (8)) is considered. Thus, the optimization problems with constraints are described as follows:

$$\text{Minimize } J = 0.5 \int_{\Omega} (T - T_d)^2 d\Omega \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Subject to } \mathfrak{R}_p = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \cong 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_u = (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} + \nabla p - \nabla \cdot [2\nu D(\mathbf{u})] - g[1 - \beta(T - T_{ref})] + \alpha(\gamma) \mathbf{u} \cong 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_T = \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T - \nabla \cdot [K(\gamma) \nabla T] \cong 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_q = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} \cong 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_v = -\nabla \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{u} - (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla q - \nabla \cdot [2\nu D(\mathbf{v})] + \alpha(\gamma) \mathbf{v} + T_a \nabla T \cong 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\mathfrak{R}_{T_a} = -\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T - \nabla [K(\gamma) \nabla T_a] + \beta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{g} + (T - T_a) \cong 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \gamma d\Omega - |\Omega|_{\text{given}} \cong 0 \quad (8)$$

The solid isotropic material using the penalization (SIMP) method [2] is considered for permeability (α) and thermal conductivity (k) to distinguish the solid and fluid regions. The sensitivity (Eq. (9)), which is the variation of augmented objective (\mathcal{L}) with respect to design variable (γ), is derived for the definition of objective and SIMP function, as follows:

$$\partial \mathcal{L} / \partial \gamma = [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{v} (\partial \alpha / \partial \gamma) + \nabla T \cdot \nabla T_a (\partial k / \partial \gamma)] \int_{\Omega} d\Omega \quad (9)$$

To obtain a distinct optimized structure, the Helmholtz PDE filtering (Eq. (10)) and Heaviside step projection (Eqs. (11) and (12)) techniques are used, as follows:

$$-R_f^2 \nabla^2 \varphi + \varphi = \varphi_0 \quad (10)$$

$$\gamma_i = 0.5 [\exp\{-\delta(1 - 2\gamma_{0,i})\} - (1 - 2\gamma_{0,i}) \exp(-\delta)] \quad (\text{for } \gamma_{0,i} \leq 0.5) \quad (11)$$

$$\gamma_i = 0.5 + 0.5 [1 - \exp\{-2\delta(\gamma_{0,i} - 0.5)\} - 2(\gamma_{0,i} - 0.5) \exp(-\delta)] \quad (\text{for } \gamma_{0,i} > 0.5) \quad (12)$$

where R_f and φ are filtering radius and scalar value of filtering target, respectively. In this study, the sensitivity and design variables are considered as the filtering target for a stable solution. Especially, the smooth variation of steepness

Figure 1: Algorithm and results of developed topology optimization for $\theta_d = 0.1$, $|\Omega|_{\text{given}} = 30\%$, and $k_s = 0.4 \text{ W/mK}$

parameter (δ) in projection is considered in the form of Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) function for stable optimal solution. The optimality criteria (OC) algorithm [3] for optimizer is implemented in the proposed solver.

Fig. 1 shows the proposed algorithm in OpenFOAM and the topology optimization results. Considering the two-dimensional natural convection problem of $Ra = 10^5$ with $Pr = 0.71$ by Barakos et al. [4], the optimized structures minimizing the objective for the desired temperature are obtained, satisfying the volume constraints. Because the developed solver considers parallel computing, an optimized structure for three-dimensional or large-sized problems can be proposed using the developed solver. For dimensionless desired temperature (θ_d) 0.1 with 30% solid volume constraints, having 15 times higher thermal conductivity of solid material than that of the working fluid (air), the optimized structure of two-dimensional problem shows a 22.6% reduced objective value for desired temperature. And, for a three-dimensional problem, the 15% reduced objective value compared with the objective value before optimization is achieved with the satisfaction of solid volume constraints.

Results show the physical characteristics to minimize the objective, including the protruding body and guide duct. The protruding body, at the top near the hot wall, interrupts the rising hot plume to prevent the hot region from expanding into the domain. On the other hand, the guide duct spreads the descending cold flow to extend the cold temperature region for the whole domain using the fluid flow and conduction heat transfer, due to the low value of the desired temperature.

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A NOVEL OPENFOAM-BASED OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK FOR AUTOMATICALLY BALANCING FLOW IN PROFILE EXTRUSION DIES

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Keywords: *Tire Manufacturing; Extrusion Die Optimization; Bayesian Optimization; OpenFOAM; Computational Fluid Dynamics; Flow Balancing*

In polymeric profile extrusion, where rheology is complex and various processing conditions and post-extrusion phenomena must be considered, proper die design is essential to achieve the desired extrudate profile. Among the factors that can alter the extrudate profile—such as swelling and cooling-induced shrinkage—flow balance is the most critical for successful production. Unbalanced flow at the die outlet can cause geometric distortions in the polymer melt as it exits the extrusion channel, leading to significant dimensional deviations and defects that compromise product quality. Therefore, maintaining uniform flow distribution across all regions of the die outlet is vital. However, achieving this is often challenging due to the complex geometries required, particularly in automotive and tire manufacturing, where asymmetrical and intricate profiles are common. These challenges require special attention and remain a concern for these industries, especially since current die design methods typically rely on trial-and-error iterations, resulting in substantial material and financial waste.

In response to these issues, this work is a collaboration between the Institute for Polymer and Composites at the University of Minho and the R&D team at tire manufacturer Michelin. It involves implementing a novel fully automated computational framework to improve the performance of profile extrusion dies, focusing on maximizing flow balance at the die exit and minimizing pressure drop in the channel. It integrates extrusion die flow simulation in OpenFOAM with an automatic geometry update method in FreeCAD [1] for parameterized CAD design and employs a Bayesian optimization algorithm from Scikit-Optimize [2] to propose new parameter combinations for testing. To automate these steps, a complex framework composed of Python code and Bash scripts was developed to facilitate communication between OpenFOAM simulation results and FreeCAD geometry updates based on analyzed outcomes, executing all pre-, current, and post-processing tasks throughout the optimization loop.

The calculation begins with an initial parameterized geometry modeled in FreeCAD, which is subsequently exported to OpenFOAM for meshing with cfMesh [3]. A simulation is then performed for a non-isothermal, non-Newtonian flow using a custom solver designed to model temperature-dependent viscosity with the Bird-Carreau-Arrhenius model, incorporating viscous dissipation and a novel boundary condition to replicate the thermal regulation used in the experimental process. For optimization, the outlet cross-section is divided into several elemental sections to quantify outlet flow distribution and a faster convergence strategy, proposed in Vidal et al. [4], is used. Channel pressure drop (ΔP) and velocity uniformity (U_{unif}) at the outlet are quantified based on the simulation data, and the objective function (F_{obj}) is computed with weighting factors (w_1 and w_2) for each objective, as shown in Equation 1.

$$F_{obj} = w_1 \Delta P + w_2 (1 - U_{unif}) \quad (1)$$

Finally, the `gp_minimize` function [5] from Scikit-Optimize is used to perform Bayesian Optimization based on Gaussian Process regression [6], estimating how the objective function behaves for different combinations of parameters and proposing the next combination to test in order to reach the minimum value.

To validate the implemented framework, a case study was conducted using a representative geometry of an extrusion die for tire manufacturing, with a tire tread cross-section defined as the outlet shape of the die. To control flow distribution and achieve minimum values, an obstruction with three design parameters (A, B, and C) was studied, as shown in Figure 1a. Weighting factors for pressure drop and outlet uniformity were defined as 0.2 and 0.8, respectively, and the optimization loop was set to run for 19 trials, with convergence demonstrated in Figure 1b. From the geometries proposed by the Bayesian algorithm, the optimal value was 0.1626 (Trial 19), while the worst value was 0.4966 (Trial 5), representing an enhancement of 67.3%. The comparison of flow balance improvement between Trial 5 and Trial 19 is shown in Figure 1c.

Figure 1: Case study used to test the optimization framework: (a) geometry and obstruction parameterization; (b) objective function evolution; and (c) outlet velocity field at worst (Trial 5) and best (Trial 19) parameter combinations.

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AN APPROXIMATE NEWTON-KRYLOV PRESSURE-BASED INCOMPRESSIBLE RANS SOLVER FOR AERODYNAMIC SHAPE OPTIMIZATION

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Keywords: *Approximate Newton–Krylov, Incompressible Flows, Pressure–based Coupled CFD Solver, Continuous Adjoint Method, Aerodynamic Shape Optimization*

In OpenFOAM, the *adjointOptimisationFoam* library, [1], developed and made publicly available by the group of authors, enables a fully automated gradient-based aerodynamic Shape Optimization (ShpO) loop to be performed by making use of the continuous adjoint method, [2, 3], to compute the objective and constraint function gradients with respect to (w.r.t.) the design variables. Since ShpO usually requires successive calls to the CFD/primal evaluation tool (and its adjoint), the efficiency and robustness of these tools is of major importance.

In each optimization cycle, *adjointOptimisationFoam* solves the Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) equations for an incompressible flow which are coupled to the Spalart–Allmaras, [4], or the $k - \omega$ SST, [5], eddy viscosity models. The SIMPLE algorithm, [6], is used to handle the pressure–velocity coupling in both the primal and adjoint problems. In each iteration, it solves the momentum equations for the velocity field and the continuity equation for the pressure, in a segregated manner. The continuity equation, if discretized over a finite volume P , reads $\sum_{N \in Neighbors(P)} \phi^{PN} = 0$, where ϕ^{PN} is the volume flow–rate crossing the face that is shared by control volumes P, N . In pressure–based solution algorithms for collocated grids, ϕ is computed from the Rhie–Chow interpolation, [7], as follows

$$\phi^{PN} = \overline{v_i}^{PN} S_i^{PN} + \left(\frac{1}{D_v^P} \right) \Big|_{PN} \left[\left. \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_k} \right|_{PN} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_k} \Big|_{PN} \right] n_k^{PN} \Delta S^{PN} \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is derived from the semi-discrete form of the momentum equation. Overlined quantities are linearly interpolated from cell to face centers. The second term on the right hand side (r.h.s.) is an artificial dissipation term to eliminate odd–even decoupling in the solution. D_v^P is the diagonal element of the matrix resulting from the discretization of the momentum equations, also depending on ϕ . For this reason, eqs. 1, at all faces, can be seen as the residuals of extra governing equations. The main drawback of the segregated solution approach is that the convergence rate tends to deteriorate in complex or large–scale problems due to the weak resolution of the pressure–velocity coupling. To address this issue and thus accelerate the convergence of the CFD solver, coupled solution strategies can be used instead, see for instance [8] for the development of a coupled pressure–based solver for compressible flows. To enhance efficiency and robustness of CFD tools involved in ShpO, this work considers the implementation of an Approximate Newton–Krylov (ANK) method, [9, 10, 11], in OpenFOAM, due to the favorable convergence properties of Newton’s method and the advantages of the Jacobian-free implementation. In each iteration of the ANK algorithm, the update of the mean flow variables, $\Delta w^{(n)} = [\Delta v_i^{(n)}, \Delta p^{(n)}, \Delta \phi^{(n)}]$, is computed by the solution of the following linear system

$$\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w} \right)^{(n)} \Delta w^{(n)} = -\mathcal{R}(w^{(n)}) \quad (2)$$

where the superscript n indicates the iteration number. \mathcal{R} is the vector of the residuals of the discretized mean flow PDEs using second–order accurate discretization schemes and also includes the residuals of the Rhie–Chow interpolations (eq. (1)). This is a novelty of the proposed solution algorithm since, according to the authors’ knowledge, it is the first time that the face–fluxes are treated implicitly during the solution of the coupled linear system (eq. (2)). $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}$ is the Jacobian matrix obtained from the differentiation of an approximate residual vector $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}$; $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}$ is formulated from \mathcal{R} by eliminating the cross diffusion term in the momentum equation as well as the high bandwidth term in the pressure equation and the Rhie–Chow interpolation. Due to this discrepancy between $\tilde{\mathcal{R}}$ and \mathcal{R} , the exact Newton method (which is known to provide with quadratic convergence rates)

Figure 1: Verification cases for the proposed ANK flow solver. Top: computed flow fields. Bottom: plots of the convergence of the flow residuals with the ANK and the segregated SIMPLE solvers.

is not used, but a better-conditioned linear system is formulated and solved in each solver iteration. The turbulence model PDEs are solved decoupled from the mean flow ones, after solving eq. (2) and updating the mean flow variables.

Eq. (2) is solved using the flexible variant of the generalized minimal residual method (FGMRES), [12]. Since FGMRES only requires the product of $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}$ by given vectors, the storage of $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}$ can be avoided. Thanks to this matrix-free implementation, high-order bandwidth terms due to the second-order discretization of convection and diffusion terms can also be considered during the multiplications by $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}$ without a significant impact on the memory footprint. To better cluster the eigenvalues of $\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}$ and improve the convergence of FGMRES, the segregated SIMPLE algorithm is used to right-precondition eq. (2), [13]. Details on how the SIMPLE algorithm can be written in the form of a fully-coupled preconditioner for the incompressible RANS equations will be given in the full paper.

The performance and efficiency of the ANK solver is investigated in three test cases, namely an isolated NACA 0012 airfoil (fig. 1a), a conical diffuser (fig. 1b, [14]), and a 3D turbomachinery stationary blade cascade (fig. 1c). The convergence of the segregated and ANK solver are also plotted. Compared to the segregated approach, the use of the ANK solver results in a reduction of the CPU cost by ~ 35% in all three cases. In the full paper, further investigations are performed in order to showcase the significance of the implicit treatment of the Rhie-Chow interpolation during the solution of eq. (2).

To demonstrate the benefits of the proposed ANK solver within a ShpO, the turbomachinery case is optimized for a minimum total pressure drop between the inlet and outlet, while also imposing inequality constraints on the flow angle at the exit to remain within certain bounds. The *Think Discrete-Do Continuous* adjoint method, [15], is used to compute the derivatives of the objective and constraint function w.r.t. the design variables with an accuracy dictated by discrete adjoint, without, though, requiring excessive memory. To enhance the robustness of the adjoint solver, the full system of adjoint equations

$$\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial w}\right)^T \Psi = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial w} \quad (3)$$

is solved in a coupled manner to compute the vector of adjoint variables Ψ using FGMRES with Deflated-Restarting (FGMRES-DR), [16]. In contrast to the solution of the primal equations, the exact Jacobian matrix is used on the left hand side (l.h.s.) of eq. (3) which results in a fully-implicit approach. The advantage of the proposed approach for solving the adjoint system of equations is that since FGMRES-DR minimizes the residual norm inside a Krylov subspace, it can also guarantee the convergence of the adjoint equations provided that enough vectors are used to form the Krylov subspace. Note, however, that the number of basis vectors can be reduced provided that a fairly good approximation of $\left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{R}}{\partial w}\right)^T$ is used as a

preconditioner. Here, $\left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\mathcal{R}}}{\partial w}\right)^T$ is used to right-precondition eq. (3).

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Multiphysics

OPEN-SOURCE APPROACH TO THE PROTOTYPING OF LASER SHOCK PEENING

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Keywords: *laser shock peening (LSP), prototyping, Blender, OpenFOAM, solids4foam, model order reduction (MOR)*

Laser shock peening (LSP) is a modern approach to improving fatigue resistance and surface hardness of mechanical components by endowing their surface with compressive residual stresses. One of the advantages of LSP compared to standard shot peening is precision – a specific area may be treated with 0.1 mm accuracy. Still, the state of the art of industrial LSP is based on experimental testing of at best few variants for each processed component, which hinders the LSP potential.

In long-term collaboration with industrial partners and other research institutions, we have developed a framework for the computational support of component-specific LSP prototyping. The key areas (KA) of the support are:

- KA1: Capability of computer-aided design of component positioning with respect to a fixed laser beam on an LSP station.
- KA2: Possibility of fast visualization of preliminary LSP treatment on a component combined with the capability to directly share LSP parameters between manufacturing and simulation.
- KA3: Manufacturing support through high-fidelity simulations with predictive capabilities.
- KA4: Simulation-based and computationally feasible process optimization.

Figure 1: Scheme of the approach to computer-aided prototyping of laser shock peening

Currently, the computational support comprises three consecutive steps; see Figure 1. In step one, the component is analyzed using the LIATool software [1], a custom-built open-source plugin for Blender. LIATool addresses KA1 and KA2. Consequently, this analysis leads to a suitable set up of the positioning robot at the LSP station. Furthermore, critical component parts are identified, the treatment of which is to be supported by high-fidelity simulations.

In step two, the detailed simulations are constructed and evaluated, providing the first insight into the effects of LSP on the treated component (KA3). The simulation approach is built on the solids4Foam package [2], was presented at previous OpenFOAM workshops, and is detailed, for example, in [3]. The insight into the system behavior gained in the step two is used to identify feasible bounds for LSP parameters.

In step three, the detailed simulations are evaluated for different combinations of LSP parameters within the identified feasible bounds. The set of evaluated simulations is used to construct a cheaper-to-evaluate surrogate model. Afterwards, the surrogate is coupled with genetic algorithms for robust optimization of the LSP process parameters completing the treatment design. Finally, the proposed treatment design is validated in pre-production tests and released for production.

Figure 2: Scheme of the used approach to model order reduction. By Y we mark the matrix of all the available problem solutions, POD and ANN stand for proper orthogonal decomposition and artificial neural network, respectively

It is the third step of the process that is currently under the most active development. The construction of the surrogate model is based on the approaches to model order reduction stemming from [4, 5] and illustrated in Figure 2. The genetic algorithm of choice for the optimization is the NSGA-II [6] in the variant implemented in the open-source Platypus python package [7].

In the presentation, we will focus on the details of the individual LSP prototyping steps and on data transfer between them.

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NON-SPHERICAL DEM CONTACT MODEL CONSISTENT WITH HERTZIAN FORMULATION FOR LARGE-SCALE CFD-DEM

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Keywords: *non-spherical particles, discrete element method (DEM), CFD-DEM*

Suspensions are prevalent in both nature and industry. They are present in diverse contexts, from riverbed transport and water seepage in gravel soils to industrial applications such as fluidized bed reactors and pharmaceutical microdosing [1]. Various approaches can be used to describe such systems, the most common being empirical, experiment-based correlations [2], which are standard in engineering practice. A more detailed alternative is the utilization of two-fluid models, where the particles are considered as the second fluid, and the fluid–fluid interaction is phenomenologically modeled. Lastly, a high-fidelity alternative is the combination of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for the description of flow, and Discrete Element Method (DEM) for the description of particles.

The coupling of CFD-DEM is commonly done using one of three strategies: (i) one-way coupling, where only the fluid influence on the particle motion is considered; (ii) two-way coupling, which accounts for the mutual interactions between fluid and particles but neglects the particle-particle interactions; and (iii) four-way coupling, which additionally considers particle–particle interactions.

Recently, we have been developing a four-way coupled CFD-DEM solver called openHFDIB-DEM [3], which is implemented as a custom extension for the OpenFOAM C++ framework. The software is detailed in [4]. It is designed as a CFD-DEM library for both pure DEM and CFD-DEM applications; the CFD-DEM library primarily focuses on four-way coupled particle-resolved DNS simulations for coarse-grained slurry flows. In the present contribution, we will focus on pure DEM because the code was extended by a new formulation of a contact model for simulations of granular matter consisting of arbitrarily shaped polyhedral particles represented by triangulated surfaces (STL).

In its original formulation, DEM was proposed only to account for spheres, with easily described geometry using only two parameters: center position and radius, while contact forces were calculated analytically using Hertzian contact theory [5], scaling them proportionally to the length of the particle overlap. However, since spheres are not prevalent, more realistic geometrical representations with varying levels of fidelity are required. The most widely used shape models can be divided into three types: (i) the multisphere model, (ii) superquadrics, and (iii) polyhedral-based particles [6]. Models (i) and (ii) are particularly suited for particles with smooth, curved surfaces, benefiting from the standard contact model with minor modifications. On the other hand, the polyhedral model is the most general and ideal for representing particles with sharp edges and flat faces [7]. On the other hand, this approach demands estimation of particle properties such as mass, center of mass, and moment of inertia, along with significant adjustments to contact detection and force calculation with respect to particle overlap characterization.

The main novelty of this contribution is focused on the recent reformulation of the contact model and its alignment with the LIGGGHTS DEM solver [8]. As a demonstration, we provide simulation results for repose angle tests. We first analyze spherical particles, comparing the results of openHFDIB-DEM with those of LIGGGHTS, as shown in Figure 1. The comparison is then extended to non-convex polyhedral particles (Figure 2). These cases were chosen because of the significant role of tangential forces in the overall behavior of the system. The differences in behavior between spherical and non-spherical particles are apparent. Thus, a correct DEM implementation is of utmost importance for large CFD-DEM simulations of coarse-grain slurry flows. More details and results will be presented at the conference presentation.

Figure 1: Repose angle ($\tilde{\alpha}$) study results, displayed as overlay in end time $t = 2$ s for the two tested solvers and three different friction coefficients (μ). The study contained 1700 particles.

Figure 2: Results of repose angle ($\tilde{\alpha}$) study, displayed in end time $t = 2$ s for the non-convex STL-based particles and three different friction coefficients (μ). The study contained 770 particles.

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A NUMERICAL FRAMEWORK FOR WEAR ANALYSIS OF ROUGH SURFACE CONTACTS ACROSS LUBRICATION REGIMES

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Keywords: Numerical wear analysis, Lubricated contacts, Rough Surfaces, Archard model, Finite Area Method, *foam-extend*

The presence of wear in lubricated tribological systems, and its effect on mechanical component performance, is well-documented. Traditional approaches to studying wear often rely on experimental methods, which, although effective, are costly and complex compared to numerical alternatives. Numerical simulations offer enhanced efficiency and provide deeper insights into wear mechanisms under various lubrication regimes.

Archard [1, 2] defined wear as the progressive loss of material due to mechanical interaction at surface asperities during relative motion, typically sliding or rolling. Adhesive wear is one of the predominant forms of wear in mechanical systems [3] and, as such, is the focus of this research. The Archard Wear Model, widely recognized for its general applicability [4], serves as the foundation for the wear model used in this work.

In this research, a numerical framework based on the Finite Area Method (FAM) [5] and implemented in *foam-extend* is presented for simulating wear of rough surfaces under varying lubrication regimes. The model couples a wear algorithm based on Archard's law with a deterministic asperity contact model, enabling the use of actual measured surface profiles. The lubrication effects are captured by solving a modified Reynolds equation with cavitation modelling [6], formulated within the Finite Area framework. Surface evolution due to wear is modeled by iteratively updating the surface geometry based on contact and lubrication parameters.

Validation was conducted using several tribological test cases, including Pin-On-Disc and Ring-On-Block configurations. Numerical results demonstrated excellent agreement with data from the literature in terms of contact pressure distribution, wear depth, and surface evolution. Additional test cases, such as Ball-On-Flat and Ring-On-Ring setups using real surface scans, further confirmed the ability of the model to predict wear progression under both dry and lubricated contact conditions. Finally, the framework was applied to simulate wear in a lubricated Ball-On-Disc configuration using Shell Turbo T68 oil, accurately capturing lubrication regime transitions from mixed to near-boundary lubrication.

The developed wear framework shows robust performance across various tribological scenarios, supporting its applicability for advanced wear prediction and surface evolution studies in lubricated contact problems.

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Progress in Design and Analysis of Fusion Power Plant Breeder Blanket Systems using OpenFOAM

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Keywords: Fusion, Blankets, Multiphase, MHD, Thermal-Hydraulics

Fusion power plants are a potential key technology on the road to achieving a net zero, sustainable future. However, they must be commercially viable and a significant engineering effort is essential to realise the potential of fusion energy.

One of the most vital components to a successful magnetic confinement fusion concept is the breeder blanket. This component is multi-purpose and needs to be able to cope with the heat loads of close plasma proximity and those generated by fusion neutrons, as well as generating a sufficient amount of tritium to complete the fuel cycle and do all the above with maximal efficiency.

The design and analysis of breeder blankets is a challenging multiphysics problem. From a fluid dynamics perspective they include a high heat flux thermal-hydraulics problem, which might include phase changes, coupled bi-directionally to the neutronics through doppler broadening. Additionally, where liquid metals are used as a breeder or multiplier material, magnetohydrodynamic effects are also significant due to the strong magnetic field and flowing conductive fluid. To successfully model such a coupled system computationally, a scalable solver is required.

As part of our wide ranging digital engineering program at UKAEA, we use OpenFOAM as a scalable and well established finite volume code. The open source nature of the framework and file formats enables easy coupling into our high performance engineering software ecosystem. In particular here we present our progress on advanced heat transfer modelling and magnetohydrodynamics using publicly available OpenFOAM solvers.

For a heat transfer problem representative of the high heat flux conditions experienced by breeder blankets in proximity to the plasma, we present our progress on modelling multiphase flow through a Hypervapotron[1]. As a design that leverages phase changes this presents an excellent target for both development and demonstration of capability. Here we incrementally build complexity, starting with fluid flow, adding heat transport and finally inclusion of multiphase boiling models.

In our investigation of OpenFOAM's magnetohydrodynamics capability, we look first at verification and validation against the known solutions of Shercliff and Hunt. This is then extended to comparison with experimental magnetohydrodynamics rigs at UKAEA, including a cross-comparison and benchmarking against other available codes.

Our investigation and development of OpenFOAM has found it to be scalable and suitable for use on our high performance computing clusters[2]. This has significant benefits in enabling engineering analysis in greater detail, higher accuracy and physical complexity. Not only is it possible to scale up, it is also trivial to scale out design simulations onto any available hardware, allowing for simulation driven design that fully incorporates complexity and uncertainty quantification from the outset.

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EFFICIENT CFD-PBM APPROACH FOR MODELLING COOLING CRYSTALLIZATION SCALE-UP PROCESSES

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Keywords: *Crystallization, Reactors, PBM, CFD, Pharmaceutical*

1 Motivations

Crystallization is a fundamental process in which solid crystals form from a solution, it plays a crucial role in the pharmaceutical industry, as most Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs) are manufactured or purified through crystallization. Controlling this process is challenging but it is key to ensure consistent drug quality, optimizing yield and achieving the desired purity of pharmaceutical compounds. For these reasons, the current work aims to develop a numerical tool able to accurately represent crystallization processes using an efficient 3-step CFD-PBM model.

2 Fundamental principles

Primary nucleation occurs when the supersaturation zone is reached, primary nucleation can be homogeneous (in the bulk of the flow) and/or heterogeneous (on foreign solid surfaces). On the other hand, secondary nucleation - which consists of new nuclei being formed in the presence of existing crystals - takes place in both the metastable and supersaturation zones [1]. These zones are represented in Figure 1, where the black line is the solubility, and the orange line is the supersolubility.

Figure 1: Representation of the characteristic crystallization zones

Growth of existing nuclei and crystals takes place in both the metastable and supersaturated zones and can be either size-independent or size-dependent based on the compound studied. Growth is defined by Zhang et al. [2] as the process in which solute molecules are transported to the particle surface, then oriented and incorporated into the particle lattice.

3 Model presentation

The flow mixing model is based on the Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) approach and on Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) turbulence modelling, using the $k - \omega$ SST turbulence model. The heat transfer model uses the steady-state flow field computed with the mixing model and solves only the energy equation without recomputing the flow field. This

strategy has been adopted due to the significant differences in the characteristic times between mixing (\sim seconds) and cooling (\sim hours). The heat transfer model includes a custom boundary condition that computes the energy transfer inside the reactor walls since the cooling is performed using a jacket in which the reactor is positioned. Finally, the 1D-PBM model has been developed in Python, it solves the Number Density Function (NDF) of particle sizes in different bins. It includes primary and secondary nucleation, size-independent and size-dependent growth as well as seeding. The PBM model takes the average tank temperature computed using the heat transfer model as input and computes the evolution of the PSD through time.

4 Demonstration case

A scale-up demonstration case is presented, showing how the model can be used to control a scale-up process from a 100 mL lab-scale reactor to a 20 L production-scale plant. The compound simulated is L-Glutamic Acid (LGA) for which crystallization kinetic data is available in the literature [3]. The simulation results show that with the same input cooling ramp the median crystal size obtained differs by almost 10%, and by modifying the solute concentration accordingly, it is possible to recover the initial median crystal size.

Figure 2: Different Crystal Size Distribution (CSD) obtained with different input parameters

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrates that an efficient three-step approach can be used to simulate cooling crystallization processes with a low computational effort. OpenFOAM proves to be a great tool for such simulations, allowing quick and easy development of custom boundary conditions. This work is the foundation for a potential future development of a coupled CFD-PBM solver that would compute the spatial crystallization evolution in the tank. Finally, the present work highlights several key points that are crucial in crystallization modelling such as the impact of stirring speed, cooling ramp, growth dispersion, wall roughness and spatial non-uniformities that are often neglected in the literature when it comes to developing crystallization PBM solvers.

Acknowledgments

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TURBULENT GAS-LIQUID SIMULATIONS OF JET KNIFE FOR HOT-DIP GALVANIZING OF WIRES

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Keywords: Hot-dip galvanising, Large eddy simulation, Volume of fraction, Jet knife, Turbulence modeling

Introduction

Hot-dip galvanising is a widely employed method for protecting steel structures from corrosion by applying a durable zinc coating. During the galvanising process, steel wires are immersed in molten zinc at high temperatures and then withdrawn at controlled speeds, dragging a layer of liquid zinc along their surfaces [1]. To regulate the coating thickness, gas jets are directed onto the moving wire, stripping excess zinc and returning it to the bath. Understanding the fluid dynamic interactions between the liquid zinc and the gas jets is critical for optimising coating uniformity and minimising surface defects, as the wire's coating properties (uniformity and concentricity of the coating thickness) are highly dependent on jet parameters: fluctuating pressure and shear stress associated with the unsteadiness of the turbulence in the jet are underlying causes of waviness on the coating surface [2, 3, 4]. In this work, a Large Eddy Simulation coupled with a Volume of Fluid (LES-VOF) approach is employed to investigate the pressure distributions around the wire at the impingement region, as well as the resulting coating thickness and its non-uniformity at the nozzle exit.

Mesh independence analysis was conducted using three grids containing approximately 4.9k, 1.9M, and 6.5M cells. A cylindrical mesh refinement was applied around the jet and near the wire to accurately resolve turbulent structures. Figure 1a shows the refined 6.5M-cell mesh. The incompressible Navier–Stokes equations were solved using spatial filtering for Large Eddy Simulation (LES), with the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-viscosity (WALE) subgrid-scale model to capture unresolved turbulence stresses. Simulations were carried out using OpenFOAM v2312, employing a second-order Gauss linear scheme for spatial discretisation and a second-order backward scheme for time integration. Figure 1b illustrates the instantaneous velocity field in the jet region. The jet exhibits a flapping motion, which induces pressure oscillations at the impingement zone and can potentially lead to variations in the final coating thickness on the wire.

(a) Refined 6.5M-cell mesh around the jet and wire

(b) Instantaneous velocity field showing jet flapping

Figure 1: (a) Computational mesh and (b) velocity contours at the jet impingement region.

Figure 2a shows the effect of wire speed on the coating thickness at the exit. As expected, increasing the wire speed raises the average coating thickness but also leads to greater variation across the surface. On the other hand, Figure 2b presents the effect of flow rate. While an increase in flow rate results in a reduction in the overall coating thickness, the variation in thickness remains relatively unchanged.

Figure 2: Time evolution of coating thickness at the exit under varying wire speed and flow rate conditions.

Figure 3 shows the frequency analysis of the coating thickness and pressure fluctuations. In Fig. 3a, the frequency spectrum of the coating thickness at the exit is presented, while Fig. 3b displays the frequency of pressure at the impingement point. As observed, both thickness and pressure signals exhibit two dominant peaks around 4 Hz and 18 Hz. The presence of matching peaks in both spectra suggests a strong correlation between pressure fluctuations and coating thickness variations. This supports the hypothesis that pressure fluctuations are the main driver of thickness instability at the exit.

Figure 3: Frequency analysis of coating thickness and pressure fluctuations.

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PORTING AND VALIDATING AN OPENFOAM SOLVER FOR URBAN MICROCLIMATE SIMULATION IN TROPICAL REGIONS

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Keywords: *Environmental flow; urban microclimate; thermal multi-region simulation; urban simulation.*

Urban microclimate refers to the local atmospheric conditions within urban areas that differ from the surrounding regions, often resulting in slight to substantial temperature variations. Accurately assessing this process is crucial for defining strategies to ensure pedestrian thermal comfort. In addition to physical sensors placed strategically, numerical simulations play a vital role in this field. There are open-source codes like PALM-4U [1] and commercial software like ENVI-met dedicated to these simulations.

In recent years, OpenFOAM has also been utilized in this area. One framework, *urbanMicroclimateFoam (uMF)* [2], is an open-source solver for modeling coupled physical processes in urban microclimates, developed by a team from the Department of Mechanical and Process Engineering at ETH Zurich. It is a multi-region solver that includes an air subdomain and subdomains for porous urban building materials. A computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model addresses turbulent, convective airflow and heat and moisture transport in the air subdomain, while a coupled heat and moisture (HAM) transport model manages the absorption, transport, and storage of heat and moisture in the porous building materials.

The original version of *uMF* is implemented for the OpenFOAM Foundation using versions 6 to 8, incorporating its own implementation of the view factor radiation model, including solar load effects. Additionally, the cases where the code is typically applied are generally related to non-tropical areas using relatively simple meshes and domains. This work ports *uMF* to OpenFOAM v24.06, aiming to leverage recent implementations of the view factor radiation model and solar load calculations, enabling the simulation of complex domains at a reasonable computational cost.

In *uMF*, special boundary conditions transfer information between regions, along with solvers for each region, pre- and post-processing utilities, and libraries for material and radiation models. Since the standard view factor model in OF v24.06 includes all necessary radiation implementations, the challenge was to adapt the radiation structures in *uMF*, which differ significantly between OF Foundation v8 and OF v24.06. After porting all relevant components to the code, validation was performed to ensure the accuracy of the work within a complex simulation framework designed to model various interconnected physical phenomena.

Figure 1: Domain used in the simulation: the red buildings represent the AOI, while the grey buildings, in the distant zone, are modeled as impermeable porous regions.

The area around the sensors, where accuracy is crucial for evaluating thermal comfort, is called the area of interest (AOI). The mesh in this area is more refined. In addition to the AOI, some distant structures are relevant to the flow features. To incorporate the effects of these structures on the flow without significantly increasing computational costs, these buildings are treated as impermeable porous regions, where the velocity is null, the temperature is constant (28 °C), and the mesh is coarser. The AOI is represented by the red structures in Fig. 1, while the distant buildings modeled as porous blocks are shown in grey.

For validation, an area of Singapore, a tropical country with weather conditions very different from Europe (where the original version of *uMF* was primarily tested), was used. Data from three sensors in the area, including temperature, humidity, and wind

speed inside the AOI from June 2020, were provided.

The simulation utilized the ported *uMF*, coupled with the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) multi-layer urban canopy model (MLUCM). The coupling between the WRF-MLUCM mesoscale model and *uMF* is achieved through one-way coupling from the WRF simulation output into the initial and boundary conditions of *uMF*.

Figure 2: Ambient temperature over time in sensors (a) P1, (b) P2, and (c) P3.

Table 1: Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between *uMF* and sensor data

Sensor	RMSE [°C]
P1	1.338
P2	1.044
P3	1.134

The numerical results of air temperature using *uMF* are presented in Fig. 2 for the three sensors. Tab. 1 shows the root mean square error (RMSE), a quantitative measure for evaluating result quality. The RMSE is calculated considering N , the number of points over time, by

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (T_{numerical} - T_{measured})^2}. \quad (1)$$

As shown in Fig. 2 and Tab. 1, the temperature evolution over three diurnal cycles aligns well with the sensor measurements. These results from a complex case study enhance confidence in the code porting, the standard view factor radiation model with the solar calculator in OF v24.06, and the adopted methodology (e.g., treating distant structures as impermeable porous regions). Some differences between the measurements and *uMF* at the beginning and end of the simulations stem from the boundary conditions of the WRF mesoscale model, which do not fully replicate the existing weather conditions (e.g., cloud cover levels). Another source of the observed minor differences is that in the final hours of the last day the sensor data indicate precipitation, which is not yet addressed by the calculation framework.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A PRECICE ADAPTER FOR FOAM EXTEND

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Drilling is essential for the access to sub-surface energy resources, such as oil, gas and geothermal heat. Optimal drilling operations require an efficient transport of cuttings from the drill-bit to the surface. As drilling often reaches several kilometers below the surface, in-situ measurements of drilling parameters are very challenging. Therefore, limited field knowledge about the underlying phenomena exists and many investigations rely on simplified laboratory setups and detailed software-based simulations.

Besides, technical challenges, drilling projects are always very costly, e.g. in case of deep geothermal wells only the drilling costs account for at least 50% of the total project costs [1]. Large shares of these costs are caused by non-productive time during the drilling process due to damages to underground equipment or borehole integrity issues. These can cause days for pulling out and tripping in again the drill string or re-conditioning of the borehole. Particular importance in these fatigue processes are lateral vibrations of the drill string. Previous work already analyzed different factors influencing the damping of drill string vibrations, e.g. drilling mud, fluid flows, rotation.

The research problem studied by the author attempts to evaluate the influence of the cuttings transport on the damping of lateral vibrations. Due to the nature of the research question, this requires a simulation consisting both of particle transport and fluid-structure interaction. In a previous workshop presentation, the author discussed future directions of a solver for coupled fluid-structure-interaction and particle transport simulations [2].

Figure 1: Approach for coupling solid solvers from solids4Foam and the particle solver LIGGGHTS®-PFM

The multiphysics library preCICE [3] was selected as method to achieve the intended coupling. Since the OpenFOAM workshop presentation in 2023, the software development of preCICE and the OpenFOAM flavour foam-extend continued which calls for changes to the legacy adapter of foam-extend for the new preCICE version [4]. The new development is based on the existing precice OpenFOAM adapter [5]. The presentation discusses the differences between OpenFOAM.org and foam-extend in terms of porting the adapter. Furthermore, adjustments for the different foam-extend versions and the testing approach are presented. Currently, the adapter is developed with support for the foam-extend versions 4.0, 4.1, 5.0 and the development branch. The support for these versions is realized by containerizing the installations for reproducible testing. Additionally, the container approach simplifies for the support of older versions which require nowadays unsupported versions of dependencies. The presentation will close with a small demonstration of a test-case running on the supported versions of foam-extend.

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COUPLING PLASMA-INDUCED EHD FORCES WITH OPENFOAM FOR SCALABLE FLOW CONTROL IN PLASMA CATALYSIS REACTORS

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Keywords: plasma catalysis, electrohydrodynamic force, gas recycling, flow control

Plasma catalysis is an emerging solution for enabling low-temperature, non-equilibrium chemical conversion of greenhouse gases such as CO₂, CH₄, and CF₄ into value-added products. This approach offers a promising path toward sustainable chemical production, particularly within defossilization and circular carbon strategies. By operating under low temperature conditions and using renewable electricity as an energy source, plasma-assisted processes can overcome thermodynamic limitations of conventional catalysis and open new pathways for efficient CO₂ utilization. Applications include dry reforming of methane (DRM), methanol synthesis, and the recycling of exhaust gases from the semiconductor industry - sectors with high carbon footprints and a strong need for innovation.

A key factor in plasma-catalytic reactor performance is the precise control of the gas flow, which affects residence time, mixing, and the targeted delivery of activated species to catalytic zones. Without flow control, both energy and material efficiency are at risk. At enaDyne, we develop scalable reactor architectures using different plasma sources such as surface dielectric barrier discharges (sDBD). These systems are compact, robust, and well-established in the flow control community for their ability to manipulate gas motion via electrohydrodynamic (EHD) forces. Their dual role - both activating chemistry and shaping flow—makes them ideal for process-intensified reactor concepts.

Figure 1: Schematic of a modular plasma-catalytic reactor with ten parallel sDBD plates. A gas mixture (e.g., CO₂ + CH₄) flows through the reactor and is converted into products such as methanol. The plasma ignition induces local vortices that couple with the gas flow and affect species transport. The dashed blue rectangle indicates the region of interest analyzed in this work, focusing on flow dynamics between two adjacent sDBD electrodes. [1]

Figure 1 shows a modular reactor concept comprising ten parallel sDBD plates, through which a gas mixture such as CO₂ and CH₄ is converted into methanol - a green chemical and potential renewable fuel. During plasma ignition, local vortices are generated that interact strongly with the incoming flow, producing a coupled system where plasma and gas dynamics are intrinsically linked. This interaction influences the spatial distribution of reactive species, energy input, and ultimately, conversion efficiency. A region of interest (ROI) - marked with a blue dashed rectangle - highlights the domain between two sDBD electrodes. This ROI forms the basis for our detailed numerical investigation aimed at understanding and optimizing flow control in the vicinity of active plasma zones.

To characterize the plasma behavior at the electrode scale, we perform detailed simulations using a 2D fluid plasma code [1,2,3]. These simulations resolve space- and time-dependent electric fields, charge densities, reaction kinetics, and transport processes. Of particular interest is the resulting EHD force [1,3], which is extracted and transferred to the flow simulation. Further output fields - such as gas temperature or densities of reactive species (e.g., atomic oxygen, ozone, vibrationally excited CO₂) - are available for future coupling strategies. This physically detailed plasma data provides the foundation for understanding how local discharge behavior influences reactor-scale phenomena.

In order to explore larger spatial domains beyond the reach of plasma simulation, we integrate key results from the 2D plasma simulation into OpenFOAM. The EHD force is implemented as a source term in the momentum equations, enabling the study of plasma-driven flow modification at the reactor scale. The present study focuses on two-dimensional slices of the ROI; however, the framework is designed for future extension to three-dimensional models that account for real reactor geometries, edge effects, and non-uniform boundary conditions. By simulating these plasma-induced effects in OpenFOAM, we aim to support design optimization, control strategies, and scale-up scenarios for advanced plasma-catalytic reactors.

The overarching objective of this study is to understand how plasma-induced flow structures influence transport phenomena and spatial reactivity in plasma-catalytic systems. We focus on numerically analyzing the interplay between electrohydrodynamic (EHD) forces and convective transport within a representative domain between two sDBD electrodes. By resolving the flow patterns under the influence of plasma actuation, we aim to assess how the distribution of velocity, residence time, and species transport can be modified to support reaction efficiency and reactor design. The developed simulation framework enables the systematic evaluation of how plasma-induced flow control affects zone separation, species localization, and the delivery of reactants to catalytically active surfaces.

This hybrid simulation approach - combining detailed plasma modeling with scalable CFD in OpenFOAM - provides a powerful framework for the development of next-generation plasma-catalytic reactors. Future work will focus on bidirectional coupling (e.g., incorporating temperature and chemistry feedback), validation against experimental data, and the development of reduced models for rapid design iteration. The integration of plasma-induced forces into OpenFOAM represents a key step toward predictive, application-oriented reactor engineering for CO₂ utilization and green chemical production.

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AN OPEN-SOURCE CFD FRAMEWORK FOR OPEN ABSORPTION PROCESSES

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Keywords: open absorption, liquid desiccant, dehumidification, falling film

Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is widely applied to analyze and optimize open absorption systems such as falling film absorbers. However, most studies rely on in-house or commercial software, limiting reproducibility and broader access [1]. To address this, we developed an open-source CFD framework based on OpenFOAM for simulating coupled heat and mass transfer in open absorption processes. The solver, *openAbsorptionSolver*, is openly available at <https://github.com/FelixHochwallnerAIT/openAbsorptionSolver> and has been validated against experimental measurements in a previous work [2].

The *openAbsorptionSolver* resolves temperature and species transport in a gas-liquid system with a sharp interface. A minimal computational domain for modeling absorption in falling film absorbers with vertical plates, illustrated in Figure 1, consists of a desiccant film flowing down a wall and half of the adjacent air channel. The solver is not restricted to this geometry and can be extended to more complex setups, as has been shown in [3].

Figure 1: Minimal computational domain for modeling absorption in falling film absorbers: liquid desiccant falling film on a wall (left) and half of the adjacent air channel (right).

To achieve computational efficiency while maintaining sufficient physical realism, the following assumptions are applied:

- Ideal gas behavior is assumed for air and water vapor.
- All thermophysical properties except water vapour pressure are assumed to be constant and evaluated at inlet conditions.
- Local thermodynamic equilibrium is enforced at the interface.
- The liquid film is flat and undeformable; surface waves and film thickness variations are not resolved.
- The absorbent is non-volatile, allowing unidirectional water vapor transport from air to solution.
- Air flow is pressure-driven and gravitational effects are neglected in the gas phase.

These assumptions allow the flow to be decoupled from the absorption problem, optimizing computational efficiency - particularly valuable for parametric studies. The solver can be operated both steady-state and transient.

Heat and mass transfer are modeled by convection–diffusion equations for temperature and species transport:

$$\frac{\partial T_i}{\partial t} + \vec{u}_i \cdot \nabla T_i = \kappa_i \nabla^2 T_i, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \chi_{w,i}}{\partial t} + \vec{u}_i \cdot \nabla \chi_{w,i} = D_i \nabla^2 \chi_{w,i}, \quad (2)$$

where T_i denotes the temperature, $\chi_{w,i}$ the water mass fraction, κ_i the thermal diffusivity, and D_i the binary diffusion coefficient in region $i = a$ (air) or s (solution). The air and solution domains are solved sequentially within each timestep or iteration until convergence is achieved.

At the gas-liquid interface, coupling conditions enforce mass and energy conservation and local thermodynamic equilibrium. Temperature equilibrium is imposed by setting the air and solution temperatures equal at the interface. Vapor pressure equilibrium is achieved by computing the water vapor pressure at the film surface from the solution temperature and concentration, which is then used to set the specific humidity of the air at the film surface via the ideal gas law.

The heat flux jump across the interface accounts for latent heat transfer:

$$\lambda_s \partial_n T_s - \lambda_a \partial_n T_a = \dot{\varphi} (h_s - h_a), \quad (3)$$

where λ_i is the thermal conductivity, $\dot{\varphi}$ the mass flux, and $\Delta h_v = h_a - h_s$ the latent heat of vaporization.

Mass flux coupling follows from unidirectional vapor diffusion and results in the Eckert-Schneider relation:

$$\dot{\varphi} = -\frac{\rho_s D_s \partial_n \chi_{w,s}}{1 - \chi_{w,s}} = -\frac{\rho_a D_a \partial_n \chi_{w,a}}{1 - \chi_{w,a}}. \quad (4)$$

Due to its nonlinearity, this interface coupling is implemented using Picard iterations with under-relaxation to ensure numerical stability.

The *openAbsorptionSolver* is designed with modularity and extensibility in mind. Python scripts in the repository allow fully scriptable mesh generation and boundary setup, and provide test cases with documentation to support rapid adoption. The code can be easily extended to support alternative mass flux coupling methods, variable fluid properties, or interfacial shear modeling. As the most promising extension, the implementation of film thickness variations and surface instabilities is highly recommended [4]. The solver provides a practical platform for CFD research on open absorption systems and aims to foster community collaboration in this field.

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COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF OIL DISTRIBUTION ON ELECTRIC MOTOR SHAFT BEARINGS USING SPH AND CFD METHODOLOGIES

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Keywords: *Multiphysics Analysis, Coupling CFD-SPH, Lubrification, VoF, RBM, ePowertrain*

The efficient lubrication of electric motor shaft bearings is critical for minimizing wear and ensuring operational reliability. This study presents a comparative analysis of oil wetting distribution on bearing elements using different numerical methodologies: Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH), Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), and a coupled CFD-SPH approach. The simulations were conducted using ANSA-SPH for Lagrangian particle-based modelling and OpenFOAM for CFD multiphase flow analysis.

Three modelling strategies were employed: (i) SPH single-phase oil flow simulation, (ii) CFD-based multiphase modelling, and (iii) a hybrid approach coupling CFD-computed air velocity field with SPH oil distribution. Each method was evaluated in terms of wetting coverage accuracy, computational complexity, and simulation efficiency.

The results highlight the strengths and limitations of each approach, revealing differences in predicted oil behaviour and wetting of bearing components. While CFD is the best choice when a detailed representation of multiphase interactions or a study of fine design features is needed, however, it can be computationally intensive and very sensitive to mesh resolution. In contrast, SPH offers robust handling of free-surface flows and dynamic interfaces, but with limitations in capturing air interaction. The coupled methodology presents a balanced compromise, enhancing realism without the full computational burden of a fully resolved multiphase CFD simulation.

This study provides valuable insights for selecting appropriate modelling strategies for bearing lubrication analysis, especially in early design stages where trade-offs between accuracy and efficiency are crucial.

Figure 1: Velocity field and streamlines in the considered domain

A HIGH-PERFORMANCE MULTIPHYSICS SIMULATION FRAMEWORK BASED ON OPEN-SOURCE CFD FOR LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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Keywords: lithium-ion battery, multi-domain coupling, multi-physics coupling, simulation framework

The development of battery design is transitioning from traditional trial-and-error method to model-based virtual simulation, significantly enhancing efficiency and reducing costs. The core of simulation lies in high-performance numerical solver. This study develops an electrochemical-thermal parallel solver tailored for lithium-ion batteries based on the open-source CFD platform OpenFOAM. This solver overcomes the theoretical limitations of the P2D model, by innovatively adopting heterogeneous model. Compared to the P2D model, this approach provides a more detailed description of the microstructural of the porous electrode, including solid-liquid phase separation, solid-solid partitioning, particle size distribution, and non-uniform porosity. Additionally, due to its significantly lower computational requirements compared to three-dimensional reconstruction model, particle packing model is more suitable for industrial application.

Figure 1: Multi physics simulation framework based on OpenFOAM for lithium-ion batteries

Lithium-ion batteries constitute a multi-scale, multi-physics coupled system characterized by hierarchical architectures spanning primary particles (nm-scale) to porous electrodes (μm -scale). Their complex internal processes involve mass/charge transport, ion migration and diffusion, and interfacial electrochemical reactions. This study has developed an integrated electro-thermal-aging coupling model that comprehensively simulates both short-term electrothermal behaviour and long-term degradation phenomena. The multi physical fields couple through bidirectional interactions: the electrochemical module calculates real-time heat generation, which feeds into thermal simulations governed by energy conservation laws, while temperature-dependent kinetic parameters will be dynamically modified by Arrhenius relationships. Concurrently, aging sub-model account for degradation mechanisms such as SEI growth, lithium plating, and active material loss, which alter critical parameters like interfacial resistance, active surface area, and porosity. These aging-induced changes further modulate electrochemical and thermal behaviours, while temperature reciprocally influences degradation kinetics through thermally activated side reactions, thereby achieving fully coupled electro-thermal-aging predictions across operational timelines.

The increasing demand for higher specific energy in lithium-ion batteries has driven the adoption of silicon-based materials, yet the substantial volume expansion during lithiation/delithiation poses significant challenges to battery design and longevity, particularly in rigid-shell configurations and large-format cells where mechanical effects critically impact stability and cycle life. Building upon existing electro-thermal-aging modules, this framework focuses on the mechanical interactions of high-expansion materials such as sulfur-based cathode and silicon-rich anode. Conventional mechanical-electrochemical models, limited by small-strain assumptions and oversimplified multi-scale representations, inadequately bridge particle-level expansion behaviours to electrode-level predictions. To address these limitations, the proposed framework integrates dynamic structural evolution, such as porosity, electrochemically active area, tortuosity, during lithium-ion intercalation, coupled with stress-dependent ion transport mechanisms. By resolving multi-scale interactions, the model aims to capture critical phenomena such as pore collapse and particle fracture, while

incorporating strain-modulated ionic diffusivity and reaction kinetics to advance predictive capabilities for stress-driven degradation in next-generation high-energy systems.

Validation against experimental data and COMSOL demonstrates high accuracy, ensuring rigorous satisfaction of conservation laws and flux continuity. To address the significant computational demands of the heterogeneous model, the solver utilizes an efficient parallel computing strategy, substantially enhancing computational efficiency. Benefiting from the robust CFD capabilities of OpenFOAM, the proposed battery simulation framework exhibits excellent multi-physics coupling capabilities. Furthermore, the layered and modular architecture ensures scalability and versatility, making it applicable to various electrochemical systems, including lithium-ion batteries, solid-state batteries and sodium-ion batteries. To sum up, this study provides a universal foundation for the simulation of electrochemical devices, offering a powerful tool for the design and optimization of next-generation high-power batteries.

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Complex flow phenomena

NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF PATIENT TECHNIQUE EFFECTS ON PMDI PERFORMANCE

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Keywords: *Drug delivery, lungs, pMDI*

Introduction

Pressurized Metered Dose Inhalers, or pMDIs, are devices widely used in the treatment of pulmonary diseases, such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): using a propellant, a precise dose is administered when the device is activated by the patient itself. The effectiveness of the device could be measured in terms of the dose fraction that can reach the deeper airways. In the present work, the performance of a pMDI will be investigated through the use of numerical CFD simulations, calculating the air flow inside the airways, described by a Eulerian approach, and the drug delivery and deposition into the lungs, described through a Lagrangian approach. Then, a sensitivity analysis of the performance to several parameters related to the patient technique (inhalation profile, device position, inhalation timing) has been performed to evaluate the possible criticality for these devices. A numerical model has been developed through OpenFOAM, preliminary tested and used to perform the required simulations.

Numerical model

Based on the work of Spasov et al. [1] [2], the OpenFOAM model has been developed to simulate the pMDI coupled within the airways. The numerical mesh has been generated through `snappyHexMesh`, based on the mesh sensitivity analysis performed in [1]. The model is a Euler-Lagrange one: the air flow, due to the patient's inhalation, is represented through the Eulerian approach, while the drug is represented through a Lagrangian approach. The Eulerian model represents an incompressible and turbulent flow, where only the mean effect of the turbulence is represented, with an unsteady approach. The employed RANS turbulence model is the `kOmegaSST`, as suggested by the majority of the authors involved in the field. A fixed time step of $5e-5$ s has been imposed to have a mean `maxCo` lower than 1 [1]. Lastly, the model is able to represent different inhalation profiles (steady, time-dependent and with different mean flow rates). The outflow splitting into the lung lobes has been imposed according to [3], to represent a physiological flow distribution. The Lagrangian model is a one-way coupled and is able to represent the mean pMDI plume feature, such as plume cone angle, plume velocity and plume duration. All the parameters have been set in agreement with the experiments performed on a specific pMDI. The main forces acting on the particles have been taken into account: gravity, spherical drag, Brownian motion (due to the small diameter of the simulated particles) and the stochastic dispersion. The wall-particle interaction has been modeled through the `stick` algorithm of OpenFOAM: the particles that impact the boundaries are trapped there and considered deposited. The time-step employed to calculate the particles trajectories has been set to be smaller than the relaxation time of the smaller simulated particles. The particles diameters have been selected based on the plume Particles Size Distribution curves, calculated through NGI experiments and specifically modified to take into account the losses on the Induction Port, not considered when the NGI data was elaborated. The PSD has been divided into 15 characteristic diameters and for each one 10k particles have been injected.

Parametric analysis

A first ideal case has been simulated as a reference, considering an inhalation profile with a mean flow rate of 30 l/min, device perfectly horizontal and pMDI actuation perfectly synchronized within the patient inhalation. The performance of the device has been analyzed in terms of extra-thoracic, intra-thoracic, and peripheral deposition, as a percentage of the emitted dose. A parametric analysis has been carried out that includes the effect of the inhalation profile, actuation timing, and device position.

Conclusions

The simulations can predict the drug deposition fraction in each of the regions of interest. The PSD of the deposited fraction can be calculated to analyze the dimensions of the particles deposited in each region. The sensitivity analysis to the main parameters involved will allow one to understand how these parameters affect the performance on the device, showing how good practice in the use of the device can provide or not a better effectiveness of the therapy. For a more robust analysis, several phenomena have yet to be implemented in the model, such as the two-way coupling between fluid and particles and the particles evaporation, to have a more realistic representation of the particles delivery process.

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IMPACT OF HEMODYNAMIC AND STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS ON CEREBRAL ANEURYSM GROWTH: INSIGHTS FROM FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION ANALYSIS

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Keywords: Fluid-Structure interaction, cerebral aneurysm, oscillatory shear index, wall shear stress

Cerebral aneurysms are identified in approximately 2-5% of the population [1]. The rupture of these aneurysms can result in subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH), which is commonly linked to high rates of mortality and morbidity. Research has identified numerous clinical, genetic, morphological, and hemodynamic factors associated with the formation, expansion, and rupture of cerebral aneurysms [2,3,4].

The advancements and increased use of medical imaging technologies have facilitated the detection of a higher number of unruptured aneurysms. This rise in detection necessitates informed decisions regarding treatment. Treatment should predominantly target those aneurysms that are on the verge of rupturing, as the procedures carry significant risks for the patient. Consequently, there is a need for reliable decision-making tools to optimize patient care.

Numerous studies employing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) have revealed significantly different hemodynamic characteristics in ruptured versus unruptured aneurysms [5-7]. Hemodynamic behavior generates mechanical triggers, which subsequently convert to biological signals that drive aneurysm growth and eventually rupture. The geometric configuration of the aneurysm impacts the hemodynamics, and thus, the morphological parameters are influential [5-7]. While many intricate fluid dynamics simulations, including complex flow models, have been executed [2,3,5-7], limited research has focused on structural dynamics assessments [8,9]. Previously, we detailed a method involving fluid-structure interaction (FSI) analysis in OpenFOAM with the solids4Foam library [10], validated through experimental setups [11-13]. This approach enables detailed monitoring of cerebral aneurysm evolution and the quantitative evaluation of changes in aneurysm behavior by comparing medical imaging data from successive examinations.

In this work we analyze with the help of our established FSI workflow important fluid dynamic phenomena like the wall shear stress (WSS) as well as the oscillatory shear index (OSI) as well as structural mechanical parameters for their role in aneurysm growth and ultimately rupture. For this we evaluate the local distribution of these quantities in an aneurysm in its individual growth stages and indicate important changes in fluid dynamics and their influence on the growth as well as rupture process.

Figure 1: Oscillatory Shear Index in the same cerebral aneurysm at different growth stages

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IN-SILICO EVALUATION OF THE PULMONARY ARTERY HYPERTENSION USING CFD SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: CFD; Pulmonary arterial hypertension, Cardiovascular flow, Patient-specific simulation

Cardiovascular diseases encompass a range of conditions impacting the heart and blood vessels and remain a primary cause of mortality globally. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) enables detailed examination of blood flow within the pulmonary arteries and allows for the simulation of different physiological states. This approach provides significant benefits compared to invasive methods during diagnostic and surgical planning stages. This study specifically focuses on analyzing the fluid dynamics of the pulmonary artery by comparing blood flow patterns between a healthy individual and a patient with pulmonary arterial hypertension. We performed CFD simulations with the OpenFOAM C++ library using a purposely developed solver that features the Wind-Kessel model as a pressure boundary condition [1]. This approach, which has been scarcely used in the past for this type of problem, enables a thorough analysis and precise quantification of key fluid-dynamic parameters, such as flow velocity, pressure distribution, and wall shear stress (WSS), with greater accuracy and resolution than traditional simulation and diagnostic methods. The reliability of the method in replicating blood flow was confirmed by comparison with experimental data. A detailed comparative analysis highlights the differences between healthy and pathological cases in hemodynamic terms. Figure 1 reports the average pressures computed over a heartbeat for a sane person and a pathological patient.

Figure 1: Average pressure in a heartbeat for the sane and diseased patients.

The outcomes of this work contribute to enlarging the knowledge of the blood flow characteristics in the human pulmonary artery, revealing substantial differences between the two clinical scenarios investigated and highlighting how

arterial hypertension drastically changes the blood flow. The data analysis highlighted the value of CFD as a complementary tool for understanding, diagnosing, and tracking the pathophysiological processes involved in cardiovascular diseases, demonstrating its potential to aid in the personalization of surgical treatments.

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Particulate fluid dynamics

ASYNCHRONOUS EULER-LAGRANGE COUPLING METHOD

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Keywords: Euler-Lagrange simulations, HPC, Parallel computing, GPUs

Motivation

Clouds play pivotal role in weather and climate, e.g. by influencing precipitation and the Earth's radiative budget. Understanding cloud microphysical and dynamical processes, their interactions, and their coupling with aerosol particles is a challenging task due to the turbulent and vast-scale nature of clouds. Cloud chambers offer a solution by creating controlled supersaturated environments for repeatable experiments [1]. While cloud chambers are valuable for studying cloud microphysics, they are often complemented by simulations, especially for properties without suitable measurement techniques or those challenging to measure across the entire domain.

Such simulations typically employ the Euler-Lagrange (E-L) method, where the continuous phase, such as air, is represented within the Eulerian frame of reference and the dispersed phase, such as discrete droplets, within the Lagrangian frame of reference. In the case of clouds, the two phases significantly affect each other. This is depicted in the model by the so-called two-way coupling that considerably complicates simulations. A representative result of such a simulation for the Pi-Chamber [2] is shown in Figure 1. It shows particle distribution and size as well as the relative humidity in a diagonal plane.

Figure 1: A snapshot of a simulation of the Pi-Chamber showing the relative humidity in a diagonal cross section and a random selection of droplets and their diameters.

While Lagrangian particle tracking is well suited for parallel execution because each particle can be tracked independently, achieving efficient parallel scaling for the two-way coupled E-L method is a well-known challenge [3]. Consequently, tracking all particles in real-world situations, such as an 81 m³ cloud chamber with a particle/droplet concentration of 1000 cm⁻³ (equalling a total of $81 \cdot 10^9$ particles) as currently being designed, is not viable, even with the most powerful computers. The presented approach is pushing these boundaries.

Algorithm Design

The calculations within the Eulerian and Lagrangian frames of reference are executed asynchronously on CPUs and GPUs, respectively. In the novel algorithm, transfer of the Eulerian data that is necessary to perform the Lagrangian particle tracking is initiated as soon as it becomes available and the transfer of the Eulerian source terms calculated within the Lagrangian particle tracking is initiated as soon as the particle tracking is finished. The conservation of exchanged properties such as total liquid mass or total linear momentum are satisfied in a time-average sense. This can be achieved by predicting the Eulerian source terms based on values from previous time steps and correcting them later such that the integral matches what has been calculated by the Lagrangian tracking. Furthermore, the particles are

organised in chunks in a cache friendly way, and a bounding box around each chunk is maintained to facilitate dynamic load balancing across GPUs and to optimise data transfers between GPUs and CPUs.

Results

The algorithm's scalability and efficiency are demonstrated by simulating a 81 m³ cloud chamber containing up to 256 billion particles. Results from this simulation are presented, including information on the parallel efficiency and comparison to reference cases simulated with conventional CPU-based particle tracking in OpenFOAM. Figure 2 shows strong scaling for the cloud chamber discretised into 24 million cells and containing 8 billion droplets. For every 20 cores there is one dedicated Nvidia H100 GPU. The calculations belonging to the tracking algorithm show an almost ideal strong scaling. The overall performance scales approximately up to 512 cores, which is due to scaling limitations of OpenFOAM.

Figure 2: Strong scaling results showing execution time per simulated time step on the left y-axis and time-to-solution for 30'000 iterations on the right.

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LAGRANGIAN PARTICLE TRACKING IN A STIRRED TANK: COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA

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Keywords: Stirred tank, Rushton turbine, Lagrangian, AMI

In chemical engineering, agitated vessels are commonly used to mix multiphase systems. IFP Energies nouvelles develops chemical processes for biofuels creation. In these processes, biomass is decomposed by using enzymes produced by a filamentous fungus, called *Trichoderma Reesei*. This enzyme is able to convert cellulose into glucose, which can further be converted to ethanol through fermentation processes. The opaque fungus culture is grown in aerated agitated vessels. The reactor configuration is that of the standard Rushton stirred tank, abundantly documented in the literature [1]. In order to extrapolate this mixing process from a laboratory scale to an industrial scale, it is essential to be able to model the process at all scales, thanks to Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). In this work, the hydrodynamic characteristics are experimentally obtained at the laboratory scale using Positron Emission Particle Tracking (PEPT) [2, 3], a non-invasive, three-dimensional measurement technique. This data is then compared to CFD simulations.

In the PEPT experimental setup, gamma rays are emitted by a $300\mu\text{m}$ diameter particle radioactively labelled with Fluorine-18 ions. Particle positions are tracked over time, therefore trajectories as well as local velocities and statistics can be determined. Experiments are performed over a long duration (approximately a minimum of 3 hours) to achieve ergodic statistics. Numerically, a similar process is reproduced through tracking of the position of a particle simulated with the `icoUncoupledKinematicCloud` Lagrangian function object, available in the `openfoam.com` distribution. CFD simulations of rotating machinery are modelled with either the Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) [4] steady state approximation or fully unsteady Sliding Mesh (SM) approach. However, for unsteady Lagrangian simulations, only the SM approach is relevant. As the SM approach is highly CPU-intensive, only a short amount of physical time can be achieved numerically, of the order of 5-10 seconds. In order to gather a sufficient amount of particles' tracks for comparison with experiments, thousands of independent Lagrangian particles (i.e. without particle-particle interactions and collisions) are computed simultaneously using CFD.

Figure 1: Instantaneous fields in a glycerol-water system of a Rushton turbine stirred tank of 0.2m diameter.
Left: Q criterion iso-surface coloured by velocity magnitude. **Right:** Lagrangian particles coloured by their velocity

The current work looks at producing simulations for a range of Reynolds numbers ($Re = 500$ to $Re \approx 2000$) comprising of

an aqueous solution of Glycerol (70% (w/w)) exhibiting Newtonian rheological properties. The simulations are conducted on a stirred tank of 0.2 m diameter agitated by a Rushton turbine. The incompressible solver `pimpleFoam` was used in conjunction with a SM solid body rotating grid, with the connection between the rotating and stationary regions being handled by a `cyclicAMI` boundary condition. Figure 1 shows some sample flow field images taken from a simulation at 530 RPM.

Incorporating Lagrangian particle tracking into CFD simulations offers valuable insights that go beyond a typical standard Eulerian approach. As Lagrangian particle data provides a wealth of statistical information, it can be used to identify stagnant or under-mixed zones within the vessel, which is crucial for optimising vessel geometry and performance. Lagrangian particle tracking can also be used for calculating circulation times and circulation locations, gaining an improved in-depth understanding of the mixing efficiency and performance. Scalar and vector velocity fields can also be constructed, allowing for an understanding of local and global hydrodynamics.

The accuracy of particle motion in CFD simulations can be evaluated by directly comparing them with PEPT measurements. One effective approach shown in literature is through the use of parity plots [5], allowing for a voxel-by-voxel assessment of how closely the CFD results align with the PEPT data.

We will also present progress on investigations in applying Lagrangian particle tracking on a series of two-phase, gas-liquid cases. This will highlight the challenges of understanding these systems in both computational and experimental contexts.

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Continuum-particulate modelling of the sediment transport process using coarse-grained CFD-DEM approach

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Keywords: *Sediment Transport, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), Discrete Element Modelling (DEM), Turbulence modelling, Reynolds Average Navier Stokes (RANS) ;*

Alluvial sediment beds are composed of particles of varying shapes and sizes which have been formed by constant erosion and deposition due to fluid flow. Hence, modelling sediment transport is of critical importance in understanding the evolution of such structures. Sediment transport is fundamentally a micro-mechanical phenomena where the movement of particles is caused by inter-particle collisions and fluid-particle interaction forces. The coupling of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Discrete Element Modelling (DEM) thus provides an appropriate tool to study the sediment transport process.

A resolved approach to CFD-DEM, where the CFD mesh is fine enough to resolve the flow around individual particles, would allow the direct evaluation of the fluid-particle interaction forces. Although this approach is more accurate, the computational cost is prohibitive when applied to a large volume of particles which is essential when modelling the sediment transport process. Hence, this study applies a coarse-grained approach, where the particles are substantially smaller than the CFD cell size, and thus fluid-particle interaction forces have to be modelled rather than resolved. This approach allows the modelling of a large number of particles, which is appropriate for sediment transport research. The modified Navier-Stokes equations for the coarse-grained approach are represented in equations 1 and 2. In this study we use the CFDEM package which couples the open source codes OpenFOAM (CFD) and LIGGGHTS (DEM) to perform the simulations.

Continuity equation of the fluid:

$$\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \alpha_i^f}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Momentum equation of the fluid:

$$\rho^f \alpha \left(\frac{\partial u_i^f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial u_i^f u_j^f}{\partial x_j} \right) = \alpha \frac{\partial P}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}^f}{\partial x_j} + F_{ex} + B_f + E_f \quad (2)$$

where α is the porosity, t is the time, x_i is the distance in direction i , u_i^f and u_i^s are the velocity of the fluid and particle in ' i ' direction respectively, P is the pressure, τ_{ij}^f is the shear stress of the fluid in ' i ' direction and experienced in ' j ' face respectively, ρ^f is the density of the fluid and solid, ν^f is the viscosity of the fluid, K is the drag parameter, F_{ex} , B_f and E_f are the fluid-particle interaction forces, body forces and external forces respectively. F_{ex} is the forces determined from the movement of particles in the DEM simulations. At the same time the particle movement is determined in the DEM code from Newton's second law based on particle-particle collision and the fluid-particle interaction forces.

In this study, sediment beds of uniformly distributed spherical particles of diameter (d) 0.1mm, 1mm and 10mm are analysed. The sediment beds of $d = 0.1$ mm, 1mm and 10mm exhibit laminar, buffer and turbulent flow regimes respectively above the bed and the flow regime is a very important driver of particle movement. Turbulence is incorporated in the simulation with the Reynolds Average Navier Stokes (RANS) equations to capture fluid flow behaviour above the bed.

The effect of the inclusion of DEM particles is added as a blocking phase (through a porosity term) and incorporated in the source-code of the turbulence model (k - ϵ). Turbulence dissipation is observed to be essential for the CFD-DEM model, which was similarly essential for the multiphase models [1]. Hence, a turbulence dissipation term is added as a source term in the ϵ equation to damp the turbulence in the sediment bed region [2]. Additionally, a driving shear stress is applied at the top of the CFD domain to maintain the k and ϵ profiles[3]. Hence, with the phase inclusion, the turbulence dissipation and driving shear stress, the profiles of the turbulent kinetic energy (k), dissipation rate (ϵ) and turbulent viscosity match the analytical vertical

Figure 1: Simulation setup with CFD cells and DEM particles

profiles at different points along the length of the sediment bed.

With satisfactory simulation of the fluid flow, the fluid-particle interaction forces are calculated by applying the appropriate drag and lift models in the DEM simulations. In this study, the instance at which sediment transport commences is analysed with the Shields diagram (which is based on the shear stress at the sediment bed). Modification of the shear stress on the bed is carried out based on the Y^+ value of the bed incorporating the logarithmic wall function. For the 3 sediment beds of different sizes analysed in the different flow regimes (0.1mm, 1mm and 10mm) the results show good agreement with the results from the Shields diagram. Hence, this study shows promising application of the coarse-grained CFD-DEM approach in sediment transport research.

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Porous media

MODELING CAKE FILTRATION VIA POROUS MEDIA APPROACH

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Keywords: Porous media, Cake filtration, Modeling

Cake filtration is a widespread form of solid-liquid separation in industrial applications [1]. The flow behavior in cake filtration is commonly described using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), where the cake is often modelled as porous media [2]. The principle of cake filtration, in the present context, is to remove solid particles from a liquid through a porous medium that permits fluid flow while retaining solids. As a slurry approaches the medium, particles accumulate on its surface, progressively forming a filter cake. The thickness of this cake increases over time, making cake formation and growth key dynamics in filtration. Further, cake height and structure might spatially differ. Despite their significance, these dynamic behaviors of the filter cake are often overlooked in existing numerical models. Out-of-the-box available models for porous zones have fixed static coefficients describing the pressure loss, e.g., the often-applied Darcy-Forchheimer model, and are not able to adequately model the dynamics of the process.

To acknowledge the spatial and temporal change of cake resistance, a new porous zone model is presented. The cake height (assuming all solids are retained on the filter, no liquid remains the cake, and a constant porosity) is defined by:

$$h_{cake} = \frac{c_{susp}}{(1-c_{susp})(1-\varepsilon)} \frac{V}{A} \quad (1)$$

where V is the filtrate volume, A the filter area, c_{susp} the solid volume fraction in the suspension and ε the cake porosity. The pressure gradient in the porous zone is then:

$$\nabla p = \frac{(R_m + R_{cake})}{h_{porous}} \mu U \quad (2)$$

Where R_m is the filter media resistance, μ the kinematic viscosity of the liquid, h_{porous} the height of the porous zone and R_{cake} the cake resistance. The cake resistance is based on constant specific cake resistance α_H , is:

$$R_{cake} = \alpha_H h_{cake} \quad (3)$$

The implementation follows the available Darcy-Forchheimer model but is limited to laminar flows, and subsequently, the quadratic contribution is removed. The resulting pressure gradient of each cell is added then as source term in the momentum equation. The presented model is validated with experimental data from two classic dead-end cake filtration experiments [3], [4]. In constant pressure difference experiments, the resulting filtrate volume and resulting cake height were compared to the simulation. Given the cake porosity and the specific cake resistance, the model can accurately simulate the collected filtrate volume over time as well as the cake height.

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MULTISCALE FIXED BED REACTOR MODELING WITH INTERNAL PORE DIFFUSION: COMPARING 3D PRCFD AND 2D POROUS MEDIA SIMULATIONS

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Keywords: Fixed bed reactor; packed bed reactor, pore diffusion; porous media; PRCFD

Fixed (aka packed) bed reactors with porous catalysts are commonly used in the chemical process industries, hence the accurate modeling of these reactors is of interest. The catalytic pellets that comprise the bed are often highly porous to increase the internal surface area, which also increases the number of active catalytic centers. These active catalytic centers are generally accessible only via tortuous and narrow (e.g., micron scale or smaller) passages through which flow is controlled by diffusion, not convection (Fig. 1). Such diffusion limitations can lead to a difference in concentration between the surface of the pellet and the interior of the pellet, which can affect the observed reaction rates. To improve simulation accuracy, internal mass transfer (i.e., intra-particle pore diffusion resistances) must often be considered when modeling fixed bed reactors. Two of the most common models for internal pore diffusion are the effectiveness factor method and the 1D reaction-diffusion method.

Figure 1: A schematic of the internal pore structure of a typical fixed bed reactor catalyst pellet

The effectiveness factor is the ratio of the reaction rate with and without internal diffusion limitations [1]. The rates for each specie i are modified by the effectiveness factor, η , such that $\dot{s}_{i,eff} = \eta \dot{s}_i$. Here, $\dot{s}_{i,eff}$ is the effective surface reaction rate accounting for concentrations within the particle differing from concentrations at the surface of the catalyst pellet, and \dot{s}_i is the surface reaction rate calculated with concentrations at the (outer geometrical) surface of the catalyst. When there are no external mass transfer resistances across the boundary layer between the bulk flow and the catalyst surface, the surface concentrations are known from the CFD solution of the species transport equation. η can then be calculated using an analytical solution. However, when a more rigorous approach is needed to address internal mass transfer resistances, the 1D reaction-diffusion equation (Eq. 1, [1]) can be solved directly (on a subgrid) at each catalytic face (for a surface reaction) or cell (for reactions in porous media). For specie i , $D_{i,eff}$ is the effective diffusivity [1], and C_i is the specie concentration.

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_{i,eff} \cdot \nabla C_i) = R_i \quad (1)$$

The chemistry library DETCHEM [2] solves for the effective surface reaction rate using either the effectiveness factor or 1D reaction-diffusion equation approaches. DETCHEM is coupled with OpenFOAM [3] via the DUO solver (**D**ETCHEM **u**nd **O**penFOAM), allowing for access to these pore diffusion approaches within OpenFOAM. In prior work [4],[5],[6], DUO modeled packed bed reactors either with a porous media model (using packed bed heat transfer correlations) or with Particle Resolved Computational Fluid Dynamics (PRCFD, where each individual catalyst pellet is resolved in the grid). However, prior work with DUO did not consider internal pore diffusion effects. Also, it was not known whether PRCFD would still match 2D porous media models when pore diffusion modeling is enabled. The present work addresses this question by comparing PRCFD with a 730-particle bed against porous media models for methane Catalytic Partial Oxidation (CPOX) (Fig. 1), Dry Reforming of Methane (DRM), and Steam Methane Reforming (SMR). CPOX is exothermic, but DRM and SMR are endothermic reactions. Also, microkinetics models are used for CPOX and DRM, while a global reaction mechanism is used for SMR.

Examples CPOX results are shown below. Fig. 2 showcases 3D PRCFD results while Fig. 3 compares 3D and 2D (porous media) results along the symmetry axis of the bed when pore diffusion modeling is disabled. Meanwhile, in Fig. 4. the

reaction diffusion (pore diffusion) is enabled. As expected, pore diffusion can have a strong impact on results. For example, the temperature peak which can be seen in Fig. 2 is smoothed out in Fig. 3, and the overall CH₄ conversion is lower because reaction rate is slowed down due to internal diffusion resistances. For both conditions the match between PRCFD and 2-D model is good for the species concentrations and temperature. As a benefit, 2D calculation is much faster than 3D calculation (e.g., days of computation time for 3D PRCFD with 36 cores vs. minutes on a single core for 2D).

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TOWARDS THE DEVELOPMENT OF CASTING ADVISORY SYSTEMS: SIMULATION OF DIRECT CHILL CASTING PROCESSES

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Keywords: *solidification, metal casting.*

The stability and success of this continuous casting technique depends on the right choice of the process parameters, and their precise control throughout the entire progress. Substantial and/or consistent deviations from the nominal conditions can soon lead to a loss of quality and appearance of defects (e.g. grain size distribution, cracks in the billet). In some cases, this results in production-stopping failures such as *freeze-in* (i.e. the melt solidifies upstream in the mould and blocks the inlet) or even serious safety risks such as *bleed-outs / run-outs* (i.e. molten material escaping/spilling out from the mould).

Traditionally, finding a working set of casting parameters for new alloys or formats has been a complex task involving several *trial-and-error* iterations. Furthermore, the process heavily relies on the expertise of highly experienced technicians.

To address these challenges, we envisioned the development of casting advisory systems, that will eventually offer real-time suggestions based on trained digital twins of the process. This user-focused approach aims to ensure safer and more efficient operations. Along with data arising from the actual process, these machine-learning algorithms benefit from the results of several simulated scenarios (Figure 1). These CFD simulations help to identify the limits of the process window as well as to predict the final quality and possible defects in the casted billets.

Figure 1: Different simulated examples for direct-chill casting of aluminium billets (thermal views): a) vertical open-top configuration using combo-bag melt inlet distributor. b) horizontal axis-symmetric configuration.

Initially, we employed a solver based on the continuum mixture model of [1], namely *solidificationFoam* [2], [3] and incorporated a specialised thermal boundary condition that mimics the behaviour of the chill water across the different thermal regimes (i.e. pre-boiling, nucleation boiling, transition boiling, and film boiling) [4]. While the solver *solidificationFoam* is suitable for simple alloys, its formulation becomes inadequate for modelling the behaviour of most industry relevant alloys i.e. alloys containing several different elements. In such cases, modelling the melt fraction based on CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagrams) predictions results in a more accurate and efficient calculation. The same applies to the concentration of the different alloying elements in the melt. For that reason, a more recent solver called *directChillFoam* [5] was adopted. The released version of this solver is designed to work with a customised version of *solidificationMelting* fvModel, that allows for the temperature-dependent phase change. This is achieved by reading a Function1 relation between the temperature and the melt fraction. During the research activities, the code was ported to more recent OpenFOAM versions and modularised, thus enabling its components to be called independently. Moreover, this minimally invasive coding approach allows for automatic inheritance of refactorized functionality such as in-runtime mesh topology changes, that is essential for studying the transient stages of the casting process. For instance, Figure 2 shows how to replace *directChillFoam* with a specialised class of *fluid*, named

coupledFluid, that contains the functionality to ensure the convergence between the energy and phase fraction. Additional changes promote an even faster and more stable convergence of the solver.

Figure 2: Inheritance scheme of implemented *coupledFluid* class (derived from [6]).

The code, along with exemplary cases is publicly available under GNU/GPLv3-license and is under active development [7]. Contributions to it are, of course, welcome.

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Posters

NUMERICAL STUDY OF A BLUFF BODY STABILIZED LEAN PREMIXED HYDROGEN FLAME USING ARTIFICIALLY THICKENED FLAME MODEL IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *Reacting flow, Combustion, Hydrogen, Thickened Flame Model, LES, OpenFOAM*

In recent years, hydrogen has garnered significant attention due to its carbon-free nature, making it an appealing candidate for sustainable energy solutions. Its unique properties as an energy vector, such as high energy density and versatility across various applications, have further highlighted its potential in the transition to cleaner energy systems. It is important to characterise numerical models to expand knowledge in hydrogen combustion. In this study, the Thickened Flame Model [1] is implemented in the opensource software OpenFOAM v8. New solver is therefore developed from *reactingFoam*. Thermal diffusion effects will also be investigated by integrating the Soret effect into the governing equations. A case study of a single sector hydrogen burner is selected. The test case will show the characteristics of hydrogen in terms of diffusion during the reactive process. Analysis of the atmospheric test bench operating with a lean, perfectly pre-mixed, hydrogen-air flame stabilised on a conical bluff body [2] will be carried out. LES simulations are conducted in which the impact of modelling the interaction between the flame front and turbulence through the definition of efficiency function is analysed. In addition to the one proposed by Colin [1], the efficiency function presented by Charlette [2] is implemented. The simulation is conducted in parallel using the *DLBFoam* library [3] to balance the load in the reaction rate computation. An extension to the original library is also proposed for the reference zonal mapping model to speed up the chemistry. In reference mapping, the mixture fraction is replaced by the progress variable and the flame sensor to map a reference solution to reference cells that satisfy a conditions. The investigation is done by the qualitative comparison of the three-dimensional flame visualisation with the experimental test case. The quantitative one is conducted by comparing detailed Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV)/ OH-Planar Laser-Induced Fluorimetry (OH-PLIF) measurements, which allow the characterisation of the flame behaviour. The comparisons will make it possible to identify the optimal flame representation models among those selected.

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Simulation based Optimization of Wetting Phenomena

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Keywords: Wetting Phenomena, Optimization, Multiphase flow, Doctor Blading

We consider a wetting process that is motivated by gravure printing, a process where a gravure cylinder is rotated, while an ink reservoir is used to wet the surface with ink and a doctor blade is then pulled over the surface by the rotation of the cylinder to remove the excess fluid. This printing process is described by the two-phase Navier-Stokes equation with surface tension, see for example [1], and a dynamic contact line model. The optimization framework and doctor blade test case were developed by Diehl in [2].

The optimization algorithm is composed of an outer initialization and optimization framework that is implemented in Matlab. The inner simulation part is performed with OpenFOAM, where a sensitivity approach or an adjoint approach can be chosen for the calculation of the derivatives. We use the multiphase solver *interFoam* of OpenFOAM to compute the state and have extended it to compute the derivative of the objective function. This framework is schematically depicted in Figure 1. In a first step, discretization methods for the VOF-based sensitivity equations were derived and implemented in *interSensFoam* by Diehl in [2] following an optimize-then-discretize approach. Here, the terms containing sensitivities of the face fluxes must be discretized by suitably selected schemes, since for example the upwind direction has to be determined by the original face flux. Furthermore, particular attention is required for the linearisation of the surface tension term which is used by *interFoam*. In this approach the sensitivity $\delta\alpha$ is not corrected by the MULES algorithm, but rather computed with an upwind scheme and the sensitivities of the velocity and the pressure are calculated by the PISO algorithm in the same way as the state variables, where the additional terms are treated as source terms.

The development of an adjoint solver based on *interSensFoam* is currently in progress.

Figure 1: Coupling of Matlab and OpenFOAM simulations.

The geometrical setup consists of a domain with a doctor blade and homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions on the upper and left boundaries for the velocity u while on the lower wall a velocity u_{cyl} is applied. The fluid flows out on the right border. In the simulation, two initial conditions of the fluid are considered illustrated in Figure 2.

An example of an optimization problem is the effect of the viscosity of the printing fluid on the film formation occurring behind the doctor blade, where the sensitivities are calculated using the *interSensFoam* solver. Another optimization goal is the reduction of air bubbles inside the printing fluid to avoid printing failures. Therefore, the minimization of the vorticity inside the ink reservoir is of interest. This can be influenced by changing the inclination angle of the doctor blade.

Figure 2: On the left side are the velocity boundary conditions of the doctor blading test case. In the middle is scenario 1 and on the right side scenario 2.

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CO₂ PHASE CHANGE SIMULATIONS IN A CROGENIC INSULATED TANK BY OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *Crogenic, CO₂, OpenFOAM, Phase change*

As Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies have recently emerged as a key part of climate change mitigation strategies, reliable and efficient storage, and transportation of liquefied carbon dioxide (CO₂) has become an important area of research. Cryogenic insulated tanks are used as an essential device for CO₂ storage, but the phase change phenomena that occur inside the tank directly affect boil-off gas (BOG) generation and storage efficiency. In particular, the phase change process due to changes in temperature and pressure in the tank can affect the safety and long-term operational efficiency of the storage system, so quantitative analysis is essential. However, this phenomenon is a transient problem involving multiphase flow, heat transfer, and phase change, which is limited to be analyzed experimentally. In this study, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) was used to accurately analyze the phase change phenomenon of liquid CO₂ in a cryogenic insulation tank, and analyze the characteristics of BOG generation and its effect on storage performance. Based on the simulation results, the optimal operating conditions to maximize CO₂ storage efficiency was derived.

OpenFOAM, an open-source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) platform, was used as the simulations [1]. Figure 1 shows the geometry used in the simulations. The insulation is wrapped around the tank and the total number of unstructured meshes is 540,000. The external temperature of the insulation is set to 20°C to account for ambient temperature. In Figure 2, the initial state of liquefied carbon dioxide is set to 94.5% of the total tank volume.

Figure 1: Tank shape and typical mesh

Figure 2: Initial liquid CO₂ filling level (94.5%)

To evaluate the accuracy of the simulation results, convergence was tested using three different grids: coarse, medium, and fine, with coarse consisting of 250,000 unstructured grids, medium consisting of 540,000 unstructured grids, and fine consisting of 1.2 million unstructured grids. The convergence test was performed by measuring the pressure at four locations as shown in Figure 3. The results in Figure 4 show that the simulation converges sufficiently, so for the sake of computational time and economy, the simulation was performed using the medium case. It was found that the heat transfer between the tank and the insulation was well simulated due to the lowered liquid and vapor interface and the temperature of the tank caused by the BOG over time.

Figure 3: Prove locations

Figure 4: Pressures at each prove locations

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DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIPHASE EULERIAN - PBM MODEL FOR BUBBLE TRANSPORT WITH APPLICATIONS TO AN ELECTROLYSER CELL

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Keywords: Multiphase, Eulerian, Hydrogen, Interfacial models, Population Balance Model, Method of Moments

Hydrogen produced from Electrolysers utilising renewable electricity is termed as 'Green' Hydrogen. Alkaline Water Electrolysers (ALK) and Proton Exchange Membrane Electrolysers (PEME) are the two most mature Electrolyser technologies currently in use [1]. There have been improvements in design, materials and process configuration, but their energy efficiency is limited to 50% for more extreme operating conditions. In both ALK and PEME, one of the limiting factors for operating efficiency is the transport of Hydrogen/Oxygen bubbles away from the electrodes and into the bulk flow channel (part of the Flow Field Plate). Some of the issues of bubbles in Electrolysers are highlighted in the schematic in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of Bubble coverage issues

In general, the formation of bubbles can be classified into 2 ways; a homogenous and a heterogenous one. In the former route bubbles nucleate in open spaces, while in the latter bubbles nucleate from the surface of the electrode/CL. In electrolysers, the nucleation of bubbles is strongly heterogenous in nature and takes place in a supersaturated solution. Bubbles nucleate at the Catalyst Layer (CL) (see Figure 2) and can grow upto an average size of 70 - 120 microns [2]. The electrogenerated bubbles then grow, detach and are transported from the CL to the bulk channel. Numerous electrogenerated bubbles are accounted by a size distribution [3]. The discrete bubbles can be modelled using a Lagrangian or a Statistical approach. Modelling this distribution through a statistical approach is achieved by the Population Balance Equation (PBE) and is known as Population Balance Modelling (PBM) [4]. The PBE is a continuity statement that is characterised by a distribution function (size distribution for example).

Figure 2: Schematic of PEM Electrolyser cell (left) [5] and transport phenomena at Catalyst Layer (right) [6]

In previous studies modelling was done at the macroscopic scale. These models had limitations, for example in properly defining closure models for transport, mass transfer or capillary effects [7]. A full 3D macroscopic model was developed by Olesen et al. [8]. They did not account for interfacial forces and electrochemical reactions. Most studies analyze the bubble behaviour based on electrochemical performance rather than from a fluid dynamics perspective. The available bubble transport models were primarily developed for the Anode side, often neglecting the Hydrogen evolution [9]. The models do not account for transport within the Porous Transport Layer (PTL) (Figure 2) and from the PTL into the channel (Figure 2). Furthermore, the existing models for electrolyser performance characterise the bubbles with a uniform distribution.

The objective of this current study is to develop a Eulerian - Population Balance Model (PBM) in OpenFOAMv12 based on the built-in PBM model in the dispersed multiphase flow solver. A Eulerian (Two Fluid) model for Gas-Liquid flow is considered. To more accurately account for the distribution of bubbles (size), a Population Balance Model (PBM) is considered with the Eulerian model. The electrolyser geometry is simplified to a horizontal channel with two-phase dispersed bubble flow. Only the growth and transport of the bubble is considered in the presented model. The aim of our study is to understand the system, characterise the bubble behaviour and identify where the improvements are needed in the model. These can include using the Method of Moments to replace the PBE, tuning of the Eulerian model for interfacial forces and/or inclusion of boundary conditions for bubble nucleation. The model we develop is validated against the experimental work of Tomasoni [3]. Building on this work, The overall research objective is to address the nucleation, growth and transport of the Hydrogen/Oxygen bubbles from the Catalyst Layer through the PTL into the bulk flow channel, by developing a 3D macroscopic multiphase CFD model.

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SPECTRAL UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION OF PRESSURE LOSS THROUGH A 90° PIPE BEND USING SST K-OMEGA

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Keywords: Uncertainty Quantification, RANS, SST K-Omega, Internal Flow, Polynomial Chaos, 90° Pipe Bend

This work looks to apply Uncertainty Quantification (UQ), using the OpenFOAM [1] implementation of the SST k-Omega [2] Reynolds-Averaged Navier Stokes (RANS) solver, to determining the pressure loss / loss coefficient of flow through a 90° pipe bend. Using the extensive numerical and experimental data that exists for this flow, this work aims to produce validated results as probability distributions, from uncertain inputs to a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) solver. Spectral UQ using Polynomial Chaos (PC) Expansion, with the DAKOTA [3] toolkit, is used to perform this analysis with less computational effort than a naïve Monte-Carlo surrogate.

Flow Domain

The flow domain consists of a 1-inch (25.4 mm) diameter pipe with a 90° bend of radius 46.5 mm. A length of 50 pipe diameters (50D) upstream allows the flow to fully develop while providing a straight pipe length unaffected by the bend, for comparison to the downstream length. One diameter downstream, the flow is mapped back to the inlet to provide an ‘infinite length’ for flow development. The pipe is treated as hydraulically smooth.

The downstream pipe length is 55 diameters (55D), as Ito [4] showed 50D to be sufficient to resolve all post-bend effects, and the flow domain is sampled 5D from the outlet to exclude any variations induced by the fixed value boundary condition. The flow medium considered is water. The meshing used Salome [5] to create inputs for SnappyHexMesh [1].

Figure 1: Flow Domain and Mesh

Mesh Sensitivity & Validation

A two-part mesh sensitivity analysis was used. An arbitrary ‘inner mesh’ resolution was used for the initial ‘boundary layer’ sensitivity analysis, and the resulting boundary layer resolution used in the subsequent inner mesh sensitivity.

The boundary layer sensitivity analysis plotted pressure losses against average y^+ , and the inner mesh analysis against total cell count. The losses measured are:

- TotalLoss – The pressure loss from 10 pipe diameters (10D) upstream of the bend to 50D downstream.
- Loss30 – The pressure loss from a 30D length of pipe, taken upstream of the bend, starting 15D from the inlet to ensure fully developed flow and to avoid effects from the bend.
- BendLoss – The total loss attributable to the bend, including post-bend effects. Calculated by subtracting $2 \times \text{Loss30}$ from TotalLoss. The primary Quantity of Interest (QoI).

The pressure losses were plotted against empirical / calculated values over a range of Re for the chosen mesh, to allow comparison to other research data. The Darcy-Weisbach equation was used for Loss30 and Ito’s [4] equations for BendLoss. Empirical TotalLoss is calculated from these. BendLoss varied from the empirical values by less than 2.3 % for Re values between 34,000 and 60,000, validating the method’s accuracy for calculating the bend loss.

Figure 2 - BendLoss vs. Reynolds Number

Uncertainty Quantification

Spectral UQ aims to construct the functional dependence of the solution on the ‘germ’, ξ , which is a vector of independent Random Variables (RVs) used to parameterise the input data (with known probability distributions). The functional dependence can be expressed in the form of a series, which shares the basic form of a PC Expansion:

$$U(\xi) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} u_k \Psi_k(\xi) \quad (1)$$

Where Random Vector U is the PC representation of a set of RVs, u_k the deterministic PC coefficients, and Ψ_k are suitably selected functionals of the RVs. A Prior PC Expansion describing the input data (truncated to order P to allow numerical solution) is constructed from the deterministic and probabilistic inputs. Samples of these input parameters are run through the deterministic solver. The output samples are used to estimate the PC coefficients for a Posterior PC Expansion, from which it is computationally cheap to generate a large sample size for statistical analysis. This work uses multidimensional integration by the Smolyak sparse grid method [6] to estimate the posterior expansion PC coefficients. Couaillier and Savin [7] provide a comprehensive explanation of the PC UQ method utilised, with the exact techniques detailed in DAKOTA’s documentation [3]. This is a non-intrusive method that does not require modifications to the standard OpenFOAM solver.

Figure 3 shows an example output for a single source of uncertainty, giving bend loss as a probability distribution for uncertain inlet velocity, with a mean inlet velocity U of 1.8 ms⁻¹ and standard deviation of 0.1:

Figure 3 - Pressure drop probability distribution

Ongoing Work

This ongoing work aims to incorporate uncertainty from multiple sources into the UQ analysis, without greatly increasing the number of simulations required for the sampling, quantify the accuracy of the PC surrogate modelling technique used, and apply this same analysis to systems other than a 90° pipe bend.

The potential benefits foreseen from this work include enabling the informed inclusion of known uncertainties into the performance of analysed systems, rather than using arbitrary error bands; quantifying the probability of desirable / undesirable outcomes, to inform tools such as probabilistic safety cases; and enabling the informed use of less accurate or reliable methods or data, given that this uncertainty can be incorporated into the results.

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NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF COAL AND BIOMASS COMBUSTION USING ARRHENIUS-BASED MODELS AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

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Keywords: *Combustion, Arrhenius Kinetics, Emission Reduction, Sparse Chemical Kinetics*

The transition toward more sustainable energy production requires a detailed understanding of how alternative fuel mixtures behave during combustion. In this study, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis examines the effects of fuel composition and key operating parameters on the combustion behaviour of coal and biomass mixtures. The numerical simulations are performed using the open-source computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software OpenFOAM, employing Arrhenius-based reaction [1] models to represent the combustion kinetics [2].

The primary objective of the study is to assess how variations in the biomass-to-coal ratio, reaction kinetics parameters, and operational conditions influence the final composition of combustion products and overall combustion efficiency. By systematically altering these input variables, the sensitivity of the combustion process is quantified, allowing the identification of the most influential factors. This approach provides valuable insight into the interplay between fuel properties and operating conditions, and how they collectively affect flame stability, pollutant formation, and energy release.

The combustion model implemented in OpenFOAM relies on simplified chemical kinetics governed by Arrhenius equations, which capture the essential characteristics of the oxidation reactions involved. Specific attention is given to monitoring parameters such as the concentrations of major combustion products (e.g., CO_2 , CO , and NO_x) [3] as well as temperature profiles and burnout efficiency. Mesh independence studies and validation against available experimental data are conducted to ensure the robustness of the simulation results.

The outcomes of this sensitivity analysis aim to provide guidelines for optimizing combustion systems utilizing coal and biomass blends, offering potential pathways to enhance performance while minimizing environmental impact. Additionally, the study highlights the flexibility and capability of OpenFOAM for conducting parametric studies and advanced combustion simulations. Future work will involve extending the approach to more complex chemical mechanisms and a broader range of biomass types.

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NUMERICAL MODELING OF ALUMINUM ANNEALING IN INDUSTRIAL FURNACES USING OPENFOAM

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Keywords: Computational Fluid Dynamics, Heat Transfer Simulation, Annealing Process Optimization

The annealing process is a crucial step in aluminum production, ensuring the desired mechanical and metallurgical properties of the final product [1]. Achieving uniform temperature distribution during annealing is essential to optimize product quality and minimize energy consumption. In this work, a numerical model was developed to simulate the temperature evolution of stacked aluminum plates during the annealing process in an industrial furnace. The model was implemented in OpenFOAM, using the chtMultiRegionFoam solver. This solver enables the coupling of heat transfer in both solid and fluid domains, allowing for an accurate representation of conjugate heat transfer mechanisms.

The study focuses on an industrial annealing furnace consisting of multiple heating zones and an air recirculation system driven by dedicated fans. The computational model incorporates key furnace design features, including the influence of air recirculation, steel support frames, and thermal anisotropy caused by air micro-gaps in the stacked aluminum plates. The computational mesh was generated using snappyHexMesh, while simulations were performed using parallel computing to handle the complex flow and heat transfer calculations.

Model validation was performed by comparing numerical predictions with experimental measurements from thermocouples placed at different positions within the aluminum stacks. The results demonstrated a strong agreement between simulated and measured temperatures, confirming the model's accuracy. Beyond the validation, the model can also investigate different furnace geometries and loading configurations to evaluate their effect on heat distribution and process efficiency. By simulating various scenarios, it becomes possible to optimize furnace operation, reducing cycle times and energy costs while maintaining high-quality aluminum products.

Figure 1 illustrates the airflow patterns within the furnace, showcasing the recirculation behavior that influences temperature distribution. This visualization highlights the complex interactions between airflow and stacked aluminum plates, reinforcing the importance of accurate modeling for optimizing furnace performance.

Figure 1: Airflow patterns inside the annealing furnace, illustrating the recirculation behavior around the stacked aluminum plates. The recirculating flow significantly affects heat distribution and temperature uniformity during the annealing process.

Overall, this work demonstrates the potential of OpenFOAM in enhancing industrial annealing processes through advanced CFD modeling. By utilizing open-source simulation tools, manufacturers can achieve improved process control and better energy efficiency highlighting the role of computational modeling in modern industrial applications.

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RESEARCH ON UTILIZATION TREND AND SERVICE APPLICATION OF GPU-BASED OPENFOAM

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Keywords: GPU, HPC, OpenFOAM, sparse iterative solver

In computational continuum mechanics, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) requires relatively greater computational resources than computational structural dynamics (CSD) because it must analyse complex flow phenomena such as turbulence, multiphase flow, and combustion. GPU accelerators have a larger number of computational cores than CPUs and provide high-performance results even in double-precision (FP64) operations for high-fidelity fluid analysis. Dynamic environment of computer hardware technology development is underway, with the latest GPU accelerator developments such as NVIDIA H200, GH200, AMD's MI325X, and Intel's Data Center GPU Max 1550, as well as expansion into NPUs and TPUs that can replace GPUs. Looking at the world's supercomputer rankings [1], supercomputers with GPU accelerators account for 42% of the total. In particular, the transition to GPU-based supercomputers is expected to accelerate with the installation of the latest NVIDIA GH200 accelerators at TACC (USA) and upcoming installations at Jülich Supercomputing Centre (Germany). GPU accelerators have made a significant contribution to supercomputer performance in recent years, with the installation space being reduced to a level where a single rack of El Capitan (LLNL), the #1 exascale supercomputer with 87 racks, can match the entire performance of our Nurion supercomputer (72 racks), currently ranked 91st.

South Korea's sixth national supercomputer will be built this year as a heterogeneous GPU system by HPE and will be officially put into service next year. A GPU-driven system is proposed with LinPack benchmark performance of 600+PF and specifications such as # of CPU: # of GPU = 1:2 or Higher (ex. 1:1) [2]. National Supercomputer No. 5 is an only CPU system, and OpenFOAM usage was confirmed to be only 1% of the total usage, showing relatively low usage compared to other software. Moreover, in Unit 6, it was important whether NVIDIA or AMD GPU modules were included as official services because the PELE-LM software, which had little usage in Unit 5, rather than OpenFOAM, had to be selected as the benchmark target software in the continuum mechanics field.

There are also issues with several programs (CUDA, HIP, SYCL, OpenMP, OpenACC, Kokkos, etc.) that are not yet fully supported by the major GPU developers NVIDIA, AMD, and INTEL [3]. And, mainly from the perspective of OpenFOAM users, they want to reduce code development as much as possible through the GPU module library. In addition, unlike CPUs, trade-offs (overhead, memory, instructions per clock (IPC) and clock speed, etc.) in GPU environments must be reexamined, and a trial-and-error process such as effective solver selection and option adjustment is required. For example, the GAMG linear solver uses a lot of RAM on the GPUs compared to PCG/PBiCG, but there is a trade-off in terms of faster computation speed, so an efficient method must be found [4].

Open source software for molecular dynamics applied at the atomic or molecular level (GROMAC, Quantum ESPRESSO, LAMMPS, etc.) has been providing GPU modules as official services for a long time to increase user satisfaction [5]. On the other hand, in open source software in the field of continuum mechanics such as OpenFOAM, individual development activities have been carried out in various ways by utilizing several external GPU libraries. However, even at this point in time when GPUs have become widely available, it is regrettable that it is not provided as an official service for GPU modules. ANSYS Fluent, a representative commercial software, has been promoting official GPU solver development cooperation with NVIDIA for 10 years and is currently equipped with a powerful GPU solver service module. Recently, efforts to actively respond to the GPU-based hardware environment were confirmed by performing large-scale automotive fluid analysis using the Native Multi-GPU solver via the GH200 GPU [6].

The most time-consuming part of the OpenFOAM code procedure is iterative solving, which is where linear algebra matrix operations are performed. Most of the GPU modules presented in Table 1 are utilizing plug-in methods to increase computational time efficiency by applying offloading from the host to the GPU so that the computation for the implicit sparse iterative solver is processed on the GPU [7]. In Table 1, the scope is reduced to a total of 10 GPU modules, and the presentation scope is reduced to only one major literature article or Github for each GPU module. Except for some such as PETSC, AMgX, RapidCFD, GPU modules such as Culises and SpeedIT have not been maintained for more than 10 years, and these modules are mostly developed by companies. In particular, Culises and SpeedIT collaborated with NVIDIA about 10 years ago on OpenFOAM's GPU modules for marketing NVIDIA's application software, but this is no longer confirmed as a normal service.

Table 1: Investigation of GPU modules for OpenFOAM

GPU module name	Developer	GPU solver	Reference
AmgxCoupled4FOAM	Stefano Oliani, Ettore Fadiga, Ivan Spisso, Luigi Capone, Federico Piscaglia	AMgX	[8]
Cufflink	Daniel P. Combest & Jeremy Day		[9]
Culises	FluidDyna		[10]
gpuFOAM	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd		[11]
Ofgpu	Symscape		[12]
PARALUTION	Dimitar Lukarski and Nico Trost		[13]
PETSc4FOAM	Mark Olesen, Simone Bna, Stefano Zampini	PETSC	[7]
RapidCFD	simFlow		[4]
SpeedIT	Vratis		[14]
zeptoFOAM	exaFOAM		[3]

We also studied the usability and performance of GPU modules examined in Table 1 by considering trade-offs through GPU-based neuron systems currently being served as independent queues, such as V100, A100, H100, H200, and GH200. However, GPU-based tests from AMD and Intel were excluded as a priority since there is no queue that includes those GPUs. For this review, a 3D lid-driven cavity was used as a simple example.

In this study, we investigated several papers and companies' development activities to gain insight into the use of various GPU acceleration methods. Just like other engineering open source software such as Quantum ESPRESSO, GROMACS, and LAMMPS, there should be active efforts to provide GPU-based OpenFOAM modules as official services on the OpenFOAM site.[5] Through this, we aim to contribute to the activation of domestic OpenFOAM users by securing sufficient functions in advance as a GPU module integrated platform with performance optimization for the GPU accelerator of the soon-to-be-built supercomputer No. 6.

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VENTILATION PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS ACCORDING TO THE OPENING RATIO OF A SENSOR GUARD

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Keywords: CFD, Hazardous material detection sensor, Opening ratio, ACH, sensor guard, pimpleFoam

1. Introduction

The frequency of hazardous material leakage incidents in industrial sites has escalated sharply, raising significant concerns due to their profound human and economic impacts. According to the incident report of U.S. Chemical Safety and Hazard Investigation Board (CSB) [1], 153 industrial chemical accidents were recorded in the United States between March 2020 and May 2022. In response to these risks, the deployment of sensors for detecting hazardous material leaks has become increasingly common in industrial environments. Traditional detection systems rely on fixed sensors installed at predetermined locations, but these systems face challenges in confined or poorly ventilated spaces, where limited convection can delay leak detection, particularly when the leak source is distant from the sensor. To overcome these limitations, portable hazardous material sensors are being developed to provide real-time alerts to workers in their immediate vicinity.

However, portable sensors must withstand the harsh conditions typical of industrial environments. Effective detection demands adequate airflow into the sensor chamber, yet effective ventilation also exposes the sensor to environmental contaminants. Fine particulate matter, prevalent in industrial settings, can impair sensor accuracy and cause malfunctions. Therefore, ensuring protection from both mechanical shocks and dust intrusion is critical. The balance between sufficient ventilation and protective shielding remains a critical design challenge. Yet, many commercially available sensors prioritize aesthetic considerations over functional reliability, despite the critical nature of this trade-off.

Although previous studies have not directly investigated the optimal opening ratio for sensor guard ventilation, inspiration was drawn from indoor ventilation research [2, 3], which explores the relationship between window size and ventilation performance. However, applying orifice-based flow rate measurements, derived from pressure differential equations to sensor-scale environments poses significant challenges due to differences in Reynolds numbers between building-scale and sensor-scale scenarios. These discrepancies render correction factors derived from larger-scale studies unsuitable for accurate sensor applications.

Previous studies simplified the effective inflow area as half of the total opening area when calculating flow rates. For instance, Chu et al. [2] adopted this simplification in their wind tunnel experiments to determine inflow rates from a window. While this approach served its purpose, it introduces potential inaccuracies in flow measurement. In this study, we accounted for the actual effective inflow area in our flow rate calculations and validated the free-stream velocity ratio at the opening in experiments to assess the accuracy of the proposed method. Furthermore, while prior computational studies [4, 5] have employed turbulence models such as k- ϵ or LES to predict flow rates, our results demonstrate that accurate flow predictions can be achieved under laminar conditions, without the need for turbulence model.

To propose the optimal opening ratio for the sensor guard, this study employed the PIMPLE algorithm to analyze internal ventilation performance. Flow rates were precisely calculated based on the effective inflow area, offering a more sensitive and robust approach to ventilation optimization.

2. Method

To quantify ventilation performance, the mean flow rate was calculated based on 10 different opening ratios $O_r = A/A_w$ where A is the open area and A_w is the area of the external wall. The sensor was designed with internal dimensions of $0.01m \times 0.01m \times 0.01m (L_{in} \times H_{in} \times W_{in})$. To capture near-wall flow behaviour accurately, the first layer height was specified as 0.05mm. The freestream velocity was set to 1.3m/s, reflecting the average walking speed of an adult male, to mimic realistic ambient wind conditions.

To assess the ventilation performance of the sensor guard under wind-driven single-sided ventilation, the flow rate for each computational cell was calculated. The effective mean velocity (\bar{U}_{eff}) for each cell was obtained by time-averaging the normal component of the velocity vector, as described in Eq. (1), where \vec{n} denotes the unit normal vector of the open surface. The unsteady simulation was performed for 5 seconds, and the time-averaged velocity was calculated over the interval from $T_0 = 3s$ to $T_1 = 5s$.

The total flow rate (Q_{tot}), passing through the opening was calculated by integrating the effective velocity and the effective inflow area across the entire opening as given in Eq. (2). This total flow rate was subsequently used to calculate the Air Change per Hour (ACH), as shown in Eq. (3), by considering the internal volume V_s of the sensor.

$$\bar{U}_{eff}(\vec{x}) = \frac{1}{T_1 - T_0} \int_{T_0}^{T_1} \vec{U}(\vec{x}, t) \cdot \vec{n} dt \quad (1)$$

$$Q_{tot} = \int_A \max(\bar{U}_{eff}(\vec{x}), 0) dA \quad (2)$$

$$ACH = \frac{3600 \times Q_{tot}}{V_s} \quad (3)$$

3. Results

Figure 1 Effect of opening ratio on internal flow pattern and effective inflow area

When the opening ratio decreased from 0.5 to 0.4, the ACH reduction was minimized, confirming that the performance degradation due to the reduction in opening was the lowest within this range. Additionally, the internal airflow characteristics were classified into three distinct patterns based on the opening ratio. For opening ratios between 0.9 and 0.4, the internal flow remained stable and effectively managed. Conversely, at opening ratios below 0.3, airflow inertia proved insufficient to adequately ventilate the sensor's interior, resulting in significantly diminished ventilation effectiveness. Consequently, considering the necessary balance between effective ventilation and internal protective requirements, an opening ratio of 0.4 was identified as optimal for gas sensor guard applications.

4. Conclusion

This study investigates how the opening ratio affects internal ventilation in portable gas sensor guards. Unlike previous studies [4, 5] using the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, this study adopts pimpleFoam under laminar condition to calculate the flow rate at the opening by considering the effective inflow area at the opening, enabling more accurate and efficient evaluation of internal ventilation performance.

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An OpenFOAM based-based multi-physic multi-region model for All Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries

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Keywords: Redox Flow Battery, Electrochemistry, Multi-physics, Multi-regional, OpenFOAM

The increasing integration of renewable energy sources, driven by the urgent need to address climate change, has underscored the importance of efficient and scalable energy storage systems. Among the various available technologies, all-vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs) stand out as particularly promising due to their long cycle life, inherent safety, and excellent scalability. In this work, we present a structured and extensible mathematical model of a VRFB, developed using *OpenFOAM* version 10, with the flexibility to accommodate alternative redox chemistry in future developments.

To accurately capture the diverse physical phenomena occurring across different components of the battery, a multi-region modeling approach was adopted. This approach led to the selection of the *chtMultiRegionFoam* solver as a foundation, due to its modular structure and native support for heat and mass transfer across multiple regions. In addition to fluid dynamics and species transport, the model was extended with chemical and electrochemical equations to describe the core processes governing battery operation. The solver architecture is built around the *PIMPLE* algorithm, which provides robust and efficient handling of the coupled system of equations. The implementation also required the development of several custom boundary conditions to ensure accurate inter-region coupling and numerical stability throughout the simulations. This paper focuses on the development of the solver, detailing the modeling strategies and numerical techniques employed. Additionally, the simulation results are compared against selected data from the literature to assess the validity and reliability of the proposed approach.

A typical flow battery consists of five key components: bipolar plates, the negative and positive electrodes, and the membrane. In alignment with this structure, the model is divided into three distinct regions: the electrode, current collector, and membrane. Each region is governed by a set of equations tailored to capture the specific physical, chemical, and electrochemical phenomena occurring within it.

Starting with the electrode, which represents the most complex region of the battery, it is modeled as a porous medium through which the electrolyte flows. The fluid flow is described by a modified Navier-Stokes equation that accounts for porosity effects. Given that the electrolyte consists of various chemical species, mass transport must be accurately captured. In the present model, a dilute solution assumption is incorporated into the solver structure, and the flux of species such as V^{2+} , V^{3+} , V^{4+} , V^{5+} , and S_t is described using a modified Nernst-Planck equation. S_t represents a sum of both sulfate compounds, HSO_4^+ and SO_4^{2+} that are present in the electrolyte. Additionally, the concentrations of the remaining species are calculated using a set of equilibrium equations, which form a cubic function that properly represents species distribution [3]. Current flow through the electrode is treated separately for the two phases - fluid and solid -. Electric and ionic potentials are computed using two separate charge conservation equations that are coupled by a source term computed with Butler-Volmer equation that describe the kinetics happening at the electrode surface.

The second type of region developed is the membrane region. In redox flow batteries, the membrane serves to separate the positive and negative electrolytes while enabling passage of the ionic current. It prevents the mixing of different vanadium ions, thereby preserving the battery's efficiency and lifespan. For the purposes of this model, an idealized cation exchange membrane was developed. Only hydrogen ions (H^+) are present within the membrane domain, and no fluid flow equations are solved there. Based on the electro-neutrality condition, the concentration of protons in the membrane is constant and equal to the concentration of the charged groups.

The final region incorporated into the model is the solid body bipolar plates or current collector. The solver is capable of managing the presence of flow channels in the bipolar plates. This region facilitates the transfer of electrons between the external circuit and the electrodes. To ensure current conservation within this domain, Ohm's law is applied as the sole equation governing this region.

The multi-region approach adopted in the model requires careful handling of the order in which the equations are solved. To

speed up the computation time and avoid instabilities a so-called *global mesh* concept was introduced in order to compute electrolyte potential. The global mesh is nothing more than the mesh of all regions before separating them. To utilize this method a mapping between regions and global mesh had to be added to the solver. Another challenging aspect of the battery modeling is a proper application of both *potentiostatic* and *galvanostatic*. The first operational mode applies a constant potential, while the second applies a constant current flux at the external current collector patches. *Potentiostatic* operation are not problematic as they are conducted by applying at least one Dirichlet boundary condition in order to solve Laplace's equation for the electrode. *Galvanostatic* mode is more demanding, because electric charge conservation equation will not result in unique solution with two Neumann boundary conditions. This issue has been addressed by many before (e.g. [4]) To avoid this problem an algorithm proposed by Colli in [1] was incorporated. Instead of setting the flux at the boundary, another Dirichlet condition is applied and the value of the potential is iteratively computed using Newton-Raphson method with under-relaxation applied to avoid rapid fluctuation and solver crashes. A complete solver structure presenting both modes of battery operation is presented in Figure 1 (a).

Figure 1: (a) Solver block diagram, (b) 2D computational domain representation, (c) Chosen parameters distribution across the computational domain, (d) Chosen parameters plots along the battery mid-height cross-section including anode, cathode and membrane

The solver was tested on a 2D computational domain Figure (Figure 1 (b)), for various initial conditions settings. An exemplary distributions and plots are presented above (Figure 1 (c) and (d)). Additionally achieved results were validated against results of Colli at [1], outcomes from a commercial software [2] showing good fit and proving that the model properly captures complex electrochemical phenomena of the simulated battery.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A DENSITY-BASED SOLVER FOR HIGH-SPEED TURBINE FLOW AND FILM COOLING ANALYSIS USING OPENFOAM

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Keywords: *Density-based solver, Film cooling, High-speed turbine flow simulation*

1. Introduction

A critical parameter governing the performance of a gas turbine is the Turbine Inlet Temperature (TIT); increasing the TIT enhances the thermal efficiency of the turbine. However, elevated TIT levels expose turbine components—especially turbine blades—to severe thermal loads, often surpassing the temperature limits of conventional heat-resistant alloys. In practical applications, the combustor and turbine stages are subjected to working fluid temperatures above 1400°C, which exceed the melting points of most metallic materials [1].

To ensure structural integrity under such extreme thermal conditions, various cooling technologies have been developed. Of the available external cooling strategies, film cooling stands out as one of the most actively applied and widely adopted methods. It works by injecting relatively cool air through an array of small holes on the blade surface, creating an insulating layer between the hot mainstream flow and the blade, thereby protecting the component from thermal damage. Film cooling holes represent a thermally sensitive region within gas turbine components, where detailed thermal analysis is crucial. Over the years, film cooling performance has predominantly been assessed through RANS-based CFD simulations, with ANSYS-CFX serving as a widely adopted commercial solver throughout this period. Nonetheless, discrepancies arise between RANS-based predictions and experimental measurements of film cooling effectiveness. These inconsistencies are primarily attributed to the limitations of pressure-based RANS solvers in accurately capturing the complex flow characteristics involving heat transfer. To address this issue, a density-based RANS solver was developed with appropriate modifications to the boundary conditions to ensure an accurate representation of the flow field.

2. Methodology

This study develops a density-based solver, developed solver, to accurately simulate high-speed compressible flows in gas turbines. Unlike pressure-based RANS solvers, the density-based approach effectively captures flow discontinuities under high-speed, high-pressure conditions. The developed solver extends the capabilities of the High-speed Aerodynamics Solver (HiSA) [2] by incorporating several enhancements specifically designed for film cooling analysis. A significant improvement in the numerical method is the adoption of a density-based formulation, which enables robust and accurate modeling of high-speed compressible flows, including shock waves.

To this end, a density-based solver was employed to analyze high-speed compressible flows, enabling robust and efficient modeling of numerical discontinuities, including heat transfer.

Another enhancement lies in the flux splitting scheme, where, in addition to the previously implemented HLLC [3] and AUSM+up [4] methods, the Roe [5] scheme has also been incorporated. The Roe scheme is particularly suitable for resolving basic shock waves, while the HLLC method has strengths in capturing both shock waves and contact discontinuities. The AUSM+up scheme improves the coupling between pressure and velocity, thereby increasing the overall accuracy of the flow predictions. To enhance performance in low-speed flow regions, the HLLC method has been modified based on improvements suggested by Nico Fleischmann [6].

To improve temporal discretization, a matrix-free implicit solver has been implemented. This allows the solver to reduce computational cost while maintaining numerical stability for implicit time integration methods such as the Euler and backward schemes. The combination of this time-stepping method with various spatial and temporal discretization strategies contributes to the overall robustness and efficiency of the solver.

The numerical formulation is based on solving the conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy, enabling the simulation of unsteady, compressible, and viscous flows. These equations are closed using the ideal gas law and incorporate the viscous stress tensor components.

Regarding the implementation of boundary conditions, due to the inherent limitations of OpenFOAM that prevent the use of ghost cells, the solver employs a Riemann problem formulation compatible with the AUSM+ scheme. Specifically, wall boundary conditions are linearized and applied based on the method proposed by Liou, which is particularly well-suited for scenarios involving zero-velocity boundaries.

3. Results

The film cooling effectiveness (η) measured from PSP experiments conducted by Kim et al.[7] was compared with computational results from the CFX analysis performed by the Korea Aerospace Research Institute (KARI)[8], as well as the results obtained from the developed solver in the present study. The simulations using the developed solver employed the same fan-shaped cooling hole geometry and conditions as those used in the experiments by Kim et al [7].

$$\eta = \frac{T_m - T_{aw}}{T_m - T_c} \quad (1)$$

Where T_m is the mainstream temperature, T_c is the coolant temperature, T_{aw} is the adiabatic wall temperature. The adiabatic film cooling effectiveness quantifies the cooling performance at the wall surface.

Figure. 1 Comparison of area-averaged film cooling effectiveness between CFD and experiment results

The area-averaged film cooling effectiveness values over the range from $x/D=3$ to $x/D=25$ according to the blowing ratio are presented. As shown in Fig. 1, the developed solver results show cooling effectiveness trends similar to the experimental data by Kim [7] and the CFX analysis [8], indicating high accuracy in predicting film behavior and heat transfer.

4. Conclusion

The developed density-based solver exhibited fast convergence and high accuracy under high-speed compressible flow conditions. It also demonstrated excellent numerical stability and computational efficiency in complex cooling flow simulations, suggesting its strong potential for future applications in turbine flow and cooling system design.

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DEVELOPMENT OF AN UNDERGROUND CARBON DIOXIDE MIGRATION MODEL IN OPENFOAM

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Keywords: porosity, permeability, relative permeability, underground flow, carbon storage, geological carbon sequestration

Due to the high cost and logistical challenges of large-scale field experiments, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) models offer a practical and economical alternative for studying CO₂ migration in geological reservoirs. The CO₂ injection project initiated in Norway in 1996 marked the first industrial-scale implementation of geological carbon sequestration (GCS), demonstrating its long-term feasibility [1,2]. Subsequent studies employed the TOUGH simulator, based on the finite difference method, to construct simplified models of the Sleipner field and analyze the mechanisms governing the interaction between supercritical CO₂ and stratified saline aquifers [3,4]. Horgue et al. [5] developed a multiphase flow simulation toolbox in OpenFOAM®, adopting the widely used Implicit Pressure Explicit Saturation (IMPES) approach from black oil reservoir modeling. Ernestos et al. [6] applied the Volume of Fluid (VoF) method to capture the CO₂–brine interface dynamics, demonstrating its effectiveness in resolving interfacial behavior. To unify free-flow and porous flow dynamics, Carrillo et al. [7] proposed a two-phase Darcy–Brinkman framework and released open-source models for permeability and relative permeability. Building on this, Soulaire et al. [8] integrated the PHREEQC geochemical reaction module into the OpenFOAM-based platform (porousMedia4Foam), enabling reactive transport simulations from pore to reservoir scale.

In this study, we develop a customized multiphase solver based on `icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam`, incorporating porosity and permeability models and preparing for the integration of geochemical reactions and capillary effects. This framework aims to support the simulation of complex interactions among CO₂, brine, and natural gas, contributing to Taiwan’s national decarbonization initiatives.

To validate our developing solver, which is adapted from `icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam` with incorporated porosity and permeability effects, we compare it against `hybridPorousInterFoam` [7], which closely reproduces the Buckley–Leverett [9] semi-analytical solution for two-phase flow in a horizontal one-dimensional system without capillary effects. In the simulation presented in **Figure 1** and **Figure 2**, water is separately injected into an air-saturated reservoir (using the Brooks-Corey [10] relative permeability model with parameter $m=3$) and an oil-saturated reservoir (using the Van Genuchten [11] relative permeability model with parameter $m=0.5$). The one-dimensional domain is 4m long and discretized into 2000 cells with a porosity of $\phi=0.5$ and an inverse absolute permeability of $k_0^{-1}=1\times 10^{11} \text{ m}^{-2}$. The simulation is performed under the following boundary conditions: a constant inlet Darcy velocity $= 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, zero pressure gradient at the inlet ($\frac{\partial p_{inlet}}{\partial x} = 0 \text{ Pa m}^{-1}$), and zero outlet pressure ($p_{outlet} = 0 \text{ Pa}$). The fluid properties used in the simulations are listed in **Table 1**. In **Figure 2**, the water shock front and trailing saturation gradient predicted by our developing solver (solid line) deviate from the semi-analytical solution approximated by `hybridPorousInterFoam` (dashed line). While the shock wave slope matches well, a phase shift is observed. Additionally, discrepancies in variable distributions within each phase suggest insufficient coupling between saturation and pressure fields, indicating areas for solver improvement.

We developed a multiphase flow solver for high-pressure porous media, extending `icoReactingMultiphaseInterFoam` rather than using conventional two-phase solvers. Designed to simulate natural gas, CO₂, and brine interactions in geological reservoirs, the solver incorporates porosity, permeability, and relative permeability models. Validation against the 1D Buckley–Leverett solution [9] and `hybridPorousInterFoam` results revealed differences likely due to the absence of capillary pressure effects and interface capturing. We welcome feedback from the OpenFOAM® community to further enhance solver accuracy and robustness.

Figure 1: Schematic of the simulation setup, including boundary conditions and mesh configuration.

Figure 2: Comparison of time-dependent water saturation predicted by our solver and hybridPorousInterFoam. (Solid: current solver; Dash: hybridPorousInterFoam)

Table 1: Table of Fluid Properties

Properties	Values
Water Density & Viscosity	1000 kg m ⁻³ & 1 × 10 ⁻³ Pa s
Air Density & Viscosity	1 kg m ⁻³ & 1.76 × 10 ⁻⁵ Pa s
Oil Density & Viscosity	800 kg m ⁻³ & 0.1 Pa s

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EULERIAN-LAGRANGIAN TRANSPORT OF SOLID SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS IN A LIQUID METAL MHD FLOW FOR FUSION REACTOR APPLICATIONS

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Keywords: Discrete Particle Method, Solid inclusions, Liquid Metals, MHD, OpenFOAM

Technological challenges that must be overcome to successfully develop nuclear fusion as an energy source, include the demonstration of tritium self-sufficient production in the Breeding Blanket (BB), the management of extremely high heat loads at Plasma Facing Components (PFCs), and economic competitiveness against other energy sources. To achieve these goals in a compact fusion reactor, an attractive solution is to develop an integrated PFC/BB in which a liquid metal (LM) fulfils the functions of plasma-facing material, coolant, tritium breeder and carrier. A neutron multiplier, introduced in the LM as solid spherical inclusions entrained in the main flow, is necessary to improve the breeding performance (tritium breeding ratio). The aim of the study is to characterize the transport, and the distribution of these spherical solid inclusions embedded in a LM flow under the influence of an applied magnetic field which may affect the behaviour of the LM BB [1].

A custom numerical code (called LMMHD-DPMfoam) has been developed to solve the transient flow of a solid (discrete) phase carried by a fluid (continuous) phase. The latter relies on the Eulerian-Lagrangian DPMFoam solver (OpenFOAM v-2212). The code considers the effect of the particle phase volume fraction on the continuous phase considering four-way coupling interactions: fluid-to-solid particles, particles-to-fluid, particle-particle and particle-wall collisions. Regarding the continuous phase, the code has been integrated with the magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) equations based on the low magnetic Reynolds number assumption. Meanwhile, in the discrete phase, two MHD drag models for non-electrically conductive spherical bodies were implemented: one for cases where the magnetic field is aligned (eq. (1) from Ref. [2]), and another one where the magnetic field is perpendicular (eq. (2) from Ref. [3]) to the main flow direction.

$$C_{D_{MHD}}(N_p) = 0.33\sqrt{N_p} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{D_{MHD}}(Re_p, N_p) = \left[\frac{\beta_0}{Re_p^{\beta_1}} (\beta_2 + \beta_3 e^{\beta_4 N_p}) + \beta_5 e^{\beta_6 N_p} \right] N_p^{\beta_7 + \beta_8 e^{\beta_9 N_p}} \quad (2)$$

In eq. (1) and eq. (2), $N_p = \sigma_f d_p B_0^2 / \rho_f |\vec{v}_f - \vec{v}_p|$ is the particle interaction number where the notations “f” and “p” stand respectively for fluid and particle, σ_f is the electrical conductivity, d_p is the diameter, B_0 is the magnetic field, ρ is the density, \vec{v}_f and \vec{v}_p are fluid and particle velocities, and $Re_p = \rho_f |\vec{v}_f - \vec{v}_p| d_p / \mu_f$ is the particle Reynolds number where μ_f is the fluid viscosity. In eq. (2) the β_n are the correlation coefficients evaluated by the numerical study performed in Ref. [3].

To substantiate the confidence in the numerical model, two validation cases are presented. The MHD drag model for a magnetic field aligned with the main flow direction was validated by comparing the particle terminal velocity to that of a solid sphere rising in a stagnant liquid metal, with the magnetic field parallel to the particle motion [4]. Similarly, the drag model for a magnetic field perpendicular to the main flow direction was validated by comparing the rising velocity of the particle to that of rising bubbles in a stagnant liquid metal [5].

The prototypical PFC analyzed in this study can be described as a quarter of a 2D hollow cylinder (fig. 1 (a)) in which the LM is injected with a specified flow rate. The LM considered is lithium at 800 °C. The simulations were performed in two steps. The LM flow was first computed in a 3D geometry derived by the extrusion of fig. 1 (a) in the out-of-plane direction, by assuming that the LM adheres to the substrate and develops into a film of uniform thickness. The LM is bound by a no-slip cylindrical wall on the outer radius, and the free surface is modelled as free-slip cylindrical boundary condition on the inner radius. In the spanwise direction, a finite span is modelled with no-slip boundary conditions representing Hartmann walls. All these surfaces are assumed to be perfectly electrically insulated. A uniform magnetic field \vec{B}_0 is applied transverse to both gravity and the flow. The LM velocity profile recovered, presented in fig. 1 (b), it is the typical one for the configuration previously described, as presented in literature [6].

Fig. 1: (a) Geometry model used in the simulations.

(b) Fully developed velocity profile along azimuthal direction. The free surface is located at $R=0.4\text{m}$.

The second step consisted in mapping the mid-plane velocity solution (in fig. 1 (b)), computed in the 3D geometry, into the equivalent 2D one (in fig. 1 (a)) to perform the simulations with solid particles. The latter were conducted in one-way coupling (fluid-to-solid), including particle-particle collisions. The solid inclusions were considered as a core of lead surrounded by a silicon carbide shell [1], resulting in a density that is 12 times greater than that of the lithium. They were injected from the inlet cross-section of the LM domain, continuously in time, with a flow rate equal to 19% with respect to that of the LM. The PatchInjection model was modified to support physical particle injection. The original random position generator, combined with the collision module and particles larger than $200 \mu\text{m}$, was causing non-physical velocities in the initial time steps due to overlapping particles. To address this, the authors introduced a control on the particle position at injection surface. The control consisted in tracking the positions of particles already introduced in the LM domain, updating them over time according to the fluid velocity, and ensuring that new particles were inserted at a minimum distance of 1.2 diameters from existing ones. The simulations were performed changing the solid inclusions diameter ($700 \mu\text{m} \leq d_p \leq 1\text{mm}$) and the hydrodynamic drag model used (sphere drag and Ergun Wen-Yu drag models). The results show that decreasing the solid inclusions diameter or increasing the magnetic field, the particle residence time in the LM domain increases, meanwhile the modification of the hydrodynamic drag model used implies modification on the particle spatial distribution.

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OPTIMISING THE OVERSET MESH SOLVER IN OPENFOAM FOR MODELLING AERODYNAMICS OF WIND TURBINES

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Keywords: OpenFOAM; overset mesh; offshore renewable energy; aerodynamics and hydrodynamics

Introduction: One of the most popular overset mesh solvers is the one developed in the open-source toolbox OpenFOAM [1]. This powerful tool has been used for numerous applications such as simulating focused wave impacts on point absorber wave energy converters [2], modelling the aerodynamics of a floating offshore wind turbine [3] and hydrodynamics of floating structures [4]. The overset solver has regularly been updated through later versions of OpenFOAM, but minimal updates have focused on the efficiency of the solver. Nevertheless, major improvements have been made to other aspects of the solver. For example, ESI-OpenCFD OpenFOAM v2212 upgraded the ‘hole-cutting’ procedure which allows cells that are used for information exchange via interpolation to be done further away from solid body boundaries. This is beneficial as it allows interpolation further away from areas where the flow exhibits high gradients, consequently improving the flow solution around the body. This improvement is also hypothesised to increase the efficiency of the solver. Given the problems with computational expense, the primary objective of this work is to optimise the OpenFOAM overset mesh solver for offshore renewable applications by improving its efficiency. In particular, the primary efficiency bottleneck is identified and a solution subsequently developed. The new method is validated for the test case of the aerodynamic modelling of an offshore wind-turbine rotor in constant wind. A secondary objective of this work is to also establish whether the updated hole cutting procedure introduced in ESI-OpenCFD OpenFOAM v2212 improves the accuracy of solutions and reduces computational time. This is also established through the test case.

Figure 1: Overset meshes (left) and hierarchically decomposed parts of the background and overset meshes on a single processor at two points in time (right).

Identifying the efficiency bottleneck and proposed new method: A profiling investigation of the OpenFOAM overset solver indicates that the donor searching part of the OGA procedure is the primary efficiency bottleneck. In particular, the markDonors function is found to be the main culprit due to its inefficiency and consequent negative effect on parallel efficiency. The reason for this is that donor searching is done for every cell on both background and overset meshes regardless of whether the cell is actually marked as INTERPOLATED. This means that donors are found for every cell, including HOLE (red) and CALCULATED (blue), even though this is not strictly necessary. The number of necessary inter-processor communications drastically increases if donors have to be found on processors different to the ones containing the corresponding INTERPOLATED cell. This is particularly true if continuously large displacements are present (such as for rotating bodies). To combat the aforementioned problems, a new optimised method is developed which aims to optimise the markDonors function so that it only finds donors for INTERPOLATED cells. This new method is hypothesised to improve computational efficiency by reducing the number of cells for which donors are found 2 and the number of inter-processor communications. This optimised method works in conjunction with the ‘hierarchical’ decomposition method in OpenFOAM which is previously known to be optimal for the overset solver when compared to the default ‘scotch’ method. To understand in detail how inter-processor communications are actually reduced, consider Figure 1. The background and overset meshes (left figure) have been hierarchically decomposed onto four processors with the right figure showing processor 4 in particular. At time $t = 0.01$ s, the decomposed parts of the background and

overset meshes overlap, meaning that most donors can be searched for locally on the same processor. This implies low inter-processor communications. In contrast, at time $t = 0.04$ s, the background and overset meshes no longer overlap, meaning that all donor must be found on remote processors. This implies high inter-processor communications. Therefore, by only finding donors for INTERPOLATED cells at $t = 0.04$ s, the number of times that remote processors have to be searched is greatly reduced. This then implies low inter-processor communications.

Test case: This test case considers the aerodynamics of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) 5 MW wind turbine rotor in constant wind. This test case was originally done using an older OpenFOAM version in [3], hence for comparison, the same geometric and computational setups are used here. The background mesh has dimensions $x \times y \times z \in [-30, 75] \times [-100, 100] \times [-100, 100]$ (m) with mesh configuration $N_x \times N_y \times N_z = 150 \times 120 \times 120$; In addition, the cylindrical body-fitted overset mesh has a radius of 75 m in the yz plane with $x \in [-10, 10]$. The turbine rotor blades are cut from the overset mesh using the snappyHexMesh utility. When modelling wind turbine aerodynamics, it is essential to accurately capture the turbulent boundary layer flow around the rotor. Figure 2 compares time histories of (a) thrust and (b) power for both old and new methods when pushing the hole back 5 layers and for maximum CFL numbers 0.5 and 1, alongside the benchmark FAST and COSA code results [5]. Table 1 compares the computational time as a percentage when using the old and new methods on 8 nodes (1024 processors) for max CFL = 0.5 and 1. The comparisons demonstrate that while the accuracy of the solutions is maintained, the new method substantially improves the computational efficiency of the overset mesh solver in OpenFOAM.

Figure 2: Comparison of the solutions between the old and new methods

Table 1: Comparison of execution times

Case	CFL0.5: Old	CFL0.5: New	CFL1: Old	CFL1: New
Execution time (s)	344,512	122,014	171,603	57,566
Reduction (%)		64.6		66.6

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AERODYNAMICS DESIGN AND CFD SIMULATION OF A COMPACT CAR USING OPENFOAM: A CASE STUDY FROM THE CITY OF BUCARAMANGA, COLOMBIA

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Keywords: CFD, aerodynamics, OpenFOAM, RANS-LES.

Global efforts to mitigate climate change, reinforced by the Paris Agreement, has prompted countries such as Colombia to pursue substantial reductions in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The transportation sector is one of the main contributors to these emissions [1], particularly in urban environments such as Bucaramanga, which is characterized by a warm climate and high-density mobility over short distances. In electric or hybrid vehicles, aerodynamic drag can account for over 50% of total energy consumption at cruising speeds [2], underscoring the necessity to enhance their aerodynamic behavior to improve their efficiency.

This study presents the aerodynamic design and simulation of a compact two-passenger vehicle, employing OpenFOAM as the principal computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tool. The project integrates CAD modeling, meshing strategies, initial RANS-based simulations, and detailed turbulence analysis through a RANS-LES hybrid approach, using high-performance computing resources to reduce simulation time.

The methodology is structured in three main phases:

During the preliminary phase of the project, the vehicle's conceptual design was developed using computer-aided design (CAD) software, prioritizing a low frontal area, smooth transitions, and an aerodynamic profile suitable for urban environments, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CAD model of the compact electric or hybrid vehicle

The initial aerodynamic performance was evaluated using steady-state RANS simulations with the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model (viscous model) selected for its robustness in predicting boundary layers and flow separation zones, due to the viscosity limiter [3]. The computational domain was defined in accordance with the standard recommendations outlined in references [4] and [5]: the inlet length was set to $3H$, outlet length to $10H$, and the lateral and top margins to $4H$ and $6H$, respectively (It should be noted that H indicates the vehicle height). Adequate mesh resolution was ensured by maintaining a value of $y^+ \approx 1$ on the surface, allowing direct resolution of the viscous sublayer without relying on wall functions, thereby improving the accuracy of aerodynamic coefficient predictions.

Mesh generation involved local refinements around the vehicle surface and in the wake region to capture key phenomena such as vortex shedding and recirculation. Mesh independence was verified through a convergence study by analyzing residuals, as well as surface forces and stress moments, where drag coefficient (C_d) variations between successive refinements were below 1%.

The second phase of the study involved a parametric study to assess the effect of three key variables on aerodynamic performance: 1. Vehicle speed, ranging from 40 km/h to 70 km/h to represent typical urban conditions in Bucaramanga; 2. Ground clearance, which was modified between 250 mm and 300 mm to study its influence on underflow and lift; and 3. The angle of certain aerodynamic accessories, such as side mirrors and the rear spoiler, which significantly affect

drag and stability. For each configuration, drag (Cd) and lift (Cl) coefficients were evaluated, and surface pressure distributions were analyzed to identify areas of improvement.

In the third phase, a hybrid simulation approach was implemented using the $k-\omega$ SST-DDES (Delayed Detached Eddy Simulation) model, which combines the robustness of RANS modeling in near-wall areas with the level of detail of LES in regions away from the solid, such as the vehicle wake, which is due to the nature of turbulence as a non-local process, i.e. the motion is statistically correlated in space [6]. This methodology is particularly well-suited for complex geometries, such as those found in automobiles, where thin boundary layer zones and highly separated flow regions coexist. One of the primary limitations of the pure LES approach pertains to the stringent requirements for spatial resolution in both the spanwise and streamwise directions. If the mesh does not meet these requirements, the result is poor turbulence resolution and unreliable predictions in the LES zone [7]. In this context, the DDES model offers an effective solution. By incorporating a delay in the regime shift between RANS to LES, it ensures that the boundary layer is not treated as LES, even in areas where the mesh is not sufficiently fine. Consequently, this prevents premature switching to LES within the boundary layer, thereby preserving its accurate resolution with RANS and circumventing the numerical errors characteristic of the classical DES model.

The model was configured to operate in RANS mode near the vehicle surfaces using the $k-\omega$ SST formulation, while LES mode was automatically activated in regions where the flow detaches and three-dimensional turbulent structures are formed. To ensure physically realistic initial conditions for this phase, the turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate obtained from the previous RANS simulation were used to initialize the turbulence field.

Throughout the study, OpenFOAM proved to be a powerful tool not only for simulation but also as a core component of the iterative design process, accelerating prototyping and highlighting the potential of open-source environments for the development of sustainable vehicle solutions in Latin American contexts.

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EXTENDING INTERFOAM FOR COUPLED ELECTROHYDRODYNAMICS: A STUDY OF ELECTRO-FLOW-FOCUSED LIQUID JETS

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Keywords: *interFoam, flow-focusing, electric field, jetting, electrospray, liquid jet*

Introduction

We report a successful extension of the standard interFoam solver to model the electrostatic force produced by a high-voltage electric field. The solver was validated using experimental data [1] and was used to model micron-sized jets produced by a combination of flow-focusing and electrospraying, also called electro-flow-focusing [2]. Following experimental exploration [3,4] and proof-of-concept simulation [5], we are investigating the influence of the liquid electrical properties on the produced jet. The investigated properties are the electrical conductivity K_l and the electrical permittivity ε_l of the liquid phase. Other parameters, namely the liquid flow rate Q , applied gas pressure ΔP , applied electric potential ϕ_0 , gas electrical properties and the nozzle geometry were kept constant.

Methods

The standard interFoam solver provides the incompressible Navier-Stokes equations for multiple fluids:

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla P + \nabla \cdot \left[\mu (\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T) - \frac{2}{3} \mu (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{I} \right] + \mathbf{f}_E + \sigma \kappa \delta_s \mathbf{n}, \quad (2)$$

where ρ , \mathbf{v} , P , μ , σ , κ , δ_s and \mathbf{n} denote density, velocity, pressure, dynamic viscosity, surface tension, interface curvature, Kronecker surface delta function and surface normal, respectively. Additional source term \mathbf{f}_E represents the volumetric electric force,

$$\mathbf{f}_E = \rho_E \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{2} E^2 \nabla \varepsilon. \quad (3)$$

The first term on r.h.s. represents the force exerted on the free electric charges seeded in the liquid, while the second term represents the force exerted on the molecular dipoles of the phase constituent. Here, \mathbf{E} denotes the electric field and ρ_E is the volumetric charge density. The electric model was derived directly from the Poisson-Nerst-Planck equation without reaction and thermal diffusion term,

$$\frac{\partial n_k}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_k \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla \cdot (n_k e z_k w_k \mathbf{E}), \quad (4)$$

where n , e , z and w denote the molar concentration, elementary charge, valence number and the mobility of ionic species k . Moles of ionic species per unit volume are transformed into charges per unit volume, $\rho_{E,k} = F z_k n_k$, where F is the Faraday's constant. Summation over all species $\rho_{E,k}$ yields the macroscopic or volumetric charge density, as used in Eq. (3)

$$\rho_E = \sum_k \rho_{E,k} = F \sum_k z_k n_k. \quad (5)$$

We can transform the Poisson-Nerst-Planck equation into the conservation equation of macroscopic charge density by multiplying both sides with $N_A e z_k$ and summing over all k species,

$$\frac{\partial \rho_E}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_E \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla \cdot (K \mathbf{E}), \quad (6)$$

where we introduced another macroscopic variable, the electrical conductivity $K = \sum_k w_k F e z_k^2 n_k$. The omission of the thermal diffusivity term from Eq. (6) is justified since the induced ion velocity due to the thermal diffusion is several orders smaller than the mechanism of electric drift. The usage of fully reacted solvents reasons the zero rate of species production. The model is closed with the electrostatic Maxwell equations,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\varepsilon \mathbf{E}) = \rho_E. \quad (8)$$

Case setup

An axisymmetric computational domain replicating the EFF experimental setup described by Gañán-Calvo et al. [2] was created. The setup includes a charged capillary with a diameter of 100 μm , positioned inside a pressurized metal cylinder (acting as an electrode) held at zero electric potential. This cylinder features an orifice with a diameter of 50 μm , aligned

with the capillary. The separation distance between the capillary tip and the orifice was 100 μm . The outlet chamber dimensions are 1.575×0.5 mm, and the capillary's length-to-radius ratio is set to 6 to allow for the fully developed velocity profile. The operating conditions and the electric properties of the gas were maintained constant in all simulations: the liquid flow rate was fixed at 0.75 mL/h, the gas overpressure at 20 mbar, the applied electric potential at 2 kV, the gas electrical conductivity at $1\text{E-}14$ S/m, and the relative gas electrical permittivity at 1. A structured hexahedral mesh with five levels of local refinement was employed. Cells at the finest refinement level were sized 0.31×0.31 μm , with a total cell count of 650k. The solution was computed on a HPC cluster (AMD EPYC 7402 2.8 GHz) using two nodes, each equipped with 48 cores.

Preliminary results

A snapshot of selected computed fields is shown in Fig. (1) and (2) for the case with $\epsilon_l = 1.93$ and $K_l = 1\text{E-}6$ S/m. The highest Mach number in all simulations was below 0.3, which justifies using the incompressible solver. The electric force influence is mostly contained in the intermediate region between the Taylor cone and the fully developed jet, which agrees well with the electro spray theory [6].

Figure 1: Electric potential (top) and velocity (bottom) fields.

Figure 2: Electric field (top) and electric force (bottom) magnitude with electric field lines and force vectors.

We anticipate jet diameter reduction by increasing the liquid electrical conductivity, thereby further focusing the jet via the electric force while providing stabilization of the jet with the co-flowing gas. Such configuration can potentially produce thinner jets than electro spray only or flow-focusing only.

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INSIGHTS INTO CONCENTRATION POLARIZATION AND FLOW DYNAMICS IN A CH₄/CO₂ SEPARATION MEMBRANE MODULE

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Keywords: Gas Separation, Membranes, Module, CO₂, CFD, OpenFOAM.

The separation of CO₂ from CH₄ is a critical process in gas purification, with significant implications for energy efficiency, environmental sustainability, and greenhouse gas mitigation. This study employs Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to analyze and visualize the flow behavior in a zeolite membrane module designed for CO₂/CH₄ separation, with applications in biogas purification and biomass-derived gas treatment. Based on the experimental framework of Jeong et al. (2022) [1], the research investigates the underlying phenomena governing separation performance, focusing on flow dynamics, concentration polarization and depletion effects.

The membrane module geometry (Figure 1(a)) comprises a feed inlet, a retentate outlet and a permeate outlet, with a zeolite membrane (5 cm in length) layer supported by an impermeable structure (Figure 1(b)). Simulations were performed using *OpenFOAM v11*, employing the *multicomponentFluid* solver, in laminar conditions. The computational mesh, generated with *snappyHexMesh*, consisted of 196,824 cells with refinement near the membrane interface. Membrane permeances were derived from Jeong et al.'s [1] high-flow-rate data: $2.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s Pa})$ for CH₄ and $1.13 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s Pa})$ for CO₂, with these values held constant.

Figure 1: Membrane module.

The CFD results closely match experimental data for CH₄ concentration at the retentate outlet (Figure 2), validating the model's accuracy. Flow dynamics are further analyzed through concentration distributions at feed flow rates of 100 mL/min and 1000 mL/min (Figures 3(a) and 3(b)). The simulations reveal distinct performance characteristics at different flow rates. At 100 mL/min, the retentate outlet achieves higher CH₄ concentration, despite stronger concentration polarization near the membrane surface. The 1000 mL/min condition exhibits improved bulk mixing but yields lower CH₄ purity. Streamline visualizations (Figure 4) reveal asymmetric flow patterns, with recirculation zones near the permeate outlet entrance, reducing active membrane area utilization.

The interplay between flow rates and concentration gradients underscores the need to optimize feed distribution to minimize polarization while maximizing membrane contact. For biogas and biomass-derived gas applications—where CO₂ removal directly impacts methane purity and emission reductions—these findings suggest operational adjustments. For instance, intermediate flow rates or baffle-enhanced mixing could balance energy use and separation efficiency. Additionally, the impermeable support layer (Figure 1(b)) influences local flow resistance, motivating further study into alternative support geometries.

In conclusion, this CFD study provides insights into zeolite membrane module performance by visualizing flow behavior and its impact on CO₂/CH₄ separation. Future work will explore dynamic flow control and membrane material variations to further improve separation efficiency and scalability.

Figure 2: CH₄ Molar fraction on the retentate outlet: comparison between experimental [1] and numerical results.

Figure 3: CH₄ mass fraction distribution for two flow rates.

Figure 4: Streamlines of gas flow through the module, for 1000 mL/min.

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CFD SIMULATION OF DEGRADED VISUAL ENVIRONMENTS AT THE CUES SITE ON MAMMOTH MOUNTAIN, CA

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Keywords: *Blowing Snow, Degraded Visual Environments, Atmospheric Flow*

The impact of blowing snow on visual environments in mountainous terrain is a critical concern for both safety and operational efficiency. Predicting degraded visual environments is difficult due to complex wind dynamics at high altitudes interacting with varied terrain features at multiple scales. We use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to simulate the wind field around the CUES (Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory / University of California Santa Barbara Energy Site) observation area at Mammoth Mountain in California, USA. Simulations were performed using the open-source finite volume toolbox OpenFOAM for multiple wind speeds and directions at sub-meter resolution near solid surfaces. This approach allows for the calculation of high-resolution shear stresses on the surface, which are used to calculate snow saltation potential. Results reveal the intricate interplay between topography, wind speed, and snow transport, identifying fine-scale topographic features that result in significant visibility reduction.

Figure 1: Left: Regional velocity profile for a winter storm event. Right: Shear stresses generated on Mammoth mountain contributing to degraded visual environments. Flow is from left to right.

Acknowledgments

Funding for this work was provided by the US Army Corps of Engineers Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory (CRREL). Atmospheric data was acquired from the National Weather Service and topography data was provided by the CRREL/UCSB Energy Site (CUES).

Suppression of electroconvection around ion-selective membrane using shear-thinning electrolyte

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Keywords: Ion-selective membrane, Electroconvection, Chaotic flow, Electrolytes

Ion-selective membranes have received a wide range of applications in medical and industrial processes, such as electro-dialysis for the removal or isolation of chemicals, desalination, flow-electrode capacitive de-ionization, redox-flow battery systems, etc. Typically, when an electric field is applied across an ion-selective membrane, it induces an electrophoretic force on the ions in the vicinity of the membrane surface, leading to a net push or pull on the fluid element, which alters the corresponding flow and ionic potential distribution within the electrolyte. The flow of ions can be mapped and quantified as the net electro-convective current, where an external electric field interacts with the space charge density of surfaces within the flow system's boundaries. The current work investigates the electroconvection phenomena within a shear-thinning electrolyte entrapped between an ion-selective membrane and an electrode surface. The resulting velocity and ionic concentration profiles are analyzed and delineated in terms of the instantaneous velocity and concentration contours, streamlines, ionic current density, and average kinetic energies of the electrolyte. Moreover, the phenomenon of ionic mixing or the flow stability near the membrane surface is delineated by examining the transition of the flow from a steady state to periodic oscillation and subsequently to the 'chaotic or mixed' behavior. A governing framework of Poisson-Nernst-Planck equations coupled with the momentum equation has been used to develop and design a two-dimensional numerical model to investigate the flow and ionic flux and the subsequent ionic stability and mixing to identify the 'over-limiting' current regimes in ion transfer in ion-selective membranes present in microfluidic and electrochemical flow systems. In essence, the increase in shear-thinning behavior or the decrease in the value of the power-law index of liquid electrolyte and the decrease in the value of the applied potential appear to dampen the intensity of electroconvection near an ion-selective surface, leading to the suppression of the flow circulations and hence a consequent decrease in the induced ionic current.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of a model problem.

References

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Organization

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Tuesday		Plenary session	Invited and topical talks	1
		Chairperson	M. de Gennaro	
		Room	Auditorium	
9:00		C. Chimani	Opening word	Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
9:15		A. Quarteroni	A Journey from the America's Cup to the Human Heart: 20 Years of Fluid Dynamics (and Much More)	Politecnico di Milano (Italy), Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland)
10:05		E. de Villiers	Accelerating CFD: Progress on HELYX GPU-Powered Solvers and Next-Gen Mesher	Engys S.R.L.
10:40		BoF coffee break		
		Technical session	Numerical methods	1
		Chairperson	H. Rusche	
		Room	Auditorium	
		<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
11:00		IMPLEMENTING A JACOBIAN-FREE NEWTON-KRYLOV METHOD IN OPENFOAM BASED ON PETSC: APPLICATIONS TO SOLIDS, FLUIDS AND FLUID-SOLID INTERACTION	PHILIP CARDIFF, DYLAN ARMFIELD, ZELJKO TUKOVIC, IVAN BATISTIC	University College Dublin
11:20		MULTI-VARIATE NON-NEWTONIAN VISCOSITY MODEL IN CFD	BAHRAM HADDADI, MOHAMMAD AMIN GHORBANI, CHRISTIAN MARSCHIK, MOHAMMAD POURHOSSEINIAN	Competence Center CHASE GmbH
11:40		A TEMPORALLY SECOND-ORDER ACCURATE FINITE VOLUME DISCRETIZATION OF ONE-FIELD NAVIER-STOKES EQUATIONS WITH HIGH DENSITY RATIOS	JUN LIU, TOBIAS TOLLE, DAVIDE ZUZIO, JEAN-LUC ESTIVALEZES, SANTIAGO M. DAMIAN, DIETER BOTHE, TOMISLAV MARIC	Technical University of Darmstadt
12:00		Lunch break		
		Technical session	Compressible flows	1
		Chairperson	G. Keetels	
		Room	Auditorium	
		<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
13:30		APPLICATION OF ADVANCED ACTUATOR LINE METHOD FOR COMPRESSIBLE PROPELLER SIMULATIONS IN OPENFOAM	LOUIS FLIESSBACH, MOHAMED SUHAIL ERAMASRAYILLATH ABDULSEMATH, HENDRIK HETMANN, THILO KNACKE, GUILLAUME MARTINAT, CHARLES MOCKETT, NILAKANTHA SAHOO	Upstream CFD GmbH
13:50		EVOLUTION OF AN UNDER-EXPANDED JET OF HYDROGEN-ENRICHED NATURAL GAS FOLLOWING ACCIDENTAL RELEASE FROM A PIPELINE	YARA OMAR, JOSHUA BRINKERHOFF	University of British Columbia
14:10		rhoCubic4KFoam: A FOURTH-ORDER MULTI-SPECIES COMPRESSIBLE FLOW SOLVER ON UNSTRUCTURED GRIDS	Francesco Duronio, Andrea Di Mascio, Carlo Villante	Universita degli studi dell'Aquila
		Technical session	Compressible flows + PP	2
		Chairperson	M. Popovac	
		Room	Auditorium	
		<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
14:30		SIMULATING GAS DYNAMICS OF MULTI-SPECIES, HIGH-PRESSURE JETS USING blastFOAM: SENSITIVITY TO EQUATIONS OF STATE, GAS COMPOSITION, AND MODEL GEOMETRY	YARA OMAR, JOSHUA BRINKERHOFF	University of British Columbia
14:50		VALIDATION OF A PRESSURE-BASED COUPLED SOLVER FOR HIGHLY COMPRESSIBLE TURBOMACHINERY FLOWS	PAOLO GEREMIA, GEORGIOS KARPOUZAS, APOSTOLOS KRASSAS, SALVATORE RENDA, THOMAS SCHUMACHER	Engys S.R.L.
15:10		Poster presentation 1: two-minutes oral presentations of the posters from the Poster session Group 1	.	.
15:30		Afternoon coffee break		
		Technical session	Multiphysics	1
		Chairperson	H. Nilsson	
		Room	Auditorium	
		<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
15:50		DEVELOPMENT OF A PRECICE ADAPTER FOR FOAM EXTEND	PATRICK HOHN, JULIAN KUNKEL	University of Gottingen
16:10		A HIGH-PERFORMANCE MULTIPHYSICS SIMULATION FRAMEWORK BASED ON OPEN-SOURCE CFD FOR LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES	QIYU CHEN, LANCE ZHAO, ZHE LI	Tsinghua University
16:30		NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF PATIENT TECHNIQUE EFFECTS ON PMDI PERFORMANCE	FEDERICO ANGIUS, RICCARDO ROSSI, ANDREA BENASSI	Red Fluid Dynamics
		Technical session	Multiphysics	2
		Chairperson	H. Marschall	
		Room	Auditorium	
		<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
16:50		COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF OIL DISTRIBUTION ON ELECTRIC MOTOR SHAFT BEARINGS USING SPH AND CFD METHODOLOGIES	SERGIO TOSI, ANTONELLA CALAMIELLO	Dumarey Automotive Italia S.p.A.
17:10		COUPLING PLASMA-INDUCED EHD FORCES WITH OPENFOAM FOR SCALABLE FLOW CONTROL IN PLASMA CATALYSIS REACTORS	S. WILCZEK, S. SAKR, D. FILLA, M. VASS, T.MUSSENBRÖCK, C. KOCH	Technical University George Agricola
17:30		TURBULENT GAS-LIQUID SIMULATIONS OF JET KNIFE FOR HOT-DIP GALVANIZING OF WIRES	EMAD TANDIS	Aston University

Tuesday

9:00

9:15

10:05

10:40

BoF coffee break

Technical session Thermofluids, reacting flows, combustion **1**

Chairperson D. Dvorak

Room Business Stage 1.1

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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11:00

	TOWARD FIRE DYNAMICS SIMULATIONS OF THERMAL RUNAWAY PROPAGATION IN BATTERY ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS	DANYAL MOHADDES, YI WANG	FM, Research Division
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11:20

	A GENERALIZED DYNAMIC THICKENED FLAME FRAMEWORK FOR HYDROGEN COMBUSTION IN AERO-ENGINES WITH CSP DIAGNOSTICS	Federico Ghioldi, Christos E. Frouzakis, Federico Piscaglia	Politecnico di Milano
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11:40

	EFFICIENT CFD-PBM APPROACH FOR MODELLNG COOLING CRYSTALLIZATION SCALE-UP PROCESSES	ALFRED REID, RICCARDO ROSSI, ANDREA BENASSI, CIRO COTTINI	Red Fluid Dynamics
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12:00

Lunch break

Technical session Numerical methods **2**

Chairperson T. Uroic

Room Business Stage 1.1

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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13:30

	MODELLING OF FOAM DRAINAGE AND FLOW IN STOKES REGIME	MARAT MUKHAMETZHANOV, DMITRY ESKIN, ALEXANDER VIKHANSKY	University of Alberta
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13:50

	Tuning OpenFOAM's GAMG settings using Bayesian optimization	Janis Geise, Tanuj Ravi, Tomislav Maric, Mohammed Elwardi Fadel, Alessandro Rigazzi, Andrew Shao, Andre Weiner	Technical University of Dresden
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14:10

	VERIFICATION OF A FINITE VOLUME SOLVER FOR ACTIVE AND PASSIVE CARDIAC MATERIAL BEHAVIOUR	AARON MULLEN-HALES, PHILIP CARDIFF	University College Dublin
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Technical session Numerical methods **3**

Chairperson C. Mockett

Room Business Stage 1.1

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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14:30

	ON DEVELOPMENT OF FINITE VOLUME METHOD IMPLEMENTATION OF MINDLIN THICK PLATES IN SOLIDS4FOAM	TOMAS VALLDEPERAS, IVAN BATISTIC, MASSIMILIANO RENZI, PHILIP CARDIFF, SEEVANI BALI	Free University of Bolzano
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14:50

	Forced-motion simulations of vortex-induced vibrations of wind turbine blades coupling open-source CFD tool with advanced RBF mesh morphing	Andrea Lopez, Emiliano Costa, Daniel Deising, Marco Evangelos Biancolini	Leonardo S.p.A.
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15:10

	A FRAMEWORK FOR INITIAL TRANSIENT DETECTION AS STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF CONVERGENCE IN CFD SIMULATIONS	L. SCANDURRA, P. ALEXIAS, E. DE VILLIERS	Engys S.R.L.
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15:30

Afternoon coffee break

Technical session Multiphase, dispersed flows **1**

Chairperson R. Gomez

Room Business Stage 1.1

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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15:50

	A COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS MODEL FOR THE SIMULATION OF FLASH-BOILING FLOW INSIDE PRESSURIZED METERED DOSE INHALERS	RICCARDO ROSSI, ANDREA BENASSI, CIRO COTTINI	Red Fluid Dynamics
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16:10

	ADVANCES IN LIQUID FILM SIMULATIONS USING GEOMETRIC VOLUME-OF-FLUID	TIAGO CAMPOS, GEORG BROSIGKE, LIONEL GAMET, OLIVIER LAGET, VERONIQUE PENIN, PASCAL ALIX, JENS-UWE REPKE	IFP Energies nouvelles
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16:30

	On the implementation of free-surface for a prolate spheroid submerged underwater	Lakshmi Madhavan Miller	Virginia Tech
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Technical session Multiphase, dispersed flows **2**

Chairperson R. K. Shanmugasundaram

Room Business Stage 1.1

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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16:50

	HYBRID VOF TO LAGRANGIAN CFD MODEL FOR JET BREAKUP AND SPRAY TRANSPORT	ULRICH HECK, MARTIN BECKER	DHCAE Tools GmbH
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17:10

	CFD-BASED DESIGN OPTIMISATION INVESTIGATION OF AN ARGON STIRRED STEEL LADLE	ZINEDINE KHATIR	University of Leeds
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17:30

	Modeling High-Viscosity Spray Injection Using Volume-of-Fluid Method and Large Eddy Simulation	Po-Han Chen, Alberto Ceschin, Junjun Guo, Hong G. Im	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology
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Tuesday

9:00

9:15

10:05

10:40

BoF coffee break

Technical session **Aeroacoustics** **1**

Chairperson H. Kuehnelt

Room Business Stage 1.2

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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11:00

	IMPLEMENTATION OF THE ACOUSTIC RADIATION FORCE IN OPENFOAM	FILIP STRNISA, SIMON KUHN	KU Leuven
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11:20

	HYBRID COMPUTATIONAL AEROACOUSTIC SIMULATIONS OF UAV PROPELLER NOISE	FRAN PIPUNIC, LUKA BALATINEC, TESSA UROIC	University of Zagreb
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11:40

	An accurate near-field aeroacoustic model for low Mach number flows	Benedetto Di Paolo, Eugene de Villiers, Jakub Knir, Paolo Geremia	Engys S.R.L.
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12:00

Lunch break

Technical session **Offshore, wind, energy** **1**

Chairperson P. Cardiff

Room Business Stage 1.2

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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13:30

	CFD ANALYSIS OF TRIPLY PERIODIC MINIMAL SURFACE AIR-AIR HEAT EXCHANGERS: INFLUENCE OF GEOMETRY AND CELL SIZE ON PERFORMANCE	MILAN KARDOS, IMRE GELLAI, MIRZA POPOVAC	Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
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13:50

	NUMERICAL MODELLING OF SCOUR AROUND OFFSHORE STRUCTURES	Ranjith Khumar Shanmugasundaram, Sergey Lesnik, Henrik Rusche , V. S. Ozgur Kirca, B. M. Sumer	WIKKI GmbH
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14:10

	OPENFOAM CFD SIMULATION OF STEAM AXIAL TURBINE STAGE ON GPU	SIMONE BNÁ, ETTORE FADIGA, GIUSEPPE GIAQUINTO, TOMMASO ZANELLI	CINECA Consorzio Interuniversitario
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Technical session **Offshore, wind, energy** **2**

Chairperson M. Nobrega

Room Business Stage 1.2

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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14:30

	SWENSE-Based CFD: A faster approach to wave structure simulations	Sithik Aliyar, Henrik Bredmose, Johan Roenby	DTU Wind and Energy Systems
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14:50

	MULTI-REGION CFD SIMULATION OF THE THERMAL BEHAVIOUR IN AN AUGER PYROLYSIS REACTOR	THORSTEN JONACH, CHRISTIAN JORDAN, KARIN WIELAND, ANGELIKA, LUCKENEDER, DANIELA MEITNER, BAHRAM HADDADI, MICHAEL HARASEK	Technical University of Vienna
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15:10

	VALIDATION OF A FINITE VOLUME SIMO-REISSNER BEAM METHOD FOR MOORED FLOATING SOLAR PLATFORMS	COLM MC ALISTER, AMIRHOSSEIN TARAN, MORGAN CAMPBELL, SEEVANI BALI, MADJID KARIMIRAD, VIKRAM PAKRASHI, PHILIP CARDIFF	University College Dublin
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15:30

Afternoon coffee break

Technical session **Porous media** **1**

Chairperson B. Haddadi

Room Business Stage 1.2

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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15:50

	MULTISCALE FIXED BED REACTOR MODELING WITH INTERNAL PORE DIFFUSION: COMPARING 3D PRCFD AND 2D POROUS MEDIA SIMULATIONS	ERIC DAYMO, MATTHIAS HETTEL	Tonkomo, LLC
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16:10

	MODELING CAKE FILTRATION VIA POROUS MEDIA APPROACH	JOSEF TAUSENDSCHÖN	Research Center Pharmaceutical Engineering GmbH
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16:30

	APPLICATION OF THE CUSTOM DRIFT-FLUX SOLVER FOR ANNULAR FLOW OF FLUID WITH PARTICLES	ALEXANDER STAROSTIN	Baker Hughes
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Technical session **Molding, casting** **1**

Chairperson H. Patrick

Room Business Stage 1.2

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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16:50

	IMPLEMENTATION AND VERIFICATION OF A FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION SOLVER FOR INJECTION MOULDING SIMULATION	R. RIBEIRO, B. RAMOA, R. COSTA, J. M. NOBREGA	University of Minho
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17:10

	TOWARDS SMART MANUFACTURING IN EXTRUSION BLOW MOLDING: A COMPUTATIONAL APPROACH FOR SUSTAINABLE PROCESS OPTIMIZATION	WAGNER DE CAMPOS GALUPPO, PEDRO SANTANA, FRANCISCO ALVES, JOAO MIGUEL NOBREGA	University of Minho
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17:30

	TOWARDS THE DEVELOPMENT OF CASTING ADVISORY SYSTEMS: SIMULATION OF DIRECT CHILL CASTING PROCESSES	RODRIGO GÓMEZ VÁZQUEZ, SIAMAK RAFIEZADEH, AMIR HERR, SOFIJA MILICIC, DAVID BLACHER, LEO SCHWARZMEIER	LKR Light Metals Technologies, AIT
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Tuesday

9:00

9:15

10:05

10:40

BoF coffee break

Technical session | **OpenFOAM HPC Challenge** | **HW1**

Chairman: Mark Wasserman/Sergey Lesnik/Henrik Rusche

Room: Business Stage 1.3

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
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11:00	Introduction	Mark Wasserman Sergey Lesnik, Henrik Rusche	Huawei Wikki GmbH
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11:20	Summary of Contributions for the Hardware Track	Mark Wasserman Sergey Lesnik, Henrik Rusche	Huawei Wikki GmbH
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11:40	Hardware Track Participant Talks		
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12:00

Lunch break

Technical session | **OpenFOAM HPC Challenge** | **HW2**

Chairman: Mark Wasserman/Sergey Lesnik/Henrik Rusche

Room: Business Stage 1.3

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
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13:30	Hardware Track Participant Talks		
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13:50	Hardware Track Participant Talks		
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14:10	Hardware Track Discussion		
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Technical session | **OpenFOAM HPC Challenge** | **SW1**

Chairman: Mark Wasserman/Sergey Lesnik/Gregor Olenik

Room: Business Stage 1.3

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
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14:30	Summary of Contributions for the Software Track	Mark Wasserman Sergey Lesnik Gregor Olenik	Huawei Wikki GmbH TUM
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14:50	Software Track Participant Talks		
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15:10	Software Track Participant Talks		
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15:30

Afternoon coffee break

Technical session | **OpenFOAM HPC Challenge** | **SW2**

Chairman: Mark Wasserman/Sergey Lesnik/Gregor Olenik

Room: Business Stage 1.3

	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
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15:50	Software Track Participant Talks		
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16:10	Software Track Discussion		
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16:30	Summary + Next Steps for OHC		
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16:50

17:10

17:30

Tuesday

9:00
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14:30
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15:10
15:30

BoF coffee break

Lunch break

Afternoon coffee break

Poster session	Group 1		
Room	Multimedia Stage		
	Title	Authors	
		Affiliation (first author)	
15:50	1) DEVELOPMENT OF AN UNDERGROUND CARBON DIOXIDE MIGRATION MODEL IN OPENFOAM	FENG-HSIEN OU, TA-JUNG CHENG, MING-LUNG LI, WEN-YI CHANG	National Center for High-performance Computing (TW)
	2) VENTILATION PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS ACCORDING TO THE OPENING RATIO OF A SENSOR GUARD	KYEONGHEOUM NA, DOYEON PI, HEETAJEON, HYUNCHAE LIM, CHANKYU SON	Chungju university
	3) INSIGHTS INTO CONCENTRATION POLARIZATION AND FLOW DYNAMICS IN A CH4/CO2 SEPARATION MEMBRANE MODULE	ADRIANO ROSA	University of Brasilia
	4) CO2 PHASE CHANGE SIMULATIONS IN A CROGENIC INSULATED TANK BY OPENFOAM	SEYON AHN, SUNHO PARK	Korea Maritime and Ocean University
	5) SPECTRAL UNCERTAINTY QUANTIFICATION OF PRESSURE LOSS THROUGH A 90° PIPE BEND USING SST K-OMEGA	WEEKS, B., TABOR, G.	University of Exeter
	6) OPTIMISING THE OVERSET MESH SOLVER IN OPENFOAM FOR MODELLING AERODYNAMICS OF WIND TURBINES	RANJODH RAI, LING QIAN, ZHIHUA MA, WEI BAI	Manchester Metropolitan University
	7) NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF COAL AND BIOMASS COMBUSTION USING ARRHENIUS-BASED MODELS AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS	IVAN HEINRICH, MATEJ CORAK, TESSA UROIC	University of Zagreb
	8) NUMERICAL STUDY OF A BLUFF BODY STABILIZED LEAN PREMIXED HYDROGEN FLAME USING ARTIFICIALLY THICKENED FLAME MODEL IN OPENFOAM	RICCARDO VADI, ANTONIO ANDREINI	University of Florence
	9) AERODYNAMICS DESIGN AND CFD SIMULATION OF A COMPACT CAR USING OPENFOAM: A CASE STUDY FROM THE CITY OF BUCARAMANGA, COLOMBIA	ADRIAN VARGAS-LIZARAZO, JORGE LUIS CHACÓN-VELASCO	Universidad Industrial de Santander
17:50	10) RESEARCH ON UTILIZATION TREND AND SERVICE APPLICATION OF GPU-BASED OPENFOAM	TAE HO YOON	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information

Wednesday	Plenary session	Invited talks	2
	Chairperson	M. Popovac	
	Room	Auditorium	
9:00	H. Jasak	A year in review	University of Cambridge
9:50	A. Soldati	Physics of the complex interface dynamics in drop-laden turbulence	Technical University of Vienna
10:40	BoF coffee break		
	Technical session	General CFD, HPC, GPU	1
	Chairperson	P. Cardiff	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
11:00	Addressing the Over- and Undersubscription Challenge of GPU Based Linear Solver	GREGOR OLENIK, HARTWIG ANZT	Technical University of Munich
11:20	EXPRESSION TEMPLATES IN OPENFOAM	MATTIJS JANSSENS	ESI-OpenCFD
11:40	BEST MESHING PRACTICES FOR HIGH-QUALITY CFD SIMULATIONS	IVAN OREMOVIC, FRANJO JURETIC	Creative Fields, Ltd.
12:00	Lunch break		
	Technical session	Optimization methods	1
	Chairperson	A. Weiner	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
13:30	On the Use of Model Order Reduction Techniques for Thermal Topology Optimization	Luis Fernando Cusicanqui Lopez, Lieven Vervecken, Ine Vandebek Florian Feppon, Karl Meerbergen	KU Leuven
13:50	A BAYESIAN OPTIMISATION FRAMEWORK FOR DESIGNING HYDROGEN INJECTION SYSTEMS IN NATURAL GAS PIPELINES	DANIEL SILVA, EDGAR FERNANDES, MARCELO MARTINS	HyLab – Green Hydrogen Collaborative Laboratory
14:10	STUDY OF OPTIMIZED SOLUTION FOR TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION BASED ON THE BUOYANTBOUSSINESQSIMPLEFOAM WITH THE CONTINUOUS ADJOINT METHOD	JAE SUNG YANG, SANG DON LEE, JUNE KEE MIN	Pusan National University
	Technical session	Optimization methods + PP	2
	Chairperson	M. Popovac	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
14:30	AN APPROXIMATE NEWTON-KRYLOV PRESSURE-BASED INCOMPRESSIBLE RANS SOLVER FOR AERODYNAMIC SHAPE OPTIMIZATION	NIKOLAOS GALANOS, EVANGELOS PAPOUTSIS-KIACHAGIAS, KYRIAKOS GIANNAKOGLU	National Technical University of Athens
14:50	A NOVEL OPENFOAM-BASED OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK FOR AUTOMATICALLY BALANCING FLOW IN PROFILE EXTRUSION DIES	GABRIEL WAGNER, JOAO VIDAL, PIERRE BARBAT, JEAN-MARC GONNET, JOAO M. NOBREGA	University of Minho
15:10	Poster presentation 2: two-minutes oral presentations of the posters from the Poster session Group 2	.	.
15:30	Afternoon coffee break		
	Technical session	Multiphysics	3
	Chairperson	J. Nagy	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
15:50	A NUMERICAL FRAMEWORK FOR WEAR ANALYSIS OF ROUGH SURFACE CONTACTS ACROSS LUBRICATION REGIMES	LUKA BALATINEC, TESSA UROIC, HRVOJE JASAK	University of Zagreb
16:10	IN-SILICO EVALUATION OF THE PULMONARY ARTERY HYPERTENSION USING CFD SIMULATIONS	Francesco Duronio, Paola Marchetti, Carlo Villante	Universita degli studi dell'Aquila
16:30	OPEN-SOURCE APPROACH TO THE PROTOTYPING OF LASER SHOCK PEENING	MARTIN ISOZ, PAVEL GRUBER, LUCIE KUBICKOVA, ANNA KOVARNOVA, DUSAN GABRIEL, JAN KAUFMAN, JAN BRAJER	Czech Academy of Sciences
	Technical session	Multiphysics	4
	Chairperson	S. Lesnik	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
16:50	NON-SPHERICAL DEM CONTACT MODEL CONSISTENT WITH HERTZIAN FORMULATION FOR LARGE-SCALE CFD-DEM	ONDREJ STUDENIK, MARTIN KOTOUC SOUREK, MARTIN ISOZ	Czech Academy of Sciences
17:10	Progress in Design and Analysis of Fusion Power Plant Breeder Blanket Systems using OpenFOAM	Aleksander Dubas, Benedict Smith, Pranav Naduvakkate, Rupert Eardley-Brunt, Gerasimos Politis, Andrew Davis	UK Atomic Energy Authority
17:30	PORTING AND VALIDATING AN OPENFOAM SOLVER FOR URBAN MICROCLIMATE SIMULATION IN TROPICAL REGIONS	GABRIEL M. MAGALHAES, JUAN A. ACERO, BORIS HULJAK	University of Minho
17:50	Group photo		

Wednesday		
9:00		
9:50		
10:40	BoF coffee break	
	Technical session	Thermofluids, reacting flows, combustion
	Chairperson	G. Magalhães
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
11:00	ADAPTIVE AND MULTI-OBJECTIVE LOAD BALANCING FOR DETAILED CHEMISTRY SIMULATIONS IN OPENFOAM	ALBERTO CUOCI
		Politecnico di Milano
11:20	REDUCED CFD, NUMERICAL CONTINUATION FOR ROTATING DETONATION ENGINES	TREVOR KICKLITER, VISHAL ACHARYA
		Georgia Institute of Technology
11:40	Numerical Investigation of Heat Transfer in Nanoparticle-Enhanced Taylor Flow Using thermalMPPICInterFOAM	Fahad S. Al-Gburi, Faysal Khaleel, Yulong Ding, Jason Stoford
		University of Birmingham
12:00	Lunch break	
	Technical session	General CFD, HPC, GPU
	Chairperson	E. de Villiers
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
13:30	USING EXPRESSION TEMPLATES FOR MEMORY LOCALITY	ILYA POPOV, DMITRY ASTAKHOV
		ISTEQ BV
13:50	TOWARDS A COMPETITIVE OPEN-SOURCE GPU SOLVER FOR OPENFOAM	HENDRIK HETMANN, GREGOR OLENIK, CHARLES MOCKETT
		Upstream CFD GmbH
14:10	POLYHEDRAL CELL DECOMPOSITION ON STRUCTURED CARTESIAN GRIDS FOR FLUID DYNAMICS	R. SIGNORIELLO, R. MEREU, F. PISCAGLIA
		Politecnico di Milano
	Technical session	General CFD, HPC, GPU
	Chairperson	R. Gomez
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
14:30	SPUMA: A MINIMALLY INVASIVE PORTING OF OPENFOAM TO GPU	SIMONE BNÀ, ETTORRE FADIGA, GIUSEPPE GIAQUINTO, TOMMASO ZANELLI
		CINECA Consorzio Interuniversitario
14:50	OPENFOAM OPTIMIZATION FOR NEXT-GEN ARM CPUS	BERKOW ANTHONY, TSARFIS IGAL, WASSERMAN MARK, ZAMERET ALON, DELORME, YANN, DING ZHAOHUI, PEI WEICHENG
		Toga Networks, Huawei
15:10	BENCHMARKS IN THE TENDERING PROCESS FOR HPC CLUSTERS	CARSTEN THORENZ, FABIAN BELZNER
		Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute
15:30	Afternoon coffee break	
	Technical session	Multiphase, dispersed flows
	Chairperson	B. Haddadi
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
15:50	SIMULATION OF POOL SPREAD AND EVAPORATION OF CRYOGENIC LIQUID HYDROGEN ON SOLID SURFACES USING FILM MODEL	KHALED YASSIN, STEPHAN KELM, HARISH POTHUKUCH, ERNST-ARNDT REINECKE
		Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
16:10	Interface-Resolved Modelling of Droplet Evaporation Using a Finite Volume Moving-Mesh Method	KARLO JURINA, LARRY BAXTER, HONG G. IM, HRVOJE JASAK
		University of Cambridge
16:30	REDUCING SPURIOUS CURRENTS BY IMPROVING GRAVITY DISCRETISATION IN THE INTERFACIAL FLOW SOLVERS OF OPENFOAM	JOHAN ROENBY, KONSTANTINOS MISSIOS, HENNING SCHEUFLER
		Roskilde University
	Technical session	Multiphase, dispersed flows
	Chairperson	H. Nilsson
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
16:50	NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF HIGH-PRESSURE CAPILLARY VISCOMETER	MOHAMMAD POURHOSSEINIAN, BAHRAM HADDADI
		Competence Center CHASE GmbH
17:10	BUBBLE FORMATION AND FLOW DYNAMICS INDUCED BY LIQUID SLOSHING	KOHEI OKITA, HIROKAZU SUGIZAKI, TOMONOBU SHIOYASU, SHU TAKAGI
		Nihon University
17:30	Enhanced interface force modelling in MPPICInterFOAM for three-phase flow simulations	Faysal Khaleel, Fahad S. Al-Gburi, Yulong Ding, Jason Stoford
		University of Birmingham
17:50	Group photo	

Wednesday		
9:00		
9:50		
10:40	BoF coffee break	
	Technical session	Naval hydrodynamics
	Chairperson	H. Jasak
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
11:00	SUBMARINE COLLAPSE AND WAVE GENERATION DURING THE 2011–2012 TAGORO ERUPTION: INSIGHTS FROM 3D OPENFOAM MODELING	EDUARD PUIG MONTELLA, ALESSANDRO ROMANO, GABRIEL BARAJAS, JOSE A. LOZANO RODRIGUEZ, JAVIER L. LARA, EUGENIO FRAILE-NUEZ
		Instituto Espanol de Oceanografia
11:20	Semi-resolved DEM-FV simulations for ocean engineering applications	G.H. KEETELS, B.J. NIEUWBOER, M. VERHOOG
		Delft University of Technology
11:40	Implementation of a Physics-Based Cavitation Model in OpenFOAM for Marine Propeller Simulations	Hyeongjun Kim, Nikolai Kornev
		HD Hyundai Heavy Industries Co., Ltd.
12:00	Lunch break	
	Technical session	Numerical methods
	Chairperson	G. Keetels
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
13:30	TOWARDS EFFICIENT CHEBYSHEV POLYNOMIAL SMOOTHING FOR MULTIGRID SOLVERS	MATEJ CORAK, TESSA UROIC, HRVOJE JASAK
		University of Zagreb
13:50	THE IMPORTANCE OF CELL VOLUME RATIO ON THE DISCRETISATION OF THE PRESSURE EQUATION IN FINITE VOLUME CFD	FRANJO JURETIC
		Creative Fields d.o.o.
14:10	ASYNCHRONOUS MODIFIED CONJUGATE GRADIENT METHOD	Ranjith Khumar Shanmugasundaram, Henrik Rusche
		WIKKI GmbH
	Technical session	Numerical methods
	Chairperson	T. Uroic
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
14:30	IMMERSED BOUNDARY METHOD FOR SIMULATION OF FLOW AND HEAT TRANSFER IN MECHANICAL METAMATERIALS	LUCIE KUBICKOVA, ONDREJ STUDENIK, MARTIN ISOZ
		Czech Academy of Sciences
14:50	A Second-Order Accurate Topology Preserving Remap for ALE Methods	Ali Shayegh, Philip Cardiff
		University College Dublin
15:10	DEVELOPMENT OF A VOLUME-AVERAGED DIRECT SURFACE DESCRIPTION METHOD FOR MODELING WAVE INTERACTION WITH POROUS STRUCTURES	MOHSEN FARHADZADEH, ERIK DAMGAARD CHRISTENSEN
		Technical University of Denmark
15:30	Afternoon coffee break	
	Technical session	Data driven simulations, machine learning, AI
	Chairperson	T. Maric
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
15:50	ON ADAPTIVE MACHINE-LEARNING-ASSISTED RANS MODELLING	Mourad Oulghelou, Paola Cinnella, Xavier Merle
		Sorbonne University
16:10	Generative AI for Extreme Ocean Waves for Ship CFD	Kevin Maki, Benedetto Di Paolo, Adam Sak, Eric Heilshorn, Paolo Geremia
		University of Michigan
16:30	AI-POWERED SURROGATE MODEL FOR TRUCK CABIN AIRFLOW	IRINA MARIC, THOMAS BAUML, DRAGAN SIMIC, MIRZA POPOVAC
		Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
	Technical session	Data driven simulations, machine learning, AI
	Chairperson	H. Marschall
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
16:50	ONLINE MACHINE LEARNING FOR MESH DEFORMATION	TOMISLAV MARIC, ANDREW E. SHAO, ALESSANDRO RIGAZZI, YUAN KAI, REINER BIRKL, MOHAMMED ELWARDI FADELI, ANDRE WEINER
		Technical University of Darmstadt
17:10	COMPARISON OF HODMD MODES OBTAINED FROM NUMERICS AND EXPERIMENT ON THE EXAMPLE OF CYLINDER IN CROSSFLOW AT $Re \sim 5000$	MAREK BELDA, TOMAS HLAVATY, MARTIN ISOZ
		Czech Technical University in Prague
17:30	OPENFOAMGPT: AN AI ENGINEER	JINGSEN FENG, RAN XU, XU CHU
		University of Exete
17:50	Group photo	

Wednesday			
9:00			
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10:40	BoF coffee break		
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12:00	Lunch break		
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15:30	Afternoon coffee break		
Poster session	Group 2		
Room	Multimedia Stage		
	Title	Authors	Affiliation (first author)
15:50	1) DEVELOPMENT OF A DENSITY-BASED SOLVER FOR HIGH-SPEED TURBINE FLOW AND FILM COOLING ANALYSIS USING OPENFOAM	CHEOLSOON HONG, TEAWOO KIM, CHANKYU SON, DONG-HO RHEE	Chungju University
	2) EULERIAN-LAGRANGIAN TRANSPORT OF SOLID SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS IN A LIQUID METAL MHD FLOW FOR FUSION REACTOR APPLICATIONS	PIGNATIELLO S., FAVRE E., GIOVACCHINI V., SIRIANO S., TASSONE A.	Sapienza University of Rome
	3) CFD SIMULATION OF DEGRADED VISUAL ENVIRONMENTS AT THE CUES SITE ON MAMMOTH MOUNTAIN, CA	EDEN FURTAK-COLE	Desert Research Institute
	4) Simulation based Optimization of Wetting Phenomena	Clara Bernklau, Stefan Ulbrich	TU Darmstadt
	5) DEVELOPMENT OF A MULTIPHASE EULERIAN - PBM MODEL FOR BUBBLE TRANSPORT WITH APPLICATIONS TO AN ELECTROLYSER CELL	ASWATH ASHOK, SILVANIA LOPES, DELPHINE LABOUREUR, GERALDINE J. HEYNDERICKX	von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics
	6) NUMERICAL MODELING OF ALUMINUM ANNEALING IN INDUSTRIAL FURNACES USING OPENFOAM	NIKOLAOS CHAMAKOS, GEORGE PASHOS, DIMITRIOS KORTSELIS, DIMITRIOS TSITSIRIDAKIS, ANDREAS MAVROUDIS, IOANNIS CONTOPOULOS	ELKEME SA
	7) An OpenFOAM based-based multi-physic multi-region model for All Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries	Maciej Marczak, Edoardo Gino Macchi	Fondazione Bruno Kessler
	8) Suppression of electroconvection around ion-selective membrane using shear-thinning electrolyte	Saurabh Maurya, Mohit Trivedi, Neelkanth Nirmalkar	Indian Institute of Technology
	9) EXTENDING INTERFOAM FOR COUPLED ELECTROHYDRODYNAMICS: A STUDY OF ELECTRO-FLOW-FOCUSED LIQUID JETS	BOR ZUPAN, BOŽIDAR ŠARLER	University of Ljubljana
17:50	10) A NOVEL UTILITY TO CALCULATE THE FORCE AND TORQUE FOR VISCOELASTIC MATERIALS	MOHAMMADREZA AALI, JORGE PEIXINHO, J. MIGUEL NOBREGA	University of Minho
18:10	Group photo		

Thursday	Plenary session	Invited talks	3
	Chairperson	H. Kuehnelt	
	Room	Auditorium	
9:00	P. Cinnella	Advances in interpretable and generalizable data-driven turbulence models	Sorbonne University
9:50	A. Otto	Beam me up, OpenFOAM: Boosting knowledge in laser processing	Technical University of Vienna
10:40	BoF coffee break		
	Splash Talks	3-minutes presentation format	1
	Chairperson	B. Gschaider	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
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12:00	Lunch break		
	Training session	Class 1	.
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Author</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
13:30	Debugging complex simulation codes in parallel	Höhn Patrick	University of Göttingen
14:30	multiRegionFoam – A Modular Framework for Multiphysics Simulations in OpenFOAM	Constantin Habes	TU Darmstadt
15:30	Afternoon coffee break		
	Training session	Class 2	.
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Author</i>	<i>Affiliation</i>
15:50	Bayesian optimization for parameter tuning and design optimization	Andre Weiner, Tomislav Marić	TU Dresden, TU Darmstadt
16:50	OpenFOAM Catalyst: Solve any PDE using OpenFOAM Programming Language	Ali Shayegh	University College Dublin

Thursday

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BoF coffee break

Technical session	Thermofluids, reacting flows, combustion	3
Chairperson	M. Kardos	
Room	Business Stage 1.1	
Title	Authors	Affiliation (first author)
CLOUD-BASED AUTOMATED CFD DESIGN TOOLS USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE HEAT TREATMENT OF TITANIUM COMPONENTS	ULRICH HECK, MARTIN BECKER	DHCAE Tools GmbH
CFD MODELING OF BREAD BAKING PROCESS: INTERNAL TRANSPORT AND LOAF LARGE DEFORMATION	TOMAS HLAVATY, MARTIN ISOZ, ANNA KOVARNOVA, TOMAS MOUCHA, MARCELA SLUKOVA	University of Chemistry and Technology (CZ)
LASER-BASED MANUFACTURING SIMULATIONS USING A COMPRESSIBLE MULTIPHASE MASS-OF-FLUID MODEL	Michele Buttazzoni, Constantin Zenz, Tobias Florian, Katherine Elizabeth Crespo Armijos, Rodrigo Gomez Vazquez, Gerhard Liedl, Andreas Otto	Vienna University of Technology

Lunch break

Training session	Class 3	.
Room	Business Stage 1.1	
Title	Author	Affiliation
Execute OpenFOAM on the cloud	Ruggero Poletto	CFD FEA SERVICE SRL
OpenFOAM Basic Training	Haddadi Sisakht Bahram	Competence Center CHASE GmbH

Afternoon coffee break

Training session	Class 4	.
Room	Business Stage 1.1	
Title	Author	Affiliation
How to Add a Model to OpenFOAM 12	Haddadi Sisakht Bahram	Competence Center CHASE GmbH
CFD-DEM coupling between OpenFOAM and PhasicFlow	Haddadi Sisakht Bahram	Competence Center CHASE GmbH

Thursday		
9:00		
9:50		
10:40	BoF coffee break	
	Technical session	Aerodynamics
	Chairperson	F. Mastropiero
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
11:00	Towards a generalized open-source turbulence model for external aerodynamics	Eric Segalerba, Tony Di Fabbio, Viola Rossano, Joel Enrique Rivas Guerrero
		Leonardo Labs, Leonardo S.p.A.
11:20	Verification and Validation of OpenFOAM for High-Speed Aerodynamics	Viola Rossano, Tony Di Fabbio, Eric Segalerba, Joel Enrique Rivas Guerrero
		Leonardo Labs, Leonardo S.p.A.
11:40	ANALYSIS OF PERFORMANCE DEGRADATION ON HIGH-ALTITUDE LONG-ENDURANCE UAV DUE TO ICING	JEONG-HO SHIN, YONGHWAN KIM, CHANKYU SON
		Cheongju University
12:00	Lunch break	
	Training session	Class 5
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Author</i>
13:30	Rotating machinery in OpenFOAM(.com)	Håkan Nilsson
		Chalmers University of Technology
14:30	Demystifying meshing with snappyHexMesh	Joel Guerrero
		Wolf Dynamics SRL
15:30	Afternoon coffee break	
	Training session	Class 6
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Author</i>
15:50	solids4foam for solid mechanics & fluid-solid interactions in OpenFOAM: training & new features	Philip Cardiff
		University College Dublin
16:50	Advanced OpenFOAM Techniques for Liquefaction Modeling in Marine Environments	Ranjith Khumar Shanmugasundaram
		WIKKI GmbH

Friday	Plenary session	Invited and topical talks	4
	Chairperson	M. Popovac	
	Room	Auditorium	
9:00	J. Nagy	OpenFoam Journal	eulerian-solutions e.U.
9:15	S. Pirker	Particulate flow modelling through space and time	Johannes Kepler University
10:05	C. Mockett	Industrialisation of high-fidelity CFD	Upstream CFD GmbH
10:40	BoF coffee break		
	Technical session	Complex flow phenomena	1
	Chairperson	T. Baeuml	
	Room	Auditorium	
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Affiliation (first author)</i>
11:00	IMPACT OF HEMODYNAMIC AND STRUCTURAL PARAMETERS ON CEREBRAL ANEURYSM GROWTH: INSIGHTS FROM FLUID-STRUCTURE INTERACTION ANALYSIS	JOZSEF NAGY, WOLFGANG FENZ, JULIA MAIER, ZOLTAN MAJOR, ANDREAS GRUBER, MATTHIAS GMEINER	eulerian-solutions e.U.
11:20	AN OPEN-SOURCE CFD FRAMEWORK FOR OPEN ABSORPTION PROCESSES	FELIX HOCHWALLNER, CLARISSA STACKE, JOHANN EMHOFER, CHRISTOPH REICHL	Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
11:40	Tesla Cybertruck Aerodynamics - A fully automated reverse engineering methodology using 3D Scanning and OpenFOAM	Wouter Remmerie, Nikola Majksner	AirShaper
12:00	DESIGN OF LOW REYNOLDS NUMBER AIRFOILS CONSIDERING MANUFACTURABILITY	HYOJUN KIM, CHANKYU SON	Cheongju University
12:20	Lunch break		
	Special Interest Group	Data Driven Modelling	Auditorium
13:50	Chairperson	Andre Weiner	
	Birds of a feather (BoF)		Auditorium
14:50	Chairperson		

Friday		
9:00		
9:15		
10:05		
10:40	BoF coffee break	
	Technical session	Particulate fluid dynamics
	Chairperson	J. Page
	Room	Business Stage 1.1
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
11:00	ASYNCHRONOUS EULER-LAGRANGE COUPLING METHOD	SERGEY LESNIK, SILVIO SCHMALFUB, HENRIK RUSCHE
		Wikki GmbH
11:20	LAGRANGIAN PARTICLE TRACKING IN A STIRRED TANK: COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL DATA	W.J. PEACE, L. GAMET, F. AUGIER, C.R.K. WINDOWS-YULE, M.J.H. SIMMONS
		University of Birmingham
11:40	Continuum-particulate modelling of the sediment transport process using coarse-grained CFD-DEM approach	Saugat Shrestha, Adnan Sufian, Gavin Tabor, Prakash Kripakaran
		University of Queensland
12:00		
12:20	Lunch break	
	Special Interest Group	Business Stage 1.1
13:50	Chairperson	
	Birds of a feather (BoF)	Business Stage 1.1
14:50	Chairperson	

Friday		
9:00		
9:15		
10:05		
10:40	BoF coffee break	
	Technical session	Fluids and solids
	Chairperson	A. Ryzhov
	Room	Business Stage 1.2
	<i>Title</i>	<i>Authors</i>
11:00	A unified framework for coupled fluid-mooring modelling in OpenFOAM	AMIRHOSSEIN TARAN, SEEVANI BALI, ŽELJKO TUKOVIC, VIKRAM PAKRASHI, PHILIP CARDIFF
		University College Dublin
11:20	THE HIGHER-ORDER FINITE VOLUME METHOD FOR SOLID MECHANICS IN OPENFOAM	IVAN BATISTIC, PHILIP CARDIFF
		University of Zagreb
11:40	Integration of an Explicit Godunov-Type Riemann Solver for Solid Dynamics in Solids4foam	KHODER ALHAMWI ALSHAAR, JADAV CHANDRA MANDAL
		IIT Bombay
12:00		
12:20	Lunch break	
	Special Interest Group	Business Stage 1.2
13:50	Chairperson	
	Birds of a feather (BoF)	Business Stage 1.2
14:50	Chairperson	

The 20th OpenFOAM Workshop was organized and hosted by

Conference Chairman

Mirza Popovac

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